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Toxicity of potato extract on *Tetranychus urticae* (Acari: Tetranychidae) and its effect on biology and life table parameters

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Tetranychus urticae, potato extracts, solanine, biology and control.

Abstract:

The present study aimed to evaluate the unless and harmful part of the potato plant, which is the green part of tubers contains solanine, as a botanical pesticide. The red spider mite *Tetranychus urticae* Koch (Acari: Tetranychidae) is one of the most dangerous pests all over the world. It has been reported to attack about 1200 species of plants. It causes damage to vegetables, sweet corn, beans, peas, hops, grapes, deciduous fruit trees, strawberries and many other fruit, flowers and ornamental plants. Due to the problems of chemical acaricides to all organisms and environment, natural control replaced pesticides. The green potato extract contains solanine which is toxic and effective material in control. Different little concentrations of green potato extract were applied in control of red spider mite and caused high mortality proportion. In this study, the used concentrations were 1000, 3000, 5000 and 10000 ppm and the mortality increased when the concentrations increased. LC_{50} of the extract was 3503.69 ppm and LC_{90} was 62667.81. Then, LC_{50} was applied on adult female for recording its effect on biology and life table.

Introduction

Potato, *Solanum tuberosum*, is the fourth major crop around the world. In Egypt, it has an important position among all vegetable crops, where about 20% of total area devoted for vegetable production is cultivated with potato. In addition, any disturbance in its production affects severely its local and more importantly export variable. Potato plants are subjected to numerous pathogens and insect pests which cause considerable loss in Egyptian quantitative and qualitative potato yield.

Solanine is a natural toxic chemical

compound that is a glycoalkaloid produced in some species of the nightshades family (Solanaceae) such as potato, tomato and eggplant (Tajner-Czopek, 2008). It is produced in potatoes when exposed to light, turning to green and increase glycoalkaloid production.

Several pests attack potato plants, one of these pests is the red spider mite, *Tetranychus urticae* Koch (Acari: Tetranychidae). This spider mite is extremely polyphagous, it has a broad host-plant range (Tsagkarakou *et al.*, 2002 and

Tehri, 2014). This mite is a generalist species that can feed on hundreds of hosts plants and causes considerable damage to field, greenhouse and horticultural crops, as well as ornamental and fruit-bearing trees including Rosa (Sedaratian *et al.*, 2010 and Jafari *et al.*, 2012). Feeding activity of spider mite leads to the appearance of typical yellow chlorotic spots on leaves with profuse webbing on the underside of leaves. In severe infestations, leaves may fall, and the flowering may be considerably reduced (Khodayari *et al.*, 2008). The short life span and high reproductive potential causes a fast-growing population that allows the mite to achieve economic injury level in appropriate conditions, resulting in a rapid decline of host plant yield and quality (Jalalvandi *et al.*, 2015).

Pesticides produced from natural products, recently, have been attracting the attention of many scientists to avoid many problems caused by synthetic compounds. They are deeply interested in their chemical constituents and biological properties (Abou-Yousef *et al.*, 2010). The aim of this study is to determine the toxicity of extract of green parts of potato, contains solanine, on the red spider mite *T. urticae* and the effect of the extract on biology and life table of the mite.

Materials and methods

1. Rearing mites:

T. urticae were collected from unsprayed potato leaves of unsprayed fields and reared, in laboratory, at $25 \pm 2^\circ \text{C}$ and $60 \pm 5\% \text{RH}$.

2. Preparation of plant sample and extraction:

Green parts of potato tubers were collected and left to dry at room temperature then grinded into fine powder. Powder was soaked in a mixture of hexane, acetone and ethanol solvents of equal proportions (1:1:1) in a flask for about one week. Finally, the flask was shaken in a shaker and its contents were filtered. The solvents were evaporated

under reduced pressure, the crude extract was weighted and kept in deep freezer until use.

3. Preparing the stock solution of the tested plant extract:

Convenient stock, concentrations of green potato extract, was prepared on basis of the tested powder weight and the volume of the distilled water (w/v) in the presence of tween 80 (0.1%) as emulsifier. The stock concentrations were kept in glass stoppered bottles and stored under refrigeration. Such stock solutions were prepared periodically. Four diluted concentrations for the plant extract were used to draw the LC-P Lines. Four replicates were used for each concentration.

- Green parts of potato tubers contain solanine (C₄₅H₇₃NO₁₅) (The Merck Index , 1976).

Desfosses, 1820

4. Application method:

4.1. Toxicity experiment:

For conducting this experiment, potato tubers were planting in pots until the green leaves were appeared to use these leaves as discs for application. Thirty newly emerged adult females were transferred to the lower surface of potato leave discs (2 cm diameter) placed separately on moist cotton wool in Petri dishes. Each petri dish contains three replicates, ten individuals in each replicate. The extract had four concentrations which were sprayed on the individuals. The concentrations used were 250, 500, 750 and 1000 ppm. The percentage of mortality was recorded after one, three, five and seven days and the data were corrected relatively to

control mortality (Abbott, 1925). LC_{50} values were determined using probit analysis statistical method of Finney, (1971).

4.2. Biology and life table:

After calculating LC_{50} of the extract, 3506 ppm, three discs of treated potato leaves with LC_{50} of the extract were prepared comparing with three discs of untreated potato leaves (as control). Three females, for each group, of *T. urticae* were put over the three discs, for each group, one female on each disc. The daily laid eggs were evaluated and counted carefully for life table calculation. Life cycle and life span of *T. urticae* were, also, calculated, for the two groups.

Results were analyzed by life table program (Abou-Setta *et al.*, 1986) and L.S.D. values were calculated by costat program (Costat software, 1990).

Results and discussion

1. Efficiency of potato extract on female of *Tetranychus urticae*:

The data in Table (1) demonstrated that, although the extract concentrations were low, the mortality rate of female of *T. urticae* was high and when the concentrations increased, the total mortality increased. These results agreed with Zbigniew *et al.* (2014) which proved the effectiveness of potato leaf extract against *Galleria mellonella* (L.) (Lepidoptera, Pyralidae).

However, Table (2) and Figure (1) demonstrated that, LC_{50} was 3503.69 ppm and LC_{90} was 62667.81 The probability was 0.092. Zbigniew *et al.* (2014) indicated that potato leaf extract, especially solanine, caused mortality to the larvae of *G. mellonella*.

Table (1): Corrected mortality % of the female of *Tetranychus urticae* treated with potato extract under laboratory conditions 27 ± 2 °C and $65\pm 5\%$ RH.

Treatment	Conc. (ppm)	Mortality after treatments %				Total Mortality %
		One day	Three days	Five days	Seven days	
Potato extract	1000	10	6.67	10	6.67	33.34
	3000	20	3.33	10	6.67	40
	5000	23.33	13.33	10	6.67	53.33
	10000	40	16.67	10	3.33	73.33

Table (2): Efficiency of potato tubers extract against *Tetranychus urticae*.

Treatment	Conc. (ppm)	Corrected mortality%	LC_{50}	LC_{90}	Slope \pm S.D.	LC_{90}/LC_{50}	R	P
Potato extract	1000	33.34	3503.69	62667.81	1.023 \pm 0.180	17.89	0.956	0.092
	3000	40						
	5000	53.33						
	10000	73.33						

R: Regression

P: Probability

Figure (1): LC-P line for potato extract of *Tetranychus urticae*

2. Effect of LC₅₀ of potato tuber extract on biology of *Tetranychus urticae*:

Results in Table (3) indicated that, each of incubation period, larval duration, protonymph and deutonymph of *T. urticae* fed on untreated leaves had smaller periods than *T. urticae* fed on treated leaves. As the result of this, the total life cycle decreased in case of untreated leaves than the treated ones which was 14.2 and 16.2 days, respectively. Also, Table (3) described that longevity and generation periods decreased in case of untreated leaves than the treated ones. However, the life span of *T. urticae* decreased in case of untreated leaves than the treated ones, which was 34.8 and 38.4 days,

respectively. These results explained that, green potato extract (contains solanine) increasing all biological durations and as the result of this, generation periods significantly increased so the number of generations per year decreased. Nenaah (2011) indicated that, potato gas reduced the growth rate, food consumption rate, and food utilization by adult *Trogoderma granarium* Everts (Coleoptera: Dermestidae), probably due to their toxic and antifeedant activity. Zbigniew *et al.* (2014) proved the inhibitory effects of potato leaves extract and α -solanine on survival, fecundity and fertility of *G. mellonella*.

Table (3): Effect of green potato extract on life cycle and life span of *Tetranychus urticae*:

Stages	<i>Tetranychus urticae</i> Fed on leaves untreated	<i>Tetranychus urticae</i> Fed on leaves treated
Incubation period	3.1 ± 0.57	3.8 ± 0.63
Larvae duration	3.6 ± 0.52	4.1 ± 0.57
Protonymph	4.2 ± 0.42	4.4 ± 0.52
Deutonymph	3.3 ± 0.48	3.9 ± 0.57
Life cycle	14.2 ± 0.92	16.2 ± 0.79
longevity	20.6 ± 2.97	22.2 ± 1.64
Generation period	15.8 ± 0.55	18.6 ± 0.55
Life span	34.8 ± 2.97	38.4 ± 1.64

In Table (4), longevity and fecundity of female of *T. urticae* on both treated and untreated leaves of potato were examined. In

the obtained results, longevity of *T. urticae* female fed on untreated potato leaves decreased significantly than the treated ones

and recorded 20.6 and 22.2 days, respectively. While, fecundity of female increased highly significant in case of *T. urticae* female fed on untreated potato leaves than the treated ones and recorded 98.4 and 79.2 eggs/ female, respectively. So, daily rate of eggs/ female was 9.9 and 6.08 eggs/ female, respectively. These results were good guideline that the extract of green potato (contains solanine) had great effect on fecundity of female and reducing the next generations of *T. urticae*. Similarly, α -

chaconine (in potato leaves extract) decreased reproduction rates of the potato aphid *Macrosiphum euphorbiae* (Thomas) (Hemiptera: Aphididae) (Guntner *et al.*, 1997). α -solanine and α -chaconine added to an artificial diet, in concentrations lower or like those observed in potato leaves, reduced fecundity, feeding, and increased mortality in adults peach potato aphids *Myzus persicae* (Sulzer) (Hemiptera: Aphididae) (Fragoyiannis *et al.*, 1998).

Table (4): Effect of green potato extract on longevity and fecundity of *Tetranychus urticae* female.

		<i>Tetranychus urticae</i> Fed on leaves untreated	<i>Tetranychus urticae</i> Fed on leaves treated
Average duration (days)	Pre oviposition Period	1.6 ± 0.55	2.4 ± 0.55
	Oviposition period	10.2 ± 2.17	13.0 ± 2.00
	Post oviposition Period	8.8 ± 1.30	6.8 ± 0.84
Longevity (Days)		20.6 ± 2.97	22.2 ± 1.64
Fecundity	Egg / Female	98.4 ± 13.50	79.2 ± 15.45
	Daily Rate	9.9 ± 1.73	6.08 ± 0.79

In Table (5), data represented that, the net reproduction rate (R_0) was very high in *T. urticae* fed on untreated leaves (4446), while it was (3573) in *T. urticae* fed on treated leaves. However, the mean generation time (T) was little in *T. urticae* fed on untreated leaves (19.14) comparing with *T. urticae* fed on treated leaves (22.57).

Intrinsic rate of increase (r_m) and finite rate of increase (\exp_{r_m}) were little higher in *T. urticae* fed on untreated leaves (0.44 and 1.55), respectively than *T. urticae* fed on

treated leaves (0.36 and 1.44), respectively. As the result of this, the generation doubling time was 3.21 and 3.93 days for *T. urticae* fed on untreated leaves and *T. urticae* fed on treated leaves, respectively. Nenaah (2011) proved that, potato gas also reduced the growth rate for adult *T. granarium*. Similarly, Guntner *et al.* (1997) indicated that, α -chaconine of potato leaves extract decreased reproduction rates of the potato aphid *Macrosiphum euphorbiae* (Thomas) (Hemiptera: Aphididae).

Table (5): Effect of green potato extract on life table parameters of *Tetranychus urticae* female.

Parameters	<i>Tetranychus urticae</i> Fed on leaves untreated	<i>Tetranychus urticae</i> Fed on leaves treated
Net reproduction rate (R ₀)	4446	3573
Mean generation time (T)	19.14	22.57
Intrinsic rate of increase (r _m)	0.44	0.36
Finite rate of increase (exp r _m)	1.55	1.44
Generation doubling time (days)*	3.21	3.93

$$\text{Generation doubling time (days)} = \ln_2 / r_m$$

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Seed bugs *Graptostethus servus* and *Spilostethus pandurus* (Heteroptera: Lygaeidae) as a newly attracted pests on oil crops and bindweed in Egypt

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Abstract:

The Lygaeidea is one of the most diversified group, comprises of about 4000 species under 500 genera all over the world, it includes some species are pests of agriculture and vegetation, most species of this family are known as seed bugs. The aim of this work is to study the taxonomy and morphological characters of the two species of family Lygaeidea by redescription of them as well as the role of essential oil (EO) of bindweed (*Convolvulus arvensis* L.) as semiochemical attractive of these two genera. The results indicated that, two species under two genera of seed bugs were recoded for first time on oil crops such as *Sesamum indicum* (Pedaliaceae) and sorghum crops (*Sorghum bicolor*) and weed plant milkweed *C. arvensis* as an alternative host plant during summer 2017, 2018 and 2019 and early winter seasons 2020. These two species are *Graptostethus servus* (Fabricius) and *Spilostethus pandurus* Scopoli (Heteroptera: Lygaeidae) and both of them were recorded as a highly number of nymphs and adults feeding on sap of milkweed plants and oil crops (sesamum, sunflower seeds, *Zea mazi* , sorghum, soybean and cotton).

Introduction

Over the world, oilseeds crops are the most important sources of oilseeds such as sesamum *Sesamum indicum* , sunflower *Helianthus annuus* L., Europe and America account for nearly 70% of total area and 80% of total production, *Sorghum halepense*, soya bean or soybean *Glycine max* (L.); about 35% of the world's production is in the United States, 27% Brazil, 19% Argentina, 6% China and 4% in India (Damodaran and Hegde, 2007). In Egypt, soybean and

sunflower seed production in marketing year to reach 28,000 and 24,000 metric tons, total area of *Zea maize* L. about 25.17 % of the total cultivated agricultural land while average yield is 7.80 ton/ hectare. (FAO, 2011 and Abdi, 2019). Cotton *Gossypium barbadense* L. known as Creole, Egyptian, South American, Pima or Sea Island cotton, native to tropical South America (8% of world production)., that are very important crops in agriculture and industrial economy,

there are many insect pests attracted to oilseed plants inducing more damage and loss of yields, such as thrips, aphids, whiteflies, jassids, bugs, and mites that are feeding habitat could have sucking mouthparts eat parts of the crops such as flowers, foliage, stems, roots or buds, delayed flowering usually cause discolor or twist and curl the plants (Ziaee, 2012). The genus *Spilostethus* known as a seed bug, ground bugs or milkweed bugs that family Lygaeidae (Heteroptera), it is one of the most diversified group, comprises of about 4000 species under 500 genera all over the world (Henry, 2009). Also, it is one of the most ecological impacts and this insect feed on plant juices of *Convolvulus arvensis* L. (Burdfield-Steel and Shuker, 2014), *Spilostethus pandurus* Scopoli (Heteroptera: Lygaeidae) milkweed bug is very common in South Sinai, living in small groups and feeding on the seeds and tissues of Sinai milkweed, *Asclepias (Gomphocarpus) sinaica* (Boiss.) (Mahmoud *et al.*, 2014). Also, it is recorded on South Indian as a pest of gingelly (*Sesamum indicum*), *Sorghum vulgare* (Poaceae) and *Gossypium hirsutum* (Malvaceae) are also confirmed as host plants of this species. *Vernonia cinerea* (Compositae) and *Hibiscus sabdariffa* (Malvaceae) are reported as host plants of this polyphagous species (Thangavelu, 1979). *C. arvensis* milkweed is one of the most problematic weeds in agricultural fields in different parts of the world, it causes important economic losses through reduction of germination and yield of wheat as 14 and 80% (Bogatek *et al.*, 2005). It is a species of bindweed that is rhizomatous and is in the morning glory family (Convolvulaceae), native to Europe and Asia. It is a climbing or creeping herbaceous perennial plant growing to 0.5–2 m high, the leaves are spirally arranged, linear to arrowhead-shaped, 2–5 cm long and alternate, with a 1–3 cm petiole (Parnell and Curtis, 2012). This genus of *C. arvensis* mostly is distributed on large scale in the old

world, there are 18 species only on Ethiopian, Australia, Europe, South Pacific Island, China, Ceylon, Burma, Indonesia, Pakistan, India, Turkey, Syria and Africa, they can cause serious damage to the crops of *Sesamum indicum* (Pedaliaceae), sunflowers, sorghum crops (*Sorghum bicolor*), tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum*), tobacco (*Calotropis gigantea*), it can also attacks, *Calotropis procera* (Apocynaceae), *Pennisetum americanum*, *Arachis hypogaea*, *Eleusine coracana* and *Phaseolus mungo*, etc. Hussain *et al.* (2014) and Sabry and Ragaei (2015) recorded that field bindweed, *C. arvensis* is recorded as a new host plant to tomato leafminer *Tuta absoluta* (Meyrick) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) as a first time in Egypt.

The aim of this work is to study the taxonomy and morphological characters of the two species of family Lygaeidae by redescription of them as well as the role of essential oil (EO) of bindweed (*C. arvensis*) as semiochemical attractive of these two species.

Materials and methods

1. Sample of insect:

During June 2017, 2018 and 2019 seasons in Giza Governorate, Egypt, adult and nymph samples were collected by hand then putted in small vials, transferred to laboratory, then these specimens were identified by Insect taxonomy and Survey Department, Plant Protection Research Institute as illustrated in Figure (1).

2. Bioassay test of novel nano bio-pesticide for controlling seed bug *Spilostethus pandurus* :

At laboratory conditions experiments were carried out in glass jar contain 5 nymphs /replicate of target pest *S. pandurus* of each treatment. Then 5 capsules of milkweed plant *C. arvensis* were dipping on water then put 0.5 gm of all nano materials “boiled chicken eggshells white and brown color, *Moringa oleifera* Lam. leaf powder, kapritia Swia water and control. (Ibrahim, 2019).

Figure (1): Sample of insects were collected from different locations.

a, b, c, d and e: nymphs and f: adults.

Results and discussion

1. Field studies:

During growing seasons, 2017 *S.indicum* crop, 2018 cotton *Gossypium barbadense* and 2019 *Z. maize* until summer season 2020 at Giza Governorate, these insect pests were observed during three years, and recorded on all crops after post-harvest of these crops it were transfer to the

alternative host milkweed plant *C.arvensis* as shown in Figure (2), these polyphagous bugs feed on flowers and seeds of many plants, they preferentially fed on the plants of the family Apocynaceae. They can cause serious damage to the crops of *S.indicum* and *S. bicolor* crops on Sohag and Qina Governorate during 2019 season.

Figure (2): Sample of two species collected during three years in Giza, Egypt. a: nymphs of *Spilostethus pandurus* on sesame *Sesamum indicum*, b: Adults of *Spilostethus pandurus* on sorghum, c: Two shape of adults of *Spilostethus pandurus*, d: Red color of *Spilostethus pandurus*, e: Brown color of *Spilostethus pandurus*.

2. Laboratory studies:

2.1. Taxonomy of two species:

Family Lygaeidae, member of this family ranged 4-12 mm. in long, having a pair of ocelli between the compound eyes, antennae and rostrum mouthparts 4-segmented; without cuneus in hemelytra, the membranous portion of the front wing bears only 4-5 veins; Lygaeidae are best recognized by the impressed line across the calli and y-shaped pattern on the scutellum.

2.1.1. *Graptostethus servus* (Fabricius, 1787).

Genus *Graptostethus* Stal, 1868

Antennae about half of the length of the body, 2nd and 3rd antennal segments equal in length, rarely the 2nd longer than third; 1st

segment of rostrum reaching or passing the anterior the anterior margin of the pre sternum; posterior margin of pronotum straight, a central carina absent or sub-obsolete, femore unarmed.

***Graptostethus servus* (Fabricius, 1787).**

Cimex servus Fab., Mant.Ins.,2(1787):300, Description: about 9mm.in Length.

Body paler in cooler and pilose; basal spot and apical to membrane greyish ; abex of head, a small spot at inner margin of eyes, scutellum, a large sub-claval spot and membrane, a large spot -on the sternal segment laterally leg, antennae and rostrum are black; rostrum reaching posterior coxae, as showed in (Figure , 3).

Figure (3): *Graptostethus servus* a: Adult, b: Female, c: Male

The morphological characters of all stages of *G. servus*, described in Figure (4). After mating of males and females, the eggs were putted on groups or clusters within the plant tissue or on the soil, as showed (Figure, 4 a) the egg are it measured about 0.6 mm., symmetrically rounded ends , yellowish – white in color, shining white with a slightly yellowish tinge, then after four days these eggs were light pink, the developing embryo on the seventh day one end was darkened

(Figure, 4 a b), and hatching took place in nine days at room temperature 26°C and 75 % relative humidity (RH.) emberoinc development were recorded the color of eggs changes from orange color to red (Figure, 4 c), the first nymph observed on (Figure, 4 d), it has four to six nymphal stages and nymphs can be found in clusters (Figure, 4 e and f). Adults female, male and nymphs cause damage to plants by sucking sap.

Figure (4): Female and male of *Graptostethus servus*, a: Eggs, b: Embryonic development, c:1st nymph, d:2nd nymph, e: 3rd nymph, f: 4th and 5th nymphs .

Distribution:

World: India, china, Myanmar, Srilanka and South Africa

The mention result investigated with Sheikh *et al.*, 2017 and Hussain *et al.*, 2014 description of *G. servus*. Black sanguineous or reddish brown; head ventrally and laterally red; vertex, tylus, transverse anterior fascia, two basal fascia to pronotum, scutellum, large oblique subclaval and small marginal (sometimes fused) to corium legs and labium black; antennae brownish black; anterior and posterior halves of pronotum except transverse black band, interior collar region inner and apical margins of clavus red sanguineous and it Distribution on Africa, Europe, South Pacific Island, china, Burma, Ceylon, Australia, Indonesia, Pakistan, India, Turkey, Syria, Australia, China, Myanmar, Sri Lanka, South Africa. Kondorosy *et al.*, 2006 and Magsi *et al.*, 2018 observed that *Graptostethus* was is a genus in the insect family Lygaeidae (seed bugs). Although originally restricted to the Old World (Palearctic, Ethiopian, and Oriental Regions) some species like *G. servus* have spread to parts of the New World, foliage of

hibiscus and cotton, buds of Sonchus and Emilia, hibiscus bud and blossoms, Euxolus and describe the morphological thorax, clavus and corium red and having black markings. In mediterranean countries it's very scarce and the biology and host plants are less known (Dioli, 2010). *Graptostethus* swarms remain for an extended period, and are causing physical damage to flowers or fruit, *Graptostethus*, also known by local growers as 'Crusader' bugs generally start swarming onto rural properties in early May. *Graptostethus* are sap-sucking bugs that are about 9 mm long, orange/red in color and have black and orange markings on the back in a 'cross' pattern (Hussain *et al.*, 2014). *Graptostethus* is a genus in the insect family Lygaeidae (seed bugs).Although originally restricted to the Old World (Palearctic, Ethiopian, and Oriental Regions) some species like *G. servus* have spread to parts of the New World. These bugs are sapsuckers but do not feed on fruit trees. They usually feed on seed pods of native legumes, grasses or weeds. When these bugs swarm, they generally do not feed but may cause physical damage by

breaking off stems or cause scratch marks on leaves, flowers or fruit trees, ornamentals and vegetables by moving on the plants in such large numbers, they occasionally cause indirect damage (seen as pin-prick spots) by feeding on moisture found on fruit, shoots or flowers. Besides their need for water, they also like to form large groups to aggregate and mate. The control of the *Graptostethus* is difficult, subsequently, to reduce infestations

around houses and buildings, surface sprays by pesticides such as permethrin, (Chin *et al.*, 2018).

2.1.2. Genus *Spilostethus* Stal , 1868

Diagnosis: Posterior margin of the pronotum straight, scutellum carinated from middle to apex; the clavus is sub-amplitede posteriorly.

Spilostethus pandurus (Scopoli, 1763)

Description: As shown in Figure (5).

Figure (5): a: *Spilostethus pandurus* adult, b: Female, c: Male

The adult is about 10-13 mm in length; males are smaller in size; body pale yellow in color with grayish spot changes gradually to black, legs and antennae black ; head with y- shaped marking ; vertex convex basally ; antennae clavate with 1st segment is thickest and shortest one and 2nd segment is longest one; pronotum with black stripes laterally soldier bug (*S. pandurus*) is widely distributed in tropical and subtropical parts of the eastern old world. Adult *S. pandurus* are active in April, increasing in abundance through early summer months and peaking in July; they have a bimodal activity pattern during the day, avoiding high midday temperatures Individuals have been observed to fly more than 30 m, visiting different *Asclepias* plants if these are reasonably close

together, but individuals tended to return to the same plant for shelter overnight (CAB International, 2003 and El-Banna, 2004 and Awad *et al.*, 2013).

2.2. Appearance phenomena of two shape of *Spilostethus pandurus*:

Laboratory studied of new phenomena of one more shape and cooler of the species *S.pandurus* as in Figure(6), female lygaeids generally lay eggs in clusters, which can range in size from 10 to over 100 eggs, nymphs typically live in similar environments to their parents and are often gregarious. Importantly, sibling cannibalism is known to occur in Lygaeidae, nymphs of the species *S. pandurus* showing characteristic black and red coloration.

Figure (6) : Two shapes of *Spilostethus pandurus*.

The source of this variation may be by genetic diversity of *S. pandurus*, that was studied by Mahmoud *et al.* (2014) at St Katherine area by using RAPD markers in individuals sampled, a total of 109 different RAPD bands were generated for the whole sample: site-specific bands occurred at low frequency. Even though there were many genetic differences among individuals within sites, the sites were statistically distinct. *S. pandurus* (Scop.) prefers to feed on the leaves of the plant *Calotropis procera*, they obtain glycosides from plant and use it during

defense hatching (Sweet, 2000 and Magsi *et al.*, 2018).

3. Bioassay test of novel Nano bio pesticide for controlling seed bug *Spilostethus pandurus*:

The obtained results as shown in Table (1), the 1st and 2nd nymphs of the milkweed bug *S. glaseri* recorded a highly affect than the 3rd and 5th nymphs, the mortality reach to 90 and 100 % after 5days of treatment of white eggshells powder, while after treatment with brown eggshells powder causes 73.and 80 % mortality for 1st and 2 nymphs.

Table (1): Bioassay of different nymphs of *Spilostethus pandurus* after treatment with bio-pesticide materials.

<i>Nymphs Spilostethus pandurus</i>			Treatments				
			White eggshells Powder	Brown eggshells powder	<i>Moringa oleifera</i> leaf powder	<i>Kapritia Swia</i> water	Control
Mortality % after	1 st and 2 nd Nymphs	3 Days	90	73	0	6.6	0
		5 Days	100	80	0	16.6	0
		7 Days	-	20	0	16.6	0
		14 Days	-	24.13	0	30	0
	3 rd Nymphs	3 Days	0	13.7	0	10	0
		5 Days	10	17.24	3.3	16.12	0
		7 Days	20	20	3.3	16.12	0
		14 Days	23.3	24.13	3.3	38.71	0
	5 th Nymphs	3 Days	0	4	6.6	26.6	0
		5 Days	0	0	0	30	0
		7 Days	12	40	8	43.3	0
		14 Days	12	84	32	53.3	0

Bioassay studies were carried out using the brown eggshells powder was highly effective of mortality percentage were 80 and 73% against 1st, 2nd nymphs after 3 and 5 day of treatment and 84% after 14 days. While the mortality percentage decreased when early nymphs fed on *M. oleifera* leaf powder, *Kapritia Swia* water affected with 53.3% on 5th nymphs after 14 days of treatments compare with control there are zero mortality during laboratory experimental that illustrate on Table 1. least amount of the new materials as a bio-pesticides that used having good highly effective against early nymphs' instars are probably the most chemical-sensitive stages, it can be utilized for biological control management of that insect pest. Field bindweed (*Convolvulus arvensis* L.) is one of the most serious weeds of agricultural fields in temperate regions of the world. In favorable conditions it can grow to 2 m tall and produce over a million seeds. It competes with crops for water and nutrients and additionally it shades crops because of its greater height. All stages adults and nymphs

of two genera *S. pandurus* and *G. servus* recorded fed on field bindweed (*C. arvensis*) in Egypt. 140 species of insects of arthropods, three species of mites attacked to over part of plants injurious to *C. arvensis* and most three pathogenic fungi as microorganisms being associated with the leaves (Nunez-Ormeno *et al.*, 1988).

The future studies require more applied researches on this topic to explain the difference morphological shape of genus *S. pandurus* and explain the roll of semiochemical field bindweed (*C. arvensis*) to attractive two genera of bugs, the behavior of bugs requires ripe seeds, they move from host to host, as the seeds of each become available and used natural compound to increases nymph mortality and egg production from generation. In addition to, the oilseeds crops occupy an important position in agriculture and industrial economy, so, the crop integrated management program could increase the quality and quantity of the products by using traditional control as chemical pesticides and

the other methods such as cultural control, biological control, physical control, host plant resistance, and nanomaterials as used on our paper that decreases resistance of insect pests after treatment with long term exposure to insecticides can protect farmers from disease, increased organic farms, prevent pests from causing significant losses, encouraging increased population of natural enemies like predators, parasitoids, and pathogens, saving money to producing a high quality and quantity of crops with less pollution, and less environmental impacts.

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Control of wireworms by wood ash and aqueous extract of olives

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Abstract:

This study was conducted to evaluate the role of four concentrations (25, 50, 75 and 100) g /L from the aqueous extract of the olive wood plant and ash to control the worm, *Agriotes lineatus* (L.) (Coleoptera: Elateridae). The results showed that the worm, *A. lineatus* mortality rate increased significantly when it reached the water extract of olive plant (10,30,50 and 70%) after three hours of treatment . While it reached using olive wood ash (30, 50 , 80 and 100%) after 24 hours .The results also showed that the ash of olive wood as is more effective than the aqueous extract of olive plant and the same concentrations above ,and the results were analyzed using a complete randomized design .

Introduction

Wireworms are important and dangerous pests on potatoes, the species of the genus *Agriotes*, *Agriotes lineatus* (Linnaeus) (Coleoptera: Elateridae) is one of the most important pest species on potato crop. Wireworms feed on newly grown seeds, small roots and seedlings, killing plants directly or injuring them (AL-Jorany and Sadik, 2014). These wounds are an ideal gateway to opportunistic pathogens that aggravate symptoms. In the potato crop, potato seeds can be dug in the spring into growing tubers in the fall. Symptoms are caused by the stage of immature larvae and can be up to 2 cm long, and have slender and cylindrical objects with a yellowish-white or coppery color. Crop damage is usually detected after planting and it is too late to take effective measures. This makes sure that

the field is free from the worm. It is possible to implement a number of agricultural measures that help to reduce the acidity of the soil and create unfavorable conditions for the worm habitat (Vernon and Pats, 1997) The olive tree is one of the oldest trees that man has dealt with since ancient times (Guinda *et al.* , 2004). Researchers have found that linoleic acid, which is present in olive leaves, can kill many bacteria, viruses and parasitic primitives (Gordon *et al.*, 2001). Ash is used as an organic fertilizer to improve agricultural soils, being a source of potassium and calcium carbonate and is an environmentally friendly alternative. It is used to control the smell of compost in agricultural applications, especially in fertilization. Studies show that kiln ash plays an important role in controlling pests of

stores. The ancient Egyptians relied on mixing grains with the ashes of furnaces because of its great role in absorbing moisture from grains and seeds (Abdel Gawad and Khatab, 1985) , as well as scratching the layer of cuticle covering the body of the insect lose moisture and die (Akob and Ewete, 2007).

The aim of this study is to evaluate the role of the aqueous extract of the olive wood plant and ash to control the wireworm, *A. lineatus*.

Material and methods

Samples were obtained from the soil of onion field in Kirkuk containing the worm and the soil PH was measured by a sunflower leaf. The color from yellow to red is an indicator of the acidic soil and placed in plastic cans capacity of one liter and covered cans with cloth. The olive tree pruning was then collected, the wood burned and the resulting ash sifted and sifted on a 40m sieve in order to obtain homogeneity of the ash pellets for use in subsequent experiments. Four concentrations of ash 20, 50, 75 and 100% were used. Prepare aqueous extract after crushing the plant by 1-2 fabric / water using hot distilled water and placed in the incubator vibrator at 40 ° C for 48 hours after filtering by filter paper and then put the filtrate in the centrifuge for 4 minutes at a speed (4000 r / min), then was prepared. Several concentrations (100,75,50 and 25) per sample, 10 wireworms were taken for each repeater and sprayed at the above concentrations using a plastic sprinkler and three replicates for each concentration. After three hours, the mortality rate was calculated, and the results were analyzed using the complete random design. Chemical detection of some active compounds in olive leaves was also used: Mulchen reagents, benedict, and iodine test to detect the presence of multiple glycosides. It revealed the aldehyde amino acids. and aqueous ferric chloride to detect phenols. Turbidity revealed resins. marquez (prepared from the addition of 40%

formaldehyde to 10 ml of concentrated sulfuric acid) and a volume of 3 ml and picric acid 2 ml to detect alkaloids. The shaking method was also used in detecting soap. To detect the turbines, 1 g of dry extract was taken in a little chloroform and a drop of anhydrous acetic acid from concentrated sulfuric acid was added.

Results and discussion

The results of Table (1) of the olive plant showed that it contains the active compounds glycosides, phenolic compounds, resins, soaps, alkaloids and turbines. It was observed that there was a significant and direct effect on the worm *A. lineatus* mortality rate at different concentrations of olive leaf extract. The reason may be due to the presence of some toxic compounds resulting from the metabolic activities of the olive plant that affect and interfere with many physiological activities of the insect (Al-Araji, 2003). Bowers (1984) explained that larval mortality was caused by the action of certain plant compounds in killing the epithelial cells lining the insect's gut duct. As shown in Table (2), there is a direct correlation between the concentration of the extract of the olive plant and the percentage of insect decay as the percentage of wire worm decay using concentrations (25,50, 75 and 100). Wireworms and the results are identical with Abbas (1998) and Al-Rubaie *et al.* (2000). As for Table (3) a direct correlation was observed between the concentration of olive wood ash and insect mortality. The effectiveness of olive wood ash concentration was evaluated (25,50,75, and 100) g. The mortality rate was calculated after 24 hours due to the physical properties of the ash. Different types of ash are effective in protecting seeds from storage insects (Ofuya and Salami, 2002 and Appel *et al.*, 1999). The modern control strategy relied on reducing the possible use of pesticides and replacing them with other safe materials and methods to preserve the environment (Hagstrum *et al.*, 2010). The most important

of these methods are the use of repellents, extracts, vegetable oils and furnace ash as one of the modern trends of insect pests. Ash is used as an organic fertilizer to improve agricultural soils, being a source of potassium

and calcium carbonate and is an alternative to the environment, Ash is also light weight, so it is applied in a very large amount to make the soil alkaline due to low pH (Misra *et al.*, 1993 and Jean *et al.*, 2015).

Table (1) : Effective chemical compounds in olive leaf extract.

Effective chemical compounds	The result
Glycosides	+
Phenolic compounds	+
Resins	+
Alkali	+
Soaps	+
Turbines	+

(+) Means the presence of the compound in the plant extract.

Table (2): Effect of olive plant extract on *Agriotes lineatus* .

Concentrations / G / l	<i>Agriotes lineatus</i>	%Perdition
25	9	10
50	7	30
75	5	50
100	3	70

P - Value = 0.000

Table (3): Effect of olive wood ash on soil containing *Agriotes lineatus* .

Time	Concentrations / G / l	<i>Agriotes lineatus</i>	%Perdition
24	25	7	30
	50	5	50
	75	2	80
	100	0	100

p - Value = 0.000

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Control of the brown garden snail *Eobania vermiculata* (Gastropoda : Helicidae) adults using baits of usable and expired Kz mineral oil and its effect on aminotransferase enzymes activity

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Abstract:

Mineral oils are considering a promising control agent against wide varieties of pests all over the world. In this paper, focus on the baits of usable and expired Kz mineral oil against the adults of the brown garden snail *Eobania vermiculata* (Müller) (Gastropoda : Helicidae) under both of laboratory and field conditions. The baits of expired Kz oil against *E. vermiculata* adults, considering as novel technique. Under laboratory conditions, the highest mortalities (%) of snails were (73.33 %) recorded with a concentration 20 % of usable Kz oil followed by (66.67 %) for expired Kz oil at the same concentration after three weeks of treatment. Field results were recorded reduction in population of snails by (31.93 and 27.83 %) from used baits of usable and expired Kz oil, respectively at concentration (10 %) after three weeks from treatment. At concentration (20 %) and the same field conditions, mortalities (%) were (68.19 and 62.08 %) with usable and expired Kz oil, respectively. Biochemical studies were recorded increasing percentage reached its maximum level for tested snails after one week of aspartate aminotransferase (AST) and alanine aminotransferase (ALT) enzymes recorded (-11.92 and -3.52) and (-33.33 and -5.39) for snails treatment using baits of usable Kz oil, at concentrations 10 and 20 % respectively, (- 9.26 and - 4.58) and (- 29.93 and - 12.53) for snails treatment using baits of expired Kz oil, at the same concentrations, respectively.

Introduction

Snails are gastropod animals which live in marine and fresh water, but others have successfully colonized land and known as pests in many places of the world. Some of land snails are very important pests of agricultural crops, in addition to the role as intermediate hosts for many parasitic diseases

which infest human, animals and birds (Godan, 1983; Barker, 2002 and Mahrous *et al.*, 2002). Therefore, land gastropods cause costly damage to field crops, vegetables and fruit trees as well as ornamental plants (Nakhla *et al.*, 1993 and Godan, 1983). While, control of these snails is becoming

very important. The terrestrial snail (brown garden snail) *Eobania vermiculata* (Müller) (Gastropoda : Helicidae) was recorded to be harmful snails in many districts of Egypt attacking various plants (Eshra, 2013). Unfortunately, about 25 million agricultural workers in developing countries are poisoned every year by pesticides (Jeyaratnam, 1990). Attention is increasingly being paid to the use of synthetic chemical compounds became unsafe method in controlling pests as they are one of the major reasons in the environmental pollution and cause a chronic disease for humans and harmful for most of the living organisms. That's why the usage of these chemicals decreased all over the world and humans continued to find practical alternatives. Mineral oils are considering one of the safest methods in controlling pests especially the scale insects infesting different plants. Also, they play a fundamental role in the IPM programs on many pests (Helmy *et al.*, 2012). A finding by this work aimed to study the toxic (as field trials) and physiological (as laboratory trials) effects of baits of usable and expired Kz oil against adults of *E. vermiculata* snail.

Materials and methods

1. Tested animals:

Land snail, the brown garden snail *E. vermiculata* adults were collected from orchard cultivated with sago palm at Zagazig district, Sharkia Governorate, Egypt. The collected snails were immediately transferred in white cloth bags to the laboratory. Healthy and similar individuals were chosen and kept in glass terrarium filled with moist clay soil adjusted at 75 % of water field capacity. Snails were fed daily with bran for two weeks before treatment for acclimatization.

2. Tested oils:

Usable and expired oil (95%) purchased from company of Kafr El-Zayat for pesticides and chemicals, Kafr El-Zayat district at Gharbia Governorate, Egypt.

3. Toxicity studies:

3.1. Laboratory test using poisonous baits technique:

Three concentrations 5, 10, and 20 % for tested oils were prepared by incorporating the appropriate amount of each compound with bran bait. Three plastic boxes (3/4 kg capacity) were used for each concentration. Five grams of baits were spread into each box. Control treatment was prepared using bran bait. Five adult individuals of *E. vermiculata* snail were put into each plastic box, then covered with muslin cloth and secured with rubber band. Dead individuals were counted using stainless steel needle according to El-Okda (1980). Mortality percentages were calculated after 1, 3, 7, 14 and 21 days and corrected by Abbott's formula (1925).

3.2. Field application:

The field trial was conducted in orchard cultivated with sago palm at, Zagazig district, Sharkia Governorate, Egypt. The field area was divided into five plots, each including control, each plot was divided into three replicates for each treatment. Area of about 50 m² was left as buffer between each plot. Baits were offered on blue plastic pieces each provided with 100 gm. Reduction percentages were calculated according to the formula of Henderson and Tilton (1955) as follows:

$$\% \text{ Reduction} = [1 - (t_2 \times r_1) / (t_1 \times r_2)] \times 100$$

Whereas:

r_1 = Number of alive snails before treatment in untreated plots.

r_2 = Number of alive snails after treatment in untreated plots.

t_1 = Number of alive snails before treatment in treated plots.

t_2 = Number of alive snails after treatment in treated plots.

4. Biochemical studies:

4.1. Preparation of snails for biochemical assay:

The adult mollusca shells of *E. vermiculata* snails were removed and the soft tissues were weighed, pooled, and homogenized as 1:10 (w/v) in distilled water.

The homogenates were centrifuged at 5000 r.p.m for 20 minutes at 5 °C according to Abd El-Haleim *et al.* (2006). The supernatants were used as enzyme source for aspartate aminotransferase (AST) and alanine aminotransferase (ALT). Activities of enzymes were measured according to the method described by Reitman and Frankel (1957).

5. Statistical analysis:

The statistical analysis was determined by using one-way test, (ANOVA), Cohort software (2005).

Results and discussion

1. Effect of usable and expired Kz oil against adults of *Eobania vermiculata* snail under laboratory conditions:

Using baits technique, data in Table (1) revealed a highly significance between the three concentrations (5, 10 and 20%) of Kz oil (usable and expired) than control. Where mortality percentages were 26.67, 40.00 and 73.33 %, and 20.00, 33.33 and

66.67 % for usable and expired Kz oil, respectively after three weeks of treatment. Finally, results obtained revealed that mortalities increased with increasing the concentrations. For instances, Helmy *et al.* (1982) stated that mineral oils of various qualities have traditionally been used as curatives to down insects and mites. Shahawy (2005) showed that the pesticide comate 500 (85% cotton seed oil) was the lowest effective compound with 2.5 % mortality percentage against *Monacha cantiana* (Montagu) (Gastropoda : Hygromiidae) snail after 12 days. Farag *et al.* (2010) indicated that long term used frying oils displayed more deformations in rat organs than that used for shorter period. Kaleem *et al.* (2015) found that rancidity of oils can produce potentially toxic compounds associated with long-term health effects such as neurological disorders, heart and cancer, may support the reuse of usable and expired Kz oil in baits controlling snails.

Table (1): Effect of usable and expired Kz mineral oil on adults of *Eobania vermiculata* snail using baits technique under laboratory conditions.

Kz oil	Concentrations	Mortality percentages				
		One day	Three days	One week	Two weeks	Three weeks
Usable	5 %	0.00 ^c	0.00 ^d	13.33 ^{cd}	20.00 ^c	26.67 ^{cd}
	10 %	6.67 ^{bc}	13.33 ^{bc}	20.00 ^{bc}	33.33 ^b	40.00 ^b
	20 %	20.00 ^a	26.67 ^a	33.33 ^a	53.33 ^a	73.33 ^a
Expired	5 %	0.00 ^c	0.00 ^d	6.67 ^{dc}	13.33 ^c	20.00 ^d
	10 %	6.67 ^{bc}	6.67 ^{cd}	13.33 ^{cd}	20.00 ^c	33.33 ^{bc}
	20 %	13.33 ^{ab}	20.00 ^{ab}	26.67 ^{ab}	53.33 ^a	66.67 ^a
Control		0.00 ^c	0.00 ^d	0.00 ^e	0.00 ^d	0.00 ^e
LSD _{0.05}		7.64***	8.82***	10.81***	10.80***	*** 10.79

2. Effect of against adults of *Eobania vermiculata* snail under field conditions by baits technique:

The results in Table (2) showed that the initial effect after one day were (2.87 and 7.49 %) and (2.29 and 6.32 %) for usable and expired Kz oil at concentrations (10 and 20%), respectively. The residual effect on reduction percentages were (31.93 and 68.19

%) and (27.83 and 62.08 %) after three weeks for Kz oil (usable and expired) at the same concentrations, respectively. Data revealed a significance between the two concentrations (10 and 20%) of Kz oil (usable and expired) by time elapsing except after three days of treatment than control. The reduction percentages were increased.

Table (2): Effect of usable and expired Kz mineral oil on adults of *Eobania vermiculata* snail using baits technique under field conditions.

Kz mineral oil	Conc. (%)	Number of snails before treatment	Initial effect		Residual effect								
			One day		Three days		One week		Two weeks		Three weeks		Mean for red.
			No.	% Red.	No.	% Red.	No.	% Red.	No.	% Red.	No.	% Red.	
Usable	10 %	43.74	43.19	2.87 ^{bc}	43.05	5.89 ^b	41.87	10.97 ^b	40.37	19.37 ^b	35.65	31.93 ^c	14.21 ^b
	20 %	57.97	54.52	7.49 ^a	53.89	11.11 ^a	49.35	20.82 ^a	37.79	43.05 ^a	22.08	68.19 ^a	30.13 ^a
Expired	10 %	48.19	47.87	2.29 ^c	47.63	5.49 ^b	46.23	10.78 ^b	44.96	18.50 ^b	41.64	27.83 ^c	12.98 ^b
	20 %	52.09	49.61	6.32 ^{ab}	48.86	10.31 ^a	45.17	19.35 ^a	33.98	43.01 ^a	23.65	62.08 ^b	28.21 ^a
Control		63.29	64.34		66.19		68.05		72.45		75.78		
LSD _{0.05}				3.65*		5.95 ^{ns}		7.47*		5.62***		4.98***	4.51***

by increasing concentration. Similar results were recorded by Aly *et al.* (1984) found that mineral oil showed a considerable reduction (99.2% reduction after 60 days from treatment) when used on the soft scale insect *Pulvinaria psidii* Maskell (Hemiptera: Coccidae) infesting guava trees. Ismail and Abdel Kader (2011) where reduction percentages for *Monacha cartusiana* (Müller) (Gastropoda : Hygromiidae) adult snails were 39.6, 57.2 and 62.4 % for (1, 2 and 4 %), respectively concentrations of essential oil of *Syzygium aromaticum* using baiting technique under field conditions after 21 days. Farag (2012) tested castor oil at concentration (40%) against *M. cartusiana* and found that the initial effect gave (6.54%) reduction while the residual effect recorded (53.12%) reduction at three weeks. Helmy *et al.* (2012) showed that the modes of action of mineral oils on insects are death of newly hatched individuals and it's also may act as poisons, interacting with the fatty acids of the

insect and interfering with normal metabolism.

3. Biochemical studies:

The obtained results in Table (3) found remarked increase in the activity of aspartate aminotransferase (AST) and alanine aminotransferase (ALT) enzymes in adults of *E. vermiculata* treated with baits of usable and expired Kz oil compared to control. The increasing percentages reached its maximum level for tested snails by time elapsing were recorded (-29.76, -18.16 and -11.92) and (-16.05, -10.86 and -3.52) of AST enzyme and (-61.68, -55.39 and -33.33) and (-43.27, -41.76 and -5.39) of ALT enzyme for snails treatment of usable Kz oil, at concentrations 10 and 20 % respectively, (-25.53, -14.79 and -9.26) and (-11.51, -6.51 and -4.58) of AST enzyme and (-53.27, -50.20 and -29.93) and (-31.35, -16.77 and -12.53) of ALT enzyme for snails treatment using baits of expired Kz oil, at the same concentrations, respectively. The activity of AST and ALT

Table (3): Changes in (AST and ALT) enzymes activity in adults of *Eobania vermiculata* snail treated with used usable and expired Kz mineral oil using baits technique.

Kz mineral oil	Concentrations (%)		AST			ALT		
			One day	Three days	One week	One day	Three days	One week
Usable	10 %	SA	20.39 ^d	23.52 ^c	25.78 ^b	6.43 ^c	7.82 ^b	11.76 ^c
		RA%	-29.76	-18.16	-11.92	-61.68	-55.39	-33.33
	20 %	SA	24.37 ^{bc}	25.62 ^{abc}	28.24 ^{ab}	9.52 ^{bc}	10.21 ^b	16.69 ^a
		RA%	-16.05	-10.86	-3.52	-43.27	-41.76	-5.39
Expired	10 %	SA	21.62 ^{cd}	24.49 ^{bc}	26.56 ^b	7.84 ^{bc}	8.73 ^b	12.36 ^{bc}
		RA%	-25.53	-14.79	-9.26	-53.27	-50.20	-29.93
	20 %	SA	25.69 ^{ab}	26.87 ^{ab}	27.93 ^{ab}	11.52 ^b	14.59 ^a	15.43 ^{ab}
		RA%	-11.51	-6.51	-4.58	-31.35	-16.77	-12.53
Control		SA	29.03 ^a	28.74 ^a	29.27 ^a	16.78 ^a	17.53 ^a	17.64 ^a
L.S. D _{0.05}			3.90 ^{**}	3.15 [*]	2.57 ^{ns}	4.95 ^{**}	3.15 ^{***}	3.45 [*]

SA = Specific activity as ($\mu\text{g pyruvate/ml}$)RA% = (Relative activity %) = $[(\text{Treatment} - \text{Control}) / \text{Control}] \times 100$

were decreased as a result of all treatments compared to control. Data found that a significance between the two concentrations (10 and 20%) of Kz oil (usable and expired) by time elapsing except one week of treatment of AST than control. Results agree with those reported by Lebsack *et al.* (1980) who mentioned that the possible mechanism involved in the elevation of AST and ALT levels may be due to tissue damage. Tilkian *et al.* (1983) studied the pathogenesis effects which response enzymes activation and stated that the amount of AST was directly proportional to the number of cells damaged. Amer *et al.* (1994) found that the increase of AST and ALT activities may be referred to the diffusion of these enzymes from its intracellular sites due to damage caused by the insecticide on the subcellular level. Soliman *et al.* (2007) studied the effect of mineral oils on rats (as an example of mammals), they found that oils caused increase in white blood cells counts, AST and ALT activities of treated rats after 15 and 30 days from treatment comparison with control. Farag (2012) reported that using baits of castor oil on *M. cartusiana* snail caused decrease of AST activity and increase of ALT activity. Generally, alteration in the activity of AST and ALT are known to be

helpful in the diagnosis of hepatic infarcts or damage.

Paper inspected likelihood of using baits of usable and expired Kz oil as a save and inexpensive manner to control adults of the brown garden snail *E. vermiculata*. So, it is concluded that the used usable and expired Kz oil are toxic on adults of *E. vermiculata* snail where it induces the increase in reduction percentage in field. Where, the connection between baits of Kz mineral oil (usable and expired) and activity of aspartate aminotransferase and alanine aminotransferase enzymes of *E. vermiculata* snail was investigated.

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Land snails and soil as bio-indicators of some heavy metals pollution in Sharqia and Qalyubiya Governorates, Egypt

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Abstract:

Recently, land snails dispersed in the Nile Delta and it considered a perfect environmental pollution bio-indicator for many reasons. In this study, the level of Pb (Lead), Cu (Copper), Cd (Cadmium), Mo (Molybdenum) and Zn (Zinc), heavy metals as bio-indicator of metal pollution by analysis soil and snail samples in Sharqia and Qalyubiya Governorates were determined using atomic absorption device elements. Results showed that most tested elements were higher in the field border (at 5 meter far from the car road) than that inside the infested field (at 100 meter far from the car road). The highest metal concentration was Mo with *Monacha cartusiana* (Müller) (Gastropoda: Hygromiidae) with a value of 260.5411 ppm while the lowest concentration was Zn (soil) with a value of 0.105 ppm in Sharqia Governorate. Regarding Qalyubiya Governorate, Cu with *Eobania vermiculata* (Müller) (Gastropoda: Helicidae) value at 5 meters was the highest 211.275ppm and the lowest element was Cd (soil) at 5 meters 0.2025ppm. Finally, Qalyubiya Governorate was more polluted than Sharqia Governorate. These results indicated that land snails are a suitable bio-indicator of heavy metal pollution.

Introduction

The snails are very important part of the food chain and excellent source of calcium in the ecosystem for the birds during their breeding season. They are intermediate hosts of many parasites (Altaf *et al.*, 2017). Land snails are very appropriate as environmental monitor's in-situ because they are sedentary, abundant, of relative longevity, large, easily collected and weighed. Patterns of accumulation of one specific element show a remarkable consistency when different sites

are compared (Ademoroti, 1996). Biomonitoring attempts with snails have found an increasing interest during the last decade and several promising projects have already been conducted (Dallinger *et al.*, 2000). Nowakowska (2011) used terrestrial snails as bioindicators of the environmental pollution due to their capacity to accumulate heavy metals in their tissues and limited ability to excrete the metals. Heavy metals are natural components of the environment,

but they are of concern lately because they are being added to soil, water, and air in increasing amounts. This is because of the rapid growth of population, increased urbanization, expansion of industrial activities, and more (Aksoy *et al.*, 2000). Most of the heavy metals are essential elements to living organisms, but their excessive amounts are generally harmful to plants and animals; the poison of heavy metals depends a great deal on their chemical form, concentrations, residence time, etc. (WHO, 1972; Schubrek, 1973 and Mielke and Reagan, 1988). As (WHO, 2000) described, heavy metals, depending on their oxidation state, can be highly reactive and thus toxic to most organisms. They have long residence times in soil and may continue to exert long-lasting harmful effects (Menon *et al.*, 2007). Soil is the major collector for heavy metals released into the environment by anthropogenic activities. Heavy metals contamination of soil may pose risk and hazards to humans and the ecosystem through the food chain, drinking of contaminated ground water, reduction in food quality (safety and market ability), reduction in land usability for agricultural production causing doubts on food security, and land tenure problems (Malik, 2004; Manohar *et al.*, 2006 and Nica *et al.*, 2012). Paula *et al.* (2012) analyzed the snail *Theba pisana* (Müller) (Gastropoda : Helicidae) as an indicator of soil contamination by trace elements after a mine spill accident, to assess the exposure of animal and human consumption. Trace elements in the soft tissues reached greater concentrations in the contaminated soils than in the non-contaminated soils were only found for As, Cd, Cu, Fe and Hg. Cadmium content in tissues, with a maximum value of 10 mg kg⁻¹ (dry matter), was the most worrying result. Trace element concentrations in the snail bodies were still of concern for human consumption; concentrations of As and Cd were sometimes higher than the maximum concentration

authorized in food stuffs. Generally, nutritional status of the contaminated snails was not altered; concentrations of the main nutrients (Ca, K, Mg, P and S) were like those of the non-contaminated snails.

The present study aimed to evaluate the potential for using land snails and soil as biomonitors of heavy-metal pollution at metal levels that are sub-hazardous to humans.

Materials and methods

1. Snails and soil sampling:

Snails and soil specimens were collected from two infested fields. The first field cited at El-Mohammadia, Meniet El-Kamh district, Sharqia Governorate. While the second at Moshtoher, Toukh district, Qalyubiya Governorate. All collected snails were in adult stage; only fully grown specimens were collected since this is the product consumed by the local population. The snails were put in clean plastic bags and transported to the laboratory. Soil samples were collected at various intervals from the road of cars *viz* 5 and 100 meters at a depth of 0-5 cm from the surface around snail sites using a hand grab sampler. Soil samples were kept in a polyethylene bag and later air-dried in the laboratory for determination of heavy metal concentrations.

2. Snails preparation:

In the laboratory, the snails were washed thoroughly with distilled water. The shell was cracked with a wooden hammer, the body was again washed with distilled water and stored at -18° C prior to analysis with Estimate the concentration of elements in the sample by atomic absorption device elements (Perkin-Elmer, 1964) at central Agricultural Pesticides Laboratory, Faculty of Agriculture, Zagazig University.

3. Soil sample processing:

3.1. Weight 1 g of sample and put it in the combustion degree oven 500°c for two days.

3.2. Add a 3 mm nitric acid mm center of acid bear calorific.

3.3. Fully complement the sample after digestion with distilled water to the known size and run.

3.4. So, the sample is ready to estimate the concentration of the elements.

4. Measurement device:

4.1. Open the power and gas pressure regulation.

4.2. Set the item you want to soundings lamp and adjust the wavelength of the element.

4.3. Drawing the curve record on the computer waist measuring 3 concentrations equipped and information focus.

4.4. The introduction of the sample for measurement.

4.5. The computer assigns element concentration in the sample (ppm).

Results and discussion

Heavy metal concentrations in land snails and soil samples collected from Sharqia and Qalyubiya Governorates at different distances away of the road are

Table (1): Concentration of heavy metals in soil and some land snails at Sharqia Governorate.

Elements	Pb	Cu	Cd	Mo	Zn
Samples					
Soil at 5 m	0.2710	0.1495	0.0	37.603	0.105
Soil at 100 m	0.2715	0.2635	0.0	33.1985	0.169
<i>Eobania vermiculata</i> at 5 m	1.3333	64.3480	0.541	72.1521	25.7892
<i>Eobania vermiculata</i> at 100 m	1.6149	41.1013	0.4886	80.5369	13.4640
<i>Monacha cartusiana</i> at 5 m	4.7724	35.1660	0.6950	260.5411	40.8302
<i>Monacha cartusiana</i> at 100 m	1.9537	33.594	0.1891	120.0812	20.7345

Pb=Lead, Cu=Copper, Cd=Cadmium, Mo= Molybdenum, Zn=Zinc.

The present data in Table (2) mentioned that three land snails infested the field *E. vermiculata*, *M. cartusiana* and *T. pisana* in Qalyubiya Governorate. Most tested heavy metals were higher in the field border (at 5 m) than at 100m. On the other hand, Cu, Cd and Mo increased in soil samples taken at 100 m more than at 5m. 1.1175, 0.2045, 14.3785 and 0.8015 ppm respectively. Pb and Zn these elements increase inside the field in case of *E. vermiculata* where samples recorded 8.7075 and 98.2 ppm respectively. On the other hand, Cd, Mo and Zn increased in *M. cartusiana* samples taken from inside the

given. Table (1) showed that two land snails *Eobania vermiculata* (Müller) (Gastropoda: Helicidae) and *Monacha cartusiana* (Müller) (Gastropoda: Hygromiidae) infested the field at Sharqia Governorate and heavy metal concentrations in land snails, soil samples at different distances away of the road. The elements Pb (*M. cartusiana*), Cu (*E. vermiculata*), Cu (*M. cartusiana*), Cd (*E. vermiculata*), Cd (*M. cartusiana*), Mo (soil) Mo (*M. cartusiana*) Zn (*E. vermiculata*) and Zn (*M. cartusiana*) concentrations were higher in the field at 5 m than at 100 m from the cars road. Inversely, elements Pb, Cu and Zn in tested soil samples increase inside the field were 0.2715, 0.2635 and 0.1690 respectively, the level of Cd in soil was rather too low to detect. The heavy metals Pb and Mo

values in tested *E. vermiculata* tissues at 100 m were higher compared to the distance 5m as 1.6149 and 80.5369, respectively.

field (at 5 m) more than from the field border where recorded 1.5425, 56.08 and 55.35 ppm, respectively. All elements in *T. pisana* samples were higher at 5m than at 100m. Results in this study cleared that the heavy metals in Qalyubiya Governorate were more than in Sharqia governorate, except Molybdenum which was high. Generally, Molybdenum was the most elements present in Sharqia governorate, while Cu was the most element present in Qalyubiya Governorate. The heavy metals copper (Cu) and lead (Pb) is based on the use of Cu as a major constituent of agricultural pesticides, which the snails are inadvertently exposed to.

However, Pb has been an additive of petroleum products which gets introduced into the environment during burning of the fossil fuels and ultimately become deposited on the leaves and soil where the snails dwell (Otitoloju *et al.*, 2009). Cadmium has no biological function and is highly toxic to plants and animals. The major hazard to human health from cadmium is its chronic accumulation in the kidney where it can cause dysfunction if the concentration in the cortex exceeds 200mg/kg fresh weight. Cardiovascular disease has been related to ingestion and inhalation of Cadmium. (Gomot, 1997). Vyskocil and Viau (1999) a low order of toxicity of molybdenum compounds has been observed in humans. Molybdenum toxicity is associated with copper intake or depleted copper stores in the body. Wegwu and Wigwe (2006) reported that the low concentration of Zinc may be attributed to zinc-deficient soils, consequently the debris available to the snails

Theba

is zinc-poor; combined with the fact that zinc is an essential metal of a high turnover rate it may results in a low tissue content of the element. Paula *et al.* (2012) a potential risk for animal and human consumption of *T. pisana*. it seems thus advisable to avoid collecting this species for human consumption in the affected area. Periodic monitoring is recommended to assess the evolution of potential risk for animal consumption. The study of the effects of metals and other contaminants on the physiology of organisms leads to the development of several toxicity tests that can be used as a tool for environmental assessment. There are many ways in which toxicants affect the individual, such as reduction of growth, feeding activity, reproductive capacity, and metabolite storage. Feeding and growth responses of the animals are broadly accepted ecotoxicological endpoints (Carbone and Faggio, 2019).

Table (2): Concentration of heavy metals in soil and some land snails at Qalyubiya Governorate.

Elements	Pb	Cu	Cd	Mo	Zn
Samples					
Soil at 5 m	1.0465	0.7955	0.2025	6.523	1.1605
Soil at 100 m	0.7005	1.1175	0.2045	14.3785	0.8015
<i>Eobania vermiculata</i> at 5 m	4.8575	211.275	7.005	49.92	72.05
<i>Eobania vermiculata</i> at 100 m	8.7075	67.4375	1.76	44.5125	98.2
<i>Monacha cartusiana</i> at 5 m	17.935	55.455	1.5	44.945	39.875
<i>Monacha cartusiana</i> at 100 m	9.535	34.16	1.5425	56.08	55.35
<i>Theba pisana</i> at 5 m	7.32	105.2675	1.765	66.735	35.16
<i>Theba pisana</i> at 100 m	5.965	30.435	1.245	49.4475	18.2675

Pb=Lead, Cu=Copper, Cd=Cadmium, Mo= Molybdenum, Zn=Zinc.

It is concluded that land snails were found to be a good bio-indicator for air pollution. The variation in heavy metal concentrations between the studied locations is due to heavy traffic load and anthropogenic activities.

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Control of the rice weevil *Sitophilus oryzae* (Coleoptera: Curculionidae) using some insecticide alternative safe methods

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Abstract:

This work aimed to evaluate the efficacy of certain safe control methods against the rice weevil *Sitophilus oryzae* (L.) (Coleoptera: Curculionidae). Adults of *S. oryzae* were exposed to CO₂ or N₂ gas differ in relative humidity content at two degrees of temperature. Mortality of insect was influenced significantly by the level of relative humidity in the inert gas ambient. The highest percentages of insect mortality were recorded for lowest and the highest level of humidity at both degrees of temperature. At the moderate levels of humidity (50 and 60%) the insect mortality was slightly reduced than that of the lowest and the highest levels of humidity at both degrees of temperature, especially for the shortest exposure periods. It was showed also that a complete mortality was occurred for the insects exposed to the CO₂ at the lowest (35%) and the highest (80%) levels of humidity. Four doses of ECO₂-Fume gas (30, 35, 40 and 50 g/m³) were tested against the different developmental stages and adults of *S. oryzae* in wheat grains piles under natural conditions. All tested doses induced a considerable control for all stages of the rice weevil, efficacy was increased as the dose increased, so that, a dose of 50 g/m³ induced 100% mortality of all insect stages after 3 days of treatment.

Introduction

The rice weevil *Sitophilus oryzae* (L.) (Coleoptera: Curculionidae) is a very serious pest of stored grain. This species infests kernels of various cereals causing excessive losses in quality and quantity during grain storage, many practices were used, one of them was the use of insecticides, which considered the most commonly utilized

method by many countries (Harein and Davis, 1992; Bell, 1993 and Arthur, 1994). In these countries, the indiscriminate and improper use of insecticides to control the proliferation of stored grain insects, has resulted in several problems.

It is therefore imperative to develop alternative methods that are economically

feasible and ecologically oriented to control stored grain insects and fungi. Hermetic storage is considered one of these alternative methods (Villers *et al.*, 2010 and Boardman *et al.*, 2011). The use of hermetic storage for the preservation of food stuffs is as old as it is new and modern. Hermetic storage of grain was practiced in ancient times in underground pits in the dry, subtropical regions of the Middle East, North Africa and India, etc. Modified atmosphere is a technique involves changes the composition of the normal atmospheric constituents of O₂, N₂ and CO₂ in a sealed store to create an atmosphere lethal to insects at an adequate length of time. It appears that high concentrations of CO₂ in combination with low humidity could prove lethal to insects by causing rapid loss of water through the spiracles. This possibility was also suggested by the results of earlier investigations (Pearman and Jay, 1970).

ECO₂-Fume fumigant gas is a liquefied mixture of 2% wt. PH₃ (2.6% vol.) with carbon dioxide (CO₂). This mixture has been patented by Boc Gases of Australia. This mixture of PH₃ with CO₂ ensures it is non-flammable in all proportions with air. This eliminates all safety concerns with dispensing rates or dilution rates. Traditional solid formulations can generate PH₃ concentration above the lower flammability limit for PH₃ thereby creating a hazard. ECO₂-Fume is considered one of the most alternatives of methyl bromide (MB), that will not harm the ozone layer.

The present work was undertaken to investigate the following points: 1. Effect of relative humidity levels on the efficacy of CO₂ and N₂ gases against *S. oryzae* adults under laboratory conditions. 2. Efficacy of ECO₂-Fume gas against all stages of *S. oryzae* under field conditions.

Materials and methods

1. Test insect:

One of the most dangerous insect pests to cereal grains (*S. oryzae*) was chosen

for this study. The cultures were started by large batches of adults initially collected from the infested stored products in warehouses at Zagazig region, Sharqyia Governorate, the collected insects were mass reared for several generations using the following technique:

1.1. Rearing technique of stock cultures:

1.1.1. Rearing medium:

Wheat grains variety Sakha 93 was used as a rearing host. Fresh wheat grains were firstly examined to insure it is in a good case and free of toxic residues then it was tightly packaged in plastic bags and kept at -13°C, in a deep freezer for at least 48 h to kill any infestation that might be present. The kernels were conditioned with respect to the moisture content to be about 14% before starting the rearing or any experiment.

1.1.2. Rearing of adult stage developmental stages of *Sitophilus oryzae* for gas exposure:

Batches of 200 adults each of 1 - 2 weeks old were sifted out from the cultures and introduced into 1 kg glass jars half filled with fresh medium (conditioned wheat grains + dry yeast). After two days of egg deposition the adults were removed and transferred to other new prepared jars and the medium were returned to the jars. A quantity of medium with 0 - 2 day old eggs was thus maintained in the same jars of culture at the same condition of rearing until emergence of adults. Batches of 30 adults each (1- 2 weeks old) were collected from the cultures using a fine brush and glass tubes. These batches were transferred into wire gauze cages contained quantities of medium and used for testing.

2. Gas experiments:

2.1. Vessels of insect exposure to gases:

2.1.1. Cages of insect gas exposure (exposure vials):

Ready made plastic-wire gauze cages (3x6 cm) used for water household apparatus were used for insect exposure to gases.

2.1.2. Plastic bags (exposure chamber):

The known urine collection bags (call also drainage bags in field of medicine) were used as gas exposure chambers for the experiments of gases bioassay against the tested insects. These bags are rectangular in a shape (18 x 23 cm) and 2000 ml capacity. Each bag has two tubes (hoses) at the both long ends. One of the two tubes is long (inlet tube) at the front of the bag and the other tube (outlet tube) is very short and located at the other end of the bag. Each tube has at its free end a built -in valve with cover which could be tightly closed.

2.2. Gas exposure procedures:

The cages of the adults which reared and prepared as mentioned before were put (three replicates for each experiment) inside the plastic bags (exposure chambers) through a lateral cut wool were wet thoroughly by the tap water to give the respective level of relative humidity when introduced inside the gas exposure chamber. Piece of 1 g cotton wool to give about 60% RH. and a piece of 3 g to give about 80% RH.). Small hygrometer was introduced inside each gas exposure chamber to indicate the level of humidity. Silica gel bags of 20.2 g (total weight) were introduced into the exposure chamber to obtain the low level of relative humidity (35% RH.). The bags were tightly sealed using a hand pressing sealer. The air inside the bag could get out by gently pressing on the bag and then the bag was connected to gas cylinder (CO₂ or N₂) through a rubber hose and the long tube of the bag. The gas could purge very slowly inside the bag for about 20 -30 seconds to ensure completely exchanging the air inside the bag with the tested gas without any pressure inside the bag. Valves of the treated bags were tightly closed, and the bags were kept in the rearing room at the tested temperature, (20 or 30±2°C) for different periods of gas exposure, i.e., 7, 14 and 21 days. At the end of the exposure periods, the bags were aerated, and the wire gauze cages were taken

out and examined immediately for recording the death of adult stage. The percentages mortality was calculated, corrected and recorded. The data obtained were statistically analyzed using the analysis of variana F-test.

3. ECO₂-Fume gas experiment:

3.1. ECO₂-Fume formulation:

- Phosphine (PH₃): 2% (by weight) 2.6% by volume.
- Carbon Dioxide (CO₂): 98%.
- Molecular formula: PH₃ and CO₂
- Structural formula:

Ready gas cylinder manufacture by Cytec Company (Canada) was used for this experiment.

3.2. Fumigation procedures by ECO₂-Fume:

This experiment was conducted on wheat grains stored in jute bags at Sindiyun Shona, Qalyubiya Governorate. Three piles of 240 Jute bags each bag was filled with 100 kg of wheat grains for each bag. From the stock cultures maintained in the rearing room, cloth bags (10x16 cm) each contained 50 g wheat kernels infested with one of the different stages of *S. oryzae*; eggs, larvae, pupae and adults (30 individuals for each bag in case of adult) were prepared. The total numbers of bags for each concentration of ECO₂-Fume gas were 48 bags; 12 bags for each direction (North, south, middle and west). The prepared bags were introduced into the pile and distributed on the four direction as mentioned before. The pile was

covered exactly and tightly with a plastic sheet 14x20 m. After sealing the place of fumigation, whose of the gas cylinder was introduced inside the pile and the gas cylinder was put on platform balance to calculate the required dose. Four doses (concentrations) of ECO₂-Fume (30, 35, 40 and 50 g/m³) were used. After 3 days of exposure to ECO₂-Fume gas the piles were aerated, and the cloth bags of insects were inspected directly for adult mortality. Bags of the other insect stages were kept in the rearing room until adult emergence and the mortality percentages were calculated and corrected for each stage. Similar numbers of cloth bags of insect stages were distributed in another wheat pile using the same procedures without ECO₂-Fume gas to be used as a control. The concentration of phosphine gas in the treated ECO₂-Fume pile was monitored by a portable Silo. Chek MARKII manufactured by the CANARY COMPANY Pty Ltd, AUSTRALIA. This device detects high fumigation phosphine levels greater than 1 ppm up to 2000 ppm. The automatic sampling model (which used in this study) had a sample tube, which connect to the gas-sampling lines coming from the pile under fumigation and built-in pump and battery. After connecting of the sample tube with the gas-sampling lines, the key switch down turned to on. A period up to 3 minutes was elapsed to allow the PH₃ sensor to record the final reading of PH₃ concentration. The data obtain were statistically analyzed using the analysis of variance F-test.

Results and discussion

1. Effect of relative humidity on the efficiency of CO₂ and N₂ gas against *Sitophilus oryzae* adults:

The purpose of this experiment was to evaluate the relationship between the ambient

relative humidity and mortality of *S. oryzae* adults exposed to CO₂ or N₂ pure gases.

1.1. Carbon dioxide gas:

Data in Table (1) show generally that efficacy of CO₂ gas against adults of *S. oryzae* was influenced significantly by the exposure period to the gas. Mortality of adults increased as the exposure period increased recording averages of 72.75, 94 and 99.75% for the exposure periods of 7, 14 and 21 days, respectively, at 30 °C. This trend was also recorded at 20 °C averaging of 62.5, 90.75 and 98.00%, respectively. However, the mortality percentages of insects were increased at the higher temperature (30 °C) comparing with the lower one (20 °C) but the difference between them was insignificant.

Mortality of insects was influenced significantly by the level of relative humidity in the inert gas ambient. The highest percentages of insect mortality were recorded for the lowest and the highest level of humidity at both degrees of temperature. At the moderate levels of humidity (50 and 60%), the insect mortality was slightly reduced than that of the lowest and the highest levels of humidity at both degrees of temperature, especially for the shortest periods (Table, 1).

It was showed also that a complete mortality was occurred for the insects exposed to the CO₂ at the lowest (35%) and the highest (80%) levels of humidity whatever the tested temperature after the exposure period of 21 days. Averages of mortality % of insects were approximately the same for the lowest level and the highest level of humidity at both degrees of temperature.

Table (1): Effect of relative humidity levels on the efficacy of pure CO₂ gas against *Sitophilus oryzae* adults at 30 and 20± 2 °C.

Temperature (T)	Exposure periods (in days) (E)	% mortality of adults					General means of % of adult mortality at different levels of Temp.
		Relative humidity levels %(R.)					
		35	50	60	80	means	
30 °C	7	85	48	69	89	72.75	88.83
	14	100	97	79	100	94	
	21	100	100	99	100	99.75	
	Means	95	81.66	82.33	96.33		
20 °C	7	70	34	67	79	62.5	83.75
	14	100	82	89	92	90.75	
	21	100	100	92	100	98	
	Means	69	72	82.66	90.33		
General means of % mortality of adult at different levels of RH.		82.0	76.83	82.49	93.33		

LSD_{0.05} for temperature (T)=N. SLSD_{0.05} for exposure period: (E)= 2.069LSD_{0.05} for relative humidity (R)=1.915LSD_{0.05} for (TxE)=2.927%LSD_{0.05} for (ExR)=3.612%LSD_{0.05} for (TxR)= 2.708%LSD_{0.05} for (TxE x R)= 5.108%

1.2. Nitrogen gas:

The results presented in Table (2) show generally that efficiency of N₂ gas against *S. oryzae* adults at all the tested conditions was less than that of CO₂ gas. However, similar trends were found for the results of the tested factors (temperature, relative humidity and exposure period) on adult mortality of *S. oryzae*. Mortality percentages of insects was significantly increased at the higher temperature (82.47%) than that at the lower one (77.5%). Relative humidity had affected significantly the mortality of insects, high levels of insect mortality were recorded at the lowest level of humidity (35%), the mortality of insects was decreased at 50% relative humidity at both temperatures.

Mortality of insects increased again as the relative humidity was increased to 60 and

80%, recording the highest percentages of insect mortality 85.89 and 88.11 % at the two degrees of temperature 20 and 30°C., respectively. As mentioned before in case of CO₂, the mortality of insects increased gradually as the exposure period to the gas was increased. The highest percentages of insect mortality (91.08 and 87.75 %) were recorded for 21 days exposure period at both degree of temperature (30 and 20 °C), respectively. The lowest percentages of insect mortality were recorded for the shortest exposure period (7 days). The interaction effect between exposure period and relative humidity on the insect mortality was also significant. The highest percentages of insect mortality (99 and 96 %) were recorded for the longest exposure period (21 days) and the highest level of relative humidity (80%) at both temperature 30 and 20 °C., respectively.

Table (2): Effect of relative humidity levels on the efficacy of pure N₂ gas against *Sitophilus oryzae* adults at 30 and 20± 2 °C.

Temperature (T)	Exposure periods (in days) (E)	% Mortality of adults					General means of % adult mortality at different levels of Temp.
		Relative humidity levels %(R)					
		35	50	60	80	Means	
30 °C	7	74	70	79	81	76.08	82.47
	14	79	76	82	84	80.25	
	21	90	84	91	99	91.08	
	Means	81.11	76.66	84.0	88.11		
20 °C	7	68	63	71	76	69.5	77.5
	14	73	73	76	79	75.25	
	21	86	81	88	96	87.75	
	Means	75.66	72.33	78.33	83.66		
General means of % mortality of adult at different levels of R.H.		78.39	74.49	81.17	85.89	7	

LSD_{0.05} level for temperature (T)=3.726%.

LSD_{0.05} level for exposure period: (E)=1.545%.

LSD_{0.05} level for relative humidity (R)=1.892%.

LSD_{0.05} level for (EXR)=3.009%.

Very little is known about the combined effect of the inert gases (CO₂ and N₂) and ambient relative humidity. However, this point could be discussed as follows: Insect normally keep their spiracles closed, opening them just enough to satisfy their oxygen (O₂) requirements (Hazelhoff, 1927 and Wigglesworth, 1935). However, the frequency of opening and closing is influenced by several factors, including the concentration of carbon dioxide (CO₂) and O₂ in the environment. Mellanby (1934) found that a 2% concentration of CO₂ is enough to produce sustained opening of the spiracles in some insects. The same effect can be achieved if the O₂ concentration is reduced below 1%. There is considerable evidence that a large part of the water loss from insects takes place through the respiratory surfaces.

Mellanby (1934) found that when the spiracles of *Xenopsylla cheopis* (Rothschild) (Siphonaptera: Pulicidae) adult and larval *Tenebrio molitor* L. (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae) and *Tineola bisselliella* (Hummel) (Lepidoptera: Tineidae) are kept open with high concentrations of CO₂ or low concentrations of O₂, the rate of water loss was two to seven times higher than under normal concentrations of these gases. *X. cheopis* larvae, however, which lack a spiracular closing mechanism, lose water at about the same rate under all these conditions. Bursell (1957) reported that *Glossina morsitans* Westwood (Diptera: Glossinidae) in air at 0% r.h. lose water at the rate of 0.12 mg/h when its spiracles are functioning normally, but when the spiracles are blocked with paraffin wax it loses water

at the rate of 0.09 mg/h. It appears then that high concentrations of CO₂ in combination with low humidity could prove lethal to insects by causing rapid loss of water through the spiracles. Dry air having a low O₂ concentration should have the same effect. This situation presents the possibility of using altered concentrations of atmospheric gases in combination with low humidity to control insects infesting stored products. This possibility was also suggested by the results of earlier investigations by two of the authors (Pearman and Jay, 1970). They found that the mortality of *Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst) (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae) exposed to altered concentrations of atmospheric gases was greater at low than at high humidity. The high mortality levels of insects at the highest level of relative humidity may be attributed to the combine effect of high relative humidity and the high concentration of CO₂ or N₂. The results concerning the effect of the high relative humidity level on the percentage mortality of the tested insects agree with those recorded by (Navarro and Calderon, 1974). The authors reported that pupae of *Ephestia cautella* (Walker) (Lepidoptera: Phycitidae) exposed to high concentration of CO₂ gas (89%) at a high relative humidity level (95%) were completely died after 5 days of exposure. In this case insect mortality resulting from the treatments cannot be attributed to loss of water which is the

Table (3): Mortality percentages of developmental stages and adults of *Sitophilus oryzae* exposed to ECO₂-Fume gas used in wheat pills for three days under plastic sheet.

Insect stages	Gas tested concentrations (g/m ³)			
	30	35	40	50
Eggs	23	35	67	100
Larvae	39	56	80	100
Pupae	26	43	72	100
Adults	98	99	100	100
Means of mortality percentages after exposed to different concentrations of gas.	46.37	58.06	79.75	100

LSD_{0.05} level for insect stages (IS) = 8.13 %.

LSD_{0.05} level for gas concentrations (GS) = 3.08%.

LSD_{0.05} level for interactions (ISxGS) = 7.12%.

causative factor at the lower relative humidity. We suggest that carbon dioxide itself acts as a fumigant at high concentrations causing a lethal effect on insects.

2. Efficacy of ECO₂- Fume gas against *Sitophilus oryzae* under practical conditions:

Different concentrations of ECO₂-Fume gas was evaluated against the different stages of *S. oryzae* under practical conditions in wheat piles stored at Sindiyun, Qalubiyah Governorate under plastic sheet. Data presented in Table (3) showed the mortality percentages of the different developmental stages and adults of *S. oryzae* exposed to gas concentrations for three days. Insect mortality values increased as the concentration of the gas increased. Mortality values were calculated after three days of exposure to gas. A complete mortality (100%) was recorded for (eggs, larvae, pupae and adults) at the concentration of 50% g/m³. Mortality % of the abovementioned stages (eggs, larvae, pupae and adults) were 23, 39, 26 and 98% respectively, at the concentration of 30 g/m³. Thus, the results indicated that higher concentrations induced higher percentages of mortality. Adults of *S. oryzae* was the most susceptible stage to ECO₂-Fume gas recording the highest percentages of mortality, while pupae and eggs were the most tolerant, (Table,3)

As for the changes of gas concentrations during the three days immediately after treatment; results of Table (4) show generally that concentrations of the gas were very high in the initial time (at the beginning of treatment) then decreased gradually as the period post-treatment was prolonged. Concentrations of the gas at the initial time and during the three consecutive days post-treatment were the tested dose depended. The highest concentration of the gas at any time was recorded for the highest tested dose (50 g\m³) and the lowest one was recorded for the least dose (30 g\m³) (Table, 3). The rate of gas concentration decrease may be attributed to the degree of sealing and the level of gas sorption by the treated grains. As shown from the results of Table (3) that percentages of gas concentration reduction were increased as the time post-treatment was elapsed. ECO₂-Fume fumigant gas is non-flammable mixture of phosphine and carbon dioxide that enables highly effective fumigation in a wide variety of sealed storage applications. It is dispensed externally to stores or structures using simple techniques which avoid the applicator's exposure and enhance worker's safety. The obtained results are in harmony with the findings of other investigators on the efficacy of combinations of phosphine plus carbon dioxide against some stored product insects El-Lakwah *et al.* (1992a) studied the efficacy of mixtures of phosphine and carbon dioxide against the various stages of *Callosobruchus maculatus*

(F.) (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae). Adults of *C. maculatus* proved to be the most susceptible stage. The time of exposure was a more critical factor than the concentration of phosphine. El-Lakwah *et al.* (1992b) investigated the efficacy of phosphine and carbon dioxide mixtures against the various stages of *Rhyzopertha dominica* (F.) (Coleoptera: Bostrichidae). These mixtures were effective on all stages of the insect. Adults of *R. dominica* proved to be the most susceptible stage at 30°C. El-Lakwah *et al.* (1992c) investigated the efficacy of phosphine and carbon dioxide mixtures against the various stages of *S. oryzae*. These mixtures were effective on all stages of the insect. Adults of *S. oryzae* proved to be the most susceptible stage at the 30 °C. El-Lakwah *et al.* (1989) investigated the efficacy of phosphine with that of mixtures of the gas plus carbon dioxide against diapause larvae of *Trogoderma granarium* Everts (Coleoptera: Dermestidae). It was found that for longer exposure periods of 48 and 72 hours, the addition of CO₂ to phosphine induced significantly higher larval mortality than that by PH₃ alone. In conclusion, ECO₂-Fume gas is considered one of the most promising fumigants for controlling *S. oryzae* in stored grains causing a complete mortality of the insects after 3 days of exposure to 50 g\m³ of stored grains in good sealing atmosphere.

Table (4): Changes in the concentrations of ECO₂-Fume gas during three consecutive days immediately after initial gas dosing in wheat pile under the plastic sheet.

Tested doses (g/m ³)	Gas concentrations (in ppm)				
	Initial time	1 st day	2 nd day	3 rd day	Average Concentrations
30	844.8	484.8 (42.6%)*	244.2 (71.0%)	217.8 (74.2%)	447.9 (46.9%)
35	1011.6	441.0 (56.4%)	223.8 (77.8%)	221.4 (78.1%)	474.5 (53.1%)
40	1020	391.8 (61.6%)	253.6 (75.1%)	174.2 (82.9%)	459.9 (54.9%)
50	1104	683.4 (38.1%)	435.6 (60.5%)	206.4 (81.3%)	607.35 (44.9%)

* Numbers between brackets represent % reduction of gas concentrations.

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Impact of chromenes compounds on some biological aspects of the three cotton bollworm species under constant temperature.

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Abstract:

The experiments were conducted in Plant Protection Research Institute, Sharkia branch, Agriculture Research Center to study the toxic and biological effects of chromens compounds against the pink bollworm (PBW), *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) the spiny bollworm (SBW), *Earias insulana* (Boisd.) and the American bollworm (ABW), *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hübner) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae). Data revealed that chromens compounds had highest toxic effect against newly hatched larvae attained of American followed by spiny and pink bollworms larvae. On the other hand, the latent effects of the chromens compounds on the three insect species were presented in increasing the accumulated of larval and pupal mortality percentages, non-significant increasing on larval duration of the three cotton bollworms insects, and significantly decreased in larval and pupal weight, increasing pre and post-oviposition periods, decreasing oviposition periods, male and female longevities and also reduced fecundity, while the highest reduction in laid eggs recorded on spiny followed by pink and American bollworms compared with untreated control, while the hatchability percentages decreased significantly with pink bollworm and highly significant with spiny and American bollworms compared with untreated control.

Introduction

Cotton plants are one of the most important economical crops in Egypt and all over the world. The pink bollworm (PBW), *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) the spiny bollworm (SBW), *Earias insulana* (Boisduval) and the American bollworm (ABW), *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hübner)

(Lepidoptera: Noctuidae). The pesticides were used to control the American bollworm. The level of resistance to some insecticides has increased and new group of chemicals was needed to manage resistant populations in cotton fields. Chromenes showed larvicidal and antifeedant activities against the larvae of *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisduval)

(Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) (Emam *et al.*, 2009). Chromenes are often active against a limit number of insects, biodegradable to nontoxic products and potentially suitable for use in integrated pest management programs, they could be lead to the development of new classes of safer insect control agents (Park *et al.*, 2002 and Mansour *et al.*, 2004). Also, chromenes have many biological activities such as molluscicidal activity (Hmamouchi *et al.*, 2000), larvicidal activity (Mookey *et al.*, 2002), and repellent activity (Hadis *et al.*, 2003). Also, this compound has a play role as feeding deterrent to larvae of *S. littoralis* and *Heliothis virescens* (Fabricius) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) (Enriz *et al.*, 2000). Chromenes exhibit insecticidal and well as repellency against several insects (Soares *et al.*, 2010; Khanikor *et al.*, 2011 and Hazarikaa *et al.*, 2012).

The aim of the present study was to evaluate the toxic and latent effects of chromens compounds against the pink, spiny and American bollworms infested cotton crop in Egypt.

Materials and methods

1. Chemicals used:

Three synthetic chemical compounds namely:

A= (3-(3- phenyl-1,4-dihydro-1,2-diazete-1-carbonyl)-2H-chromene-2-one).

B= (5-amino-1-(2- oxo-2H-chromene-3-carbonyl)-3-phenyl-1H-pyrazole-4-carbonitrile).

C= (3-(5-methyl-1,3,4- oxadiazol-2-yl)-2-chromene-2-one).

were synthesized at the laboratory of faculty of science – Zagazig University.

2. Rearing technique:

The proper conditions diet for maintaining a mass culture of *P. gossypiella*, *E. insulana* and *H. armigera* were followed according to the method described by Abd El-Hafez *et al.* (1982). The artificial diet was changed after 7 days of treatment in case of spiny and American bollworms with fresh one (Amer *et al.*, 2010).The larvae were

incubated at constant conditions of 26 ± 1 oc. and $70 \pm 5\%$ relative humidity (RH.) in an electrical incubation in bollworms laboratory, Plant Protection Research Institute (Sharkia branch) at Zagazig district , Sharkia Governorate , Egypt.

3. Methods of procedure:

3.1. Toxicity tests:

One gram of each chromen compound from each three compounds were dissolved in 30 ml ethyl alcohol 95% mixed with 30 ml of deionized water and put in a dark bottle color as stock solution . The concentrations / compound were prepare, each concentrate per compound was replicated four times compared with untreated check .

3.2. Toxicity effect on larvae:

Five grams of artificial diet were put on a petri-dish (7.50 x 2.00 cm). One ml of the tested concentration/ compound alone were added to the surface of the diet , homeopathic , one ml of ethyl alcohol mixed with water as control, and then left until dryness added concentration . Twenty five newly hatched larvae of PBW, SBW and ABW, each species were transferred and separately put on to treated artificial diet then left to fed. The alive and dead larvae of three insects were recorded after 48 hrs. The LC_{50} and LC_{90} values were determined according to Finney method (1952).

3.3. Latent effect on larvae:

The alive larvae under test , which exposed to different concentrations in treatments and control were transferred individually into glass tube (2x7.5 cm) and incubated under the previous condition. The tubes were inspection daily until pupation to recorded weight and mortality of larval and pupal . The pupae were separated on glass jar (half kg.) until moth's emergence. The newly emerged moths were sexed and put in glass jar (half kg.). Each jar contains two pair of moths and replicated four times for each treatment and control. The emerged moths were fed on 10% sugar solution. Pre-oviposition periods, oviposition and post-

oviposition, longevity of adult males and females, hatchability percentage and number of deposited eggs were recorded.

4. Statistical analysis:

The obtained results of biological measurements were subjected to analysis of variance between the different tested compounds against each insect using Costate computer program Cohort Software. P. O. Box 1149, Berkeley CA 9471 (Costat Statistical Software, 2005).

Results and discussions

1. Toxicology test:

1.1. Larvae:

Results in Table (1), indicated that at LC50 and LC90 values were 146.95, 212.65, 364.39 and 1112.33, 2421.94, 3967.24 ppm

Table (1): Toxicity of chromenes compounds against larvae of the *Pectinophora gossypiella*, *Earias insulana* and *Helicoverpa armigera*.

Insects	Compounds	LC ₅₀	LC ₉₀	Slop
<i>Pectinophora gossypiella</i>	A	146.95	1112.33	1.4579
	B	212.65	2421.94	1.2131
	C	364.39	3967.24	1.2360
<i>Earias insulana</i>	A	126.85	1218.17	1.3045
	B	227.71	1539.73	1.5440
	C	330.64	2364.25	1.5440
<i>Helicoverpa armigera</i>	A	258.70	876.03	2.4194
	B	442.79	3130.10	1.5089
	C	220.8351	741.8863	2.4353

A= (3-(3- phenyl-1,4-dihydro-1,2-diazete-1-carbonyl)-2H-chromene-2-one).

B= (5-amino-1-(2- oxo-2H-chromene-3-carbonyl)-3-phenyl-1H-pyrazole-4-carbonitrile).

C= (3-(5-methyl-1,3,4- oxadiazol-2-yl)-2-chromene-2-one).

2. Effect of chromenes compound on some biological aspects of the pink, spiny and American bollworms:

2.1. Larval duration:

Data in Table (2) indicated that it can be concluded that the chromenes caused prolongation in duration of the larval stage of PBW and ABW, which was significant only with compound C as compared with untreated larvae.

2.2. Larval weight:

Statistical analysis of data presented in Table (2) showed that all tested compounds significant decreased larval weight of bollworms.

2.3. Larval mortality percentage:

for A,B,C on newly hatched larvae of PBW, while mortality concentrations were 126.8512, 227.71, 330.64 and 1218.17, 1539.73, 2364.25 ppm for A,B,C for SBW, meanwhile, the LC50 and LC90 values were 258.70, 442.79, 220.83 and 876.03, 3130.10, 741.89 ppm for A,B,C for ABW after 48hs from treatment. The slope value was (1.3045, 1.5440, 1.5001) for A,B,C for SBW, while these value was (1.4579, 1.2131, 1.2360) for A,B,C for PBW. On the other hand, the slope value was (2.4194, 1.5089, 2.4353) for A, B, C for ABW. Data obtained showed that the newly hatched larvae of PBW was the highest susceptible for chromenes compound than other insects.

Results presented in Table (2) indicated that the larval mortality percentages of PBW, SBW and ABW increased significantly than untreated larvae. The highest average percentage of larval mortality (52.00%) was obtained with ABW for compound A compared with (5.00%) with control. while, the lowest percentage (22%) was recorded for SBW for compound B compared with control which was (4.00%) larval mortality.

2.4. Pupal duration:

Data presented in Table (2) indicated that all compounds caused more significant increases on pupal durations of SBW and ABW compared with control. The mean pupal durations of PBW were 9.99, 10.25 and

9.39 for A, B and C. respectively, while it was 9.50 for control . The longest pupal period was 10.25 days for B compound, while the lowest one was 9.39 days for C compound compared with 9.50 days for untreated..

2.5. Pupal weight:

Concerning the effect of the tested compounds on the pupal weight of SBW and

Table (2): Effect of treated newly hatched larvae of the *Pectinophora gossypiella*, *Earias insulana* and *Helicoverpa armigera* with chromenes compounds on the immature stages.

Insects	Compound	Larval duration (days)	Larval weight (gram)	larval Mortality %	Pupal weight (grams)	Pupal duration (days)	Pupal Mortality %
<i>Pectinophora gossypiella</i>	A	15.33 a	0.0263 a	45.00 a	0.0222 a	9.99 a	13.00 b
	B	14.33 a	0.0271 ab	25.00 c	0.0226 a	10.25 a	15.00 a
	C	15.50 ab	0.0313 b	35.00 b	0.0231 a	9.39 a	12.00 b
	Control	13.50 b	0.0356 b	5.00 d	0.0244 a	9.50 a	0.00 c
	F-test	NS	**	***	NS	NS	***
	LSD _{0.05}	1.607	0.00489	1.8828	0.00223	1.882	1.631
<i>Earias insulana</i>	A	15.83 ab	0.06303 b	40.00 a	0.05356 b	10.75a	23.00 ab
	B	15.00 b	0.06053 b	22.00 c	0.0507 b	10.25ab	25.00 a
	C	16.33 a	0.05723 b	31.00 b	0.05003 b	10.33ab	18.00 b
	Control	15.59 ab	0.0743 a	4.00 d	0.0618 a	10 b	6.333 c
	F-test	NS	*	***	**	NS	***
	LSD _{0.05}	1.2453	0.009804	3.7656	0.00607	0.5435	6.2682
<i>Helicoverpa armigera</i>	A	17.26ab	0.036b	52.00a	0.0325b	16.07a	13.00a
	B	16.66b	0.0368ab	50.00a	0.0324b	16.38a	10.00b
	C	18.10a	0.03893ab	49.66a	0.0319b	16.06a	11.00ab
	Control	15.33c	0.0422a	5.00b	0.0432a	14.66b	5.00c
	F-test	***	N. S	***	***	**	***
	LSD _{0.05}	1.22	--	8.55	0.02	0.81	2.66

*Means followed by the same litter vertically did not differ significantly.

2.7. Pre-oviposition period:

Data presented in Table (3) showed that the chromenes have non-significant effect on pre-oviposition period of bollworms.

2.8. Oviposition period:

The egg laying period of the emerged female from treated newly hatched larvae of PBW & SBW were highly significant shortened compared with the untreated Table (3). Also, the mean oviposition periods of ABW were 4.27, 4.60 and 4.78 days for A, B and C compound, while, the untreated control was 6.00 days.

2.9. Post -oviposition period:

Date in Table (3) indicated that the post-oviposition period of the bollworm

ABW, the result indicated highly significant effect than PBW as shown in Table (2).

2.6. Pupal mortality percentage:

Data in Table (2) indicated that it can be concluded that the chromenes caused increased in pupal mortality percentages of bollworms compared with untreated.

female developed from newly hatched larvae treated with the three compounds were nonsignificant compared with control.

2.10. Adult longevity:

Data in Table (3) indicated that the chromenes had highly significant effect on male and female longevity of PBW. Also, the three compounds had most significant effect on the ABW male longevity.

2.11. Number of deposited eggs / female :

The number of eggs deposited by female was most significantly affected by chromenes compound compared with untreated. Generally, the fecundity of female produced from newly hatched larvae treated with chromene compounds were greatly reduced than that obtained from control.

2.12. Hatchability of eggs:

Data presented in Table (3) showed that chromenes compounds caused more significant reduction in the viability of eggs deposited by ABW, PBW and SBW survived

from treated newly hatched larvae. Generally, the chromenes compounds caused higher reduction than that of control on the hatchability rate.

Table (3): Effect of treated newly hatched larvae of the *Pectinophora gossypiella*, *Earias insulana* and *Helicoverpa armigera* with chromenes compounds on the mature stages.

Insects	Compound	Oviposition period (days)			Adult longevity (days)		No. of eggs/Female	% Hatchability
		Pre-	Ovi	Post	Female	Male		
<i>Pectinophora gossypiella</i>	A	3.66 a	8.33 b	3.166 a	15.16 b	16.00 c	91.00 b c	69.66 b
	B	5.33 a	6.00 c	4.33 a	15.66 b	17.3 bc	106.66 b	81 ab
	C	3.5 a	9.33 b	4.16 a	17.00 ab	18.66 ab	75 c	70.66 b
	Control	3.33 a	11.66 a	3.50 a	18.5 a	19.33 a	210 a	96.33 a
	F-test	NS	***	NS	*	**	***	*
	LSD _{0.05}	2.157	2.105	1.823	2.0337	1.631	22.502	17.282
<i>Earias insulana</i>	A	5.50 ab	6.00 bc	4.50 a	16.00 a	13.33 a	68.33 b	82.66 b
	B	6.50 a	5.00 c	4.66 a	16.16 a	13.5 a	76.66 b	67.33 c
	C	5.33 b	6.66 b	5.00 a	17.00 a	13.83 a	62.33 b	58.00 d
	Control	5.00 b	8.33 a	4.00 a	17.33 a	14.00 a	112.00 a	91.33 a
	F-test	NS	**	NS	NS	NS	**	***
	LSD _{0.05}	1.087	1.215	1.513	2.4307	1.6077	20.431	17.721
<i>Helicoverpa armigera</i>	A	2.40 a	4.27 a	2.87 a	9.54 b	8.00 d	251.66 b c	40.00 c
	B	3.60 a	4.60 a	2.13 ab	10.33 ab	9.00 c	273.33 b	50.00 bc
	C	3.63 a	4.78 a	1.66 b	10.07 b	9.66 b	213.33 c	60.00 b
	Control	3.20 a	6.00 a	2.57 ab	11.77 a	10.00 a	507.66 a	80.00 a
	LSD _{0.05}	N.S.	N.S.	N.S.	N.S.	N.S.	***	***
	F-test	--	--	--	--	0.27	40.73	18.83

*Means followed by the same litter vertically did not differ significantly.

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Seasonal activity of the guava long scale insect *Lepidosaphes tapleyi* (Hemiptera: Diaspidiae) infesting guava trees in Luxor Governorate, Egypt.

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Abstract:

The present work was carried out throughout two successive years (2017/2018 and 2018/2019) at Esna district, Luxor Governorate. As a basic study for developing future management of the guava long scale insect, *Lepidosaphes tapleyi* (Williams) (Hemiptera: Diaspidiae), to determine the seasonal activity of this insect. In this investigation, two insect expressions were utilized, *i.e.*, Insect numbers and incidence of infestation, which articulated the population density of this pest. The obtained results showed that insect population of *L. tapleyi* occurred on guava trees all the year round and has four to five peaks of seasonal activity per year, which was recorded on the beginning of April, mid-May, mid-July, beginning of October and mid-November during the first year (2017/2018) and through the mid-April, mid-July, mid-September and beginning of November during the second year (2018/2019). Furthermore, the percentages of infestation incidence by pests showed, also, have four to five peaks per year. Also, the total population density by *L. taplyi* was higher through the second year in compared to the first year of study, which may be due to the influence of favorable factors (such as environmental conditions.... etc.). It seems that, the climatic conditions of autumn and summer months during the two years were more suitable for the population density and its activity and the maximum values of the infestation incidence by *L. taplyi*. As well, it was generally found that autumn season was more favorable for the insect multiplication and build up, than the remaining three seasons in each year during the two years. The obtained results showed that, the effect of weather factors (mean daily of air temperature, mean of relative humidity and mean of dew point) on the insect population and on the percentages of infestation incidence by *L. taplyi* were, highly significant during the two successive years, and these factors varied from year to another. Also, the dew point was the most effective variable for the changes in the insect population and the percentages of infestation incidence under the studied years.

Introduction

The guava long scale insect *Lepidosaphes tapleyi* (Williams) (Hemiptera: Diaspididae) has a wide range of host plants, it attacks 28 host plants in 17 countries (Williams, 1960; Williams and Watson, 1988; Muniappan *et al.*, 2012 and Malumphy *et al.*, 2012) and Egypt (Swailem, 1974 and Ghabbour, 2001). It was dangerous pest of economic crops on mango trees in Benin (Germain *et al.*, 2010) and guava in Mali and Senegal (Muniappan *et al.*, 2012). This pest injures the shoots, twigs, leaves, branches and fruits by sucking the plant sap with the mouth parts, causing thereafter deformations, defoliation, drying up of young twigs, dieback, poor blossoming, death of twig by the action of the toxic saliva. A characteristic symptom of infestation by pest is the appearance and accumulation of its scales on attacked guava parts (Swailem, 1974; El-Nahal *et al.*, 1980 and Williams and Watson, 1988).

The objective of this study is to estimate the seasonal activity, the percentages of infestation incidence by pest, the rate of monthly variation and the effect of main weather factors on insect numbers and incidence of infestation of pest, to select an effective program for its control.

Materials and methods

Many authors used different insect expressions, which articulated the population density of this pest. In this investigation, two insect expressions were utilized, *i.e.*, insect numbers and the percentages of infestation incidence. The population fluctuations of this scale found infesting guava trees in a private orchard of about one feddan were carried out at half-monthly intervals at Esna district, Luxor Governorate during two successive years extending from March 2017 until mid-February 2019. The selected orchard received the normal agricultural practices without application any chemical control measures before and during the period of study.

Four guava trees of Balady variety,

almost uniform and of similar in age and as possible in size, shape, height, vegetative growth was selected. Regular half-monthly samples were picked up to random from different directions and stratum of tree with rate of 40 leaves per tree. The samples were collected regularly and immediately transferred to laboratory in polyethylene bags for inspection using a stereomicroscope. Numbers of alive insects on upper and lower surfaces of guava leaves were individually sorted into immature stages (nymphs) and mature stages (adult females) and then were counted and recorded together opposite to each inspected date.

The *L. tapleyi* population density was estimated, while its infestation incidence percentages were calculated according to the formula of Facylate (1971):

$$A = (n / N) \times 100.$$

Where, A = Percentage of infestation incidence.
n = No. of infested leaves in which the pest appeared.

N = Total number of picked leaves (Uninfested + Infested) in each inspection date.

Also, the rate monthly variation in the population (R.M.V.P) was calculated according to the formula reported by Serag-El-Din (1998):

$$(R.M.V.P) = \frac{\text{Av. count of insect at a month}}{\text{Av. count given at the preceding month}}$$

Concerning, the effect of the main weather factors on the different stages of *L. tapleyi* population and percentages of infestation incidence. The meteorological data of some climatic factors (daily mean temperature, mean of % relative humidity and mean of dew point °C) for conditions of Luxor governorate were obtained from the Central Laboratory for Agricultural climate, Agriculture Research Center, Ministry of Agriculture in Giza. The altitude, latitude and longitude of this weather region of Luxor were 99 m, 25.67°N and 32.71°E,

respectively. According to the results of the simple correlation, regression coefficient and the partial regression formula, which was adopted to find out the simultaneous effects of, tested main weather factors on *L. tapleyi*. The partial regression method termed the C-multipliers was adopted according to Fisher (1950). All obtained data were subjected to calculations and were depicted graphically using Microsoft Excel 2010. Statistical analysis was carried out with Computer using (MSTATC Program Software, 1980) to determine the preferable time for the insect activity and the proper time for its control.

Results and discussion

1. Seasonal abundance of *Lepidosaphes tapleyi* infesting guava trees:

The half-monthly counts of *L. tapleyi* stages which infested guava trees and the percentages of infestation incidence by pest at Esna district, Luxor Governorate were recorded through the two successive years (2017/2018 and 2018/2019). Also, half-monthly mean records of climatic weather factors throughout the two years of investigation are tabulated in Tables (1 and 2) and graphically illustrated in Figures (1 and 2). The trends of fluctuation in nymphs and adult females populations were almost similar. Accordingly, its better to discuss the seasonal activity were estimated based on average number of immature (nymphs) and mature stage (adult females) counts per leaf in the successive sampling dates.

1.1. The first year (2017/2018):

Concerning, the data in the first year of (2017/2018), as recorded in Table (1) and graphed illustrated in Figure (1), it was observed that the total population of insect started to increase gradually to reach the first peak. The first peak was recorded in the beginning of April with mean numbers of 15.52 ± 0.75 individuals/leaf under field conditions at 22.06°C , 32.41% and 5.24°C for daily mean of temp., relative humidity and dew point, respectively. After that, the

population decreased took place in mid-April. Then, the population increased gradually to reach the second peak of this insect, was recorded in mid-May when the mean population reached 24.93 ± 1.22 individuals/leaf with means of 28.18°C , 18.07% and 7.43°C for mean temp., relative humidity and dew point, respectively. Thereafter, the population decreased gradually until reached in mid of June and then reincreased gradually to reach third peak in mid-July, when 28.69 ± 1.40 individuals per leaf were recorded under the means field conditions of 33.5°C , 19.79% and 12.79°C for mean temp., relative humidity and dew point, respectively. Then, the population decreased at the beginning of August and then increased gradually to reach the fourth peak at the beginning of October, where 47.98 ± 2.36 individuals/ leaf were recorded under the mean field conditions of 31.75°C , 25.5% and 14.31°C for mean temp., relative humidity and dew point, respectively. Thereafter, it decreased in mid-October and then highly increased continuously to reach the fifth peak in mid- November when the mean population reached 52.33 ± 2.57 individuals/leaf with means of 25°C , 33.64% and 11.71°C for mean temp., relative humidity and dew point, respectively. A continues decrease was observed in insect population during December until reached to the mid of February are shown in Table (1) and illustrated in Figure (1).

A similar trend in the seasonal fluctuation of nymphs (immature stages) and adult (mature stages) populations was observed. Five peaks of nymphs population were recorded in the beginning of April, mid-May, mid-July, beginning of October and mid-November when the mean population density was 11.76 ± 0.55 , 16.39 ± 0.76 , 18.47 ± 0.86 , 29.89 ± 1.39 and 32.19 ± 1.49 individuals/leaf, respectively. Similarly, however with different values the adult females had five peaks that were recorded in the beginning of April, mid-May, mid-July,

beginning of October and mid- November when the mean population density was 3.76 ± 0.20 , 8.54 ± 0.47 , 10.22 ± 0.56 , 18.08 ± 0.99 and 20.14 ± 1.10 individuals/leaf, respectively, Table (1) and illustrated in Figure (1).

Differently, the percentages of infestation incidence occurred five peaks were recorded in mid of April, mid-May, mid-July, beginning of October and mid- November when the percentages of abundance were 57.50 ± 3.23 , 70.00 ± 4.56 , 66.25 ± 3.75 , 72.50 ± 3.23 and 71.25 ± 3.75 % respectively, Table (1) and illustrated in Figure (1).

1.2.The second year (2018/2019):

The obtained results in Table (2) and illustrated in Figure (2) showed that the total population by *L. tapleyi* during the second year started to increase gradually to reach the first peak. The first peak was observed in the mid-April with mean population of 26.36 ± 1.28 individuals/leaf under field conditions at 24.46°C , 21.93% and 6.71°C for mean daily of temp., relative humidity and dew point, respectively. After that, the population decreased gradually until reached in mid of June and then reincreased gradually to reach the second peak in mid-July when the mean population reached 38.11 ± 1.84 individuals/leaf with means of 32.64°C , 26.21% and 15.57°C for mean daily of temp., relative humidity and dew point, respectively. In early August, the insect population decreased and then increased gradually again to reach the third peak in mid-September when the mean population reached 51.11 ± 2.49 individuals/leaf with means of 32.14°C , 27.36% and 15.57°C for mean daily of temp., relative humidity and dew point, respectively. Then after, it decreased in the beginning of October and then it highly increased continuously to reach the fourth maximum peak was occurred in beginning of November when the mean population reached 54.86 ± 2.67 individuals/leaf with means of 24.75°C , 35.56% and 11.94°C for

mean temp., relative humidity and dew point, respectively. Followed by a dramatic decline and gradual decrease for population during December until reached to the mid of February are shown in Table (2) and illustrated in Figure (2).

A similar trend in the seasonal abundance of nymphs was observed. Four peaks of activity were recorded in mid of April, mid-July, mid of September and beginning of November when the mean population density was 18.46 ± 0.86 , 28.06 ± 1.30 , 33.94 ± 1.57 and 37.92 ± 1.76 individuals/leaf, respectively. Differently, however with different values, the adult females had four peaks that were occurred in mid of April, beginning of August, mid of September and beginning of November when the population density was 7.90 ± 0.43 , 10.20 ± 0.56 , 17.17 ± 0.94 and 16.94 ± 0.92 individuals per leaf, respectively. Also, the adult population was relatively higher than the nymphs population in winter months (January and February) and this may referred to the cold weather and most the nymphs attained to the adults stage which sheltered on stems bark or in the stem cracks in Table (2) and illustrated in Figure (2).

Differently, the percentages of infestation incidence (abundance) showed that four peaks were occurred in April, beginning of June, mid of September and beginning of November when the percentages of abundance was 55.00 ± 2.89 , 56.25 ± 2.39 , 71.25 ± 3.75 and 70.00 ± 2.89 % respectively, Table (2) and illustrated in Figure (2).

Higher maximum population by *L. tapleyi* in November during the two years, when crawlers emerged after egg laying and their population decreased during several months due to mortality of nymphs during in the winter months. Thus, the least population density of different stages and total population of pest and the percentages of infestation incidence which were recorded during January and February during the two

years of study, which may be attributed to the high relative humidity with the gradual decrease in temperature and dormancy of the trees during winter time which is expected to effect dramatically the insect behavior and on rate of growth and infestation. It obvious that the annual fluctuations in the population density during the two years were affected by the variability in these physical factors in the both years of investigation. According to Dent (1991) clarified that the rate of insect's population abundance at any location and the number of generations are influenced by the environmental factors at that location.

From the previously mentioned results, it could conclude that insect population occurred on guava trees all the year round and has four to five peaks of seasonal activity per year for different stages and total population of pest. Also, a same trend in both the percentages of infestation incidence by pests have four to five peaks. As well as, the total population of insect and the percentages of infestation incidence through the second year was higher in comparison to the first year of study, which may due to the influence of favorable factors (such as environmental conditions, etc.).

These results were coincided with those obtained by Swailem (1974) in Egypt, reported that the guava long scale insect, *L. tapleyi* had five generations per year. A few females of the last generation began to oviposit in December, but most entered diapause and did not resume activity until March. Populations were much reduced by unfavorable weather, particularly by hot winds, and large numbers fell from the trees when the leaves dropped in April. Also, Swailem (1973) recoded that the overwintering females began to oviposit in late May and continued to lay eggs until the temperature rose in July and August. Oviposition was resumed when the temperature dropped. Females laid 8-35 eggs each (average 20). The crawlers settled mainly on the upper surface of the leaves,

especially on the parts of the trees exposed to the sun. After hatching, the two immature female stages averaged 15-35 and 9-26 days, respectively, and the immature stages of the males after hatching averaged 30-52 days. Adult females lived for 55-120 days and adult males for 1-2 days.

The obtained results are illustrated in Figure (3), showed that the highest population density of *L. tapleyi*, the nymphs stage (23.49 and 28.31 individuals/leaf), adult females (15.06 and 14.51 individuals/leaf), total mixed population (38.55 and 42.82 individuals/leaf), the percentage of infestation incidence (67.71 and 67.08%) were recorded in autumn during the two years, respectively, than those of the remaining seasons of the year, may be due to the environmental conditions which were more favorable for the insect activity.

2. Rate of monthly variation in population (R.M.V.P.) of the guava long scale insect *Lepidosaphes tapleyi*:

The monthly variation rates in the population of different stages and total population of *L. tapleyi* and the percentages of infestation incidence were calculated (Table, 3). The rate of monthly variation in the population is considered an indicator to the favorable month for insect activity expressed as the month of higher increase of this insect population through the year. When R.M.V.P. is > 1 it means more activity, < 1 means less activity and $= 1$ means no change in the insect activity. As shown as recorded in Table (1), the favorable months of annual increase for nymphs stage and total mixed population appeared to be in April, May, July, September, October and November during the first year (2017/2018), when the rates of monthly variation were (1.41, 1.26, 1.72, 1.33, 1.28 and 1.09), and (1.39, 1.40, 1.65, 1.45, 1.20 and 1.06), respectively. As well, the rates of monthly variation (R.M.V.P) for adult females showed that the favorable times for annual increase appeared to be in April, May and from July to

November during the first year when the rates of monthly variation were 1.32, 1.85 and 1.01 to 1.64, respectively. Similarly, the infestation incidence percentages were higher in months, April, May, July to September and November during the second year of study, when the rates of monthly variation were 1.17, 1.09, 1.01 to 1.13 and 1.06, respectively.

As for the second year (2018/2019) the favorable times of annual increase for nymphs stage and total population of *L. tapleyi* appeared to be in April, July, September and November when the rates of monthly variation were (2.30, 2.50, 1.55 and 1.46) and (2.26, 2.09, 1.58 and 1.49), respectively. Also, for adult females it was shown that the favorable times for annual increase observed in months, April, July, September, November and January during the second year when the rates of monthly variation were 2.17, 1.10 -1.63, 1.55 and 1.06, respectively. While, the infestation incidence was occurred in April, June, August, and September during the second year, when the rates of monthly variation were 1.10, 1.17, 1.20 and 1.12, respectively (Table, 3).

Generally, it seems that the climatic conditions of autumn months during the two years were more optimum for the insect multiplication and build up.

3. Effect of the main weather factors on the different insect expressions by *Lepidosaphes tapleyi*:

3.1. Insect population:

3.1.1. Nymphs population:

3.1.1.1. Effect of daily mean temperature:

The results of statistical analysis of simple correlation in Table (4) showed highly positively significant correlation between the daily mean temperature and nymphs population of *L. tapleyi* for the first year (r-value was 0.55), positively significantly effect (0.41) during the second year and highly positively significant relation (0.47) on the two cumulative years. The unit effect regression coefficient (b) indicated that an

increase of 1°C in the daily mean temperature, would increase the population by 0.62, 0.62 and 0.61 individuals per leaf during the two years of study separately and on the two cumulative years altogether, respectively.

The recorded partial regression values emphasized a significantly negative effect of daily mean temperature and nymphs population in the two successive years (-2.32 and -4.08), respectively and highly significantly negative relation (-2.32) on the cumulative years. As well, the partial correlation values were (-0.48, -0.47 and -0.41) and (t-test) values were (-2.43, -2.35 and -3.01) when the mean relative humidity and dew point become around their means, during the first and second years and on the cumulative years, respectively, Table (4). The obtained results revealed that, daily mean temperature above the optimum range of nymphs' activity and this factor was responsible for the certain changes in the nymphs' population by 10.56 and 11.42 % during the first and second years, respectively. While, through the two cumulative years, the daily mean temperature entirely above the optimum range and was responsible by 8.54% from changes in population.

3.1.1.2. Effect of the mean relative humidity:

Data obtained are presented in Table (4), showed that the mean relative humidity had insignificant negative effects on nymphs activity, since the correlation coefficient were (r = -0.37, -0.02 and -0.17) for the 1st, 2nd years and concerning both years, respectively. As well as, the simple regression coefficient indicated that an increase of 1% in the mean relative humidity, would decrease the population density by 0.28, 0.02 and 0.15 individuals per leaf for the two years of study separately and on the two cumulative years altogether, respectively.

The real effect of R.H. is clear from the partial regression (P. reg.) values in Table

(4). Data showed that it had significantly negative effects (P. reg. values were -0.86, -1.51 and -0.82) for the 1st, 2nd years and on the two cumulative years, respectively. Also, the values of the partial correlation were (-0.44, -0.43 and -0.36) and t-test values were (-2.17, -2.14 and -2.57) when the daily mean temperature and dew point become around their means, respectively (Table, 4). The obtained results revealed that, mean relative humidity was above the optimum range of nymphs activity and this climatic factor was the least effective variable in population changes of the nymphs by 8.48, 9.43 and 6.24% during the both the first and second years and both years, respectively.

3.1.1.3. Effect of mean dew point:

Regarding the data in Table (4) the effect of mean dew point on nymphs population was highly significantly positive (r-values were 0.73, 0.68 and 0.70) during the first, second years and on the cumulative years, respectively. Also, the calculated regression coefficient (b) for the effect of this factor indicated that for every 1°C increase, the population would increase by 1.52, 1.72 and 1.63 individuals per leaf during the three periods of study, respectively.

The partial regression values (Table, 4), emphasized highly significantly positive relations between mean dew point and the nymphs activity (P. reg. values were 3.92, 6.35 and 4.16) during the two years of study separately and on the two cumulative years altogether, respectively. As well as, the values of the partial correlation were (0.65, 0.58 and 0.60), also (t-test) values were (3.86, 3.21 and 4.93) when the daily mean temperature and relative humidity become around their means, during the both the first and second years and both years, respectively (Table, 4).

The obtained results revealed that, mean dew point entirely under the optimum range of nymphs population and this climatic factor was the most effective variable for the

changes in the nymphs' population by 26.76, 21.26 and 22.93 %, respectively (Table, 4).

3.1.1.4. The combined effect of the tested climatic factors on the nymphs activity:

The combined effect of these climatic factors on the nymphs population was highly significant where the "F" values, were 11.92, 9.44 and 20.64 during the three periods of study, respectively, Table (4). The percentage of variability that could be attributed to the combined effect of these tested factors on the nymphs population which were 64.13, 58.62 and 58.46% during the two years of study separately and for both years altogether, respectively. The remaining unexplained variances are assumed to be due to the influences of other unconsidered and undetermined factors that were not included in this study in addition to the experimental error.

3.1.2. Adult females population:

3.1.2.1. Effect of daily mean temperature:

Results are presented in Table (4) showed that the simple correlation (r) between the daily mean temperature and the population density of adult females were insignificantly positive (r-values were 0.39 and 0.17) during the first and second years, respectively and significantly positive relation (0.29) on the two cumulative years. As well as, the calculated regression coefficient (b) for the effect of this factor indicated that every 1°C increase in the daily mean temperature, would increase the population by 0.31, 0.11 and 0.22 individuals per leaf for the first and second years and two cumulative years altogether, respectively.

The precise effect of this factor on the adult females population (Table, 4) showed that it had highly significantly negative (P. reg. values were -1.74 and -1.20) for the first year and both years, respectively, while, it was insignificant negative relation (P. reg. was -0.99) during the second year. Also, the values of partial correlation were (-0.55, -0.27 and -0.40) and the values of t-test were

(-2.92, -1.27 and -2.86) when the mean relative humidity and dew point become around their means, during the first and second years and on the two cumulative years, respectively. The obtained results revealed that, daily mean temperature entirely above the optimum range of adult females activity and was responsible for the certain changes in the population of adult females by 11.69 and 7.44% during the first year and on the two cumulative years, respectively. While, it was around the optimum range during the second year and this climatic factor was responsible by 3.51% from changes in population, Table (4).

3.1.2.2. Effect of the mean relative humidity:

As shown in Table (4), the correlation between relative humidity and the adult females population was insignificantly negative (r value was -0.11) for the first year and insignificantly positive relations (r values were 0.31 and 0.07) during the second year and both years, respectively. Also, the simple regression coefficient indicated that an increase of 1% in the mean relative humidity, would decrease the population by 0.06 individuals per leaf for the first year and would increase the population by 0.13 and 0.03 individuals per leaf through the second year and on the two cumulative years altogether, respectively.

The real effect of this factor appeared from the partial regression values which showed that the effect of relative humidity was insignificantly negative (P. reg. values were -0.45, -0.21 and -0.30) during the three periods of study, respectively. As well as, the values of the partial correlation were (-0.38, -0.15 and -0.25) and t values were (-1.85, -0.66 and -1.72) when the daily mean temperature and dew point become around their means, respectively. Results revealed that, mean relative humidity was around the optimum range of adult females activity and it was the least effective variable in population changes of the nymphs by 4.69,

0.96 and 2.68% during the two years of study separately and on the two cumulative years, respectively (Table, 4).

3.1.2.3. Effect of mean dew point:

Data in Table (4) indicated that, the effect of mean dew point on adult females activity was highly significantly positive (r values were 0.70, 0.58 and 0.64) during the two years of study separately and on the two cumulative years altogether, respectively. Also, the calculated regression coefficient (b) for the effect of this factor indicated that for every 1°C increase, the population would increase by 1.04, 0.65 and 0.84 individuals per leaf during the first and second years and on the two cumulative years, respectively.

The partial regression coefficient values for the effect of mean dew point on the adult females population are shown in Table (4), revealed that this factor had highly significant positive relations (P. reg. values were 3.13 and 2.28) during the first year and on the two cumulative years, respectively. While, the relation was insignificantly positive (P. reg. was 1.86) for the second year. Also, the partial correlation values were (0.74, 0.42 and 0.60) and the values of "t-test" were (4.94, 2.08 and 4.93) when the daily mean temperature and relative humidity become around their means, during the two years of study separately and on the two cumulative years altogether, respectively.

The obtained results revealed that, the mean dew point was entirely under the optimum range of adult females population during the first year and both years and under the optimum range of the adult females activity during the second year. This climatic factor was the most effective variable for the changes in the adult females' population by 33.61, 9.47 and 22.13 % during the three research periods, respectively in Table (4).

3.1.2.4. The combined effect of the all tests climatic factors on the adult females:

The results showed that the combined effect of these tested factors on the insect population of adult females was highly

significant where the "F" values, were 17.57, 8.52 and 21.98 during the first, second years and on the cumulative years in Table (4). The multiple regression analysis revealed that the tested studied variables together were responsible for the changes in the adult females' population. The percentages of explained variance (E.V.%) were 72.50, 56.09 and 59.97% respectively for the two years separately and during the two cumulative years altogether. The remaining unexplained variances are assumed to be due to the influences of other unconsidered and undetermined factors that were not included in this study in addition to the experimental error.

3.1.3- Total population of *Lepidosaphes tapleyi*:

3.1.3.1. Effect of daily mean temperature:

As shown in Table (4), the correlation coefficient (r) between the daily mean temperature and total population was significantly positive (0.50) in the first year, insignificantly positive effect (0.35) during the second year and highly significantly positive relation (0.42) through the two cumulative years. As well as, the effect regression coefficient (b) indicated that an increase of 1°C in the daily mean temperature increased the population by 0.94, 0.73 and 0.83 individuals per leaf during the first and second years and both cumulative years, respectively.

The partial regression value emphasized significantly negative relation (P. reg. was -4.06) during the first year, insignificant negative effect (P. reg. was -5.07) for the second year and highly significantly negative relation (P. reg. was -3.52) for the two cumulative years. Also, the values of the partial correlation were (-0.53, -0.42 and -0.43) and (t-test) values were (-2.78, -2.08 and -3.18) when the mean relative humidity and dew point become around their means during the two years of study separately and on the two cumulative years altogether, respectively. An increase of one

degree in the daily mean temperature, would decrease the population by 4.06, 5.07 and 3.52 individuals per leaf provided that other two factors remain constant during the three periods of study, respectively.

The obtained results indicated that, daily mean temperature above the optimum range of total population activity during the first year, but, it was around the optimum range for the second year and while, it was entirely above the optimum range for the two cumulative years altogether. This climatic factor was responsible for the certain changes in the total population of insect by 11.72, 9.00 and 8.74% during either of three periods, respectively (Table, 4).

3.1.3.2. Effect of the mean relative humidity:

The effect of mean relative humidity on total population of *L. tapleyi* was insignificantly negative (r values were -0.27 and -0.09) for the first year and on the cumulative years altogether, respectively and insignificantly positive correlation (r-value was 0.08) for the second year. The calculated regression coefficient (b) for the effect of this factor indicated that an increase of 1% in the mean relative humidity, the population would decrease by 0.34 and 0.11 individuals for the first year and on the two cumulative years, respectively and would increase by 0.11 individuals per leaf during the second year (Table, 4).

The partial regression values (Table, 4), were significantly negative (P. reg. were -1.31 and -1.11) for the first year and on the two cumulative years, respectively and insignificantly negative during the second year (P. reg. was -1.73). An increase of one degree in the mean relative humidity would decrease the population by 1.31, 1.73 and 1.11 individuals per leaf provided that other two factors remain constant during the first, second years and on the two cumulative years, respectively. Also, the values of the partial correlation were (-0.44, -0.36 and -0.35) and (t-test) values were (-2.18, -1.73 and -2.44) when the daily mean temperature

and dew point become around their means, during either of three periods, respectively (Table, 4).

The obtained results revealed that, mean relative humidity above the optimum range of total population activity during the first year and on the cumulative years, while, it was around the optimum range through the second year. This factor was the least effective variable in the total population of insect by 7.20, 6.25 and 5.15% during the both the first and second years and both years, respectively (Table, 4).

3.1.3.3. Effect of mean dew point:

Data in Table (4) indicated that, the effect of mean dew point on total population activity was highly significantly positive (0.74, 0.67 and 0.70) during the three periods of study, respectively. As well as, the calculated regression coefficient (b) for the effect of this factor indicated that for every 1°C increase, the population would increase by 2.56, 2.37 and 2.47 individuals per leaf during the first and second years and concerning both years, respectively (Table, 4). The partial regression coefficient values for the effect of mean dew point on total population activity are shown in Table (4). Data revealed that this factor had highly significantly positive relations (P. reg. values were 7.05, 8.22 and 6.44) during the three periods of study, respectively. The values of the partial correlation were (0.71, 0.55 and 0.62) and (t-test) values were (4.55, 2.95 and 5.30) when the daily mean temperature and relative humidity become around their means, during the both the study years separately and both years, respectively. The results revealed that the mean dew point was entirely under the optimum range of total population and it was the most effective variable for the changes in the total population by 31.37, 18.13 and 24.32 % during the first and second years and for the two cumulative years altogether, respectively in Table (4).

3.1.3.4. The combined effect of the tested climatic factors on the total population of *Lepidosaphes tapleyi*:

As shown in Table (4), the combined effect of these tested factors on *L. tapleyi* total population of was highly significant where the “F” values were 15.33, 9.29 and 23.88 during the first and second years and both cumulative years, respectively. The amount of variability that could be attributed to the combined effect of these tested factors on the total population of insect was 69.70, 58.21 and 61.95% during either of three periods, respectively (Table, 4). The remaining unexplained variances are assumed to be due to the influences of other undetermined and unconsidered factors that were not included in this study in addition to the experimental error.

3.2. Effect on the percentages of infestation incidence:

3.2.1. Effect of daily mean temperature:

Results presented in Table (5) showed that the simple correlation (r) between the daily mean temperature and the infestation incidence was significantly positive effect (0.51) during the first year and highly significantly positive relations (0.69 and 0.59) through the second year and the two cumulative year's altogether. As well as, the calculated regression coefficient (b) for the effect of this factor indicated that every 1°C increase in the daily mean temperature, would increase the percentage of infestation incidence by 0.64, 1.23 and 0.94 % during either of the three periods, respectively (Table, 5). The precise effect of this factor on the infestation incidence (Table, 5) showed that it had highly significantly negative (P. reg. value was -3.42) for the first year and insignificantly negative relations (P. reg. values were -3.43 and -0.79) for the second year and the two cumulative years, respectively. Also, the partial correlation values were (-0.54, -0.39 and -0.11) and the values of t-test were (-2.87, -1.87 and -0.74) when the mean relative humidity and dew

point become around their means, during the first and second years and concerning both years, respectively (Table,5). The obtained results revealed that, daily mean temperature entirely above the optimum range of infestation incidence by pest during the first year, while, it was around the optimum range during the second year and on the cumulative years. This climatic factor was the least effective variable in changes in the percentages of infestation incidence by 18.09, 5.64 and 0.70 % during the three periods of study, respectively (Table, 5).

3.2.2. Effect of the mean relative humidity:

Data in Table (5), showed that the mean relative humidity had significantly negative effect on infestation incidence, since the correlation coefficient was (r-value was -0.43) during the first year, insignificantly negative relation ($r = -0.36$) through the second year and highly significantly negative effect ($r = -0.38$) for the two cumulative years altogether. The unit effect (regression coefficient) indicated that an 1% increase in the mean relative humidity, would decrease the percentage of infestation incidence by 0.37, 0.41 and 0.39 % for the first and second years and during the two cumulative years, respectively (Table, 5).

The real effect of mean relative humidity appeared from the partial regression (P. reg.) values in Table (5), which showed that it had highly significantly negative effect was (-1.44) for the first year, significantly negative relation (P. reg. value was -1.62) during the second year and insignificantly negative effect (P. reg. value was -0.47) for the two cumulative years. Also, the partial correlation values were (-0.55, -0.43 and -0.16) and the values of t-test were (-2.94, -2.15 and -1.08) when the daily mean temperature and dew point become around

their means, during the two years of study separately and on the two cumulative years altogether, respectively, Table (5). The obtained results revealed that, mean relative humidity was entirely above the optimum range of infestation incidence activity by pest for the first year, while, it was above the optimum range during the second year and but, it was around the optimum range of infestation incidence activity on the two cumulative years. This climatic factor was responsible for the certain changes in the infestation incidence by 18.91, 7.48 and 1.46% during the three periods of study, respectively (Table,5).

3.2.3. Effect of mean dew point:

Regarding the data in Table (5), the effect of mean dew point on infestation incidence by *L. taplyi* was highly significantly positive (r- values were 0.61, 0.76 and 0.65) during the two years of study separately and on the two cumulative years altogether, respectively. Also, the calculated regression coefficient (b) for the effect of this factor indicated that for every 1°C increase, the percentage of infestation incidence would increase by 1.43, 2.31 and 1.81% during either of three periods, respectively (Table,5). The partial regression values (Table, 5), emphasized highly significantly positive relations (P. reg. values were 4.69 and 6.03) during the first and second years, respectively and significantly positive relation (P. reg. was 2.48) for the two cumulative years altogether. The partial correlation values were (0.64, 0.54 and 0.30), also (t-test) values were (3.71, 2.87 and 2.12) when the daily mean temperature and relative humidity become around their means, during the three periods of study, respectively, Table (5). The obtained results revealed that, mean dew

point entirely under the optimum range of infestation incidence activity by pest thought the first and second years, while, it was under the optimum range for the two cumulative years. This climatic factor was the most effective variable for changes in the percentages of infestation incidence by 30.21, 13.35 and 5.67 % during the first and second years and through the two cumulative years (Table ,5).

3.2.4. The combined effect of the tested climatic factors on the infestation incidence:

The results showed that the combined effect of these tested factors on the infestation incidence by pest was highly significant where the “F” value, were 8.54, 13.92 and 11.78 during either of three periods, respectively (Table, 5). The multiple regression analysis revealed that the tested studied variables together were responsible for the changes in the infestation incidence by pest. The percentages of explained variance (E.V. %) were 56.17, 67.62 and 44.55% during the two years of study separately and on the two cumulative years altogether, respectively.

3.3. Prediction of different *Lepidosaphes tapleyi* alive stages and the percentages of infestation incidence:

Furthermore, the most effective climatic factors, which could be used to predict of different *L. tapleyi* alive stages and the percentages of infestation incidence, were daily mean air temperature, relative humidity and dew point. Prediction equations were used according to the mentioned statistical analysis on basis the two cumulative years altogether in Tables (4 and 5) and presented as follow:

For nymphs' population:

$$Y = 57.74^{**} - 2.32 x_1^{**} - 0.82 x_2^* + 4.16 x_3^{**}$$

E.V.= 58.46%

For adult females population:

$$Y = 26.10^* - 1.20 x_1^{**} - 0.30 x_2 + 2.28 x_3^{**}$$

E.V.= 59.97 %

For total population:

$$Y = 83.84^{**} - 3.52 x_1^{**} - 1.11 x_2^* + 6.44 x_3^{**}$$

E.V.= 61.95 %

For the percentages of infestation incidence:

$$Y = 66.06^* - 0.79 x_1 - 0.47 x_2 + 2.48 x_3^*$$

E.V.= 44.55%

Where is,

Y= Prediction value.

X₁= Daily mean air. temperature

X₂= Relative humidity.

X₃= Dew point.

E.V.% = Explained variance

* Significant at $P \leq 0.05$

** Highly significant at $P \leq 0.01$

The results on the effect of three considered weather factors on the insect population and on the percentages of infestation its incidence by *L. tapleyi* during the two successive years emphasized that the effect of these factors varied from year to another. Also, the dew point was the most effective variable for the changes in the insect population and on the percentages of infestation incidence by pest during either of three periods of study

Table (1): Half-monthly mean numbers of different stages of *Lepidosaphes tapleyi* and the percentages of infestation incidence on guava trees, with climatic factors affecting at Esna district, Luxor Governorate during the first year of (2017/2018).

Season	Date of inspection		Mean number of individuals per leaf ± S.E.			Infestation incidence (%)	Climatic factors		
			Nymphs (Immature stages)	Adult females (Mature stages)	Total		Mean temp.°C	%R.H.	Dew point °C
Spring	March, 2017	1	5.95 ± 0.28	2.39 ± 0.13	8.34 ± 0.40	45.00 ± 2.04	18.96	41.36	4.64
		15	8.25 ± 0.38	2.24 ± 0.12	10.49 ± 0.50	51.25 ± 2.39	19.32	30.07	4.36
	April	1	11.76 ± 0.55	3.76 ± 0.20	15.52 ± 0.75	55.00 ± 2.04	22.06	32.41	5.24
		15	8.24 ± 0.38	2.35 ± 0.13	10.59 ± 0.51	57.50 ± 3.23	23.36	25.14	6.64
	May	1	8.78 ± 0.41	2.76 ± 0.15	11.54 ± 0.55	52.50 ± 3.23	26.09	19.19	6.38
		15	16.39 ± 0.76	8.54 ± 0.47	24.93 ± 1.22	70.00 ± 4.56	28.18	18.07	7.43
Average			9.90 ± 0.72	3.67 ± 0.47	13.57 ± 1.18	55.21 ± 1.94	23.00	27.71	5.78
Summer	June	1	11.30 ± 0.52	5.51 ± 0.30	16.81 ± 0.82	62.50 ± 3.23	30.26	18.29	9.35
		15	8.98 ± 0.42	4.76 ± 0.26	13.75 ± 0.67	50.00 ± 2.04	33.32	17.21	10.86
	July	1	16.35 ± 0.76	5.48 ± 0.30	21.83 ± 1.05	51.25 ± 2.39	31.88	19.56	11.63
		15	18.47 ± 0.86	10.22 ± 0.56	28.69 ± 1.40	66.25 ± 3.75	33.50	19.79	12.79
	August	1	11.15 ± 0.52	9.09 ± 0.50	20.24 ± 1.01	62.50 ± 3.23	35.00	20.06	13.65
		15	17.70 ± 0.82	8.14 ± 0.44	25.84 ± 1.26	56.25 ± 3.75	34.30	20.86	14.07
Average			13.99 ± 0.80	7.20 ± 0.45	21.19 ± 1.12	58.13 ± 1.70	33.04	19.30	12.06
Autumn	September	1	17.85 ± 0.83	14.55 ± 0.79	32.40 ± 1.61	63.75 ± 2.39	34.76	21.71	14.88
		15	20.43 ± 0.95	13.76 ± 0.75	34.19 ± 1.69	70.00 ± 2.04	32.36	23.64	14.07
	October	1	29.89 ± 1.39	18.08 ± 0.99	47.98 ± 2.36	72.50 ± 3.23	31.75	25.50	14.31
		15	19.12 ± 0.89	12.82 ± 0.70	31.94 ± 1.57	60.00 ± 2.89	30.61	25.64	13.00
	November	1	21.45 ± 1.00	11.03 ± 0.60	32.47 ± 1.59	68.75 ± 2.39	29.35	26.94	12.41
		15	32.19 ± 1.49	20.14 ± 1.10	52.33 ± 2.57	71.25 ± 3.75	25.00	33.64	11.71
Average			23.49 ± 1.21	15.06 ± 0.72	38.55 ± 1.87	67.71 ± 1.38	30.64	26.18	13.40
Winter	December	1	20.25 ± 0.94	17.85 ± 0.97	38.10 ± 1.90	62.50 ± 3.23	23.91	35.88	10.69
		15	9.29 ± 0.43	9.54 ± 0.52	18.83 ± 0.94	58.75 ± 2.39	18.11	38.50	6.79
	January, 2018	1	7.56 ± 0.35	7.03 ± 0.38	14.59 ± 0.73	56.25 ± 3.75	17.09	39.82	5.06
		15	6.77 ± 0.31	6.45 ± 0.35	13.22 ± 0.66	53.75 ± 2.39	14.71	48.29	6.21
	February	1	4.66 ± 0.22	3.79 ± 0.21	8.45 ± 0.42	48.75 ± 2.39	15.76	45.88	5.82
		15	4.11 ± 0.19	3.61 ± 0.20	7.72 ± 0.38	42.50 ± 1.44	19.57	44.36	7.36
Average			8.77 ± 1.14	8.05 ± 1.02	16.82 ± 2.16	53.75 ± 1.68	18.19	42.12	6.99
Total			336.89	203.89	540.77				
General average			14.04 ± 0.77	8.50 ± 0.55	22.53 ± 1.28	58.70 ± 1.00	26.22	28.83	9.56
%			62.30	37.70					

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Table (2): Half-monthly mean numbers of different stages of *Lepidosaphes tapleyi* and the percentages of infestation incidence on guava trees, with climatic factors affecting at Esna district, Luxor Governorate during the second year of (2018/2019).

Season	Date of inspection		Mean number of individuals per leaf ± S.E.			Infestation incidence (%)	Climatic factors		
			Nymphs (Immature stages)	Adult females (Mature stages)	Total		Mean temp.°C	%R.H.	Dew point °C
Spring	March, 2018	1	4.99 ± 0.23	2.78 ± 0.15	7.77 ± 0.39	50.00 ± 2.89	19.39	28.86	4.86
		15	7.96 ± 0.37	3.29 ± 0.18	11.25 ± 0.55	50.00 ± 2.89	22.29	24.93	6.14
	April	1	11.34 ± 0.53	5.29 ± 0.29	16.63 ± 0.81	55.00 ± 2.04	23.53	24.71	7.00
		15	18.46 ± 0.86	7.90 ± 0.43	26.36 ± 1.28	55.00 ± 2.89	24.46	21.93	6.71
	May	1	16.05 ± 0.74	7.39 ± 0.40	23.45 ± 1.14	50.00 ± 2.89	25.34	19.94	6.94
		15	11.95 ± 0.55	5.12 ± 0.28	17.06 ± 0.83	45.00 ± 2.04	30.14	16.57	9.14
Average			11.79 ± 0.97	5.30 ± 0.41	17.09 ± 1.38	50.83 ± 1.19	24.19	22.82	6.80
Summer	June	1	9.10 ± 0.42	5.94 ± 0.32	15.04 ± 0.74	56.25 ± 2.39	32.24	16.35	9.94
		15	7.58 ± 0.35	5.31 ± 0.29	12.89 ± 0.64	55.00 ± 2.89	34.32	15.64	11.21
	July	1	13.59 ± 0.63	6.57 ± 0.36	20.16 ± 0.98	50.00 ± 2.89	32.53	21.88	13.31
		15	28.06 ± 1.30	10.05 ± 0.55	38.11 ± 1.84	55.00 ± 2.89	32.64	26.21	15.57
	August	1	16.08 ± 0.75	10.20 ± 0.56	26.28 ± 1.29	60.00 ± 2.89	32.26	23.41	14.06
		15	18.60 ± 0.86	8.03 ± 0.44	26.62 ± 1.29	66.25 ± 3.75	32.11	22.36	14.00
Average			15.50 ± 1.44	7.68 ± 0.43	23.19 ± 1.81	57.08 ± 1.50	32.68	20.98	13.02
Autumn	September	1	19.75 ± 0.92	12.52 ± 0.68	32.28 ± 1.59	70.00 ± 4.56	32.65	25.35	15.41
		15	33.94 ± 1.57	17.17 ± 0.94	51.11 ± 2.49	71.25 ± 3.75	32.14	27.36	15.57
	October	1	22.18 ± 1.03	9.86 ± 0.54	32.04 ± 1.56	66.25 ± 3.75	31.31	28.25	14.88
		15	25.12 ± 1.17	12.64 ± 0.69	37.77 ± 1.84	65.00 ± 4.56	26.61	30.43	11.93
	November	1	37.92 ± 1.76	16.94 ± 0.92	54.86 ± 2.67	70.00 ± 2.89	24.75	35.56	11.94
		15	30.93 ± 1.43	17.91 ± 0.98	48.84 ± 2.40	60.00 ± 3.54	22.93	39.36	11.57
Average			28.31 ± 1.44	14.51 ± 0.69	42.82 ± 2.06	67.08 ± 1.62	28.40	31.05	13.55
Winter	December	1	13.90 ± 0.65	9.48 ± 0.52	23.39 ± 1.15	56.25 ± 2.39	21.22	45.06	11.69
		15	9.35 ± 0.43	7.71 ± 0.42	17.06 ± 0.85	40.00 ± 2.04	18.29	45.79	9.29
	January, 2019	1	8.06 ± 0.37	9.21 ± 0.50	17.27 ± 0.87	38.75 ± 2.39	14.94	46.18	5.88
		15	7.67 ± 0.36	8.97 ± 0.49	16.64 ± 0.84	35.00 ± 2.04	16.18	49.07	7.36
	February	1	7.68 ± 0.36	7.80 ± 0.42	15.48 ± 0.78	36.25 ± 1.25	17.12	32.35	4.41
		15	3.67 ± 0.17	3.98 ± 0.22	7.65 ± 0.38	33.75 ± 2.39	17.07	35.36	5.29
Average			8.39 ± 0.65	7.86 ± 0.42	16.25 ± 1.01	40.00 ± 1.75	17.47	42.30	7.32
Total			383.95	212.08	596.02				
General average			16.00 ± 0.96	8.84 ± 0.43	24.83 ± 1.36	53.75 ± 1.26	25.69	29.29	10.17
%			64.42	35.58	100.00				

Table (3): Rate of monthly variation (R.M.V.P) in the mean number of *Lepidosaphes tapleyi* and the and the percentages of infestation incidence counted on guava trees at Esna district, Luxor Governorate through the two years of (2017/2018 and 2018/2019).

Years	Month of inspection	Immature stages (Nymphs)	Mature stages (Adult females)	Total	Infestation incidence (%)
2017/2018	Mar.	—	—	—	—
	April	1.41	1.32	1.39	1.17
	May	1.26	1.85	1.40	1.09
	June	0.81	0.91	0.84	0.92
	July	1.72	1.53	1.65	1.04
	Aug.	0.83	1.10	0.91	1.01
	Sept.	1.33	1.64	1.45	1.13
	Oct.	1.28	1.09	1.20	0.99
	Nov.	1.09	1.01	1.06	1.06
	Dec.	0.55	0.88	0.67	0.87
	Jan.	0.49	0.49	0.49	0.91
	Feb.	0.61	0.55	0.58	0.83
2018/2019	Mar.	—	—	—	—
	April	2.30	2.17	2.26	1.10
	May	0.94	0.95	0.94	0.86
	June	0.60	0.90	0.69	1.17
	July	2.50	1.48	2.09	0.94
	Aug.	0.83	1.10	0.91	1.20
	Sept.	1.55	1.63	1.58	1.12
	Oct.	0.88	0.76	0.84	0.93
	Nov.	1.46	1.55	1.49	0.99
	Dec.	0.34	0.49	0.39	0.74
	Jan.	0.68	1.06	0.84	0.77
	Feb.	0.72	0.65	0.68	0.95

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Table (4): Different models of correlation and regression analyses for describing the relationship between the main weather factors and the population density of different stages of *Lepidosaphes tapleyi* during the two years from 2017 to 2019.

Years	Stages (Y)	Tested counts (X)	Sample correlation and regression values				Partial correlation and regression values				Efficiency %	Rank	Analysis variance			
			r	b	S.E	t	P. cor.	P. reg.	S.E	t			F values	MR	R ²	E.V.%
First year (2017/2018)	Nymphs	Mean temp.	0.55	0.62	0.20	3.13 **	-0.48	-2.32	0.96	-2.43 *	10.56	2	11.92 **	0.80	0.64	64.13
		R.H.%	-0.37	-0.28	0.15	-1.86	-0.44	-0.86	0.39	-2.17 *	8.48	3				
		Dew Point	0.73	1.52	0.30	5.01 **	0.65	3.92	1.02	3.86 **	26.76	1				
	Adult females	Mean temp.	0.39	0.31	0.16	1.99	-0.55	-1.74	0.60	-2.92 **	11.69	2	17.57 **	0.85	0.73	72.50
		R.H.%	-0.11	-0.06	0.12	-0.54	-0.38	-0.45	0.25	-1.85	4.69	3				
		Dew Point	0.70	1.04	0.23	4.60 **	0.74	3.13	0.63	4.94 **	33.61	1				
	Total	Mean temp.	0.50	0.94	0.34	2.72 *	-0.53	-4.06	1.46	-2.78 *	11.72	2	15.33 **	0.83	0.70	69.70
		R.H.%	-0.27	-0.34	0.26	-1.32	-0.44	-1.31	0.60	-2.18 *	7.20	3				
		Dew Point	0.74	2.56	0.50	5.16 **	0.71	7.05	1.55	4.55 **	31.37	1				
Second year (2018/2019)	Nymphs	Mean temp.	0.41	0.62	0.29	2.14 *	-0.47	-4.08	1.73	-2.35 *	11.42	2	9.44 **	0.77	0.59	58.62
		R.H.%	-0.02	-0.02	0.20	-0.09	-0.43	-1.51	0.71	-2.14 *	9.43	3				
		Dew Point	0.68	1.72	0.40	4.31 **	0.58	6.35	1.98	3.21 **	21.26	1				
	Adult females	Mean temp.	0.17	0.11	0.14	0.81	-0.27	-0.99	0.79	-1.27	3.51	2	8.52 **	0.75	0.56	56.09
		R.H.%	0.31	0.13	0.09	1.50	-0.15	-0.21	0.32	-0.66	0.96	3				
		Dew Point	0.58	0.65	0.19	3.36 **	0.42	1.86	0.90	2.08	9.47	1				
	Total	Mean temp.	0.35	0.73	0.42	1.75	-0.42	-5.07	2.44	-2.08	9.00	2	9.29 **	0.76	0.58	58.21
		R.H.%	0.08	0.11	0.29	0.39	-0.36	-1.73	1.00	-1.73	6.25	3				
		Dew Point	0.67	2.37	0.57	4.18 **	0.55	8.22	2.79	2.95 **	18.13	1				
Two cumulative years (2017 to 2019)	Nymphs	Mean temp.	0.47	0.61	0.17	3.57 **	-0.41	-2.32	0.77	-3.01 **	8.54	2	20.64 **	0.76	0.58	58.46
		R.H.%	-0.17	-0.15	0.13	-1.16	-0.36	-0.82	0.32	-2.57 *	6.24	3				
		Dew Point	0.70	1.63	0.25	6.63 **	0.60	4.16	0.84	4.93 **	22.93	1				
	Adult females	Mean temp.	0.29	0.22	0.10	2.08 *	-0.40	-1.20	0.42	-2.86 **	7.44	2	21.98 **	0.77	0.60	59.97
		R.H.%	0.07	0.03	0.07	0.47	-0.25	-0.30	0.17	-1.72	2.68	3				
		Dew Point	0.64	0.84	0.15	5.67 **	0.60	2.28	0.46	4.93 **	22.13	1				
	Total	Mean temp.	0.42	0.83	0.27	3.13 **	-0.43	-3.52	1.11	-3.18 **	8.74	2	23.88 **	0.79	0.62	61.95
		R.H.%	-0.09	-0.11	0.19	-0.59	-0.35	-1.11	0.46	-2.44 *	5.15	3				
		Dew Point	0.70	2.47	0.37	6.71 **	0.62	6.44	1.22	5.30 **	24.32	1				

Figure (1): Means of half-monthly counts of different stages and the percentages of infestation incidence by *Lepidosaphes tapleyi* on guava trees, with climatic factors affecting at Esna district, Luxor Governorate during the first year of (2017/2018).

Figure (2): Means of half-monthly counts of different stages and the percentages of infestation incidence by *Lepidosaphes tapleyi* on guava trees, with climatic factors affecting at Esna district, Luxor Governorate during the second year of (2018/2019).

Figure (3): Population density of *Lepidosaphes tapleyi* different stages and the percentages of infestation incidence counted on guava leaves at Esna district, Luxor Governorate during the two successive years (2017/2018 and 2018/2019).

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Dipteran and coleopteran natural enemies associated with cantaloupe crop in Qalyubiya Governorate, Egypt

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Abstract:

Studying diversity of natural enemies associated with their pests in agro ecosystems is urgent for the integrated pest management. Two sampling techniques (i.e. water traps (pit-fall traps) and direct count of insects in the field) were used to survey pests, natural enemies and pollinators on six cantaloupe cultivars in Qaha region of Qalyubiya Governorate, Egypt over 2006 and 2007 summer plantation seasons. Thirty-two species belonging to two insects in Diptera and Coleoptera orders presented by 18 superfamilies and 23 families and 22 genera. They were recorded on Ideal, E81-065, Mirella, Vicar, E81-013 and Magenta cantaloupe cultivars. Diptera was represented by eighteen species belonging to 13 families (Sepsidae, Phoridae, Scenophilidae, Dolichopodidae, Otitidae, Agromyzidae, Ephydriidae, Drosophilidae, Tachinidae, Anthomyiidae, Muscidae, Syrphidae and Cecidomyiidae). Field observations indicated that *Liriomyza trifolii* (Burg), Agromyzidae infested cantaloupe leaves in moderate populations, while *Melanogromyza cuntans* (Meign) infested leaves in low populations. The present study revealed that the parasite *Tachina larvarum* L. (Tachinidae) and the predator *Syrphus corolla* F. (Syrphidae) were found in low levels. *Pheanobremia aphidivora* (Rubsamen) (Cecidomyiidae) was observed in moderate populations on leaves. However, other dipteran species were recorded in cantaloupe leaves at low levels. Most coleopteran insects in the present survey were pests, however, others were predators such as *Coccinella undecimpunctata*, *Coccinella septempunctata* and *Cydonia vicina* (Coccinellidae), *Paederus aliferii* Koch. (Staphylinidae) and *Clasoma chlorostictum* Deg. (Carabidae).

Introduction

Successful Integrated Pest Management requires a thorough knowledge of the pest insect's biology, their natural enemies and the crop to allow rational use of a cultivar of

cultivation and control techniques under differing circumstances (Gullan and Cranston, 2017). So, it is necessary to know and conserve the diversity of agents of

biological control (predators and parasitoids) present in the agro ecosystems (Crowder and Jabbour, 2014).

Vinutha *et al.* (2017) indicated the presence of several predators from the orders Coleoptera, Mantodea, Hemiptera, and Odonata. This information can be used to improve the integrated pest management in the crops. The survey of insect pests and their associated natural enemies of cantaloupe in Qaha of Qalyubiya Governorate over 2006 and 2007 summer plantation was studied. The results included survey of pests from two classes (Insecta and Arachnida). Six insect orders were recorded; Hemiptera, Lepidoptera, Orthoptera, Thysanoptera, Neuroptera and Dermaptera. Arachnida was represented by two orders (Acarina and Araneida) (Younes *et al.*, 2010).

The aim of this study was to survey dipteran and coleopteran natural enemies associated with cantaloupe crop pests.

Materials and methods

The study was carried out in the Experimental Farm of Plant Protection Research Institute at Qaha region, southwest of Qalyubiya Governorate (30°17'00 "N, 31° 12'00 "E of 133 meters (436 ft) below sea level) in Egypt. An area of about 2100 m² was cultivated with six cantaloupe cultivars (i.e. Ideal, E81-065, Mirella, Vicar, E81-013 and Magenta) over 2006 and 2007 summer plantation during the period of vegetative growth until the harvest of cantaloupe. Each cultivar was cultivated in 350 m² with three replicates (of about 116.67 m²). Seeds were sown on April 13th and 16th over 2006 and 2007, respectively at 30 cm apart between hills in CRBD. The recommended agricultural practices for cantaloupe cultivation was completely adopted without any chemical control measures through the period of study. The survey was carried out by two sampling techniques

a. Water traps filled with water and detergent (pit-fall traps) and distributed between plants

in considerable distance during only 2006 season.

b. Direct field observation followed by laboratory examination which were carried out during two investigated seasons.

Pit-fall traps, 10 cm diameter and 14 cm depth (filled with water and detergent) were installed at 14 cm below soil surface after 32 days of sowing date (they were located one trap per each replicate of the tested cantaloupe varieties). Traps were replaced every 5 days during the first season of study. The trap catches were transferred to the laboratory, where pests and natural enemies were obtained by using a sieve plate to isolate the different species in the same day.

The second sampling technique was carried out for two consecutive seasons, sampling started after about two weeks from cultivation date and on 7-day intervals (continued for 15 weeks). Samples of 180 leaves (10 leaves x 3 replicates) for each cultivar were randomly picked out from different levels "upper, middle and lower" of the plant in the morning. A primary examination was made by naked eyes, in the field then randomized leaf samples were kept separately in polyethylene bags and transferred to the laboratory. All the collected species from both sampling techniques were isolated and counted either by naked eyes (in case of large insect species) or by aid of a stereomicroscope (in case of small insects). Some of these species can be identified immediately, but others were difficult to be known, so they were assorted into orders then into species and preserved in vials containing 70% ethanol alcohol to be identified.

The different pests, predators and parasitoids recorded on leaves of cantaloupe cultivars were estimated by counting the total number on both leaf sides.

A label including all necessary information concerning locality, date of collection and name of the host plant (cantaloupe) was stuck on a vial of each

unknown specimen, also the abundance and developmental stage of species were considered. Also, there was a complete systematic arrangement of classes, orders, suborders, super families, families and sub-families of all arthropod species as possible. Identification of most insect species belong to orders Diptera and Coleoptera was carried out in Survey and Taxonomy Research Department, Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Giza.

Results and discussion

A taxonomic list of each species together with their economic importance, frequency, site occurrence, insect stage, time of occurrence were found in detail as follow:

1. Order: Diptera:

Adults are among man's greatest tormentors ever-persistent nuisances and his most effective enemies as carriers of innumerable agencies of disease and death. Although no other order of insects affects humans so adversely, many large families do much good in the reduction of carrion and in the destruction of phytophagous insects that destroy agricultural crops. Flies are among swiftest and most agile fliers and can outmaneuver any other insect on the wing. Regardless of exaggerated claims, certain species can probably travel 50 miles an hour which is a real accomplishment for such small, light and fragile bodies. While, many species are more or less noiseless in the air, most members of the group are decidedly noisy and hum with a soft or loud, low or high-pitched tune which is somewhat characteristic of the families, and may serve in locating the opposite sex in mating. This order comprises three suborders (Brachycera, Cyclorrhapha and Nematocera).

1.1. Suborder: Brachycera:

Suborder Brachycera is divided in the present survey into five superfamilies (Sciomyzoidea, Platypezoidea, Asiloidea, Empidoidea and Tephritoidea) (Table, 1). Sciomyzoidea was represented by one family (Sepsidae) and one species *Sepsis fissa*

Becker was recorded as adults in soil during August, however, this species considered as pest on cantaloupe cultivars. Superfamily Platypezoidea was represented by one species belonging to family Phoridae; *Megaselia scalaris* Loew and this species occurred as adults infested cantaloupe leaves during July-August. Superfamily Asiloidea was found to be represented by one species *Scenopinus glabrifrons* (Meign) belongs to the family Scenopinidae observed as predator adults on cantaloupe leaves and flowers during May. Superfamily Empidoidea was represented by one family (Dolichopodidae) and two predator species observed as adults; (*Hydrophorus praecox* Lehmann during July-August and *Tachytrechus planitarsis* (Becker) during August on cantaloupe leaves. Superfamily Tephritoidea was represented by one family (Otitidae) and one species (*Physiphora demandata*) observed as adult on plant flowers and this species considered as pollinator and/or visitor (Table 1).

1.2. Suborder Cyclorrhapha:

Suborder Cyclorrhapha was represented in the present study by four superfamilies (Opomyzoidea, Ephydroidea, Muscoidea and Syrphoidea). Opomyzoidea was represented by one family (Agromyzidae), comprises two species considered as pests on cantaloupe. Moderate population of *L. trifolii* at different developmental stages was observed on plant leaves during May-August and the second species was *Melanagromza cunctans* Meign which was observed as few adults individuals on leaves and stems of cantaloupe during July-August. Superfamily Ephydroidea in the present study was represented by three families. The first one (Ephydridae) was represented by two species of insect pests as few adults on cantaloupe leaves. First of them was *Allotrichoma aegyptium* (Cresson) and the second was *Elphatinosoma chnumi* (Becker) and all these species were observed during August. The second family (Drosophilidae) was represented by only one

species *Drosophila melanogaster* Mg. observed during June on plant leaves. The third family (Tachinidae) was represented during August as parasite adults on cantaloupe leaves (Table, 2). Superfamily Muscoidea contains two families (Anthomyiidae and Muscidae). The first one was presented during July by *Pegomyia hyoscyami* Panzer). The second one was represented by *Antherigona varia* (Meign) during August (Table,1). The fourth superfamily Syrphoidea was represented by one family Syrphidae. The present survey revealed that there were two insect species considered as predators on the pest infesting cantaloupe plants, the first one was *Sphaerophoria flavicauda* (Zetterstedt) observed as adults on the plant flowers during May, and the second ones was *Syrphus corollae* F. observed as larvae and adults on both leaves and flowers of cantaloupe during May- July.

1.3. Suborder Nematocera:

Only one superfamily (Bibionomorpha) was recorded. Family Cecidomyiidae belong to this superfamily. The recorded species of this family were *Contarinia forskalii* (Debski) which was observed as adult pest in few individuals on plant leaves during August, and *Pheanobremia aphidivora* (Rubsaaamen) as predator observed as eggs deposited on the cantaloupe leaves during June- July (Table, 1).

2. Order: Coleoptera:

There were two suborders belonging to this order (Polyphaga and Adephaga). Suborder Polyphaga was represented by seven superfamilies (Elateroidea, Tenebrionoidea, Curculionidea, Cucujoidea, Buprestoidea, Scarabaeoidea and Staphylinoidea) (Table, 2). The superfamily Elateroidea was represented by Elateridae. This family contained *Drasterius bimaculatus* Rossi which considered as pest affected growth of cantaloupe cultivars, and the site of occurrence of this species recorded in soil during August.

Beetles of superfamily Tenebrionoidea comprised in the present survey two families (Anthicidae and Mycetophagidae). The most abundant species belonging to family Anthicidae were *Anthicus crinitus* La Ferte which was considered as pests observed on flowers of cantaloupe cultivars during July-August. Family Mycetophagidae was represented by one species *Typhaea stercorea* L. which was considered as pest observed on plant leaves of cantaloupe cultivars during August. Superfamily Curculionoidea in the present survey was represented by one family Curculionidae which was *Ceuthorrhynchus viator* Faust and considered as a pest. It was recorded on cantaloupe during May -August. There were two families belonging to superfamilies Cucujoidea (Nitidulidae and Coccinellidae) (Table, 2). Nitidulidae was represented by two insect pests *Carpophilus hemipterus* L. and *C. humeralis* F. collected from flowers of cantaloupe cultivars during August. Family Coccinellidae (Ladybirds) was represented in the present survey on the cantaloupe cultivars by different predator species (*Coccinella undecimpunctata* L., *Coccinella septempunctata* L. and *Cydonia vicina* var *isis* cr.) which was observed on plant leaves during May-August. The present observations clearly indicated that these species observed as eggs and adults on plant leaves of cantaloupe. Superfamily Buprestoidea was represented in the present survey by one species, *Anthaxia angustipennis* Klug. belonging to family Buprstidae. It was observed as adult pest collected from the stems of cantaloupe cultivars during May. *Tropinota squalida* Scop. was considered as pest collected from cantaloupe flowers as adults during June and this species belonging to superfamily Scaraboidea and family Scarabidae. Superfamily Staphylinoidea comprised one family Staphylinidae including a familiar predator *P. aliferii* which was observed as adults collected from the plant leaves during

June-July (Table, 2). Suborder Adephaga, was represented by one superfamily Caraboidea (Table, 2).

The present study indicated there was only one species *Calosoma chlorostictum chlorostictum* Deg. belonging to family Carabidae and it was recorded as predacious insects collected as adults from plant leaves of cantaloupe cultivars during July.

Surveyed insect pests and associated natural enemies inhabiting cantaloupe plants using direct count and pit-fall traps in Qaha, Qalyubiya Governorate. The current investigation results in 33 insect species comprised 19 pests, 1 parasitoid, 12 predators and 1 pollinator on the Ideal, E81- 065, Mirella, Vicar, E81-013 and Magenta cantaloupe cultivars. *L. trifolii* was the most important pest in the current investigation attacked cantaloupe plants and recorded in moderate population. Eggs of the predator; *P. aphidivora* were also recorded in moderate population. The predator, *S. corollae* was also recorded in the current investigation in few numbers. Order Coleoptera in the current investigation was represented by different pests don't have economic high importance. In other sense, it was represented by different familiar predator species such as *C. undecimpunctata*, *C. semptempunctata* and *C. vicina* var isis cr. in family Coccinellidae and *P. aliferii* in family Staphylinidae. These results are in harmony with El-Maghraby *et al.* (1994), Bachatly and Sedrak (1997) and Gameel (2013) who found that, *C. undecimpunctata* were the most common predator species associated with the cucurbit pests. Atakan and Canhilal (2004) in Turkey assessed yellow sticky traps in a field study on cotton. They recorded leafhoppers, *Asymetresca decedens* Paoli and *Empoasca decipens* Paoli, cotton whitefly, *B. tabaci* Genn., and western flower thrips *Frankliniella occidentalis* (Pergande). Presence and abundance of different insect predators against sucking insect pest of cotton were studied by Solangi *et al.* (2008).

Younes *et al.* (2010) surveyed pests and their associated natural enemies occurring on six cantaloupe cultivars at Qaha region, Qalyubiya Governorate over summer plantation of 2006 and 2007 seasons. Authors used two sampling techniques; water traps filled with water and detergent (pit-fall traps) and direct field observations followed by laboratory examination. Two arthropod classes were recorded; Insecta and Arachnida. Insecta was represented by six insect orders (Hemiptera, Lepidoptera, Orthoptera, Thysanoptera, Neuroptera and Dermaptera). However, Arachnida was represented by two orders Acarina and Araneida. Authors also made complete systematic arrangement of species into orders, suborders, superfamilies and families. Abdel-Rahman *et al.* (2016) recorded in a field study on cantaloupe in Assiut, Egypt 22 insect species derived from 17 families and 10 orders. The most important pests were *B. tabaci*, *T. urticae*, *A. gossypii*, *T. tabaci* and *Empoasca spp.* On the other hand, *Orius sp.*, *Ch. carnea* and *C. undecimpunctata* L. were the most abundant predators. Vinutha *et al.* (2017) recorded in a survey study pest and their associated natural enemies with *C. melo* var. conomon at different stages of crop growth. They documented 24 insect pests and nine natural enemies belonging to 9 orders. The most important pest on vegetative part was *L. trifolii*. The most important natural enemies recorded belonged family to Coccinellidae. Carvalho *et al.* (2018) surveyed different pests and their associated with pests on melon. The samples were collected weekly during the cycle of melon, using passive (Pitfall and Moericke traps) and active (sweep net) collection methods. The recorded families with the highest relative abundances in the passive collection method were Labiduridae, Formicidae, Chrysopidae, Coccinellidae and Staphylinidae. These families contain important species of predator which can promote crop pest suppression in melon agricultural systems.

The obtained information showed the presence of families Cecidomyiidae and Syrphidae (Diptera) and Coccinellidae (Coleoptera). The predators of these families may play an important role in regulating

cantaloupe pests. Therefore, more detailed studies should be carried out on these families to know the potential of these predators for integrated pest management in the cantaloupe crop.

Table (1): Partial taxonomic list of dipteran pests, associated with cantaloupe cultivars in Qaha region, Qalyubiya Governorate over two successive growing seasons (2006 and 2007).

Taxonomic category	Scientific name	Insect stage	Site of occurrence	Frequency	Relationship	Period of occurrence
Order: Diptera						
A- Suborder						
Brachycera						
1- Superfamily:						
Sciomyzoidea						
Family: Sepsidae	<i>Sepsis fissa</i> (Becker)	Adults	Soil	+	Pest	August
2- Superfamily:						
Platypezoidea						
Family: Phoridae	<i>Megaselia scalaris</i> (Loew)	Adults	Leaves	+	Pest	July- August
3- Superfamily:						
Asiloidea						
Family: Scenopinidae	<i>Scenopinus glabrifrons</i> (Meign)	Adults	Flowers and leaves	+	Predator	May
4- Superfamily:						
Empidoidea						
Family: Dolichopodidae	<i>Hydrophorus praecox</i> (Lehmann)	Adults	Leaves	+	Predator	July – August
	<i>Syn: Hydrophorus inaequalipes</i> (Macqmart)					
	<i>Tachytrechus planitarsis</i> (Becker)	Adults	Leaves	+	Predator	August
5- Superfamily:						
Tephritoidea						
Family: Otitidae	<i>Physiphora demandata</i> (Fabricius)	Adults	Flowers	+	Pollinator	August
B- Suborder						
Cyclorrhapha						
1- Superfamily:						
Agromyzidae						
	<i>Liriomyza trifolii</i> (Burg)	Eggs, larve, pupae and adults	Leaves	++	Pest	May- August
	<i>Melanagromza cunctans</i> (Meign)	Adults	Leaves and stems	+	Pest	July- August

+ Few individuals were recorded in the present survey.

Table (1): continued.

Taxonomic category	Scientific name	Insect stage	Site occurrence	of	Frequency	Relationship	Period of occurrence
2- Superfamily:							
Ephydroidea							
Family: Ephydriidae	<i>Allotrichoma aegyptium</i> (Cresson)	Adults	Leaves		+	Pest	August
	<i>Elphantinosoma chnumi</i> (Becker)	Adults	Leaves		+	Pest	August
Family: Drosophilidae	<i>Drosophila melanogaster</i> Mg.	Adults	Leaves		+	Pest	June
Family: Tachinidae	<i>Tachina larvarum</i> L.	Adults	Leaves		+	Parasitoid	August
3- Superfamily:							
Muscoidea							
Family: Anthomyiidae	<i>Pegomyia hyoscyami</i> (Panzer)	Adults	Leaves		+	Pest	July
Family: Muscidae	<i>Antherigona varia</i> (Meigen)	Adults	Leaves		+	Pest	August
4- Superfamily:							
Syrphoidea							
Family: Syrphidae	<i>Sphaerphoria flavicauda</i> (Zetterstedt)	Adults	Flowers		+	Predator	May
	<i>Syrphus corollae</i> F.	Larvae and adults	Flowers leaves	and	+	Predator	May- July
C- Suborder:							
Nematocera							
Superfamily:							
Bibionomorpha							
Family: Cecidomyiidae	<i>Contarinia forskalii</i> (Debski)	Adults	Leaves		+	Pest	August
	<i>Pheanobremia aphidivora</i> (Rubsamen)	Eggs	Leaves		++	Predator	June- August

+Few individuals were recorded in the present survey.

++Moderate population.

Table (2): Partial taxonomic list of Coleopteran pests and the associated predators on six cantaloupe cultivars at Qaha region, Qalyubiya Governorate over two successive growing seasons (2006 and 2007).

Taxonomic category	Scientific name	Insect stage	Site of occurrence	Frequency	Relationship	Period of occurrence
A Suborder:						
Polyphaga						
1- Superfamily:						
Elateroidea						
Family: Elateridae						
	<i>Drasterius bimaculatus</i> Rossi	Adults	Soil	+	Pest	August
2- Superfamily:						
Tenebrionoidea						
Family: Anthicidae						
	<i>Anthicus crinitus</i> La Ferte.	Adults	Flowers	+	Pest	July- August
Family:						
Mycetophagidae						
	<i>Typhaea stercorea</i> L.	Adults	Leaves	+	Pest	August
3- Superfamily:						
Curculionoidae						
Family:						
Curculionidae						
	<i>Ceuthorrhynchus viator</i> Faust	Adults	Leaves	+	Pest	August
4- Superfamily:						
Cucujoidea						
Family:						
Nitidulidae						
	<i>Carpophilus hemipterus</i> L.	Adults	Fruits	+	Pest	August
	<i>Carpophilus humeralis</i> F.	Adults	Fruits	+	Pest	August
Family:						
Coccinellidae						
	<i>Coccinella spp.</i>	Eggs	Leaves	+++	Predator	May and July
	<i>Coccinella undecimpunctata</i> L.	Adults	Leaves	+	Predator	May- August
	<i>Coccinella septempunctata</i> L.	Adults	Leaves	+	Predator	August
	<i>Cydonia vicina</i> var <i>isis</i> cr.	Adults	Leaves	+	Predator	June
5- Superfamily:						
Buprestoidea						
Family: Buprestidae						
	<i>Anthaxia angustipennis</i> Klug.	Adults	Stems	+	Pest	May
6- Superfamily:						
Scarabaeoidea						
Family:						
Scarabaeidae						
	<i>Tropinota squalida</i> Scop.	Adults	Flowers	+	Pest	June
7- Superfamily:						
Staphylinoidea						
Family:						
Staphylinidae						
	<i>Paederus aliferii</i> Koch.	Adults	Leaves	+	Predator	June – July
B- Suborder:						
Adephaga						
Superfamily:						
Caraboidea						
Family: Carabidae						
	<i>Calosoma chlorostictum</i> Deg.	Adults	Leaves	+	Predator	July

+ Few individuals were recorded in the present survey.

+++ High population.

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Seasonal abundance on the mango shield scale *Milviscutulus mangiferae* (Hemiptera: Coccidae) infesting mango trees at Ismailia Governorate, Egypt

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Abstract:

The population density of the mango shield scale, *Milviscutulus mangiferae* (Green) (Hemiptera: Coccidae) had been studied during two successive seasons from January 2018 to December 2019 in response to the climatic factors on mango trees at Abu Suwair district, Ismailia Governorate. The obtained results indicated that *M. mangiferae* active all the year with different individual numbers, the total population density of *M. mangiferae* was relatively more abundant during the first season, 2018 (585.78 individuals/leaf) than the second season, 2019 (527.85 individuals/leaf). Obtained data showed there were three peaks of activity on mango trees for total population in January, July and November represented by 46.78, 63.85 and 87.69 individuals / leaf and in January, June and November represented by 44.49, 55.98 and 90.07 individuals / leaf for two seasons, respectively. There was highly significant negative relation between daily mean maximum temperature and total population density; while there were highly significant positive relation between daily mean minimum temperature and total population density of *M. mangiferae* in the two seasons. On the other hand, daily mean relative humidity with total population density gave significant positive relation in the first and second seasons. The percentages of explained variance (E.V. %) indicate that all tested variables were responsible on variability on the total insect population by 84.03 % and 83.53 % during the first and second seasons, respectively.

Introduction

Mango (*Mangifera indica* L.) has spread to many parts of the tropical and sub-tropical world, where the climate allows the mango to grow best. Mango rich in phytochemicals with an undisputed nutritional value for its high content of vitamins; it occupied economic importance in

the world market and in Egypt it considers one of the most important fruit for rich flavor and delicious taste (Adato *et al.*, 1995; Abd-Rabou *et al.*, 2012; Indu, 2017 and Marianna *et al.*, 2017). Soft scale insects constitute one of the most important groups of pests in agriculture, many species are destructive

especially to fruit trees and ornamental plants (Abd-Rabou, 2011). The mango shield scale, *Milviscutulus mangiferae* (Green) (Hemiptera: Coccidae) is polyphagous soft scale insect and recorded in Egypt as a new pest attacking mango orchards (Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2018). *M. mangiferae* is considered one of the most main destructive pests of mango trees. This insect is of great economic importance, causes crop losses by severely depleting plant cell nutrients resulting in a reduction of photosynthetic capacity. Heavy infestations caused damage to plants by clogging of leaf or fruit surfaces, sap sucking and excrete a large amount of honeydew, on which sooty mould subsequently grows causing considerable economic injury. Also, infestation with *M. mangiferae* reduced tree vigor and leaf size, causing yellowing of the leaves, leaf drop and death of the branches, (Ben-Dov and Hodgson, 1997 and Grimshaw and Donaldson, 2007). Ecological study of the pest is important including the environmental factors (temperature and relative humidity); the study of these parameters is particularly interesting for insect and economic importance to obtain a useful orientation for good forecasting and prediction system of insect population. Therefore, the present work aimed to study the seasonal abundance of *M. mangiferae* during the two seasons from January 2018 to December 2019 in response to the climatic factors on mango trees at Abu Suwair district, Ismailia Governorate.

Materials and methods

1. Sampling and assessment of samples:

The present study was carried out in private mango orchard at Abu Suwair district, Ismailia Governorate throughout two seasons from January 2018 to December 2019 to estimate the seasonal abundance of the mango shield scale *M. mangiferae*. The selected orchard for present investigation doesn't receive any chemical control throughout the duration of the study and

received the normal agricultural practices only. Five mango trees of Ewaisi variety were selected of the same age, height and size, as well as homogenous in their insect infestation. Forty infested mango leaves were collected half monthly from each tree and from the four directions, then packed in paper bags with minute holes and then transferred to the laboratory of Plant Protection Department, Agriculture Research Station at Ismailia Governorate for examination using a stereo microscope to count and record the number of the live individuals (nymphs and adult females) of the pest. The climatic factors data (means of maximum and minimum temperatures and mean percentage of relative humidity) were recorded half monthly for Ismailia Governorate to study these effects on the seasonal abundance of the different stages of *M. mangiferae* population, these data obtained for Ismailia Governorate from the Egypt Weather Underground,

<https://www.wunderground.com/global/EG.html>.

2. Statistical analysis:

The partial regression method termed the C-multipliers was adopted according to (Fisher, 1950). Averages of different stages of insect population and climatic factors was calculated and shown graphically by excel sheets. Statistical analysis in the present work was carried out with computer using (MSTATC, 1980) to determine the preferable time for the insect activity and the proper time for its control. Also, the rate monthly variation in the population (R.M.V.P) was calculated according to the formula reported by (Serag-El-Din, 1998):

$$(R.M.V.P) = \frac{\text{Av. count of insect at a month}}{\text{Av. count given at the preceding month}}$$

The rate of monthly variation in the population is considered an indicator to the favorable month for insect activity expressed as the month of higher increase of this insect population through the year.

When R.M.V.P. is > 1 it means more activity, < 1 means less activity and $= 1$ means no change in the insect activity (Bakry, 2009).

Results and discussion

1. Seasonal abundance of *Milviscutulus mangiferae* on mango trees at Ismailia Governorate:

1.1. The first season 2018:

Data represented in Table (1) and illustrated in Figures (1 and 2) indicated that the population of nymphal stage of *M. mangiferae* exhibited three peaks of activity on mango trees in January, July and November represented by 30.64, 42.32 and 64.54 nymphs / leaf, respectively. The population of adult females of *M. mangiferae* also had three peaks of abundance; the first peak was recorded in January, the second peak was in July and the third peak was in October, these peaks represented by 16.14, 21.53 and 23.96 adult females / leaf, respectively. The seasonal abundance of total population of *M. mangiferae* exhibited three peaks of activity in January, July and November represented by 46.78, 63.85 and 87.69 individuals / leaf, respectively. It could be noticed that the lowest peak during the first season for nymphs, adult females and total population was appeared in January with max. temp. 17.72 °C, min. temp. 12.62 °C and 62.10 % R.H. whereas, the highest peak appeared in November for nymphs and total population with max. temp. 22.60 °C, min. temp. 18.85 °C and 59.69 % R.H and in October for adult females population with max. temp. 26.94 °C, min. temp. 21.59 °C and 57.53 % R.H. This may be due to the environmental conditions which were more suitable for the insect activity.

1.2. The second season 2019:

As shown in Table (2) and illustrated in Figures (3 and 4) the nymphal population approximately similar trend of changes compared to counts of the first year. Three peaks of seasonal abundance were monitored in January, June and November, represented by 28.70, 38.08 and 66.53 nymphs / leaf, respectively. Adult female stage showed three peaks of activity were recorded in February, June and November, represented by 18.05, 17.90 and 23.54 adult females / leaf, respectively. Total population of *M. mangiferae* exhibited three peaks of activity in January, June and November represented by 44.49, 55.98 and 90.07 individuals / leaf. The previous data showed that the lowest peak for nymphs and total population appeared in January with max. temp. 18.63 °C, min. temp. 13.89 °C and 62.29 % R.H. while, the lowest peak for adult females population appeared in June with max. temp. 30.62 °C, min. temp. 25.06 °C and 49.96 % R.H. The highest peak for nymphs, adult females and total population appeared in November with max. temp. 21.96 °C, min. temp. 19.74 °C and 57.98 % R.H. This may be due to the environmental conditions which were more suitable for the insect activity.

From the previous data it could be concluded that *M. mangiferae* active all the year with different individual numbers and the population density of *M. mangiferae* was relatively more abundant during the first season than the second season with total population 585.78 and 527.85 individuals / leaf during the first and second seasons, respectively. *M. mangiferae* had three peaks per year on mango trees at Abu Suwair district, Ismailia Governorate. These are agreeing with (Attia *et al.*, 2018), they reported three peaks per year for *M.*

mangiferae on mango trees at Qalubia Governorate. In contrast, (El-Baradei *et al.*, 2018) monitored two peaks of abundance per year for *M. mangiferae* on mango trees at Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate. Abbas *et al.* (2019) stated that the total alive stages of *M. mangiferae* had four main peaks of high activity on *Laurus nobilis* at Giza Governorate, and this variance may be attributed to the different locations.

2. Rate of monthly variation in population (R.M.V.P.) of *Milviscutulus mangiferae*:

The monthly variation rates in the population of different stages and total population of *M. mangiferae* and the percentages of infestation incidence were calculated in Tables (1 and 2). As shown in Table (1) the favorable times of annual increase for total population appeared to be in April, May, June, July, September, October and November months during the first year (2018), when the rates of monthly variation were (1.13, 1.21, 1.79, 1.31, 1.45, 1.65 and 1.08), respectively. While, in Table (2) during the second year (2019) the favorable times of annual increase for total population appeared to be in May, June, September, October and November months when the rates of monthly variation were (2.33, 2.26, 1.11, 1.58 and 1.40), respectively.

The climatic conditions of autumn months during the two years were the optimal for the insect multiplication and build up, since the highest R.M.V.P value was achieved during both years. These results were coincided with those obtained by Attia *et al.* (2018) they stated that abnormal relationship between meteorological factors and the total population of *M. mangiferae*, where the total population synchrony with moderate and high temperatures during the

first two peaks of *M. mangiferae*, but during the third peak (from 1 st October till 1st Jan.) the population highly increased when the temperature started to decreased (moderate temperatures). On the other side, the low temperatures (from 1st Jan. until end of Feb.) synchrony with low population of *M. mangiferae* due to its hibernation as adult females after this time the adult females transformed to gravid females as an indicator to first peak (Spring peak) and generation. Also, Abbas *et al.* (2019) showed that the single effect of the three (maximum, minimum and means temperature) had positive highly effect on the changes in the population density of *M. Mangiferae* on *Laurus nobilis* trees at Giza Governorate.

3. Effect of some weather factors on the total population density of *Milviscutulus mangiferae*:

3.1. The first season 2018:

Data in Table (3) showed that there were significant correlations between the *M. mangiferae* total population density and weather factors (temperature and relative humidity). There was highly significant negative relation between daily mean maximum temperature and total population density of *M. mangiferae*. The simple correlation coefficient value was - 0.06, the simple regression coefficient value was - 0.26, the partial regression was -10.28 and t-test value was - 5.96. For daily mean minimum temperature data showed a highly significant positive relation between it and the total population density of *M. mangiferae*; the simple correlation coefficient, the simple regression coefficient, the partial regression and t-test values were + 0.25, +1.48, +14.92 and + 6.42, respectively. The effect of daily mean relative humidity on

total population of *M. mangiferae* indicated that the simple correlation coefficient and the simple regression coefficient were significant positive effect + 0.13 and + 0.82, respectively. According to the partial regression, the mean relative humidity exhibited a significant positive effect on the total population P. reg.= +2.97 and the t-test value was +2.95. The combined effect of these tested factors on the total population of *M. mangiferae* was highly significant where F value = +14.03 and the explained variance value (E.V. %) was 84.03 %. These results also revealed that the changes in the total population density of *M. mangiferae* on mango trees were mostly related to the combined effects of the selected weather factors for the first season at Abu Suwair district, Ismailia Governorate.

3.2. The second season 2019:

Data in Table (3) showed that there were significant correlations between the *M. mangiferae* total population density and weather factors. Daily mean maximum and minimum temperature and total population density showed a highly significant positive relation where, the simple correlation coefficient values were + 0.10 and + 0.17 and the simple regression coefficient values were + 0.35 and + 0.86, respectively. The partial regression value for daily mean maximum temperature indicated a highly significant negative relation between it and total population of the pest P. reg. = - 10.96 and the value of t-test was - 4.89. While the partial regression value and the value of t-test for daily mean minimum temperature indicated a highly significant positive relation between it and total population of *M. mangiferae* and the values were +17.68 and +

5.24. The effect of daily mean relative humidity on total population of *M. mangiferae* indicated that the simple correlation coefficient was highly significant positive relation + 0.50 and the simple regression coefficient value was + 1.98. According to the partial regression, mean relative humidity exhibited a highly significant positive effects on the total population P. reg.= + 4.51 with t-test value + 6.09. The combined effect of these tested factors on the total population of *M. mangiferae* was highly significant where the F value = 13.53 and the explained variance value (E.V. %) was 83.53%. These results also revealed that the changes in the total population density of *M. mangiferae* on mango trees were mostly related to the combined effects of the selected weather factors for the second season at Abu Suwair district, Ismailia Governorate. In general, high temperature and relative humidity conditions are beneficial to soft scale population growth (Kosztarab, 1996; El-Baradei *et al.*, 2018 and Abbas *et al.*, 2019).

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Table (1): Monthly mean numbers of different stages of *Milviscutulus mangiferae* and rate of monthly variation in population (R.M.V.P.) on mango trees with climatic factors affecting at Ismailia Governorate during the period from January to December 2018.

Date of inspection	Mean number of individuals per leaf			R.M.V.P. for total population	Climatic factors		
	Nymphs	Adult females	Total		Max. temp.°C	Min. temp.°C	% R.H.
Jan.	30.64	16.14	46.78	—	17.72	12.62	62.10
Feb.	12.44	15.63	28.07	0.60	17.69	12.39	60.30
Mar.	6.42	13.45	19.86	0.71	23.98	14.91	60.17
Apr.	9.63	12.86	22.49	1.13	26.13	17.95	57.75
May	16.50	10.70	27.20	1.21	29.38	21.45	54.58
Jun.	33.24	15.34	48.58	1.79	30.65	22.78	58.26
Jul.	42.32	21.53	63.85	1.31	32.25	22.87	62.39
Aug.	17.53	16.45	33.98	0.53	31.85	22.70	62.58
Sept.	31.34	17.92	49.25	1.45	29.58	23.51	49.91
Oct.	57.20	23.96	81.16	1.65	26.94	21.59	57.53
Nov.	64.54	23.15	87.69	1.08	22.60	18.85	59.69
Dec.	55.71	21.15	76.86	0.88	20.41	17.03	62.32
Total	377.50	208.28	585.78				
General average	31.46	17.36	48.81		25.77	19.06	58.96
%	64.44	35.56	100.00				

Table (2): Monthly mean numbers of different stages of *Milviscutulus mangiferae* and rate of monthly variation in population (R.M.V.P.) on mango trees with climatic factors affecting at Ismailia Governorate during the period from January to December 2019.

Date of inspection	Mean number of individuals per leaf			R.M.V.P. for total population	Climatic factors		
	Nymphs	Adult females	Total		Max. temp.°C	Min. temp.°C	% R.H.
Jan.	28.70	15.79	44.49	—	18.63	13.89	62.29
Feb.	13.17	18.05	31.22	0.70	15.85	13.62	60.06
Mar.	3.94	8.50	12.44	0.40	21.10	16.41	52.92
Apr.	4.72	5.94	10.65	0.86	25.17	19.74	50.61
May	15.19	9.62	24.81	2.33	28.76	23.60	48.42
Jun.	38.08	17.90	55.98	2.26	30.62	25.06	49.96
Jul.	32.10	16.39	48.49	0.87	32.20	25.16	54.09
Aug.	18.70	17.85	36.55	0.75	31.86	24.97	54.26
Sept.	27.15	13.48	40.63	1.11	36.02	25.86	61.09
Oct.	45.30	18.84	64.14	1.58	34.22	23.75	67.21
Nov.	66.53	23.54	90.07	1.40	21.96	19.74	57.98
Dec.	49.59	18.79	68.38	0.76	22.94	18.74	62.47
Total	343.15	184.69	527.85				
General average	28.60	15.39	43.99		28.49	22.30	55.90
%	65.01	34.99	100.00				

R.M.V.P.= Rate of Monthly Variation in Population; % RH. = Relative Humidity

Table (3): Different models of correlation and regression analyses for describing the relationship between total populations of *Milviscutulus mangiferae* and three weather variables on mango trees at Ismailia Governorate during the two successive seasons (2018 and 2019).

Year	Tested weather factors	Simple correlation and regression values				Partial regression value			Analysis variance			
		r	b	S. E	T	P. reg.	S. E	t	F value	MR	R ²	E.V.%
2018	Max. temp.	- 0.06	- 0.26	1.43	- 0.18	-10.28	1.73	- 5.96 **	14.03 **	0.92	0.84	84.03
	Min. temp.	0.25	1.48	1.79	0.83	14.92	2.32	6.42 **				
	% R.H.	0.13	0.82	1.99	0.41	2.97	1.01	2.95 *				
2019	Max. temp.	0.10	0.35	1.12	0.31	-10.96	2.24	- 4.89 **	13.53 **	0.91	0.84	83.53
	Min. temp.	0.17	0.86	1.62	0.53	17.68	3.37	5.24 **				
	% R.H.	0.50	1.98	1.08	1.83	4.51	0.74	6.09 **				

r = Simple correlation

b = Simple regression

MR = Multiple correlation

P. reg.= Partial regression

R²= Coefficient of determination

E.V% = Explained variance

S.E = Standard error * Significant at P ≤ 0.05 ** Highly significant at P ≤ 0.01

Figure (1): Means of monthly counts of different stages of *Milviscutulus mangiferae* on mango trees at Ismailia Governorate during the period from January to December 2018.

Figure (2): Climatic factors affecting on *Milviscutulus mangiferae* infests mango trees at Ismailia Governorate during the period from January to December 2018.

Figure (3): Means of monthly counts of different stages of *Milviscutulus mangiferae* on mango trees at Ismailia Governorate during the period from January to December 2019.

Figure (4): Climatic factors affecting on *Milviscutulus mangiferae* infests mango trees at Ismailia Governorate during the period from January to December 2019.

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Effect of alternative preys on predation upon *Aphis craccivora* (Hemiptera: Aphididae) by some aphidophagous predators larvae

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Abstract:

Effect of the presence of *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) and *Empoasca decipiens* Paoli (Hemiptera: Cicadellidae) nymphs and both on the feeding potential of the predators *Coccinella undecimpunctata* L. , *Coccinella septempunctata* L. (Coleoptera : Coccinellidae) and *Chrysoperla carnea* (Stephens) (Neuroptera: Chrysopidae) larval instars on *Aphis craccivora* Koch. (Hemiptera: Aphididae) was determined in laboratory. The presence of *B. tabaci* nymphs reduced significantly the predation of *A. craccivora* by 1st and 2nd larval instars of *C. undecimpunctata* and 1st larval instars of *C. septempunctata* and *C. carnea*, meanwhile, the presence of *E. decipiens* nymphs had not any effect. On the other hand, the presence of *B. tabaci* and *E. decipiens* nymphs affected significantly on the predation of *A. craccivora* by the 3rd and 4th larval instars of *C. undecimpunctata*; 2nd, 3rd and 4th larval instars of *C. septempunctata* and 2nd and 3rd larval instars of *C. carnea*.

Introduction

Cowpea aphid *Aphis craccivora* Koch (Hemiptera: Aphididae) is considered one of the most important insect pests attacking common bean plants (El-Solimany, 2008). Common bean plants, in Egypt, were known to inhabit by piercing sucking insect pests over than *A. craccivora* as leafhopper, and *Empoasca decipiens* Paoli (Hemiptera: Cicadellidae) and *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) (Wahba *et al.*, 1986; Heyer *et al.*, 1989; El-Sayed *et al.*, 1991; Faris *et al.*, 1991 and Bachatly, 2000), which considered as alternative preys for *Coccinella undecimpunctata* L. , *Coccinella septempunctata* L. (Coleoptera :

Coccinellidae) and *Chrysoperla carnea* (Stephens) (Neuroptera: Chrysopidae). Many predatory insects found to consume a range of prey species and can thus contribute to biocontrol of pests. However, the availability of alternative prey species may affect the degree of control the predators exert over pest species (Fitzgerald and Jay, 2010).

The aim of this study is to determine the effect of *B. tabaci* and *E. decipiens* as alternative preys on *A. craccivora* by *C. undecimpunctata*, *C. septempunctata* and *C. carnea* larvae.

Materials and methods

This experiment was conducted in the laboratory of Plant Protection, Shandweel

Agricultural Research Station, Sohag Governorate. All laboratory studies were run under room condition where ambient temperature ranged between 11 and 25 °C, and RH. varied from 44% to 60%. The larvae of *C. septempunctata*, *C. undecimpunctata* and *C. carnea* larvae on *A. craccivora*, also, *A. craccivora* was taken from the laboratory rearing stock culture. Common bean leaflets infested with *B. tabaci* and *E. decipiens* were collected from the farm of Shandweel Agricultural Research Station, Sohag Governorate, then examined carefully under a microscope for collection of the same size nymphs. Treatments included aphid only, aphid mixed with whitefly, aphid mixed with leafhopper and aphid mixed with both preys. Petri dishes were prepared to contain 20 nymphs from each prey. The first, second, third and fourth grubs of *C. septempunctata* and *C. undecimpunctata* and first, second and third grubs of *C. carnea* were examined to the previous treatment in completely randomized design with ten replicates. After 24 hours, the consumed aphids were determined by counted the remaining individuals.

For the purpose of statistical analysis, data obtained were statistically analyzed using one – way analysis of variance. Mean values were separated by the least significant difference (L.S.D.) procedure (Snedecor and Cochran, 1980) at P = 5%.

Results and discussion

Table (1): Feeding rate of different larval instars of *Coccinella undecimpunctata*, on *Aphis craccivora* in the presence of *Bemisia tabaci* and *Empoasca decipiens* nymphs for 24hrs.

Prey	Instars			
	First	Second	Third	Fourth
<i>Aphis craccivora</i> (T1)	5.00	8.10	12.10	16.10
<i>Aphis craccivora</i> + <i>Bemisia tabaci</i> (T2)	3.10	6.50	9.60	14.30
<i>Aphis craccivora</i> + <i>Empoasca decipiens</i> (T3)	4.80	7.60	9.50	14.00
Mixture (T4)	4.20	6.40	10.00	13.40
F. Value	3.85*	5.00*	10.33*	5.69*
LSD _{05%}	1.26	1.08	1.10	1.41

1. *Coccinella undecimpunctata* larvae:

Data in Table (1) revealed that the 1st larval instar of *C. undecimpunctata* predation on *A. craccivora* affected with the presence of *B. tabaci*, meanwhile, under other sets this predation reduced but insignificantly comparing with aphid treatment. The number of aphids consumed under *A. craccivora* (T1), *A. craccivora* + *B. tabaci* (T2), *A. craccivora* + *E. decipiens* (T3) and Mixture (T4) were 5.00, 3.10, 4.80 and 4.20 aphid/ larva, respectively. Comparing of the predation of the 2nd larval instar of *C. undecimpunctata*, the presence of *B. tabaci* nymphs reduced the aphid consumption by the predator larvae. T1 gave the higher number of aphids consumed followed insignificantly by T3. The mean numbers recorded were 8.10, 6.50, 7.60 and 6.40 aphids/ larva under T1, T2, T3 and T4, respectively.

The eaten aphid by the 3rd larval instar on T1, 12.10 aphids/ larva was the highest comparing with the rest treatments, 9.60, 9.50 and 10.00 aphids/ larva for T2, T3 and T4, respectively. This refer to the effect of the two preys on the predation of *C. undecimpunctata* larvae on aphid. For the 4th larval instar of *C. undecimpunctata*, the results obtained were like those of the 3rd larval instar. The mean numbers of 16.10, 14.30, 14.00 and 13.40 aphids/ larva were consumed by the 4th larval instar under T1, T2, T3 and T4, respectively.

2. *Coccinella septempunctata* larvae:

As shown in Table (2), the presence of *B. tabaci* reduced the predation of aphid by *C. septempunctata* 1st larval instar, however the presence of *E. decipiens* nymphs had not any effect. The aphid consumption on T1 was highly significant comparing with T2 and T4 with mean numbers of 15.30, 13.80 and 14.00 aphids/ larva, respectively. For *C. septempunctata* 2nd larval instar, it is clear evident that *B. tabaci* and *E. decipiens* nymphs can play as alternative prey, T1

recorded the highest mean number of consumed aphids comparing with T2, T3 and T4 with average numbers of 18.40, 16.60, 16.80 and 15.80 aphids/ larva, respectively. The same results were obtained by 3rd and 4th larval instar of *C. septempunctata*. Mean numbers of 19.50, 18.20, 17.90 and 17.40 aphids/ larva were consumed by the 3rd larval instar under T1, T2, T3 and T4, respectively. And the 4th larval instar consumed 19.90, 18.90, 18.40 and 18.00 aphids/ larva under the previous treatments, respectively.

Table (2): Feeding rate of different larval instars of *Coccinella septempunctata* on *Aphis craccivora* in the presence of *Bemisia tabaci* and *Empoasca decipiens* nymphs for 24hrs.

Prey	Instars			
	First	Second	Third	Fourth
<i>Aphis craccivora</i> (T1)	15.30	18.40	19.50	19.90
<i>Aphis craccivora</i> + <i>Bemisia tabaci</i> (T2)	13.80	16.60	18.20	18.90
<i>Aphis craccivora</i> + <i>Empoasca decipiens</i> (T3)	15.10	16.80	17.90	18.40
Mixture (T4)	14.00	15.80	17.40	18.00
F. Value	3.54	5.93	4.71	14.96
LSD _{05%}	1.17	1.29	1.19	0.61

3. *Chrysoperla carnea* larvae:

Determined numbers of aphid consumed by the 1st larval instar of *C. carnea* on four sets differed significantly. T1 recorded the highest mean number of eaten aphids, followed insignificantly by T3, the two treatments were higher than T2 and T4, with average numbers of 14.40, 14.00, 11.80 and 12.30 aphids/ larvae, respectively. Because of the previous finding, nymphs of *B. tabaci* can considered as alternative prey to the 1st larval instar of *C. carnea* in the presence of *A. craccivora*, the inverse is correct in case of *E. decipiens* nymphs

(Table, 3). In respect of 2nd larval instar of *C. carnea*, data indicated that both *B. tabaci* and *E. decipiens* nymphs reduced aphid predation by this instar. T1 gave the highest mean number of 18.20/ larva compared with the rest treatments, 16.00, 15.10 and 12.50 aphids/ larva for T2, T3 and T4, respectively.

The same trend of results was achieved for the 3rd larval instar. Treatments of T1, T2, T3 and T4 recorded mean numbers of 19.40, 17.90, 17.00 and 16.10 aphids/ larva, respectively, consumed by larvae of neuropteran predator larvae.

Table (3): Feeding rate of different larval instars of *Chrysoperla carnea* on *Aphis craccivora* in the presence of *Bemisia tabaci* and *Empoasca decipiens* nymphs for 24hrs.

Prey	Instars		
	First	Second	Third
<i>Aphis craccivora</i> (T1)	14.40	18.20	19.40
<i>Aphis craccivora</i> + <i>Bemisia tabaci</i> (T2)	11.80	16.00	17.90
<i>Aphis craccivora</i> + <i>Empoasca decipiens</i> (T3)	14.00	15.10	17.00
Mixture (T4)	12.30	12.50	16.10
F. Value	4.82	32.83	14.20
LSD _{05%}	1.67	1.19	1.08

These results are in agreement with Ostman and Ives (2003), they stated that indirect interactions between prey species [*Acyrtosiphon pisum* (Harris) (Hemiptera: Aphididae) and *Empoasca fabae* (Harris) (Hemiptera: Cicadellidae)] may depend upon spatial scale, because the factors affecting a predator's [*Nabis* spp. (Hemiptera: Nabidae)] diet choice on a small scale may differ from those factors affecting a predator's distribution at larger scales. The same results obtained by Koss *et al.* (2004), they suggested that both *Nabis* spp. and *Geocoris* spp. (Hemiptera: Lygaeidae) bugs predators exhibited weakly suppressed *Myzus persicae* Sulzer (Hemiptera: Aphididae) consumption rates when Colorado potato beetle eggs were also present (in laboratory). Also, Fitzgerald and Jay (2010) demonstrated that the potential of *C. carnea* to significantly reduce numbers of strawberry aphid, *Chaetosiphon fragaefolii* (Cockerell) (Hemiptera: Aphididae), western flower thrips, *Frankliniella occidentalis* (Pergande) (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) and capsid *Lygus rugulipennis* Poppius (Heteroptera: Miridae) when each pest was presented alone. Huang and Enkegaard (2010) found that in the presence of the aphids, the predation on eggs or larvae of *Pieris brassicae* L. (Lepidoptera: Pieridae) was either completely abandoned or reduced by about 70%, respectively, by second instar lacewings and either reduced by about 80% or maintained, respectively, by

third instar lacewings. Rouhani and Samih (2012) showed that the efficiency of *C. carnea* to biological control of the two aphid species, *Aphis punicae* Passerini (Hemiptera: Aphididae) and *Agonoscaena pistaciae* Burckhardt and Lauterer (Hemiptera: Psylloidea), is more than the leafhopper, *E. decipiens*. Jaworski *et al.* (2013) reported that the predation activity of *Macrolophus pygmaeus* Rambur (Heteroptera: Miridae) on *B. tabaci* was affected by the presence of *Tuta absoluta* (Meyrick) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) eggs or larvae in the prey complex with an opposite effect when comparing adult and juvenile predators. Cuthbert *et al.* (2018) suggested that prey switching, and prey preferences may affect on the success of invaders pest's population, alongside the capacity for biotic resistance by recipient communities. On the other hand, Medal *et al.* (1997) indicated that predation of *Spissistilus festinus* (Say) (Hemiptera: Membracidae) nymphs by *Geocoris punctipes* (Say) (Hemiptera: Lygaeidae) and *Nabis roseipennis* Reuter (Heteroptera: Nabidae) did not differ significantly in the presence of *Pseudoplusia includens* (Walker) larvae and/or *Heliothis zea* (Boddie) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) larvae as alternative prey. Also, Lucas *et al.* (2004) mentioned that the total *Aphis pomi* DeGeer (Hemiptera: Aphididae) and *Choristoneura rosaceana* (Harris)

(Lepidoptera: Tortricidae) consumed by *C. septempunctata* and *Harmonia axyridis* Pallas (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) were significantly higher when both prey were present than in single-prey treatments.

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Molluscicidal effects of acetone and ethanol extracts of clove (*Syzygium aromaticum*) against *Monacha cartusiana* (Gastropoda: Hygromiidae) snails under laboratory and field conditions at Sharkia Governorate

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Abstract:

The present study aimed to investigate the effects of ethanol and acetone extracts of clove (*Syzygium aromaticum*) flower bud against the adult snails of *Monacha cartusiana* (Müller) (Gastropoda: Hygromiidae), at concentrations of 1, 2, 4 and 6% w/v, through using spray, contact and bait techniques under laboratory conditions, and at concentration of 6% under field conditions through bait technique only. The results showed that the mortality percentage of *M. cartusiana* was increased with increasing concentration of both crude extracts and time elapsed under the used methods. The mortality and the assessment of the lethal concentrations for 50% (LC₅₀) were determined at 3, 5 and 7 days of treatment. The bioassay of *S. aromaticum* against the land snail *M. cartusiana*, indicated that ethanol extract had a more potent effect than acetone extract as regard spray and bait methods all over the experiment, however, it had a less potent effect during 5th and 7th days with contact method. The lowest lethal concentration LC₅₀ values of ethanol extract were 0.94, 1.14 and 3.47% for spray, contact and bait techniques for 7 days exposure period and for acetone extract were 1.06 and 0.52% at 5th and 7th days exposure period, respectively. Field application by using a higher concentration (6%) as toxic baits, 60.28 and 49.28 % of reduction of *M. cartusiana* snails were recorded for both clove ethanol and acetone extract, respectively within 21 days. Snails display hyperactivity, a massive of air bubbles around the shell aperature, the body water lost as a result of excessive production of mucous secretion, complete withdrawal into their shell and died by the end of the experiment.

Introduction

The land snail *Monacha cartusiana* (Müller) (Gastropoda: Hygromiidae) is an economically important terrestrial hygromniidae widely distributed all over the world (Feldkamp, 2002) especially in the Mediterranean region, causing a severe

damage in cultivated and newly reclaimed agroecosystems in Egypt. *M. cartusiana* is not only one of the worst pests of agricultural crops but also acts as a mechanical carrier and /or as a reservoir of several pathogens which infects human, animals and birds

(Cossignani and Cossignani, 1995 and Hausdorf, 2000). The last studies indicated that this snail was the most abundant snail in all localities of Sharkia Governorate (Mahrous *et al.*, 2002; Abou Senna *et al.*, 2016 and Ismail *et al.*, 2017).

During the last decade the use of natural biochemical products for pest control has been greatly increased. Plant-derived extracts and photochemical have received much effort as a potentially useful bio-active compounds to alternate the other synthetic counterparts (Isman and Grieneisen, 2014), in a trial to avoid recurrent resistance of snails (Rapado *et al.*, 2011). Clove is the dried flower bud of *Syzygium aromaticum* (L.) Merr. and Perry (Family : Myrtaceae), cultivated in many parts of the world is a well-known as food additive and it has a broad spectrum medical effects including anticarcinogenic, antibacterial, antiviral, antifungal, anti-helminthic, anti-oxidant and anti-spasmodic (Burt and Reinders, 2003; Hirotaka *et al.*, 2003 ; Dorai and Aggarwal, 2004; Fatehi *et al.*, 2004 and Chaieb *et al.*, 2007). The essential oil of *S. aromaticum* mainly act as a local anesthetic (Park *et al.*, 2009) and are known to have strong antifeedant, growth regulatory, insecticidal, acaricidal, termicidal, metamorphosis, repellency and sterility effects on insects (Fichi *et al.*, 2007; Akhtar and Yeoung , 2008; Knio and Usta (2008) and Oyeniyi *et al.*, 2015).

Most of our knowledge of a molluscicidal activity of *S. aromaticum* against snails is restricted either to aquatic snails, which are vectors for many diseases (El-Din, 2006 and Kumar and Singh, 2006) and or to terrestrial slug (Mobarak *et al.*, 2015) and there is little information, on terrestrial gastropods (Ismail and Abdel-Kader, 2011).

The current study aimed to investigate the toxicity of acetone and ethanol 70% extracts of *S. aromaticum* (clove) against the harmful snail *M. cartusiana* using spray,

contact and bait technique under laboratory and field conditions at Sharkia Governorate.

Materials and methods

1. Tested animals:

Adult snails of *M. cartusiana* were collected locally in April 2015 from heavily infested fields cultivated with Egyptian clover at Sharkia Governorate, then transferred in plastic bag to the laboratory, healthy individuals snails were kept in glass boxes containing moistened soil, fed on cabbage leaves for 10 days to acclimatization.

2. Plant material and extraction:

The buds of clove were procured from local market in Zagazig, Sharkia Governorate. The flower buds were roasted at 35 °C until weight stabilized then grounded in grinder to obtain a fine dry powder and the clove extract was obtained by maceration process. For defatting and remove fat soluble ingredients, the ground plant material (250gm.) was extracted by soaking for a weak in one liter of n-hexane at room temperature then filtered and washed with hexane three times 500 ml each. The defatted plant biomass was re-extracted successively with acetone and ethanol 70% by same way of defatting. The filtrates were separately evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure in a rotary evaporator until viscous matter as pal green and dark brown was obtained for both acetone and ethanol 70% extracts, respectively. Extracts were stored at 4 °C in an airtight container until use (Freedman *et al.*, 1979).

3. Toxicity studies:

3.1. Under laboratory conditions:

3.1.1. Spray toxicity assay:

For spraying technique, ten adult snails were placed in a covered plastic boxes and exposed to three concentrations of each acetone and ethanol extracts of clove, 2,4 and 6% by spraying it with the corresponding solution of the tested extract (3ml/10 snails) using a hand sprayer atomizer. Three replicates (ten snails each) of each

concentration were used. A parallel standard test was conducted using ethanol and acetone (3ml/10 snails) and in the control using plain water as the basic test. After 1,3,5,7 and 21 days of post treatment, plastic boxes were checked, and number of dead snails were recorded and removed. The concentrations - mortality percentages were calculated after 3, 5 and 7 days of treatment.

3.1.2. Contact toxicity assay:

Contact technique (thin layer film) was used according to Asher and Marian (1981). Different concentrations (1, 2, 4 and 6% w/v) of crude extracts, two ml of each concentration were deposited on inner surface of a petri-dish by moving the dish gently in circles. Solvents were evaporated under room conditions in a few minutes leaving a thin layer film of the tested compounds on the surface of petri-dishes. Ten snails in three replicates were exposed to the candidate concentration of both tested extracts for 24h. A parallel standard test was conducted using ethanol and acetone and, in the control, using plain water as the basic test. Mortality were counted and recorded after 1,3,5,7 and 21 days. All the snails remained completely dried within their shells without response to mechanical prodding were considered dead. The activity of both extracts against adults of *M. cartusiana* was expressed as mortality percentages.

3.1.3. Bait toxicity assay:

For preparation of baits, three concentrations of each acetone and ethanol extracts of clove, 2, 4 and 6% of clove were used as poisonous baits by incorporating it with wheat bran to give 100 parts of poisonous baits for each concentration ten snails were used in each box. About 10 gms of each poison bait were spread into each box that was covered with cloth netting secured with rubber bands to prevent snails from escaping. Four replicated were run in each case. Another two control groups were concurrently run containing wheat bran, one with ethanol and acetone extract as standard

test and the second with plain water test but without treatment. Few milliliters of water were added daily into each box to provide suitable humidity for snail activity. The tested boxes were checked after 1,3,7,14 and 21 days to recorded and removed dead animals. Dead snails were counted and reported the results as percent mortality.

3.1.4. Data analysis:

Mortality percentages were corrected for natural mortality according to Abbott's formula (1925), then subjected to statistical analysis using Finney's method (Finney, 1971) to determine the lethal concentration causing 50% mortality (LC₅₀) and 95% mortality (LC₉₅) with 50% fiducial limits of the tested extracts for *M. cartusiana* adults and slope in each case was calculated.

3.2. Under field conditions:

To evaluate reduction percentages of *M. cartusiana* snails after 1, 7, 14 and 21 days post treatment, the experiment was carried out in heavy infested field cultivated with Egyptian clover at Hehia district, Sharkia Governorate during April 2016. The toxicity of one concentration (6%) in the laboratory by maxing 6 parts of each concentration with 89 parts of wheat bran and mixed with black sugarcane syrup 5% as attractant substances. About 100 grams of bait was offered on plastic pieces and spread along the edge of fields after the dawn. Four replicates were used for each clove extract (ethanol and acetone), plus control without treatment. Number of dead and alive snails were counted in check and treatment area before application and after 1,3,5,7,14 and 21 days. Reduction percentages were calculated according to formula of Henderson and Tilton (1955).

Results and discussion

The results obtained on the molluscicidal activities as well as LC₅₀ and LC₉₅ values of *S. aromaticum* ethanol and acetone extracts at 2,4,6% concentration, against adult *M. cartusiana* after 3, 5 and 7 days exposure are represented in Tables (1, 2 and 3). Data

indicated that the toxicity of organic solvent extracted (ethanol and acetone) were dependent in time and concentration when applied as contact, spray and bait technique. Through direct spray technique, it is cleared from data shown in the Table (1), that *S. aromaticum* ethanolic extract was highly active than acetone extract, indicated by the lethal concentration that killed 50% of adult snails *M. cartusiana* were being 1.67, 0.94, 0.94% for ethanol and, 5.10, 1.82 and 1.40% for acetone extract after 3, 5 and 7 days exposure, whereas, the lethal concentrations that killed 95% of adult snails *M. cartusiana* were 13.34, 14.56, 14.56% for ethanol extract and were 1717.6, 50.65 and 15.90% for acetone extract of *S. aromaticum* after 3, 5 and 7 days respectively.

Regarding the clove extracts effectiveness against adult *M. cartusiana* when applied by contact method, it is cleared from mortality data (3rd day) that ethanolic extract was more potent for adult *M. cartusiana* ($LC_{50}=3.63$ and $LC_{95}=23.83$) than acetone extract ($LC_{50}=4.43$ and $LC_{95}=1429.8$), while mortality data in days 5 and 7 showed that acetone extract was the most toxic botanical for adult *M. cartusiana* whereas, $LC_{50} = 1.06$ and 0.52 $LC_{95}=26.83$ and 11.40% compared to ethanol extract ($LC_{50}=2.18$ and 1.14, $LC_{95}=46.29$ and 17.45%) at the same time (Table, 2).

As for baits techniques, the adult *M. cartusiana* was not affected by both clove extracts at the first 3 days (no mortality was recorded), so it was difficult to determine LC_{50} and LC_{95} values (Table,3). The lethal effect recorded at 5 and 7 days post treatment, as showed in Table (3) LC_{50} and LC_{95} values of ethanol extract were relatively higher in molluscicidal activity (LC_{50} , 4.24, 3.47% and LC_{95} 7.52 and 7.32%) than that obtained by acetone extract (LC_{50} , 5.67 and 4.53% and LC_{95} 49.92 and 28.93%), at 5 and 7 days, respectively.

Considering the toxicity regression analysis, it was appeared from our data that

fiducial limits (lower and upper limits) were positively correlated with LC_{50} values which ranged between 0.48, 12.92, and 0.56, 1.99% for acetone and ethanol extract respectively (spray method) and between 3.84 and 6.67 % for acetone extract (Bait method). The slope values indicated a homogeneity of the adults *M. cartusiana* snails in their response to both clove extracts toxicants as recorded in Tables (1,2 and 3).

In all techniques, no mortality was observed in the control groups either exposed to plain water or standard solvent. Our results showed that ethanol extract was more active in spray and bait form than acetone, however, acetone was relatively more active than ethanol when applied by contact technique. Generally, as can be seen from the above-mentioned result, that *S. aromaticum* ethanol and acetone extracts showed more molluscicidal activity against adult *M. cartusiana* when applied by contact and spray forms, than bait technique. After exposure to clove extracts examined in the present study, the snails showed the following symptoms for death including, hyperactivity, a massive of air bubbles, continuous excessive mucous secretion, and complete withdrawal inside the shell just in contact of the extract with their soft bodies followed by dehydration and finally death (Photos a, b and c).

Regarding, field application, the baits of both clove ethanol and acetone extract were applied at 6% concentration. Results in Table (4) indicated that ethanol extract was more active than acetone extract against adult *M. cartusiana* and their activity found to be the durations of exposure and concentration dependent. The population reduction percentages of these extracts after the first three days (initial effect) were to 7.93 and 7.25 % for ethanol and acetone extract respectively. While the reduction percentages after 21 days post-treatment were 60.28 and 49.28% for ethanol and acetone extract respectively.

Photos (a, b and c): Morphological feature of snail death after the treatment with plant extracts.

Table (1): Susceptibility of adult snails *Monacha cartusiana* towards the effect of clove extracts (acetone and ethanol) using spray technique under laboratory conditions.

Treatments		LC ₅₀ (w/v)	%	Fiducial limits		LC ₉₅ % (w/v)	Slope (b)
				Lower	Upper		
Ethanol extract	3	1.67		1.33	1.99	13.34	1.82±0.23
	5	0.94		0.56	1.27	14.56	1.38±0.23
	7	0.94		0.56	1.27	14.56	1.38±0.23
Acetone extract	3	5.10		3.23	12.92	1717.6	0.65±0.14
	5	1.82		1.43	2.31	50.65	1.14±0.15
	7	1.40		0.48	2.62	15.90	1.56±0.16

N. D. = Not detected (Contact)

Table (2): Susceptibility of adult snails *Monacha cartusiana* towards the effect of clove extracts (acetone and ethanol) using contact technique under laboratory conditions.

Treatments		LC ₅₀ (w/v)	%	Fiducial limits		LC ₉₅ % (w/v)	Slope (b)
				Lower	Upper		
Ethanol extract	3	3.63		3.07	5.42	23.83	2.01±0.60
	5	2.18		1.76	2.74	46.29	1.24±0.15
	7	1.14		0.35	1.87	17.45	1.38±0.15
Acetone extract	3	4.43		-----	-----	1429.8	0.65±0.11
	5	1.06		-----	-----	26.83	1.17±0.11
	7	0.52		0.39	0.65	11.40	1.22±0.14

Table (3): Susceptibility of adult snails *Monacha cartusiana* towards the effect of clove extracts (acetone and ethanol) using baits technique under laboratory conditions.

Treatments		LC ₅₀ (w/v)	%	Fiducial limits		LC ₉₅ % (w/v)	Slope (b)
				Lower	Upper		
Ethanol extract	3	-	-	-	-	-	-
	5	4.24	-	-	-	7.52	0.65±0.65
	7	3.47	-	-	-	7.32	1.16±0.63
Acetone extract	3	-	-	-	-	-	-
	5	5.67		4.9221	6.6723	49.92	1.923±0.13
	7	4.53		3.8445	5.6952	28.93	1.22±0.14

Table (4): Susceptibility of adult snails *Monacha cartusiana* towards the effect of clove extracts (acetone and ethanol) using baits technique under field conditions.

Treatment	%Reduction during indicated days						
	Initial effect			Residual effect			
	1	3	Mean	7	14	21	Mean
Ethanol extract	6.05	9.81	7.93	28.72	48.04	60.28	45.68
Acetone extract	2.41	12.09	7.25	20.12	31.04	49.28	33.48

The present results clearly indicated that the clove ethanol extract and acetone extract can be used as an effective molluscicide in

the control of land snail *M. cartusiana*. Their toxic effects were mainly dependent on time, concentration and the way in which the

extract was applied, as was evident from the negative correlations between LC_{50} and the exposure period. Adult *M. cartusiana* was susceptible to both clove ethanol and acetone extracts at different concentration whereas the ethanolic extract of clove showed higher potency in molluscicidal activity than acetonic extract along the whole time of experiment for the spray, baits and contact techniques (in 3rd day), while the acetonic extract was more potent than ethanolic extract at 5th and 7th days only for contact technique. Result revealed that ethanol extract was more toxic than acetone extract. The variation in the toxicity may be due to the fact that molluscicidal component present in clove was more soluble in ethanol than acetone solvent (Kumar and Singh, 2006), susceptibility-tolerance of the tested animals (Akhtar and Isman, 2004), or and phytochemical constituents of the plants (Olofintoye, 2010). A few studies were focused on the aquatic and terrestrial gastropods for the molluscicidal activity of *S. aromaticum*. Among the former studies, those carried out by Kumar and Singh (2006) recorded that the LC_{50} of *S. aromaticum* was 51.98 mg/l against the snail *Lymnaea acuminata* Lamarck (Gastropoda : Lymnaeidae) after 96hr and ethanol extract was more toxic than other organic extract. Also, Mobarak *et al.* (2015) they reported that clove extracted by ethanol was more toxic to the land slug, *Limax flavus* (L.) (Gastropoda : Limacidae) with an LC_{50} 0.6% than LC_{50} 0.36% of clove acetone extract.

Other researchers, Al-Zanbagi, 2005; Chauhan and Singh (2011); El-Tantawy *et al.* (2012) and Otariho and Morenikeji (2012), they showed similar higher potency of ethanol extract in extracting the secondary products which exhibited molluscicidal activity against different species of aquatic and terrestrial snails. Furthermore, the toxicity of any molluscicide depends on the point of entry of the toxins (Franz *et al.*,

2011). The potency of clove ethanol and acetone extract as observed in our study was higher in death rate when used as spray and contact methods than the bait method. This partially in agreement with Abdel-Kader *et al.* (2007) who found that using of some plant water extracts, as spraying technique was more efficient against land snails [*M. cartusiana* and *Theba pisana* (Müller) (Gastropoda : Helicidae)] than a poisonous foods or using the grinded plant parts itself. Similarly, a high effective contact technique was reported by Mourad (2014), for other tested plants extracts against *Monacha obstructa* (Pfeiffer) (Gastropoda : Hygromiidae) and *Eobania vermiculata* (Müller) (Gastropoda : Helicidae). The effect of ethanol and acetone extract in bait technique is less harmful than spray and contact techniques. This is mainly due to the way of its application, since spray and contact technique causing rapid death of snail soft tissue before digestive tract is affected (in bait technique) which needs a considerable length of time for death or may be due to other factors such as temperature, light and the presence of impurities in the compound structures that govern stability of clove application (Turek and Stintzing, 2013).

The death of the snails in the present study is shown to be primarily correlated with the foot tissue destruction due to release of excessive mucous secretion leading to the body water lost, disrupting the cell membrane of the snail and changing its permeability (Juven *et al.*, 1994 and Devi *et al.*, 2010). These toxicity symptoms and signs could be linked to the presence of several secondary metabolites such as saponins, anthraquinones, tannins, cardiac glycosides and flavonoids present in *S. aromaticum* (Agbaje, 2008) which may exert molluscicidal effect and subsequently leading to the death of the *M. cartusiana* snails in this experiment. It is believed that the action of these naturally compounds causes over excitation of the

cholinergic nervous system (Young *et al.*, 2010) and later brings a low paralysis and loss of muscular tone (Srivastava *et al.*, 2013) or causes a metabolic disturbance by inhabiting the enzyme system primarily those of respiratory chain (Sokker *et al.*, 2012 and Gonzales Correa *et al.*, 2015). However, further research is necessary to isolate and identify the molluscicidal compounds and to elucidate the mechanism of its action upon snail body.

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Effect of methomyl on developmental toxicity and oxidative stress in male mice

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Abstract:

The intensive use of pesticide leads to severe environmental pollution and health hazards. The present study was carried out to investigate the alterations in free radicals and enzyme activities induced by methomyl in testicular tissue of male mice and general reproductive performance. Animals were assigned at random to one of the following treatments: group 1 served as control, while groups 2, 3 and 4 were treated with 1mg methomyl/kg body weight for 10, 20, and 30 days, respectively. Methomyl significantly increased testicular Thiobarbituric Acid Reactive Substances (TBARS), while decreased glutathione level (GSH) and the activities of glutathione S-transferase (GST), superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), transaminases (AST, ALT) and acid phosphatase. Methomyl significantly decreased the mating and fertility index, body and testis weights and relative testis weight, serum testosterone level and sperm motility and count, but increased sperm abnormality. In conclusion, the exposure to methomyl can produce enhanced toxic effects on enzyme defense system and reproductive function on male mice and the effect was more evident in 30 days treated group.

Introduction

Pollutants in the environment cause various hazards on living organisms. Pesticides have brought about the green revolution in the world and are being widely used to control agricultural pests and insects causing public health hazards. Problems are reported to occur among animals and human from insecticide toxicity, which usually occurs either from direct exposure to insecticides or indirectly from contaminated feeds or water by such chemicals (Shalaby *et al.*, 2010). The issue of testicular toxicity is

of growing concern as many pesticides adversely affect the testicular functions in experimental animals (Shalaby *et al.*, 2010 and Joshi *et al.*, 2007). Prolonged exposures to pesticides could diminish or destroy the fertility of workers sparked a concern about the effects of hazardous substances on male reproductive health (Joshi *et al.*, 2007).

Also, insecticides cause oxidative stress, leading to generation of free radicals and alteration in antioxidants enzymes, chronic neurological syndrome, malignant

tumors, immunosuppressive action, teratogenic effect, abortion and decreased male fertility in experimental animals (Shalaby *et al.*, 2010; Joshi *et al.*, 2007; Nafstad *et al.*, 1983; Meeker *et al.*, 2006 ; El-Demerdash, 2007 and Aziz *et al.*, 2008) .

Carbamates represent a large variety of compounds which have some field applications as insecticides, herbicides and fungicides. Many of these chemicals are potential neurotoxicants, particularly following occupational, accidental or intentional exposure. Methomyl, S-methyl N-(methylcarbamoyloxy) thioacetimidate, is a carbamate insecticide with anticholinesterase activity. As a broad-spectrum insecticide, it is one of the most frequently used pesticides in agriculture (Sinhaseni *et al.*, 1995). It is classified as a highly hazardous compound by World Health Organization (Mansour *et al.*, 2009) .

Therefore, the present study was undertaken to investigate the toxicity of methomyl on mouse testis. Testicular biochemistry, oxidative stress, sperm characteristics, testosterone level and histopathological changes were the criteria used to evaluate the reproductive efficacy of treated mice.

Materials and methods

1. Chemicals:

Methomyl (HUAYANG, 90 %) is S-methyl N-(methylcarbamoyloxy) thioacetimidate with molecular weight 162.2 and molecular formula $C_5H_{10}N_2O_2S$. It was obtained from Shandong Huayang Technology Ltd. Company, China. All other chemicals were purchased from Sigma Chemical Co. (St. Louis, MO, USA). All other reagents used were of analytical grade.

2. Experimental design:

Eighty male CD-1 mice (weighing 35- 40 g) were obtained from the animal house of the Faculty of Medicine, Alexandria University, Alexandria, Egypt. The local committee approved the design of the experiments, and the protocol conforms to

the guidelines of the National Institutes of Health (NIH). Animals were caged in groups of twenty and given food and water *ad libitum*. The animal room was maintained at 21–24°C and 40–60% relative humidity with 12-h light–dark cycles, the light cycle coinciding with the day light hours. After 2 weeks of acclimation, the groups were assigned at random to one of the following treatments: group 1 served as control, while groups 2, 3 and 4 were treated daily with (1/10 LD₅₀) one mg methomyl/kg body weight (BW) orally for 10, 20 and 30 days, respectively. The LD₅₀ of methomyl when administered orally to mice was reported to be 10 mg/kg BW (Baron, 1991) .

3. Serum and tissue preparation:

Blood samples were collected from the retro orbital plexus using glass capillary tubes. Serum was obtained by centrifugation of the samples at 860 g for 20 min, and was stored at -60°C. After decapitation, testis was immediately removed, weighed, minced and homogenized (10% w/v) separately in ice-cold 1.15% KCl-0.01M sodium, potassium phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) in a Potter-Elvehjem type homogenizer. The homogenate was centrifuged at 18,000 Xg for 20 min at 4°C, and the resultant supernatant was used for the determination of different enzyme assays, TBARS and glutathione content.

4. Biochemical parameters:

Serum samples were used for testosterone determination using commercial kits (RIA). Thiobarbituric Acid Reactive Substances (TBARS) were measured in testis using the method of Ohkawa *et al.* (1979). Glutathione contents (GSH) were measured in testis homogenate after reaction with 5, 5-dithiobis-(2-nitrobenzoic acid) using the method of Ellman (1959). Testis glutathione S-transferase (GST; EC 2.5.1.18) activity was determined according to Habig *et al.* (1974), using para-nitrobenzylchloride as a substrate. Superoxide dismutase (SOD; EC 1.15.1.1) was assayed according to Misra and

Fridovich (1972). The assay procedure involves the inhibition of epinephrine auto-oxidation in an alkaline medium (pH 10.2) to adrenochrome, which is markedly inhibited by the presence of SOD. The enzyme catalase (CAT; EC 1.11.1.6) converts H₂O₂ into water. The CAT activity in tissue supernatant was measured spectrophotometrically at 240 nm by calculating the rate of degradation of H₂O₂, the substrate of the enzyme (Aebi, 1984). Testis alanine aminotransferase (ALT; EC 2.6.1.2) and aspartate aminotransferase (AST; EC 2.6.1.1) activities were assayed by the method of Reitman and Frankel (1957). For assaying acid phosphatase (AcP; EC 3.1.3.2) activity, the method of Moss (1984) was used. The protein content was determined by following the method described by Lowry *et al.* (1951) using bovine serum albumin as a standard.

5. Reproductive performance indices:

5.1. Mating:

It is the assessment of the ability of treated male mice for copulation. After daily dose exposure, each male mouse was co-housed with unexposed proven fertility, sexually receptive, female mice (one to one/box) for at most five days (regular estrous cycle) following which they were separated (Fox and Laird, 1970). The females were examined daily for the presence of the vaginal plug as a criterion of successful insemination that was considered the day zero of gestation.

5.2. Fertility:

Each plug-positive female was caged individually. The number of inseminated and/or pregnant non-pregnant females was recorded.

5.3. Reproductive outcomes:

On the 20th day of gestation, the females were anesthetized with diethyl ether and killed by decapitation. After collection of the uterus, the numbers of implantation sites, resorptions, dead and live fetuses were determined. And then reproductive indices

were calculated according to the method of Adilaxmamma *et al.* (1994).

6. Evaluation of sperm characteristics:

6.1. Sperm collection:

After the sexual cohabitation and fecundity test period (five days), the epididymides were carefully separated from the testis. The sperm count was assessed from right cauda epididymides while sperm motility and morphology were analyzed from the left one. Epididymis was excised and minced in 1ml of phosphate buffered saline (pH 7.2) to obtain sperm suspension (Narayana *et al.*, 2002).

6.2. Sperm motility:

In each semen sample, at least 10 microscopic fields were examined with at least 100 sperm/field was counted. The number of motile sperm cells in each field was divided by the total number, and the average of the fields was assayed. The percentage of motile spermatozoa was determined (Linder *et al.*, 1995 and Lobet *et al.*, 1995).

6.3. Sperm count:

The epididymal spermatozoa count was conducted in the filtrate using a Neubauer hemocytometric chamber (Narayana *et al.*, 2002) and examined under microscope at 400X. The total sperm count in squares of 1mm² each was determined to express the number of spermatozoa/epididymis. To minimize the error, the count was repeated three times on each sample.

6.4. Sperm viability:

Sperm viability was assessed using the eosin–nigrosin stain (Tardif *et al.*, 1999). The staining was performed with one drop of freshly collected semen (10µL) were placed on a slide and stained with two drops of freshly prepared staining solution (20µl) of eosin–nigrosin (1 g eosin + 5 g nigrosin/100 ml deionized water). The live unstained and dead stained spermatozoa were analyzed under the microscope at 400X. The dye exclusion was evaluated in 100 spermatozoa.

Sperm viability was defined as the percentage of dead sperm cells. Viability was evaluated according to WHO guidelines (WHO , 2001) .

7. Statistical analysis:

All data were expressed as mean ± S.D. and statistical analysis was carried using Student ‘t’ test according to Snedecor and Cochran (1986) .

Results and discussion

1. Body and organs weight:

Male body and organ weights are presented in Table (1). Male body weight and weight gain were significantly reduced after 20 and 30 days of methomyl treatment. No statistically significant differences in relative epididymides weights were noted in any of methomyl treated groups compared to the control group. Absolute and relative testis weights were reduced dramatically in the groups treated with methomyl after 20 and 30 days compared to the 10 days treated group and control.

Table (1): Effect of methomyl on body weight, testis and epididymus weights of male mice after 10, 20 and 30 days of exposure.

Period of exposure / Groups	Body weight			Absolute testis weight (g)	Relative testis weight% (g/100g B.Wt)	Absolute Epididymis weight (g)	Relative Epididymis Weight% (g/100g B.Wt)
	Initial (g)	Final (g)	% Change				
10-days							
Control	37.4±2.65	38.5 ±3.11	2.9±0.69	0.25 ±0.03	0.65±0.041	0.07 ±0.008	0.18 ±0.046
Treated	38.7±3.65	39.7 ±4.01	2.6±0.51	0.24 ±0.05	0.60±0.033	0.07 ±0.012	0.18 ±0.051
20-days							
Control	36.2±4.22	38.4±3.98	6.1±0.68	0.26±0.013	0.68±0.078	0.07±0.0045	0.18 ±0.021
Treated	37.6±4.09	33.8 ±3.25*	10.1±1.06**	0.21±0.036**	0.62±0.06*	0.06±0.012	0.18± 0.013
30-days							
Control	38.8±4.08	41.6±4.58	7.2±1.03	0.25±0.042	0.60±0.035	0.08±0.028	0.19±0.052
Treated	36.5±3.98	31.2±3.58**	14.5±1.20**	0.20±0.046*	0.64±0.044*	0.06±0.018	0.19±0.063

Values are means ± SD for 20 mice in each group.

*Significantly different at P < 0.05.

**Highly significant at P < 0.01.

2. Biochemical parameters:

Results indicated that TBARS concentration was significantly increased, while GST, SOD, CAT activities and GSH level were significantly (p < 0.05) decreased in testicular tissue of mice treated with methomyl for all periods of exposure (Table, 2). The highest inhibition value was observed after 30 days of exposure. In addition, a significant decrease in testicular AST (30 %, 41% and

52%), ALT (38%, 56%, 69%) and AcP (17%, 25% and 35%) activities was observed after treatment with methomyl for 10, 20 and 30 days, respectively. Data showed that oral administration of methomyl for 10, 20 and 30 days induced a significant (P < 0.01) decrease in serum testosterone levels in a time dependent manner as compared to the control group (Figure, 1).

Table (2): Effect of methomyl on thiobarbituric acid reactive substances (TBARS) levels, glutathione content (GSH) and some enzymatic activities in mice testes.

Parameters	Control	10 days	20 days	30 days
TBARS[†]	19.3±0.81	24.0±0.53*	25.7±1.92*	27.5±0.70**
GSH^{!!}	2.42±0.071	1.91±0.076*	1.62 ±0.060*	1.42 ±0.080**
GST⁺	0.70±0.056	0.53±0.032*	0.47±0.027**	0.37±0.020**
SOD⁺⁺	77±1.14	57±3.98*	47±2.89**	41±3.42**
CAT⁺⁺	113±4.32	95±3.21*	77±2.27**	60±1.65**
AcP[#]	13.00±0.87	10.85±0.42*	9.74±0.46*	8.51±0.39**
AST[#]	109±4.90	76±1.82*	64±3.70**	53±2.65**
ALT[#]	97.6±2.29	60.2±5.12*	42.7±2.93**	30.6±2.28**

Values are expressed as means±SD; n = 20 for each treatment group.

*Significantly different at $P < 0.05$. **Highly significant at $P < 0.01$

[†] TBARS is expressed as nmol/g tissue

^{!!} Glutathione is expressed as mmole

⁺ GST is expressed as specific activity, (µmol/h/mg protein)

⁺⁺ SOD or CAT is expressed as units/mg protein

[#] AcP, AST and ALT is expressed as IU/mg; international unit, the amount of the enzyme that under defined assay conditions will catalyze one mol of substrate/min/mg protein.

Figure (1): Serum testosterone percent after exposure to 1/10 LD₅₀ of methomyl during different periods.

3. Reproductive toxicity:

3.1. Sperm counts and motility:

Regarding sperm quantity and quality after oral administration of methomyl at 1/10 LD₅₀ for 20 and 30 successive days to male mice produced significant decreases in sperm count, viability and progressive motility in

addition to an increase in the percentage of total abnormalities of sperm morphology (Table, 3). Although the sperm quantity and quality in 10-day group were lower than the control group, there are no statistical differences between the two groups (Table, 3).

Table (3): Effects of methomyl on sperm characteristics in male mice after 10, 20 and 30 days of exposure.

Sperm Parameters	Control	10-days	20-days	30-days
Count ($\times 10^6$)	6.2 \pm 0.88	5.1 \pm 0.96	2.4 \pm 0.45**	1.3 \pm 0.33**
Motility (%)				
Progressive	69.4 \pm 6.25	65.1 \pm 5.98	25.4 \pm 4.25**	12.8 \pm 2.58**
Non-Progressive	10.9 \pm 2.65	14.4 \pm 3.01	18.9 \pm 3.27**	24.6 \pm 4.25**
Immotile	19.7 \pm 3.21	20.5 \pm 3.58	55.7 \pm 8.98**	62.6 \pm 10.2**
Morphology (%)				
Normal	83.7 \pm 15.6	79.3 \pm 14.2	68.8 \pm 10.8*	62.4 \pm 11.09*
Abnormal head	7.6 \pm 1.03	8.9 \pm 1.22	15.2 \pm 1.98*	19.0 \pm 2.11*
Abnormal tail	8.1 \pm 1.06	11.1 \pm 1.89	14.9 \pm 2.07*	17.1 \pm 2.08*
Other abnormalities	0.6 \pm 0.036	0.7 \pm 0.052	1.1 \pm 0.98*	1.5 \pm 0.79*
Viability (%)	88.5 \pm 15.6	86.5 \pm 18.9	73.13 \pm 9.89**	56.45 \pm 6.78**

Values are means \pm SD for 20 mice in each group.

*Significantly different at $P < 0.05$. **Highly significant at $P < 0.01$

3.2. Mating index and fertility index:

As shown in Table (4) mice treated with methomyl showed a significant decrease in mating and fertility indexes after 20 and 30

days of exposure as compared to control. While, the mice group treated with methomyl for 10 days did not show any significant change.

Table (4): Reproductive efficiency of male mice after 10, 20 and 30 days of methomyl exposure.

Period of exposure/ Groups	Number of males ^a	Mating index (%) ^b	Fertility index (%) ^c
10-days			
Control	20	100 (20/20)	100 (20/20)
Treated	20	95 (19/20)	94.7 (18/19)
20-days			
Control	20	100 (20/20)	100 (20/20)
Treated	20	80 (16/20)*	75 (12/16)*
30-days			
Control	20	100 (20/20)	20/20 (100)
Treated	20	60 (12/20)*	50 (6/12)**

^a; Number of males which used for mating.

^b: Number of females with vaginal plug /number of females cohabited $\times 100$.

^c; Number of cohabited females becoming pregnant/number of non-pregnant with evidence of vaginal plug $\times 100$.

*Significantly different at $P < 0.05$. **Highly significant at $P < 0.01$

3.3. Reproductive outcomes:

A statistically significant decrease in the number of live offsprings in mice groups treated with methomyl for 20 and 30 days was observed. However, the number of implantation sites and the number of late

resorptions were not significantly changed in any of the treated groups. On the other hand, a significant increase in the number of early resorptions in the 20 and 30 days treated groups was detected (Table, 5).

Table (5): Reproductive outcomes of untreated females after cohabitation with mice exposed to methomyl for 10, 20 and 30 days.

Exposure periods	Control	10 days	20 days	30 days
Number of pregnant females	20	18	12	6
Implants/litter	10.88±1.85	10.84±1.42	10.42±1.33	10.31±1.52
Live (%)	10.34±1.74 (95.03)	10.28±1.68 (94.83)	8.60±1.99* (82.53)	6.95±1.52* (67.41)
Dead (%)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Early resorption / litter (%)	0.32 ±0.106 (2.94)	0.33 ±0.189 (3.04)	1.58 ± 0.054** (15.16)	3.11 ±0.13** (30.16)
Late resorption / litter (%)	0.22 ±0.098 (2.02)	0.23 ±0.045 (2.12)	0.24 ±0.026 (2.30)	0.25 ±0.021 (2.42)
Post implantation loss % ^a	4.96±0.98	5.16±2.06	17.66±4.06**	35.11±5.22**

Values are means ± SD for 20 mice in each group

^a; [(number of implants – live fetuses)/number of implants] x100

*Significantly different at $P < 0.05$. **Highly significant at $P < 0.01$

The toxic symptoms observed in methomyl toxicity were muscular tremors, abdominal cramps, sweating, muscle incoordination, irregular respiration and heart rate (Kidd *et al.*, 1991). Reduction in male body weight can be attributed to the reduction in feed consumption and systemic toxicity of methomyl in male mice. The administration of methomyl brought about marked alteration in the weight of testes accompanied by necrotic changes and this simply reflects regressive changes in seminiferous tubules (Udoh and Kehinde, 1999). The change in testicular weight has also corresponded to the presence or absence of postmeiotic germ cell in addition to reduction in the number of spermatogenic elements and spermatozoa (Takahara *et al.*, 1987 and Sinha *et al.*, 1995).

In the present study, an increase in TBARS levels in testicular tissue in mice treated with methomyl for different periods of time was observed. The products of lipid peroxidation (LPO) formed by free-radical mediated attack on membrane lipids can propagate a chain of reactions of LPO processes in the presence of oxygen, possibly leading to membrane destruction. In consistence with the present results, El-Khawaga, 2005 and Lohitnavy and

Sinhaseni, 1998, reported that methomyl induced LPO and oxidative stress in experimental animals. The significant accumulation of TBARS may be caused by the oxidation process that takes place in testicular cell membranes of mice exposed to methomyl. The resultant lipid peroxides may also react with GSH and lead to a decrease in GSH and the activity of glutathione related enzymes (Maran *et al.*, 2010). Oxidative damage, therefore, may be attributed to the consequence of insufficient cellular antioxidant potential. Carbamates, and their degradation products act on the membranes, oxidizing its lipid components and enhancing TBARS production during their exposure. Mammalian cells have developed several defense mechanisms against reactive oxygen species (ROS). Glutathione is particularly important because it provides a first line of defense against lipid peroxidation. It also serves as the substrate for the two major antioxidant enzyme systems, glutathione peroxidase and glutathione-S-transferase (Grosicka-Maciag *et al.*, 2008). It has been reported that the toxicity of some carbamates is correlated with the decrease in GSH content, and that the GSH redox cycle is the major pathway to provide the reducing equivalents for carbamate reduction

(Grosicka-Maciag *et al.*, 2008 and Kanno *et al.*, 2003). Because glutathione is the most abundant soluble cellular redox buffer, it is predictable that its deficit can induce or facilitate oxidative stress. The antioxidative enzymes were significantly reduced in methomyl treated mice. GST, a family of isoenzymes serving a major role in the biotransformation of many reactive compounds, could also catalyze the conjugation of GSH with a wide variety of organic peroxides to form more water-soluble compounds (Vos and Van Bladeren, 1990). Consistent with the present results, Lohitnavy and Sinhaseni (1998) reported a significant decrease in the GST activity after a single intraperitoneal dose of methomyl to mice. Superoxide dismutase protects oxygen-metabolizing cells against harmful effects of superoxide free radicals through destruction. SOD protects hyaluronate against depolymerization by the action of free radicals, which indicates that exogenous SOD might possess an anti-inflammatory effect. In agreement with the present results, methomyl decreased the activity of SOD in mice through induction of oxidative stress in addition to its anticholinesterase potency (El-Khawaga, 2005). Catalase is ubiquitously present in a wide range of aerobic cell types with the highest activities in mammals. Some studies have indicated that superoxide radicals can inhibit CAT activity, and the increased H₂O₂ resulting from CAT inhibition could finally inhibit SOD activity. This is an indicative of the rate of formation of free radicals (Mansour and Mossa , 2009) .

Results showed that the increase in the duration of exposure of methomyl caused a significant decrease in the activity of AcP, AST and ALT in testes of male mice. The inhibition might be due to cellular damage or increased permeability of plasma membrane (El-Demerdash, 2004 and Ksheerasagar and Kaliwal, 2006). The AST and ALT enzymes are involved in amino acid metabolism and

any change in these enzymes indicates tissue damage due to the toxic effect of methomyl in testis. The change in AcP activity may be because of methomyl on absorptive or secretory surface of the cell membrane causing cellular leakage as an adaptive response in enzyme activity to the persistent stress (Ksheerasagar and Kaliwal, 2006). Concerning serum testosterone level, data showed that mice treated with methomyl induced a significant decrease in serum testosterone levels in a time dependent manner (Figure, 1). This finding agreed with that reported by Shalaby *et al.* (2010) and Mahgoub and Mednay (2001) who recorded a significant decrease in the level of testosterone in serum of methomyl intoxicated rats.

The spermatogenesis in mammals depends on testosterone production by Leydig cells in response to stimulation by follicle stimulating and luteinizing hormones. Follicle stimulating hormone increases Sertloji cell synthesis of an androgen binding protein needed to maintain high concentrations of testosterone. The hormonal changes produced by carbofuran compounds favour direct toxic effect of insecticide or possibly through a change in the neuroendocrine environment resulting into acetylcholinesterase inhibition (Aziz *et al.*, 2008) .

In consistence with the present results, methomyl adversely affect male reproductive organs and semen characteristics leading to significant decreases in epididymal sperm count and sperm motility, with an increase in sperm abnormal morphology. This can be attributed to the hormonal changes and testicular damage caused by methomyl (Shalaby *et al.*, 2010; Mahgoub and Mednay, 2001 and Pant *et al.*, 1997) . Other investigation was studied by Berger *et al.* (2000) who found that thiocarbamate insecticide molinate reduced the sperm fertilizing capacity of male rats concurrently with a reduction in sperm motility and

viability. In addition, Akbarsha *et al.* (2001) reported that carbendazim decreased sperm cell count; caused inhibition of sperm motility and increased incidence of sperm abnormalities.

Sperm motility is an important functional measurement to predict sperm fertilizing capacity (Aitken *et al.*, 1984). Any negative impact on motility would seriously affect fertilizing ability (Murugavel *et al.*, 1989). Marked inhibition of sperm motility may be because of low level of ATP content. Sperm motility may be affected by altered enzymatic activities of oxidative phosphorylation process that required for ATP production, a source of energy for the forward movement of spermatozoa. Full ATP pool is crucial for normal spermatozoal movement and a slight deprivation of ATP leads to reduction in motility, which may cause infertility (Tso and Lee, 1981 and Bedford, 1983). Sperm count is one of the important factors that affect fertility (Bett *et al.*, 1996). Suppression of gonadotrophins might have caused decrease in sperm density in testes (Sinha *et al.*, 1995). Also, toxicants have direct effect on Sertoli cell function, which appears to be involved in the control of spermiation, and when disturbed caused epithelial disorganization and subsequent tubular atrophy (Bardin *et al.*, 1998). The negative fertility test may be attributed to lack of forward progression and reduction in density of spermatozoa and altered biochemical milieu of cauda epididymis.

Reduction in mating and fertility indices in 20 and 30 days methomyl treated groups may simply represent the effects of methomyl exposure on sperm parameters and testis histopathologic changes with different period of treatments. Mating index reduction could be due to adverse effects on libido in relation to a possible decrease of testosterone level in addition to the other reproductive organs such as seminal vesicles or prostate have been affected (IPCS/WHO, 2001). Spermatogenesis and fertility are critically

dependent upon the maintenance of adequate levels of testosterone (Kidd and James, 1991). Therefore, the effects of methomyl on the fertility in this study can be attributed to its ability to reduce serum testosterone levels and sperm counts. Pregnancy outcomes were affected by exposure of male mice to methomyl for 20 and 30 days. Number of live fetuses was decreased while early resorption number was increased in the same groups. Therefore, the male-mediated effects of methomyl on pregnancy outcome may be attributed to the testicular toxicity.

In conclusion, the insecticide methomyl is a highly toxic compound. It has the capability to induce oxidative damage as evidenced by increasing LPO and perturbations in antioxidant enzymes. Methomyl induces reproductive toxicity in male mice manifested by decreases in the fertility index, weights of the sexual organs, semen characteristics and serum testosterone level. So, a great attention should be taken during field application of methomyl to avoid its deleterious effects on the male reproductive system of farm animals and occupationally exposed human.

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Biological activities of developmental stages of citrus tree borer *Chrysobothris dorsata* (Buprestidae: Coleoptera) on casuarina trees.

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Abstract:

Chrysobothris dorsata (Fabricius) (Buprestidae: Coleoptera), female beetle put its eggs singly under the bark through crevices and cracks with trunks and branches of trees. The eggs are pale orange to pale brown in colour, semi-circular in shape, about 1.14x 1.095 mm. The incubation period lasted 5- 12 days with an average 8.5 ± 2.1 days. The larva of *C. dorsata* has six larval instars. The duration of immature larva ranged 280- 349 days (average, 313.8 ± 20.1 days), while duration of full-grown larvae ranged 9-22 days (average, 15.2 ± 4.5 days). The prepupal duration lasted 7-15 days (average, 10.3 ± 2.5 days). The duration of pupa ranged 9-18 days (average, 12.8 ± 2.8 days). The duration of adult stage inside the pupal chamber recorded 6-11 days (average, 8.2 ± 1.4 days). The beetles lived after emergence from host about 5-13 days (average, 7.9 ± 2.1 days). The averages of pre-oviposition, oviposition and postoviposition recorded 2.1 ± 0.8 days (ranged, 1-4 days), 3.8 ± 1.1 days (range 2 – 6 days) and 2.6 ± 0.8 days (range 1-4 days), respectively. The life cycle of *C. dorsata* beetle rearing in casuarina trees recorded 369.6 ± 18.9 days (ranged 346 – 405 days).

Introduction

Casuarina tree is one of important wood trees which are widely distributed in Egypt, which are cultivated on agriculture roads (as shade and ornamental trees) and around fields as obstacle or prevent the damage of crops by winds (Tawfik *et al.*, 2014). Buprestid beetle *Chrysobothris dorsata* (Fabricius) (Buprestidae: Coleoptera), is one of the most injurious pests of fruit and wood trees. According to Bedford (1931), Shalby (1958), Nour (1963), Alfeiri (1976), Moussa (1977), Batt (1989) and Okil (1991), this pest attack

acacia, citrus, lebbek, casuarina, common fig, mulberry, poinciana, peach, apricot and mango trees. Therefore the aim of this work is to study the biology of this borer on casuarina trees.

Materials and methods

Infested casuarina branches with citrus tree borer, *C. dorsata*, were collected from Ismailia district (Ismailia Governorate), and put in wire cages (50x40x150cm). Continuous observations were carried out until starting adults emergence. Emerging beetles were collected and sexed. Each pair

(male and female) was put in glass jar (35cm. height and 18cm. diameter) on two cuttings of intact casuarina each of 25cm. long and 3cm. diameter. The ends of cutting were covered with wax and the bark at these ends were wounded by sharp blade (as oviposition sites). The beetles (10 couples) were observed until the females laid their eggs and the oviposition periods were recorded.

At hatching, the incubation period was estimated, and 30 hatching larvae were planted under the bark of other cuttings (larva /one cutting) to the same size of oviposition cuttings. The larvae were transferred to new cuttings at two intervals weeks until the larvae constructed the pupal chambers. The bark of cuttings was removed above larval tunnels to determine the number of instars by recording the molting skin, the duration of each instar was recorded. By removing to apart of wood tissues over pupal chambers, the different transformations of developmental stages were observed until emergence. The durations of different developmental stages were estimated,

whereas the life cycle of *C. dorsata* beetle was determined.

Results and discussion

Data on the biological aspects of citrus tree borer *C. dorsata* on casuarina trees showed the following results.

1. Egg stage:

The female beetle of *C. dorsata* put its eggs singly under the bark through the crevices and cracks with the trunks and branches of trees. The eggs are pale orange to pale brown in colour, semi-circular in shape, about 1.14 x 1.095mm.(Table,1). Okil (1991) found that eggs of *C. dorsata* are 0.6-0.8mm in diameter, while Batt (1999) recorded that the diameter of *C. dorsata* eggs about 0.89-1.27mm, with an average of 1.12 ± 0.09mm.

Under laboratory conditions of 31.8 °C and 62.4 % RH. the incubation period lasted 5 to 12 days, with an average of 8.5 ± 2.1days, Table (2), while Batt (1999) found that the incubation period of *C. dorsata* eggs on mango trees lasted 13.8 ± 3.33 days, ranged 8-19 days.

Table (1): Measurements of different developmental stages of *Chrysobothris dorsata* beetle on casuarina trees.

Stage	Length (mm.)		Width (mm.)	
	Range	Av. ± s.e.	Range	Av. ± s.e.
Egg	1 – 1.3	1.14 ± 0.07	0.9 – 1.2	1.095 ± 0.10
Larva	22– 27	24.6 ± 1.7	5– 7	5.9 ± 0.6 2
Prepupa	17 – 24	21.3 ± 2.1	4.5 – 6	5.33 ± 0.47
Pupa	14 – 16	14.7 ± 0.09	4 – 5	4.33 ± 0.40
Adult	13.8 – 14.5	12.8 ± 0.2	3.8 – 4.6	4.1 ± 0.3

Table (2): Durations of different developmental stages of *Chrysobothris dorsata* beetle on casuarina trees.

Stages	Duration (in days)		Lab.cond	
	Range	Av. ± s.e.	Mean temp.°C	Mean RH. %
Egg	5 – 12	8.5 ± 2.1	31.8	62.4
Immature larva	280 – 349	313.8 ± 20.1	23.1	64.6
Full grown larva	9 – 22	15.2 ± 4.5	26.2	60.7
Prepupa	7 – 15	10.3 ± 2.5	28.8	61.2
Pupa	9 – 18	12.8 ± 2.8	30.4	61.3
Adult hardness	6 – 11	8.2 ± 1.4	30.6	62.4
Adult longevity	5 – 13	7.9 ± 2.1	31.4	64.8
Total	346 - 405	369.6 ± 18.9	28.9	62.5

2. Larval stage:

The newly hatched larvae bore under the bark through cambium tissue and external layer of sapwood marking larval galleries. The larval galleries are shallow, sinuous and filled with compact saw dust mixed with pellets of wood excrements.

As the larvae grow, the tunnels increase in length and width, until they reach to full grown larvae, which are typical buprestid larvae. The larvae of *C. dorsata* moult 5 times passing through six larval instars. Table (3) shows the dimensions of these instars.

Table (3): Dimensions of the larval instars of *Chrysobothris dorsata* rearing on casuarina cuttings.

Larval instar	Width of head capsule (mm.)		Length of body (mm.)		Width of body (mm.)	
	M + SE	Range	M + SE	Range	M + SE	Range
First	0.44 ± 0.05	0.4 – 0.5	3.5 ± 0.11	3.4 – 3.7	0.77 ± 0.7	0.7 - 0.8
Second	0.88 ± 0.05	0.8 – 1.0	7.9 ± 0.7	7 – 9	1.65 ± 0.14	1.4 - 1.8
Third	1.26 ± 0.09	1.1 – 1.4	12.65 ± 0.85	11 – 14	2.8 ± 0.27	2.1 - 3.2
Fourth	1.72 ± 0.09	1.5 – 1.8	17.65 ± 1.19	15 – 19	3.86 ± 0.25	3.4 - 4.2
Fifth	1.97 ± 0.10	1.8 – 2.1	20.0 ± 1.0	19 – 23	4.77 ± 0.33	4.3 - 5.4
Sixth	2.69 ± 0.44	2 – 3.5	24.6 ± 1.7	22 - 27	5.9 ± 0.62	5 - 7

Okil (1991) mentioned that the length of full grown larva 18.4mm (16 – 23mm), while the width with 5.4mm (4.7mm, average), whereas Batt (1999) recorded that the length of full grown larvae ranged 19 – 33mm., with an average of 25.2 ± 5.2mm., while the width ranged between 5 – 7mm., with an average of 6 ± 0.56mm. Under laboratory conditions of 23.1°C and 64.6 % RH., the duration of immature larva ranged between 280 – 349 days, with an average of 313.8 ± 20.1 days (Table, 2).

Table (4) : Duration of the different larval instars of *Chrysobothris dorsata* under laboratory conditions.

Larva instar	Duration (in days)		Lab.cond.Av.	
	M. ± s.e	Range	Temp. °c	RH. %
First	60.8 ± 5.18	55 – 68	22.9	61.3
Second	49 ± 3.71	42 – 56	27.1	60.2
Third	55 ± 6.11	47 – 63	26.4	72.8
Fourth	69 ± 5.15	62 – 79	20.9	69.9
Fifth	80 ± 4.24	74 – 86	18.2	58.6
Sixth	15.2 ± 4.5	9 – 22	26.2	60.7
Total	329 ± 24.6	289 – 371	23.6	63.9

The length of first larval instar ranged 3.4 – 3.7 mm, with an average of 3.5 ± 0.11mm, while the body width ranged 0.7 - 0.8mm, with an average of 0.77 ± 0.7mm, whereas the width of head capsule ranged between 0.4 – 0.5 mm, with an average of 0.44 ± 0.05 mm. The length of full grown larva ranged 22 to 27mm., with an average of 24.6 ± 1.7mm., while the width ranged 5 – 7mm., with an average of 5.9 ± 0.62mm, whereas the width of head capsule ranged between 2- 35mm., With an average of 2.69 ± 0.44 mm.

Date presented in Table (4) show the duration of the different larval instars under laboratory conditions. The total duration of larval instars ranged between 289 – 371 days, with an average of 329 ± 24.6 days, under average lab. cond. of 23.6°C and 63.9 RH.% . When the full grown larva construct the pupal chamber in the sapwood., it transforms inside pupal chamber to prepupa which its length ranged between 17 – 24mm., with an average of 21.3 ± 2.1mm., while the width ranged between 4.5 – 6mm., with an average of 5.33 ± 0.47mm. (Table,1).

Under laboratory conditions of 26.2°C and 60.7 % RH., the duration of full grown the larva ranged 9-22days, with an average of 15.2 ± 4.5 days, while the prepupal duration lasted 7 –15days, with an average of 10.3 ± 2.5 days under laboratory conditions 28.8°C and 61.2 % RH. (Table , 2). Batt (1999) reported that the larval duration of *C. dorsata* inside mango trees, ranged 287 – 309 days with an average of 297.4 ± 4.83 days, under laboratory conditions of 25.2°C and 66.3 % RH., while he recorded that prepupal duration lasted 14.5 ± 5.8 days (ranged between 7 – 22 days), under laboratory conditions of 27.1°C and 60 % RH.

3. Pupal stage:

The prepupa transforms inside pupal chamber to pupa which its length ranged between 17 – 24mm, with an average of 21.3 ± 2.1 mm, while the width ranged between 4.5 – 6mm with an average of 5.33 ± 0.47 mm. (Table,1). Okil (1991) mentioned that the length of pupa (rearing on citrus trees) was 14.1mm (13 – 19mm), while the width 5.3mm (4 – 7 mm), whereas Batt (1999) found that the average length of pupa of *C. dorsata* (rearing on mango trees) was 14.7 ± 0.9 mm (ranged 13 – 16mm), while the average width 4.39 ± 0.41 mm (ranged 4 – 5 mm). Under laboratory conditions of 30.4°C and 61.3% RH., the pupa elapsed about 9 – 18 days (average, 12.8 ± 2.8 days) to transform to adult inside pupal chamber, (Table, 2). In this respect, Batt (1999) recorded that the pupal duration of *C. dorsata* rearing on mango trees was about $16.14 \pm$

8.57 days (ranged 5 – 25days) under laboratory condition of 27.1°C and 60 % RH.

4. Adult stage:

The adult that formed inside the pupal chamber stays a period varied between 6 – 11 days, with an average of 8.2 ± 1.4 days for hardness (under laboratory conditions of 30.6°C and 62.4% RH.) in the same chamber before its emergence from the host. The beetle lived for ranged between 5 – 13 days, with an average of 7.9 ± 2.1 days, under laboratory conditions of 31.4°C and 64.8% RH. Table (2), Similar results obtained by Batt (1999) who recorded that hardness period of *C. dorsata* (inside mango trees) ranged 4 –11 days (average 8.33 ± 2.3 days), while the beetle lived 3 – 14 days with an average of 7.4 ± 3.87 days.

The length of adult ranged between 12.8 – 14.5mm., with an average of 13.5 ± 0.2 mm., while the width ranged between 3.8 – 4.6mm.,with an average of 4.1 ± 0.3 mm. (Table,1). Okil (1991) found that the length and width of *C. dorsata* beetle ranged between 4 –14mm. and 4 – 6 mm. respectively, while Batt (1999) found that the length of adult ranged between 13.5 – 14.5mm.(average, 13.9 ± 0.4 mm),While the width ranged between 4 – 5mm. (average, 4.2 ± 0.43 mm.).Under laboratory conditions of 31.8 °c and 62.4% RH., the average periods of preoviposition, oviposition and postoviposition recorded 2.1 ± 0.8 days (range, 1 – 4 days), 3.8 ± 1.1 days (range, 2 – 6 days) and 2.6 ± 0.8 days (1 – 4 days), respectively (Table,5).

Table (5) : Ovipositional periods of *Chrysobothris dorsata* under laboratory conditions of 31.8 °C and 62.4 % RH.

State	Duration (in days)	
	Range	Av. \pm s.e.
Pre-oviposition	1 – 4	2.1 ± 0.8
Oviposition	2 – 6	3.8 ± 1.1
Post-oviposition	1 – 4	2.6 ± 0.8

The results revealed that the life cycle of *C. dorsata* beetle rearing on casuarina trees recorded 369.6 ± 18.9 days ranged 346 - 405 days, under laboratory conditions of 28.9°C and 62.5% RH., Table (2). This result is coinciding with Batt (1999) who reported that only one generation of *C. dorsata* beetle occurs each year on mango trees, where the total duration of life stages was 357.30 ± 28.8 days, ranged between 314 – 400 days.

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Soil compaction, moisture content and pupal burial depth as a new control strategy of peach fruit fly *Bactrocera zonata* (Diptera: Tephritidae)

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Abstract:

Peach fruit fly (PFF) *Bactrocera zonata* (Saunders) (Diptera: Tephritidae) is one of the most deleterious tephritid flies of horticultural crops worldwide. Since PFF spends a part of its life cycle in the soil as pre-pupae and pupae, the effects of soil texture (clay, loamy and sandy soil) on larval burrowing depth and pupal burial depth (0, 1, 2, 4, 8, 12, 16, 20 and 24 cm) on emerging adults of PFF were studied. Moreover, the effects of both compaction and moisture (SM) of a sandy-loamy soil on adults' emergence rates of PFF as well as soil hydraulic properties were investigated. Soil compaction was tested at three compaction levels (without-, moderate- and severe-compaction; corresponding to an increase in bulk density by 0.0, 11.0 and 22.0%, respectively) at three levels of moisture content (air dry soil, 20 and 80% of water content at field capacity) against PFF pupae. Results indicated that the extremely burrowing depth of PFF larvae was 4 cm in clay soil, and 5 cm in both sandy and loamy soils. In inversely proportional to pupal burial depth, the emerging flies relied significantly on both pupal depth and soil type. In addition, emerged flies' rates were negatively affected more by SM than soil compaction. Furthermore, emerged flies correlated positively related with the total soil porosity (%), quickly drainable pores and slowly drainable pores. Additionally, soil compaction altered soil hydraulic properties (i.e., total and air porosity, saturated hydraulic conductivity and water retention curve) by reducing the portion of macro pores and increasing micro pores. The study concluded that moderate soil compaction can be significantly suppressed the PFF population and enhanced soil hydraulic properties; therefore, soil compaction could be an important approach in integrated pest management (IPM) against PFF.

Introduction

Fruit flies (Diptera: Tephritidae) are the most harmful insect pests of horticultural crops throughout the world, including the

peach fruit fly (PFF) *Bactrocera zonata* (Saunders) (Diptera: Tephritidae). This pest has become widespread in Egypt and active

throughout the year, except during the cooler months, particularly January (El-Minshawy *et al.*, 1999; Hashem *et al.*, 2001; Draz *et al.*, 2002; OEPP/EPPO, 2005; El-Gendy and El-Saadany, 2012 and El-Gendy and Nassar, 2014). It has a wide range of hosts, i.e. vegetable and fruit crops (El-Gendy, 2017), causing an estimated damage of 190 million €/a year (FAO/ IAEA, 2000). Current control methods of this pest heavily rely on the aerial application of malathion, bait sprays, or ground cover sprays of potent organophosphorus pesticides (Roessler, 1989). However, globally, there is an increasing awareness of the risks of chemical pesticide residues. For this reason, there is a desperately need to produce chemical free food, which would be achieved through the organic farming. Therefore, the agriculture control practices will play an essential role in the control of these pests.

As Tephritid fruit flies stages of pre-pupae and pupae subsist in the soil habitat, therefore, they are subjected to several different abiotic variables; soil texture, porosity, density, temperature and moisture that influence pupal mortality and malformation flies (El-Gendy and AbdAllah, 2019). It has been previously reported that soil texture and moisture significantly affected pupal survival rate of *B. tryoni* (Hulthen and Clarke, 2006), adult emergence of *Anastrepha ludens*, *A. oblique* (Montoya *et al.*, 2008) and *B. zonata* (El-Gendy and AbdAllah, 2019).

In light textured soils, rain and/or irrigation water creates preferential paths, resulting in a rapid water movement, low water retention, excessive drainage, high air permeability and aeration conditions and high O₂ availability (Wei and Durian, 2014 and Shipitalo *et al.*, 2000). Such soil could be an excellent environment of the growth of PFF. Since, the macro-pores are the most dominant; such pores facilitate larval movement and penetration to greater depths (Dimou *et al.*, 2003). However, altering the

pore size distribution in light soils (by reducing total porosity and the portion of macro-pores), usually led to changes in soil hydraulic and retention properties, soil density and penetration resistance which in turn might affect the PFF. To do so, one of the means is soil compaction. Soil compaction causes a reduction in most related soil physical properties; total porosity and macro-pores (quickly drainable pores (QDP), infiltration rate and hydraulic conductivity but also, increases the portion of micro-pores (slowly drainable pores, SDP). Moreover, compaction alters the shape of the soil water retention curves (Zhang *et al.*, 2006). Varallyay and Lesztak (1990) reported that if the macro-pores volume of compacted soil was half that of un-compacted soil, the air permeability and infiltration rate will be reduced dramatically.

Basically, soil compaction dramatically affects soil porosity, pore size distribution, air porosity and water retention properties, as a result adult emergence rates of PFF might be also affected. However, there is no comprehensive study has investigated the impact of soil compaction on adult emergence rates of PFF. Therefore, the goal of this study was to investigate the impact of different levels soil compaction (moderate and severe) at different water content on adult emergence rates of PFF as well as some soil physical properties (Total porosity, pore size distribution, and hydraulic conductivity). A further objective was to study the impact of soil types; clay, loamy and sandy on pupal behavior, as well as the impacts of the pupae burial depth in these soil types on emerging adult flies' percentages.

Materials and methods

The experiments were carried out in the Laboratory of Eradication of the peach fruit fly at Damanhour, El-Beheira Governorate, Egypt. Whereas, the effect of soil compaction on soil physical properties was determined in the soil science laboratory, Department of Natural Resources and

Agricultural Engineering, Faculty of Agriculture, Damanhour University, Damanhour, Egypt.

1. Mass rearing technique:

The mass rearing technique of PFF was conducted under laboratory conditions according to El-Gendy (2002) and described by El-Gendy and AbdAllah (2019).

2. Soil characteristics used:

Three soil samples were collected from the districts of Rashid, Damanhour and Abo-Homos, El-Beheira Governorate, Egypt. Soil samples were passed through 2 mm sieve and air was dried, then sifted and autoclaved for 24hr. at 80°C before being used (Hennessey, 1994). The main soil physical and chemical properties are presented in Table (1).

Table (1): Physical characteristics of the three tested soils.

Soil type	Particle size distribution (%)				T.P (%)	B.D (g/cm ³)
	Grave(l)	Sand	Silt	Clay		
Sandy	1.26	97.30	1.46	1.24	33	1.5
Loam	2.24	50.45	29.8	19.75	44.8	1.44
Clay	1.83	35.5	24.16	40.34	56.7	1.32

T.P: Total porosity.

B.D: Bulk density.

3. Effect of soil texture on pupation depth of *Bactrocera zonata*:

Three types of air-dried soil; sandy, loamy and clay soils were tested against PFF larvae burrowing using black polyvinyl chloride (PVC) columns (7 cm height and 8 cm in diameter, sealed from the bottom, with a fine metal mesh used, and fixed in a petri-dish, 15 cm diameter). The columns, in three groups; each group was filled with one type of the tested soils up to 6 cm. Each soil type was replicated ten times; each replicate involved twenty matured larvae (pre-pupae stage) that could pop on soil surface. Soil columns were immediately covered with muslin cloth and randomized distributed on the shelves in the rearing room. Two days later, the pupae were looked for in the soil with ice cream stick, depth (distance to the surface, cm) of each discovered pupa was measured. Pupation percentages against each depth were calculated.

4. Effect of pupation depth (Burial depth) on the emergence of adults *Bactrocera zonata*:

Black PVC columns (8 cm in diameter) and transparent jars (1L) were used. The columns were consisted of two parts; the bottom part was 6 cm in height (sealed in the bottom and fixed in a petri-dish as described above), and the upper part was either 4, 8, 12, 16, 24 or 20 cm (according to the tested pupal depth). Nine soil depths, for each soil type (Sandy, loamy and clay), were tested against PFF pupae in five replicates. Twenty healthy pupae (seven-day-old) were gently placed in the center of soil surface of column-bottom part. Then, the upper part of tube was fixed above the bottom part, and gently packed with the same soil type for nine heights; 0, 1, 2, 4, 8, 12, 16, 20 and 24 cm. The upper part of the column opening was connected to the hole of the Jar, which were fixed by the silicon material. Columns were randomly distributed in the rearing room on the shelves. The numbers of emerged flies were recorded, and the adults' emergence rate was calculated using the formula: Adults' emergence rate = [(Number of adult's emergence)/ (Number of tested pupae)]*100.

5. Effect of soil compaction on adult's emergence of *Bactrocera zonata*:

Since the sandy soil showed to be in compactable, and due to undesirable impacts of soil compaction on the clay soil properties (Botta *et al.*, 2006, 2008, 2009, 2010;

Manuwa and Odubanjo, 2007; Odey, 2018 and Etana *et al.*, 2013), the effect of soil compaction on adult's emergence of PFF was investigated using a sandy loam soil (Table, 2).

Table (2): Main physical and chemical properties of a representative sandy- loam soil samples in the experimental site (0-30 cm depth).

Soil property	Value
Particle size distribution	
Sand (%)	70.2
Silt (%)	10.0
Clay (%)	19.8
Texture class	sandy- loam
Water retention points	
Saturation (%)	46.2
Field capacity (%)	21.6
PWP (%)	11.2
Available water (mm m^{-1})	104.4
Bulk Density (BD) (Mg m^{-3})	1.35
Total porosity (%)	46.2
Saturated Hydraulic Conductivity) (mm h^{-1})	72.21
Ece (dS m^{-1})	4.2
pH	8.15
OM (%)	1.17
CaCO ₃ (%)	3.22

PWP and OM permanent wilting point, and organic matter. Electrical conductivity (ECe) measured in soil paste extract. Soil reaction (PH) measured in 1:2.5 soil suspension. Organic matter (calculated by multiplying the organic carbon content by a conversion factor of 1.724).

In this experiment, two factors were investigated; the main factor was soil compaction at three levels of soil compaction; C₀ (un-compacted; control), C₁ (moderate) and C₂, (severe compaction), and the second factor was soil moisture at three levels (0, 20 and 80% of field capacity) with five replicates. Dark PVC soil columns (13 cm in height and 10 cm in diameter, Figure, 1) were used. Each soil column was divided into two parts; the lower part (4 cm height, bottomed sealed and fixed in a petri-dish, as referenced above), which contained un-compacted soil (bulk density; BD =1.35 Mg m⁻³), and the upper part (9 cm height) contained the compacted soil. The exerted compaction was calculated using BD as an indicator. For control treatment, soil was

moved into the upper portion of PVC columns at density of 1.35 Mg m⁻³. Regarding the compaction treatments, soil was moved into the upper part of PVC columns and compacted in 8 cm height by applying appropriate blows of a hammer (5 kg mass and diameter slightly less than the diameter of the columns) to two compacted levels. The 1st level was 1.5 Mg m⁻³ (moderate, C1) and the 2nd level was 1.65 Mg m⁻³ (severe compaction, C2).

For all treatments, twenty healthy pupae (seven-day-old) were placed in a small hole (1×1×0.5 cm, L: W: D) in the center of the lower soil surface (un-compacted) of each column for all treatments. Then, the upper part PVC columns were closely attached to the lower part with silicone material. Once

prepared, the compacted columns were watered to 20% or 80% of field capacity using drip irrigation system at fixed water discharge of 2 L h^{-1} as well as air dried soil columns were investigated. The upper part

was covered with muslin cloths and tied with rubber band. The columns were randomized on shelves in the rearing room. Adults' emergence rate was calculated as above-mentioned formula.

Figure (1): A schematic of the PVC column set-up. An emitter ($Q= 2.0 \text{ L h}^{-1}$) is connected to a syringe pump. The PVC column has a height of 13 cm and a cross-sectional area of $A = 78.5 \text{ cm}^2$. The soil packing has of 12 cm of soil; 8 cm of compacted soil and 4 cm of control soil).

6. Determination of soil water content at field capacity:

The soil water content at the field capacity of loamy-sand soil; compacted and un-compacted was determined by placing three columns sealed with muslin cloth from the bottom (representing each compaction treatment) in a saucer filled with water to allow soil saturation from the bottom. When the soils were saturated, the saucers were removed and excess water drained gravimetrically (overnight) until no drainage was observed from the columns (AbdAllah *et al.*, 2019; Agaba *et al.*, 2010; and Chen *et al.*, 2003). Then soil samples were dried at 105°C and soil water content was calculated.

7. Effect of soil ccompaction on ssome physical properties:

Similarly, soil columns were prepared at a BD of 1.35, 1.5 or 1.65 Mg m^{-3} to represent soil compaction treatment (C0, C1 and C2). Then total porosity, air porosity, saturated hydraulic conductivity, and pore size distribution were determined.

The pore size was calculated from the water retention curves using the following equation (Marshall *et al.*, 1996):

$$r = \frac{\rho_w g h}{2\gamma \cos\alpha} / \psi$$

where r is the mean equivalent cylindrical radius of the pores (m) at a given matric potential ψ (Pa); γ is the surface tension of water (72.75 mJm^{-2} at 20°C); α is the contact angle between the water and the pore wall, which was assumed to be zero; ρ_w is the density of the water (0.9982 Mg m^{-3} at 20°C); g is the acceleration due to

gravity (9.80 m s^{-2}); and h is the matric suction (m) applied to drain the water.

The pores size distribution was classified to quickly drainable pores (QDP) ($> 30 \mu$), slowly drainable pores (SDP) ($30\text{-}9 \mu$), water holding pores (WHP) ($9\text{-}0.2 \mu$) and fine capillary pores (FCP) ($< 0.2 \mu$), according to De Leenheer and De Boodt (1965). Delineated pore size distribution was calculated as percentage of total porosity.

8. Saturated hydraulic conductivity:

Measurements of fluid flow through a soil provide a meaningful description of compaction, because the fluid conductivity is related (Odey, 2018). Saturated hydraulic conductivity was measured according to (Moutier *et al.*, 2000). A plastic cylinder (20 cm height with a diameter of 7 cm) with a fine metal screen at the bottom were used to determine the hydraulic conductivity of control and compacted soil using three replications for each treatment. The soil was packed in the cylinder at a BD of 1.35, 1.5 and 1.65 Mg m^{-3} and covered with a filter paper to reduce soil surface disturbance. Soil cylinders were saturated by capillary rise using tap water (0.5 dS m^{-1}). After the saturation process from the bottom, the flow direction was reversed, and a constant pressure head of 4 cm was applied in the top of soil cylinder. The leachate was collected, and hydraulic conductivity was calculated.

9. Statistical analysis:

The number of pupae from each depth level of each soil type was converted into percentages. The data were normalized by an arcsine square root transformation and a linear regression was used to determine the relation between larvae burrow depth and soil type. Data of pupae burial depth in soil types and adults' emergence of PFF, as well as soil compaction and WSCL on adults' emergence of PFF were converted into percentages and normalized by an arcsine square root transformation and analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics (Version 22.0). Mean values

were compared using Tukey at significance level 0.05.

Results and discussion

1. Effect of soil type on larval burrowing depth of *Bactrocera zonata*:

The variations in pupation depth levels of PFF as shown in Figure (1) relied only on burrowing depth of larvae among the tested soil types; sandy, loamy and clay ($F=109.96$, $df=5$, $p=0.000$), however, a significant interaction between soil type and burrowing levels ($F=32.38$, $df=10$, $p=0.000$) was recorded. In the sandy soil, the larvae pupated mostly on soil surface (1st level, 0-1 cm) with 44.89% of total pupated flies of all soil levels, whereas the highest pupation level in clay and loamy soils was the 3rd level ($>2\text{-}3 \text{ cm}$) with respective percentages of 60.65 and 45.00% of total pupated flies within each soil type. The larvae burrowed in sandy and loamy soils deeper than those in clay soil, up to 5 cm in sandy and loamy soils and to 4 cm in clay soil; beyond the 4th level of clay soil and the 5th level of sandy and loamy soils no pupae were found. The drilling of PFF larvae in the soil was significantly in a negative relation to soil texture in case of both sandy ($r=-0.84$, $p=0.0001$) and clay soil ($r=-0.59$, $p=0.009$), and non-significant in loamy soil. Results also stated that, according determination coefficient, the sandy soil texture was more effective on pupation depth levels than clay and loamy soil (sandy; $R^2=0.8738$, clay; $R^2=0.1393$, loamy; $R^2=0.1201$).

2. Effect of pupation depth and soil type on adults' emergence of *Bactrocera zonata*:

Percentages of emerging PFF flies outside the soil depended significantly on both pupal burial depth and soil type (burial depth; $F=98.57$, $n=8$, $p=0.0001$, soil type; $F=139.21$, $n=2$, $p=0.0002$). In addition, a significant interaction was recorded between burial depth of pupae and soil type on emerging flies ($F=26.01$, $n=16$, $p=0.0000$). As shown in Figure (2), the rate of emerging flies outside different soil types was inversely

related to the burial depth of pupae within the soil type (loamy: $r=-0.93$, $p=0.000$, clay: $r=-0.91$, $p=0.000$, sandy: $r=-0.84$, $p=0.000$). The highest percent of the emerged flies was recorded in the first burial depth (zero cm) of all tested soil types with more emergent in loamy soil (98.33%), followed by clay (96.67%) and sandy (96.66%) soils, respectively. The emerged flies decreased gradually with the increasing of pupal burial depth to record the highest emergency at 24cm depth in sandy soil by 60% compared with 33.3 and 25% in clay and loamy soils. In sandy land, the overall average of emerging flies was greater (70.85%) than loamy (64.99%) and clay (59.44%) soils. The pupation depth was more effective than soil type on the adults emergence percentages (pupation depth: $F=61.48$, $df=1$, $p=0.0000$, soil type: $F=8.45$, $df=1$, $p=0.0047$) with 43.7 and 9.67%, respectively, with a significant combined effect (soil depth: $F=73.30$, $df=1$, $p=0.0000$, soil type: $F=16.19$, $df=1$, $p=0.0001$) by 52.22% of the total effects on emerging flies according to determination coefficient (R^2).

3. Effect of soil compaction on adults' emergence of *Bactrocera zonata*:

At SM of 80%-FC, no flies were emerged from the compacted soil at compaction levels of C0 (un-compacted soil), C1 (moderate soil) and C2 (severe soil). The same trend was obtained at SM of 20%-FC in both C1 and C2 compaction. However, in C0 at SM of 20% of FC and air-dried soil, the emerged flies were 40.0 and 81.66%, respectively, as shown in Figure (3). The

Table (3): Total porosity, pore size distribution as a percentage of total volume, of the studied soil samples at the two bulk densities.

Soil bulk density (BD) g/cm^3	Pore size distribution as a percentage of total volume						Ksat	Water content at FC
	Total porosity (%)	Quickly drainable pores (QDP) $> 30 \mu m$	Slowly drainable pores (SDP) (30-9) μm	Water holding pores (WHP) (9-0.2) μm	Fine capillary pores (FCP) $< 0.2 \mu m$			
1.35	46.2	25.3	8.32	6.26	6.32	32.14	21.6	
1.5	38	15.3	6.22	8.32	8.22	16.75	20.4	
1.65	32.3	10.32	4.3	8.3	9.4	10.33	19.6	

percentages of emerged PFF, found to be significantly different based on soil compaction and SM (soil compaction; $F=67.20$, $df=2$, $p=0.000$, SM; $F=335.03$, $df=1$, $p=0.0001$), followed by a significant interaction between them ($F=67.20$, $df=1$, $p=0.0001$). Emerged flies were negatively in a significant partial relation with soil compaction level ($r= - 0.61$, $p=0.004$) and SM ($r= - 0.80$, $p=0.000$). In parallel, the percentages of emerging flies found to be significantly affected more by SM than soil compaction level (SM; $F=33.29$, $df=1$, $p=0.000$, soil compacting; $F=10.71$, $df=1$, $p=0.004$). According to R^2 values, 61.8 and 36.1% of effects on adult emergence out of the soil results to SM and soil compacting, while 74.65% results from their combined effects ($F=30.45$, $df=2$, $p=0.000$). Side by side, the results in Table (3) show that the increased soil compaction level (BD) caused a significant decrease in the total porosity (TP) to be 38 and 32.3% compared with 46.2% for C0, un-compacted soil. As well, a significant decrease in quickly drainable pores (QDP), slowly drainable pores (SDP) and Ksat with proportional increasing to soil compaction level, while a significant increase was observed in water holding pores (WHP) and fine capillary pores (FCP). The observed changes in pore size distribution were soil correlated with the emerged flies of PFF; the emerged flies correlated negatively with FCP ($r=-0.57^*$), while they related positively with the total soil porosity (%) ($r=0.57^*$), QDP ($r=0.59^*$), SDP ($r=0.55^*$), Ksat ($r=0.59^{**}$).

The present findings elucidate that the burrowing depth of PFF larvae downwards the soil show to be affected by soil type, the highest mean pupation depth was 2-3 cm in both clay and loamy soils, and 0-1 cm in sandy soil. Obtained results are in agreement with the results of Montoya *et al.* (2008) in which they found that the most larvae of *A. ludens* (Loew), and *A. obliqua* (Macquart) (Diptera: Tephritidae), burrow in the loamy-sand soil by 1.0 to 2.0 cm depth. Dimou *et al.* (2003) reported that the deepest mean of pupation depth of *B. olive* was 3.2 cm. Furthermore, Jackson *et al.* (1998) found that in a dry sand soil, most pupae of *B. dorsalis* occurred at 0–5.5 mm depth. Also, on *A. oblique*, a few numbers of larvae and rarely of pupae occurred on the clay-loam soil surface. Interestingly, in all tested soil textures, no pupae of PFF were found deeper than 5 cm. Similarly, in sand-loam soil a rarely pupae of *A. obliqua* (1 pupae) found higher than 5 cm depth (Hodgson *et al.*, 1998). In a clay-loam soil, no pupae of *A. oblique* were found at deeper than 2 cm. However, on *Carpomyia incompleta* Becker (Diptera: Tephritidae), the highest pupation depth was about 5 cm (Risk *et al.*, 2013).

In the present studies, emergence of PFF flies was found to be affected more by the burial depth than soil type. Furthermore, percentages of adults emerging out of the soil were negatively correlated with pupal burial depth. This might be attributed to soil weight that may restrict the movement of newly emerged flies through their orienting outwards the soil. These results are in the same line with those results that indicated the emergence rate of adult flies was negatively correlated with pupal burial depth of *C. incomplete* (Risk *et al.*, 2013) and *B. oleae* (Rossi) (Diptera: Tephritidae) (Bachouche *et al.*, 2018). On the other hand, soil texture of clayey, sandy loam and sandy clay loam soils has a highly significant impact on the rate of adults emergence of *B. oleae* (Bachouche *et al.*, 2018).

The present findings also clarify that emerging rates of PFF adults outside the soil negatively influenced more by SM than soil compaction. The results reveal the highest rate of emerged flies, 81.67%, attained at the control soil-air-dried soil, which decreased with the increasing of SM, to reach 0 % of emerged flies at 80% moisture at the same soil compaction level. These results are in line with Hou *et al.* (2006), who reported that the pupae of *B. dorsalis* (Hendel) (Diptera: Tephritidae) were unable to survive at soil moisture of 80, 90, and 100%, of FC while emergence rates exceeded 90% at the conditions of 10–60% moisture levels. In contrast of our results, El-Gendy and AbdAlah (2019) reported, at 90%-FC, higher percentages of adult emergence of PFF in un-compacted soil of sandy and clay. The inconsistency among results might be attributed to the variation in the soil texture. Regarding the soil compaction on percentages of emerging flies outside the soil, the present findings show no flies of PFF emerged in moderate or severe compacted soils at low, (20% FC), or high MS levels, (80% FC). The suppression effect of soil compaction on the emerging of flies outside the soil may attributed to the shortage of O₂ as a result of reduced total porosity and macro-pores of the compacted soil (Mosaddeghi *et al.*, 2007). The soil compaction changes the pore size availability and distribution which generally leads to the reduction of the proportion of large pores and affects the movements of larger soil fauna (Nawaz *et al.*, 2013). The change in pore space restricts root growth, and the gas exchange necessary for plant growth and yield (Odey, 2018 and Weber and Biskupski, 2008). In addition, due to the increase in penetration resistance of compacted soils, the burrowing abilities of the emerging adults is reduced (Baize and Jabiol, 1995).

Soil porosity strongly inversely correlate with penetration resistance: a decrease of porosity is generally associated

with an increase of penetration resistance. It is well established that low levels of oxygen increase development time and mortality of *Drosophila melanogaster* Meigen (Diptera: Drosophilidae) (Peck and Maddrell, 2005). However, Cammack *et al.* (2010) mentioned that the soil compaction had no significant effect on the orientation (vertical or

horizontal) of puparia of *Lucilia sericata* (Meigen) (Diptera: Calliphoridae) in the soil. Un-expectedly, the emerged flies of PFF, few numbers, changed their behaviour and oriented deeply downwards the un-compacted soil layer to rim of the bottom cover. This may be result to inability of flies to penetrate the compacted soil.

Figure (1): Relationship between soil type and percentages of pupation depth of *Bactrocera zonata*. LSD. For clay soil=7.44, LSD. For sandy soil=7.84, LSD. For loam soil=7.84.

Figure (2): Adults emergence of *Bactrocera zonata* (%) and pupation depth (cm) in different soil types.

LSD. For clay soil=11.54, LSD. For sandy soil=13.31, LSD. For loam soil=10.98

Figure (3): Relationship among sandy-loamy soil compaction levels, SM and emerged flies of *Bactrocera zonata*

LSD of Levels = 2.68. $LSD_{0.05}$ of RH% = 0.88, LSD of compaction = 0.72.

The dry soil bulk density and associated total porosity are the most frequently used parameter to characterize soil compaction and physical properties of soil (Panayiotopoulos *et al.*, 1994 and Assouline, 2006 a, b). A significant reduction in TP of compacted soil was found as confirmed by the results of Botta *et al.*, 2009; Hassan *et al.*, 2007 and Kuncoro *et al.*, 2014b). However, Several authors, Gebhardt *et al.*, 2009; Kuncoro *et al.*, 2014a and Vogeler *et al.*, 2006, reported that, TP is not good indicator for soil compaction because it is not useful in characterizing compaction effects on storage and transport of water and air in terms of connectivity and continuity. In fact, at a given BD, for the same soil, the pore geometry and continuity can be different (Lenhard, 1986). For example, Marsili *et al.* (1998) found no difference in BD between treatments. The effect of soil compaction was confirmed by air porosity and pore system configuration, i.e. pore size distribution, and Ksat. This observation has been confirmed by Hillel (1998) in which they reported that, soil compaction affected pore diameter and continuity of macropores that directly significantly affected soil hydraulic properties (Odey, 2018; Soracco *et al.*, 2011, 2012, 2015; Lozano *et al.*, 2014 and Etana *et al.*, 2013).

The reduced Ksat of the compacted soil, observed in the current study, might be attributed to the reduction in macro pores, since compaction first reduce mainly large pores (Soracco *et al.*, 2011, 2012, 2015; Odey, 2018; Abdollahi *et al.*, 2014; Gebhardt *et al.*, 2009; Marsili *et al.*, 1998 and Lozano *et al.*, 2014). Etana *et al.* (2013) found that macro-porosity and saturated and near-saturated hydraulic conductivity were smaller in the compacted plots. In contrast, Richard *et al.* (2001) found higher unsaturated Ksat in compacted soil than in un-compacted soil, while Zhang *et al.* (2006) found no significant differences between compacted and un-compacted soils. The inconsistency among results might be due to the differences in soil texture soil moisture and the level/severity of soil compaction. Similarly, Pagliai (1998) observed a significant correlation between hydraulic conductivity and macro-porosity in a loam soil compacted and un-compacted was observed. This observation stressed that the compaction in light textured soils is one of the most significant aspect not only to reduce water movement, in such soils, but also of environmental degradation, since the reduction of water infiltration may increase reduce the risk on nutrients lose to ground water.

The modification in water retention curves, due to soil compaction, was observed in several studies; since a decrease of water content at high matric potentials (from 0 to -10 kPa) and an increase of water content at low matric potentials (from -250 to -1550 kPa) were recorded (Ferrero and Lipiec, 2000). For example, Zhang *et al.* (2006) applied two levels of compaction at two silty loam sites and found that, at the two sites, at high level of compaction, the water content of the surface layer at tensions of <2 kPa and -8 kPa was significantly decreased. However, a slight effect occurs in the intermediate potential range. This reflects the fact that, under compaction, as the proportion of large pores decreases, the proportion of small pores increases (Assouline *et al.*, 1997 and Van Dijck and van Asch, 2002) or remains unaffected (Matthews *et al.*, 2010). Richard *et al.* (2001) showed that the decrease in the volume of pores retaining water between -5 and -20 kPa corresponds to a decrease in the volume of pores larger than 4 mm. In the same way, they attributed the increase in pore volume retaining water at potentials ranging between -20 and -80 kPa to increase in the volume of pores between 1 and 4 mm. They suggested that the increase in water retained at potentials between -20 and -80 kPa is due to the formation of relict structural pores being remnants of structural pores distorted during traffic and accessible only through the necks of textural (lacunar) pores (Richard *et al.*, 2001).

It is concluded that, the results showed that no pupae of PFF were found beyond the 4th cm of clay soil and the 5th cm of sandy and loamy soils. The emerging flies relied significantly on both pupal depth and soil type, furthermore, emerged flies rates were negatively affected more by soil compaction and water content. Moreover, soil compaction reduced total porosity, air porosity and modified the pore system by increasing the proportion of larger pores and reducing the portion of micro pores, thus

reduced saturated hydraulic conductivity. The reduced total and air porosity reduced O_2 availability and thus the number of emerging flies was significantly reduced. Generally, moderate soil compaction significantly suppressed the PFF population therefore soil compaction could be a win-win solution in light soils through enhancing soil hydraulic properties and as an effective approach in integrated pest management (IPM) against PFF.

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Chemical properties of Egyptian fennel honey in Upper Egypt.

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Abstract:

This study was conducted during flow season of fennel honey in the year, 2018, to assess some quality properties of the Egyptian fennel honey produced from Upper Egypt. Forty-two honey samples were obtained from different apiaries located in Assiut and Qena Governorates, Upper Egypt. Moisture content was 18.395%, with range between 17.0 and 19.5%. The total acidity was 38.61 meq. /kg. of honey, with range from 25.5 to 48.0 meq. /kg. of honey. Fructose content was 44.571%, with range between 41.1 and 49.8%. Glucose content was 31.195%, with range from 24.4 – 33.2%. Trace amounts of sucrose were detected in most of fennel honey samples with an average of 0.9%. Maltose content was 1.176%, with range between 0.6 and 1.6%. Hydroxy methyl furfural (HMF) content was 4.96 mg/ kg. of honey, with range from 1.92 to 7.68 mg/ kg. of honey. The diastase number in the tested fennel honey samples was 54.31 Goth units, with range between 8.5 and 150.0 Goth units. The invertase content in the examined fennel honey samples was 167.34 unit/kg, with range from 117.6 to 219.3 unit/kg. of honey.

Introduction

Honey is a natural sweet material all over the world and viscous liquid produced by honeybee [*Apis mellifera* L. (Hymenoptera: Apidae)] that collect the nectar from blossoms, secretions of plants and from secretions of some plant sucking insect. The three major components of honey are fructose, glucose and water. In addition, some other sugars, proteins, vitamins, enzymes, organic acids, polyphenols and inorganic compounds including trace elements necessary for vital processes (Soares *et al.*, 2008). Abou-shaara (2015)

reviewed a list of the common plants in Egypt and their potential benefit to honeybee colonies, which could aid in better understanding of the suitable Egyptian flora for honeybees and guide researchers mainly during their melissopalynological studies. He showed that most potential honeybee plants are belong to first group (medicinal, aromatic and ornamental plants) with 35.2% of total plants, followed by vegetables (34.1%), fruits (21.9%) and field crops (8.8%), respectively. He also noticed that honeybees can benefit from *Foeniculum vulgare* (fennel) as a good

food source (pollen and nectar). Colour, EC, acidity, ash content and pH were the physicochemical parameters with higher discrimination power in the differentiation of nectar and honeydew honeys from central Spain. It was found that physicochemical data were not useful for distinguishing between collection places (Soria *et al.*, 2004). Solayman *et al.* (2016) described physicochemical properties, minerals, trace elements, and heavy metals in some honey samples of different origins. The higher moisture in honey content, the greater is the possibility that the yeasts will ferment and change the flavor. Namely, fermentation process results in alcohol formation and in the presence of oxygen, the alcohol will break down to acetic acid and water, which causes honey to have sour taste and to spoil. Diverse types of honey are produced in Egypt. Fennel honey is a monofloral honey produced from medical fennel plant (*Foeniculum vulgare vulgare*), which is cultivated in Egypt, especially in Assiut and Qena Governorates, Upper Egypt. This study oriented to assess the chemical properties of Egyptian fennel honey.

Materials and methods

The present investigation was carried out through flow season of fennel honey during the year, 2018. The chemical properties were conducted in Apiculture Research Department, Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza. Samples of fennel honey were collected during 2018 from Assiut and Qena, Upper Egypt where fennel honey is traditionally produced. Forty-two fennel honey samples were collected; twenty-one samples per area (three honey samples/apiary). Each of the honey samples were acquired at 1000 g for the present investigation. Honey samples collection was conducted during May 2018. All honey samples were supplied by the professional beekeepers.

Sixteen chemical properties were studied in the obtained fennel honey samples. The chemical parameters which evaluated included: moisture, pH value, free acidity, lactone, total acidity, glucose, fructose, sucrose, maltose, reducing sugars, total sugars, glucose/ fructose ratio, glucose/ water ratio, hydroxy methyl furfural, diastase number, invertase and glucose oxidase. The refractometer was used to determination, the readings of refractive index, after correction for temperature, were converted to moisture (%), using the table of White *et al.* (1962). pH was measured by "HANNA" pH- meter, model H19321, according to (A.O. A. C., 1995). Free acidity, lactone content and total acidity were measured according to White *et al.* (1962).

The examined parameters were calculated as follows:

Free acidity= (ml Na OH to bring solution to pH 8.5- blank) \times 0.05 \times 1000/10;

Lactone= (10- titer of Hcl) \times 0.05 \times 1000/ 10;

And total acidity= free acidity+ lactone.

Honey acidity is a parameter which comprise pH value, free acids, Lactone content and total acidity. Collected fennel honey samples were analyzed to evaluate their sugars content. Fructose, glucose, sucrose and maltose content (%) was identification and determined using High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), according to A.O. A. C. (1995). Reducing sugars and glucose/ fructose ratio (G/F) were also calculated.

Hydroxy methyl furfural (HMF) was determined after clarifying tested honey samples with carrez reagents (I and II) and addition of sodium bisulfate according to A.O.A.C. (1995). Absorbance was determined at 284 and 336 nm in 1cm quartz cuvette using a Labomed, inc. Spectro UV-Vis R.S. Spectrophotometer. HMF is formed in honey by the breakdown of sugars, especially fructose, when honey is stored in hot places for a long time or heated for liquification of granulation. False honey produced from

sucrose treated with weak acids contains high HMF content.

Calculation and expression of results, the transmittance is plotted against time (min) on a rectilinear paper. A straight, line is drawn through at least the three points on the graph to determine the time when the reaction mixture reaches a transmittance of 50%. Divide 300 by the time in minutes to obtain the diastase number (DN). This number expresses the diastase activity as ml 1% starch solution hydrolyzed by the enzyme in gram of honey in 1 hour at 40°C. Invertase activity was spectrophotometrically measured with 4-nitrophenyl- α -D-glucopyranoside and the results are expressed in international units (IU) (Boussaid *et al.*, 2014). Data were analyzed and compared according to method of Waller and Duncan (1969). Least significant differences (LSD) values at 0.05 probabilities were calculated using MSTAT-C software program (MSTAT-C Software program, 1988), and presented as mean \pm SD (standard deviation).

Results and discussion

The moisture (water) content (%) of the honey is very important parameter

because of its effect upon keeping quality (White, 1978). Statistical analysis found that there were significant differences in the moisture content percentages for the studied fennel honey samples between Assiut and Qena Governorates. In general, water content (%) of all analyzed fennel honey samples ranged from 17.0 to 19.5%, with a general mean value of $18.395 \pm 0.235\%$. and accepted by Egyptian Standards (2003) or Codex Alimentarius (2000).

The moisture content of the honey is the most important measured for the assessment of ripeness and shelf life. Moisture content depends on climatic factors, season of production and maturity of honey. Cantarelli *et al.* (2008) found that the water content of some Argentinean honey samples was $16.24 \pm 0.19\%$, ranged from 14.28 – 18.6% (Table, 1). Aloisi (2010) recorded that, the water content of some Argentinean honeys was low, with a mean value of 14.67%. Essa *et al.* (2010) noticed that, the moisture of some Egyptian clover honey samples ranged between 17.5 and 19.25%, with an average of 18.76.

Table (1): Moisture content (%) in fresh fennel honey samples from Assiut and Qena Governorates.

Moisture % NO. of sample	Assiut		Qena		General Mean \pm SE
	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean	Standard Deviation	
1	19.5	0.1	17.0	0.2	
2	19.5	0.2	17.5	0.2	
3	18.0	0.1	17.5	0.1	
4	18.5	0.2	18.5	0.2	
5	19.0	0.19	17.0	0.1	
6	19.0	0.1	18.5	0.1	
7	18.5	0.29	19.5	0.3	
Total (n-7)	132.0		125.5		257.5 (n=14)
Mean \pm SD	18.86 \pm 0.556 a		17.93 \pm 0.932b		18.395 \pm 0.235
Maximum	19.5		19.5		19.5
Minimum	18.0		17.0		17.0

Means not sharing a common superscript letter in row are significantly different at 5% level of probability.

Moniruzzaman *et al.* (2013) found that, the water content of some Malaysian honeys ranged between 11.59 and 19.06%. Musa *et al.* (2014) recorded that the mean value of the moisture content of some Sudanese honeys was 18.2 %. El-Metwally (2015) noticed that the moisture content of some Egyptian honeys ranged between 12.0 and 24.8%, with grand mean value of 17.26%. Valdes-Silverio *et al.* (2018) noticed that the moisture content of eucalyptus honey from the Andean region of Ecuador ranged between 11.74±1.79 and 19.42±1.81%.

The moisture content of honey depending on the botanical origin of the honey, the level of maturity achieved in the hive, processing techniques and storage conditions (Yucel and Sultanoglu, 2013). The moisture content is one of the most important characteristics influencing physical properties of honey such as crystallization and viscosity as well as other parameters: flavor, taste, specific gravity, solubility and conservation (Escuredo *et al.*, 2013).

Acidity participate not only in the flavor of honey but also to its antimicrobial

specialty. In the face of the acidity of honey is eligible, when the acidity increases very rich, the honey becomes tart. The acid content in honey is characterized by the free acidity. Statistical analysis showed that, the pH and free acidity of fennel honey samples obtained from Assiut Governorate and samples collected from Qena Governorate was not significant. On the contrary, lactone and total acidity content of fennel honey samples collected from Assiut and that obtained from Qena was statistically insignificant (Table, 2). Generally. The pH values of the examined fennel honey samples ranged from 4.1 to 4.8, with a general rate value of 4.514 ± 0.054. The free acidity ranged between 19.5 and 31.5 meq. /kg., with an average value of 25.179 ± 1.120 meq. /kg. The lactone content ranged from 6.0 to 17.5 meq. /kg., with a general rate value of 13.429 ± 0.822 meq. /kg. The total acidity of analyzed fennel honey samples ranged from 25.5 to 48.0 meq/kg., with a general rate value of 38.607 ± 1.853 meq/kg.

Table (2): Statistical analysis of acidity of fennel honey samples from (Assiut and Qena), Upper Egypt.

Location	PH	Free acidity	Lactone	Total acidity
Assiut	4.457± 0.056 a	25.14 ±4.22 a	13.93±1.902 a	39.07±5.898a
Qane	4.587± 0.146 a	25.21±4.499 a	12.93±4.036 a	38.1±8.295 a
TotalN=14	63.2	352.5	188.0	540.5
General Mean ± SE	4.514 ± 0.054	25.179± 1.120	13.429± 0.822	38.607± 1.853
Maximum	4.8	31.5	17.5	48.0
Minimum	4.1	19.5	6.0	25.5

Means not sharing a common superscript letter in column are significantly different at 5% level of probability.

It was noticed that the acidity of the studied fennel honey samples with collected from both Assiut and Qena Governorates are within the normal ranges of Egyptian Standard (2003) which states that the total acidity content of honey is ≤ 40 meq. (milliequivalents) /kg. Meanwhile, Codex Alimentarius (2000) increased the maximum amount of total acidity to be 50 meq. /kg.

Our results were in harmony with White (1978) who stated that honey was

characteristically quite acidic. pH value of honey is affected somewhat by the amount of the various acids present, but mostly by the mineral contents (Codex Alimentarius, 2000). Essa *et al.* (2010) found that the pH of studied clover honey samples ranged from 3.7 to 4.15. The results of this study are also agreement with those of Hussain (1989) who found that the pH of fresh honey ranged between 3.0 and 5.0. Fatehe (2013) found that pH values ranged 3.4 – 3.78, lactone

content ranged 1.0 – 12.5 meq/kg., free acidity ranged 28.0 – 68.0 meq/kg. and total acidity content ranged 29.0 – 75.5 meq/kg. of some Egyptian honey types. Dinkov (2014) mentioned that, the mean value of pH was 4.76 ± 0.06 and free acidity was 25.3 ± 1.33 meq./kg. of Bulgarian fennel honey. El-Metwally (2015) found that, the pH values ranged 3.28 – 5.33, with a mean value of 3.91. The total acidity ranged from 16.5 to 70.75 meq/kg., with an average value of 33.56 meq/kg. of some Egyptian honey types. El Sohaimy *et al.* (2015) recorded that, the PH values of Egyptian, Yemen, Saudi and Kashmir were 4.415 ± 0.09 , 4.114 ± 0.02 , 4.46 ± 0.02 and 4.637 ± 0.03 , respectively. Tesfaye *et al.* (2016) found that the pH values ranged 3.54 – 3.92, with an average value of 3.75, while free acidity ranged 29.55 – 36.09 meq/kg. of some honey types obtained from Ethiopia. Valdes-Silverio *et al.* (2018) reported that, the pH values ranged 3.61 – 4.2 and free acidity ranged 27.74 – 229.63 meq/kg. Of some honey samples collected from the Andean region of Ecuador.

Both active acidity pH and total acidity are properties used to characterize the quality of the honey. But pH of the honey is not directly related to the free acidity because of the buffering action of the various acids and minerals present in the honey. The pH of honey might be attributed to the content of acids, mainly gluconic acids and minerals. The pH value of honey is of great importance during storage, since the acidity can influence the texture, stability and shelf life of honey (Amril and Ladjama, 2013). It has been concluded that high free acidity values can indicate the fermentation of honey sugar by yeasts. It is well known that during fermentation, fructose and glucose are converted into alcohol and carbon dioxide. Alcohol is further hydrolyzed in the presence

of oxygen and converted to acetic acids. This greatly contributes to the level of free acidity in honey (Ajlouni and Sujirapinyokul, 2010).

Honey is primarily a carbohydrate product, and their content of sugars may make up as much, as 99% of total soluble solids of honey. Sugars are also responsible for much of the physical properties of honey, such honey viscosity, granulation, energy value and hygroscopic (White, 1978 and Codex Alimentarius, 2000). Honey is a mixture of principally two reducing sugars namely glucose and fructose giving it similar properties to invert syrup. This gives it the ability to remain liquid for long times (Tewodros *et al.*, 2013).

Generally, the sugar composition of 42 Egyptian fennel honey samples was analyzed as shown in Table (3). This investigation affirms that the percentages of fructose and glucose of all the tested fennel honey samples were ranged from 41.1 – 49.8%, with a general mean value of $44.571 \pm 0.708\%$ and from 24.4 – 33.2%, with an average value of $31.195 \pm 0.601\%$, respectively. The predominant sugar of the fennel examined honey was fructose followed by glucose. Meanwhile, sucrose and maltose were present in very low amounts in all analyzed Egyptian fennel honey samples. Obviously, a high sucrose level usually means a premature harvest of honey as sucrose has not been fully inverted to fructose and glucose by the effect of invertase. It was noticed that the sucrose percentage of all the honey samples was less than the maximum conventional limit of 5% recommended by the European Community (European Economic Community, 2002). The reducing sugars (F+G) of all examined Egyptian fennel honey samples ranged between 65.5 and 82.4%, with general mean value of $75.779 \pm 1.112\%$.

Table (3): Statistical analysis of sugar content (%) of Egyptian fennel honey samples obtained from the studied localities (Assiut and Qena), Upper Egypt.

Sample	Fructose	Glucose	Sucrose	Maltose	F+G	F/G	G/W	G/F	F -G	(G -W)/ F
Assiut	43.286 ± 1.132 b	31.96 ± 0.690 a	0.971 ± 0.690 a	1.261 ± 0.209 a	75.243± 0.980 a	1.354± 0.053 a	1.695± 0.078 a	0.741± 0.031 a	11.33 ± 1.599 b	0.303 ± 0.030 a
Qena	45.857± 3.171 a	30.429± 3.030 a	0.829 ± 0.645 a	1.093 ± 0.259 a	76.314± 5.992 a	1.507± 0.164 a	1.697± 0.231 a	0.664± 0.036b	15.43± 1.587 a	0.27 ± 0.060 a
Total (N=14)	624	464.543	12.6	16.48	1060.543	19.96	23.744	9.814	187.3	4.018
General Mean ±SD	44.571 ±0.708	31.195 ±0.601	0.9 ± 0.173	1.176 ± 0.065	75.779 ±1.112	1.426 ±0.034	1.696 ±0.044	0.701 ±0.013	13.38 ±0.700	0.287 ±0.013
Maximum	49.8	33.2	1.8	1.6	82.4	1.51	1.92	0.79	17.2	0.352
Minimum	41.1	24.4	0.5	0.6	65.5	1.27	1.32	0.60	8.7	0.144

Means not sharing a common superscript letter in column are significantly different at 5% level of probability

All examined fennel honey samples had fructose to glucose (F/G) ratios more than 1.0. The average value of F/G was 1.426 for honey samples obtained from Upper Egypt. Glucose to water ratios (G/W) ranged between 1.32 and 1.92, with a mean value of $1.696 \pm 0.044\%$. Most analyzed fennel honey samples had glucose to water (G/W) ratios less than 2.0 that are not granulating honeys. Fennel honey samples collected from Upper Egypt had glucose to fructose (G/F) ratios less than 1.0 and ranged from 0.60 to 0.79. The Fructose – glucose (F – G) ranged from 8.7 to 17.2, with an average value of 13.38 ± 0.7 . The (glucose – water) to fructose ratios ((G – W)/F) ranged between 0.144 and 0.352, with a mean value of 0.287 ± 0.013 . The general average value of F/G ratio was 1.426 ± 0.034 . Fructose to glucose ratio tells about the crystallization status of honey, when fructose is more than glucose the honey will be fluid (Venir *et al.*, 2010). Also, it has been reported that the fructose to glucose ratio may also have an effect on the honey taste since fructose is much sweeter than glucose (Alvarez-Suarez *et al.*, 2010). The general mean values of glucose to water (G/W), glucose to fructose (G/F), and (glucose – water)/ fructose ((G-W)/F) ratios for all analyzed Egyptian fennel honey samples were 1.696, 0.701 and 0.287, respectively. Also, the fructose – glucose (F-G) was calculated for all examined fennel honey samples. The general mean value of F-G was $13.38 \pm 0.70\%$.

The values of sugars contents obtained in this investigation agreed particularly with those of some researchers. Nafea *et al.* (2009) concluded that fructose content ranged 34.9 – 42.3%, glucose 26.2 – 32.2% sucrose 1.3 - 5.3% and maltose 5.0 - 11.0% of various Libyan honey samples. Fatehe (2013) reported that fructose ranged 28.0 - 40.0%, glucose 29.9 – 42.0%, sucrose 0.46 – 3.1% and maltose 1.95 – 4.9% of different Egyptian honey types. El-Metwally (2015) noticed that the mean values of

fructose, glucose and total reducing sugars were 33.33, 28.24 and 61.56%, respectively of some Egyptian honey samples. El Sohaimy *et al.*, (2015) found that the total reducing sugars were 69.84 ± 0.31 , 64.21 ± 0.18 , 72.36 ± 0.32 and $65.11 \pm 0.25\%$ of Egyptian, Yemeni, Saudi and Kashmiri honey samples, respectively. The estimated fructose to glucose ratios for the same investigated honey samples were ranged between 0.42 and 2.35. While, the estimated glucose to water ratios were ranged from 0.72 to 1.56.

Although, all samples in this study with F/G ratio ≥ 1.0 indicates a tendency to granulate rapidly, it is noted that, the fennel honey is not granulated no matter how long it is stored. However, as suggested by other researchers (Manikis and Thrasivoulou, 2001), F/G ratio may not be the best indicator of granulation tendency. Glucose and fructose constituted the primary sugars in all honey. The percentage of fructose should exceed that of glucose in honey of good quality (Kaakeh and Gadelhak, 2005). Honey samples with a glucose- water to fructose ((G-W)/F) ratio higher than 0.5 predicted rapid granulation and a ratio less than 0.2 predicted slow granulation (Manikis and Thrasivoulou, 2001). The prediction accuracy of glucose, fructose and sucrose percentages are useful for the identification of the botanical origin of honey (Persano Oddo *et al.*, 1995 and Persano Oddo and Piro, 2004).

The total monosaccharide content or reducing sugars (sum of glucose and fructose) is useful for the discrimination of some monofloral honeys and between honeys of nectar and honey dew origin (Persano Oddo and Piro, 2004). And to the determination of adulteration (Doner *et al.*, 1979 and Low and South, 1995). Reducing and non-reducing sugars together account for 85-95% of honey's carbohydrate and their amount depend on the source of nectar (Cavian, 2002). Fructose and glucose and the ratio of their preponderance is a factor in

determining the honey suitability for diabetes management (Escuredo *et al.*, 2011). Generally, the sugar spectrum of honey depends upon the sugars present in the nectar and the enzymes present in the bee and nectar (White and Doner, 1980; Zafar *et al.*, 2008 and Bogdanov, 2009).

Hydroxy methyl furfural (HMF) is, actual, a good indicator of honey purity and freshness (Codex Alimentarius, 2000). High levels of HMF in honey samples indicate poor storage or overheating conditions. HMF

is a broken-down product of some sugar solution, especially those containing fructose and glucose stored for long time or at high temperature. HMF contents in fennel honey samples that obtained from Upper Egypt it had a range from 1.92 to 7.68 mg/ kg., with a mean value (4.96 ± 0.591 mg/ kg). The average level of HMF was very low for all the fennel honey samples. This result attributed to freshness and good practices by beekeeper (Table, 4).

Table (4): Hydroxy methyl furfural (HMF) content of fennel honey samples from Upper Egypt.

HMF NO. of sample	Assiut		Qena		General Mean ± SE
	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean	Standard Deviation	
1	5.76	0.009	1.92	0.02	
2	7.68	0.020	1.92	0.01	
3	3.84	0.010	7.68	0.02	
4	5.76	0.000	3.84	0.02	
5	5.76	0.010	1.92	0.01	
6	3.84	0.002	4.16	0.01	
7	7.68	0.009	7.68	0.01	
Total (n=7)	40.32		29.12		
mean ± SD	5.75± 1.568 a		4.16 ± 2.580 b		4.96± 0.591
Maximum	7.68		7.68		
Minimum	3.84		1.92		

Means not sharing a common superscript letter in row are significantly different at 5% level of probability.

The obtained results in this investigation agreed with certain previous studies and contracted with some others. According to the International Trade Guidelines European Economic Committee, 2002 and Egyptian standard, 2003.

Hassan (1985) reported that, HMF in the fresh Egyptian honeys were zero. Bogdanov (2002) concluded that HMF is generally not present in fresh honey and its content increases during conditioning and storage depending on the PH value and temperature of storage. Tharasyvoulou (1986) found that the mean HMF content of honey obtained from Greek increased from zero to 8.8 mg/ kg. After 12 months of storage. Moniruzzaman *et al.* (2013)

reported that, the HMF contents in some Malaysian honeys ranged between 6.07 and 67.94 mg/ kg. Fatehe (2013) found that the HMF concentrations in certain Egyptian honey samples ranged from zero to 13.44 mg/ kg., El-Metwally (2015) recorded that the HMF content in investigated Egyptian honey samples was 15.05 mg/kg. Tesfaye *et al.* (2016) found that the HMF concentrations of some Ethiopian honey samples ranged from 27.1 to 40.8 mg/kg. with a mean value of 36.35±0.68 mg/kg. Lawal *et al.* (2017) reported that the HMF contents of certain Nigerian honey samples ranged between 12.77 and 62.6 mg/kg. Valdes-Silverio *et al.* (2018) concluded that the HMF concentrations of some honey samples

collected from Ecuador ranged from 3.46 to 172.53 mg/kg.

All analyzed fennel honey samples in this investigation were within the international limits (<40 mg/kg.). This result may be due to freshness and good practices by beekeepers. Also, these low values of HMF might be attributed to the climatic conditions of Upper Egypt region, unlike honey samples from tropical and subtropical countries which have naturally high HMF content due to the high temperature (White, 1978).

It has been demonstrated that the HMF parameter is correlated to the quality of the honey and its heat processing but not related to its origin (Anklam, 1998). Many factors influence the content of HMF such as storage conditions (especially the temperature) and floral origins (Fallico *et al.*, 2004 and Meda *et al.*, 2005). Also, the HMF level in honey depends on the sugar type present in honey like fructose: glucose ratio (Doner, 1979). It is well known that heating

of honey results in the HMF formation, which is produced during acid-catalyzed dehydration of hexoses, such as glucose and fructose (Tosi *et al.*, 2002).

HMF value of honey is quality criteria for testing and as index of heat treatment processing of honey and prolonged shelf life of honey. The HMF content is used as standard for testing honey's freshness and overheating of the honey. Diastase activity is measured as the diastase number (Hooper, 1983). The starch-digesting enzymes of honey are used as indicators of honey quality because of their heat sensitivity (Subramanian *et al.*, 2007). The diastase activity of the studied Egyptian fennel honey samples ranged from 8.5 to 150.0 both units (Table,5) . With a general mean value of 54.31 units on the both scales. Invertase is a natural honey enzyme which is commonly used in Europe as a determinant of freshness. Invertase level depends on the geographic and floral origins of the honey.

Table (5): Enzymes activity of Egyptian fennel honey samples from Upper Egypt.

Sample	Assiut		Qena	
	Diastase	Invertase	Diastase	Invertase
1	50.0	157.4	33.3	155.8
2	50.0	190.7	150.0	219.3
3	25.0	163.7	75.0	209.8
4	25.0	124.0	60.0	160.5
5	37.5	117.6	75.0	198.7
6	100.0	143.0	8.5	122.4
7	21.4	189.1	50.0	190.7
Total (n=7)	308.9	1085.5	451.8	1257.2
Mean ± SD	44.129 ± 27.334 b	155.07 ± 28.932 b	64.54 ± 44.480 a	179.6 ± 34.591 a
Range	21.4 – 100	117.6 -190.7	8.5 - 150	122.4 -219.3

The invertase activity of tested Egyptian fennel honey samples obtained from Upper Egypt ranged from 117.6 to 219.3 unit/kg, with a general mean value of 167.34 unit/kg honey.

The purpose of this research work is to assess the main characteristic features of Egyptian fennel honey. The obtained results aimed to proffer some advisable suggestions towards beekeepers and honey producers. The

obtained results found that the chemical properties of Egyptian fennel honey are compatible with most of the international standard specifications.

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Evaluation of some environmentally safe methods for controlling common land snail species at Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate
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Snails, *Monacha cantiana* , *Cochlicella acuta* , guava orchard, cultural and mechanical methods and control.

Abstract:

Several experiment under field condition were conducted to study some safe methods for population management of common land snail species on guava trees .During 2017 and 2018 land snail species were surveyed in guava orchard and some cultural and mechanical methods were evaluated against land snails in Sedy Salem district, Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate, *Monacha cantiana* (Montague) (Gastropoda: Hygromiidae) and *Cochlicella acuta* (Müller) (Gastropoda: Cochlicellidae) snails a dominant species on guava orchard and *M.cantiana* recorded the highest density then *C. acuta* .Through spring *M.cantiana* recorded 281.0 and 319.0 during while *C. acuta* recorded lowest density 171.0 and 202.0 animal during winter in two seasons. Controlling these species under field conditions by using some safety methods to avoid chemical control by applied soil ploughing process as agricultural control and using barriers as attractive baits and circles lime as a mechanical control. Results revealed that , soil ploughing process gave the highest reduction percentages where recorded decreasing in population from first day of application (82.7 and 70.6%) , (82.2 and 72.0 %) , (81.4 and 47.4%) , (58.9 and 46.4%) and (55.7 and 29.3%) for *M. cantiana* and *C. acuta* and (69.0 and 32.6 %) , (68.1 and 43.1%) ,(62,1 and 44.0 %) and (63.6 and 47.0 %) and (53.9 and 39.0 %) during two season 2017 and 2018. The applied of certain barriers as attractive baits and circles lime was more effective in reducing population where gave general mean(62.8 and 47.4 %) for circle lime and (44.2 and 47,6 %) for attractive baits during two seasons , respectively . Generally, it could be recommended that soil ploughing processes as cultural control method gave high reduction in population density of land snail pests .

Introduction

Terrestrial molluscus has been become one of the most serious pests in different localities especially north Delta region . In addition to some gastropod are intermediate hosts for many parasitic worms investing man

and his domestic animals (Godan,1983). In recent years terrestrial molluscus has been most serious pests years, terrestrial snails have increased rapidly in all crops causing economic damage in field crops ,vegetables

as well as horticultural crops. In Egypt ,land snails were detected in different governorate attacking many economic crops. For instance , *Helicella vestalis* (Pfeiffer), *Monacha cantiana* (Montague) (Gastropoda: Hygromiidae) and *Theba pisana* (Müller) (Gastropoda: Helicidae) were most injurious in Egypt (Kassab and Daoud,1964). On the other hand, many authors surveyed land snail species at Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate and reclaimed lands at northern regions of Egypt (Hashem *et al.*,1992; 1993a , b; Shahawy,1998 and Abd El-Karim, 2000) . They found different species of land snails on orchards , vegetables , ornamentals and field crops and it caused great damage crops , so control of these pests by safety methods to avoid environmental contamination was necessary .Roughly ploughed soil before sowing seeds was decreased the damage of seeds caused snails (Wouters,1970). Recent studies indicated that the snails , *M. cantiana* and *Cochlicella acuta* (Müller) (Gastropoda: Cochlicellidae) is the most abundant snails in all localities at Kafr El-Sheikh governorate. Therefore, we need applied some methods to control these pests. The present work was carried out to throw light on efficacy of some cultural and mechanical methods to decrease the population of snail species on guava trees during spring 2017 and 2018.

Materials and methods

1. Survey and population densities of land snail species:

Monthly snail samples collected early morning from guava trees orchards through 2017 and2018 in Abu Abdall village ,Sedy Salem district ,Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate .Ten trees were randomly chosen and marked as permanent sampling sites then snails collected from one meter around chosen trees and on five branches of the different direction of the tree at one-meter height of trunk ,(Awad, 1994), collection snails were identified according to Godan (1983) .

2. Effect of soil ploughing process :

Six kirat cultivated with Guava trees at Abu-Abdalla village ,Sedy Salem district ,Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate during 2017 and 2018 seasons ,were chosen to estimate the efficacy of ploughing soil beside and under trees on the population of *M. cantiana* and *C. acuta* land snail species . In this respect ,three kirats were subjected to ploughing using hydrolic plough machine tractive by tractor at depth of 25-30 cm under soil under . On the other hand , the three kirats were left without plowing . five trees in both of plowing and unplowing were chosen . The population density of snails were recorded in area of 50x50 cm under chosen ten trees from each karate in both of plowing and un plowing areas before plowing and the first day after plowing then the count was continued weekly for six weeks (during the period from April 13th till May 26th to first season 2017 and from 10th April to 24th May to second season after plowing) . The percentage of reduction in population density of land snail species were calculated using formula of Handerson and Tilton (1955).

3.Effect of attractive bait barriers and circle lime :

The effect of attractive baits and circle lime in reducing population density of *M. cantiana* and *C.acuta* snails infesting guava trees were study during April and May in two seasons .This study was carried out in guava orchards highly infested ,an area of about half feddan was chosen for this study .Two types of barriers were used , the first consists of attractive baits and the second from lime .The circles from attractive baits and lime were put around trees trunks on ground ,five replicates to each treatment were chosen and five trees left without any treatment as a control .All snails on trees and leaves were recorded before application. The population were counted before application and in 1 , 7 ,14 ,21 and 28 days after applied . Percent of reduction of snails were calculated according to the formula of Handerson and Tilton (1955)

Results and discussion

1. Population density of land snail species:

For two years 2017 and 2018 snail survey, defined and the number movement were recorded, and this survey showed that , two species of snails were found in the treated orchard , *M. cantiana* and *C. acuta* . The population density through the year monthly summarized in Table (1) and the obtained data cleared that *M. cantiana* recorded the highest number through May in two years 2017 and 2018 , respectively and the average density was 81 snails in Jun. The lowest average was 58.5 snail in December . The density of *C. acuta* reached maximum

through Apr. 96.0 snail in 2017 and 94.0 snail during May in 2018 (average were 108 snail) then recorded the minimum number 54.0 snail in Dec. and 56.0 animal in Oct.(average number 58.0 animals in Dec. ,to each year respectively .Eshra (2004) found that, *Eobania vermiculata* (Müller) (Gastropoda: Helicidae), *T. pisana* , *H.vestalis* and *C. acuta* recorded the highest population during spring and summer in Jun , July and August on orange ,banana, guava and grape trees investigated area in Alexandria and El-Beheira Governorates through 1999 and 2000.

Table (1) : Average density of land snail species infested guava orchard in Sedy Salem district ,Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate .

Species Months	<i>Monacha cantiana</i>			<i>Cochlicella acuta</i>			Total
	2017	2018	Average	2017	2018	average	
Dec.	62	53	57.5	54	62	85	231
Jan.	58	66	62	60	74	67	258
Feb.	60	89	74.5	57	66	61.5	272
Winter	180	208	194	171	202	186.5	761
Mar.	69	83	76	91	125	108	368
Apr.	94	124	109	96	90	93	404
May	118	112	115	78	94	86	402
Spring	281	319	300	265	309	287	1174
Jun.	93	69	81	68	70	69	300
Jul.	69	74	71.5	54	62	58	259
Sept.	74	91	82.5	80	59	69.5	304
Summer	236	234	235	202	191	196.5	863
Oct.	86	69	120.5	80	56	68	291
Nov.	62	98	80	72	69	70.5	301
Dec.	54	63	58.5	70	62	66	249
Autumn	202	230	259	222	187	204.5	831
Total	899	991	988	860	889	874	3639
Average	224.8	427.8	247	215	222.3	218.5	909.8

2. Effect of soil ploughing process on reducing population snail species on guava trees :

The ploughing process is one of the most cultural method control of land snails specially during spring seasons where all snails reached their maximum activities . Data in Tables (2 and 3) showed that the soil ploughing process decreased the individuals of *M.cantiana* and *C.acuta* from the first day post treatment from (96.0 and 51.7 snail to 16.6 and 15.6 snail/m² with reduction of 82.7 and 70.6% , respectively After 7 days

post treatment .The numbers of individual was decreased to (81.0 and 43.2 recording reduction 82.2 and 72.0 %) in the first season 2017. Also, population of snails decreased from (102.0 to 31.0 individual recording 69.6% reduction for *M.cantiana* and 89.0 to 60.0 individuals with 32.6 %reduction for *C.acuta* . The present reduction was decreased after 21 and 28 day post treatment in two seasons , where recorded 58.9 and 55.7 for *M.cantiana* in first season , 63.6 and 53.9 in second season and recorded 46.4 and 29.3 in first season and

47.0 and 39.0 in second season for *C.acuta* , respectively .Generally , It is concluded that, the ploughing process was the simplest and effective method for reducing the numbers of common snail species during spring season .These results agree with those obtained by Wouters (1970) , who mentioned that,

Table (2): Effect of ploughing soil process on reducing of *Monacha cantiana* and *Cochlicella acuta* snails infesting guava trees in Sedy Salem district ,Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate during spring 2017.

Days after ploughing	Mean number of snails							
	Untreated area		Treated area		% Reduction		L.S.D 0.05	
	<i>Monacha cantiana</i>	<i>Cochlicella acuta</i>						
1	102.0	89.0	31.0	60.0	69.6	32.6	15.5	8.8
7	91.0	102.0	29.0	58.0	68.1	43.1	9.2	10.1
14	95.0	116.0	35.0	65.0	62.1	44.0	10.0	10.8
21	98.0	96.0	35.6	51.0	63.6	47.0	10.9	17.9
28	89.0	103.0	41.0	63.0	53.9	39.0	17.9	9.2
Total	475.0	506.0	172.6	297.0	317.3	205.7		
Mean	95.0	101.2	101.2	59.4	63.5	41.1		

Table(3):Effect of soil ploughing process on reducing population of *Monacha cantiana* and *Cochlicella acuta* snails infesting guava trees in Sedy Salem district , Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate during spring 2018.

Days after ploughing	Mean number of snails							
	Untreated area		Treated area		% Reduction		L.S.D. 0.05	
	<i>Monacha cantiana</i>	<i>Cochlicella acuta</i>						
1	96.0	51.7	16.6	15.6	82.7	70.6	10.4	16.9
7	81.0	43.2	14.4	12.1	82.2	72.0	6.8	12.3
14	83.0	36.4	15.4	19.0	81.4	47.4	7.0	7.0
21	72.0	31.7	29.6	17.0	58.9	46.4	10.2	17.3
28	70.0	39.6	31.0	28.0	55.7	29.3	10.4	9.0
Total	402.0	202.4	106.0	91.3	360.9	266.9		
Mean	80.4	41.0	21.2	18.3	72.2	53.4		

3. Effect of attractive baits barriers and circles lime :

The effect of certain barriers as a bait barriers and lime circle as a mechanical method was studied in reducing population density of snail species infesting guava trees during March and April in two season 2017 and 2018. Data in Table (4) showed that the attractive baits were the most effective on reducing population of snail species compared with the live lime circle. The attractive baits barriers were recorded percentage reduction (75.1 , 57.8 , 44.6 , 34.5

roughly ploughed soil before sowing seeds of winter weather protected seeds from damage caused by land snails. Salem *et al.* (2007) mentioned that the ploughing process decreased the population of *H. vestalis* after one day with reduction 87.8 % , that was increased to 91.6 % after two weeks .

and 8.1% after 1 ,7 ,14 ,21 and 28 , respectively .The live lime circles were recorded percentage reduction , 86.4 ,81.4 ,63.5 ,50.2 and 32.4% , respectively , during 2017 ,while the attractive baits barriers were recorded reduction 74.0 ,51.8 ,42.4 ,38.5 and 31.4% and the live lime circles recorded reduction 63.0 ,58.0 ,45.0 , 36.0 and 35.0% after 1 ,7, 14, 21 and 28 day, respectively. Regarding general mean percentage reduction were 47.6 and 47.4% for two tested methods , respectively during 2018 (Table,5) . These results were agreement with those reported

by many authors. Godan (1983) recorded that , dehydrating substances as protective barriers , such as cattle salt , caustic soda , kainite or completely dry quick lime can act as a barrier. The same author mentioned for slugs, a ridge of finely ground lime around seed beds but moist air is enough to slake the lime and make it effective . Nakhla (1995)

illustrated that, a band of metal sheets around trees trunk such as aluminum sheet, copper sheet wire screen gauze (14 mesh)and fiber cord for protect orchard trees from different land snails .The wire screen rings gave the highest protection followed by copper sheet rings, while aluminum sheet rings gave poor protection.

Table (4) : Effect of certain barriers as a mechanical control method on *Monacha cantiana* and *Cochlicella acuta* snails infesting guava trees in Sedy Salem district ,Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate during spring 2017.

Days after treatment	No. of snails in untreated areas	Mean number of snails in treated areas and reduction percentage			
		Attractive baits		Circle time	
		Mean	Reduction%	Mean	Reduction%
1	40.4	10.2	75.1	5.4	86.4
7	40.2	17.2	57.8	7.4	81.4
14	38.8	21.8	44.6	14	63.5
21	38.2	25.4	34.5	18.8	50.2
28	39.8	31.9	8.1	26.8	32.4
Total	196.4	106.5	220.1	72.4	313.9
Mean	39.4	21.3	44.2	14.5	62.8

Table (5): Effect of certain barriers as a mechanical control method on *Monacha cantiana* and *Cochlicella acuta* snails infesting guava trees in Sedy Salem district ,Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate spring 2018 .

Days after treatment	No. of snails in untreated areas 43.1	Mean number of snails in treated areas and reduction percentage			
		Attractive bait		Circle time	
		Mean 41	Reduction%	Mean 43	Reduction%
1	42.0	7.3	74.0	15.0	63
7	42.3	13	51.8	18.0	58
14	36.7	19.2	42.4	23.2	45
21	35.2	28.6	38.5	25.0	36
28	38.6	23.2	31.4	27.6	35
Total	194.8	91.3	238.1	108.2	237.0
Mean	39.0	18.3	47.6	21.6	47.4

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Effect of sodium carbonate and mint oil as additives on the potency of the entomopathogenic bacteria, *Bacillus thuringiensis* against the cotton leaf worm *Spodoptera littoralis* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae)

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Abstract:

This study aimed to investigate the effect of adding the inorganic salt, sodium carbonate (Na_2CO_3) or mint oil to the bio-insecticide, *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Bay-8, 8% SC) on some of its physico-chemical properties as well as its toxicity in relation to its effect on some biochemical aspects in *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisduval) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae). The results clearly showed that adding 0.1% Na_2CO_3 or 0.3% mint oil to *B. thuringiensis* solution increased its pH value, viscosity and its toxicity against *S. littoralis* 2nd instar larvae, where its LC_{50} value was reduced from 7.079ml/l to 3.972 and 3.549 ml/l after adding Na_2CO_3 or mint oil, respectively. The biochemical studies in the treated larvae with *B. thuringiensis* combined with 0.1% Na_2CO_3 or 0.3% mint oil showed a significant reduction in the total protein content, α -esterase and phenoloxidase activities compared to treatment with *B. thuringiensis* only. The obtained results confirm the effect of Na_2CO_3 and mint oil on the activity of these enzymes towards *B. thuringiensis*, which may explain the increase in the toxicity of *B. thuringiensis* when mixed with either Na_2CO_3 or mint oil against *S. littoralis*.

Introduction

The cotton leaf worm *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisduval) (Lepidoptera:Noctuidae) is considered one of the major destructive pests in Egypt. The larval stage was known as a leaf eater accepting almost all herbaceous plants (Abdel-Wahab, 2002). The wide use of different chemical insecticides for controlling *S. littoralis* caused the development of pesticide resistance (Ishaaya and Klein, 1990). Therefore, there is always a need for an alternative method for controlling the pest

to minimize chemical insecticide's application and avoid the problem of evolved resistance in insect's field populations. *Bacillus thuringiensis* (*B.t.*) is a gram-positive soil bacterium characterized by its ability to produce crystalline inclusions during sporulation. These inclusions consist of protein which exhibited a highly specific insecticidal activity (Höfte and Whiteley, 1989). The main mode of action of this crystalliferous bacterium in different orders of insects was disrupting of the epithelial

lining of the mid-gut (Ignoffo *et al.*, 1981). *B.t.* crystal (d-endotoxin) protein must be ingested, solubilized and activated by larval gut enzymes to form its entomocidal effect (Salama *et al.*, 1984). Additives such as chemical or natural enhancers could be used to potentiate the bio-insecticide, *B.t.* The incorporation of these additives with entomopathogenic bacteria to achieve high efficacy was practiced either to extend the spectrum of activity or to overcome the short persistence of these insecticides in the field (Abdel-Hafez *et al.*, 2013). In addition, in order to increase *B.t.* potency, the conditions prevailing insect mid-gut must be modified. This might be achieved by using alkaline compounds, such as inorganic salts (Salama *et al.*, 1989). Moreover, the addition of vegetable oils could increase either the uptake of the toxicant by the insect or reduce its evaporation dissipation or both. Park and Lee (2007) cleared that low insecticide toxicity in pests may be due to biochemical mechanisms including target site insensitivity to pesticides and increased detoxification rate by enhancing the production of metabolic enzymes. Alteration in the detoxification enzymes might help in overcoming the insecticidal low toxicity that regulated by enzymes, where susceptibility variations were underlined mainly through three important tolerance mechanisms; decreased penetration, enhanced detoxification, and target-site insensitivity (Gunning *et al.*, 1996). Therefore, the current study aimed to investigate the role of each Na_2CO_3 or mint oil in the effect of *B.t.* on some biochemical parameters in *S. littoralis* larvae.

Materials and methods

1. Tested insect:

The 2nd instar larvae of the cotton leaf worm, *S. littoralis* was obtained from a laboratory strain maintained in the Plant Protection Research Institute, Agriculture Research Center, Dokki, Giza. The culture was reared using the technique suggested by El-Defrawi *et al.* (1964).

2. Bioinsecticide:

Common name: *B. thuringiensis* (Berliner) subsp. *kurstaki*. Trade name: Bay-8 (8 % SC). It is a suspension concentrate (8% SC) formulation, that contains 8% lepidopteran active toxin and 92% an inert material. It was produced by global industrial chemical Co., Gintra- Egypt.

Additives:

2.1 Sodium carbonate: Molecular formula: Na_2CO_3 . It was used at concentration 0.1% and it produced by (Adwic) El-Nasr pharmaceutical chemicals Co.

2.2. Vegetable mint oil. It contains menthol, menthone, carvenon, lemonin, and kadene. It was used at concentration 0.3% and it produced by El-captain Co. (CAP Pharm).

2.3. Surfactant agent: Emulsifier (Sisi-6) was used at a concentration 0.3%. It provided by Central Agricultural Pesticides Laboratory (CAPL), Dokki, Giza.

3. Physico-chemical properties:

Some physico-chemical properties were estimated for the solutions of *B.t.* (only or associated with each tested additive). Suspensibility test was conducted to determine the compatibility of the resulting solutions according to WHO (1979) specifications. The pH value was measured through AD 11 pH meter and viscosity was determined by using Ostwald viscometer.

4. Bioassays:

To investigate the interaction between *B.t.* and each of the additives; Na_2CO_3 and mint oil, a series of six aqueous concentrations (1.25, 2.5, 5, 8, 10 and 15ml/L) of *B.t.* were prepared as *B.t.* only or in combination with each 0.1% Na_2CO_3 (Mohamed *et al.*, 2010) or (0.3% mint oil+0.3% emulsifier) according to the method of Abdel- Hafez *et al.* (2013). The leaf-dipping technique using fresh castor bean leaves was used according to the method of Shepard (1958). The percentages mortality

after 3 days of treatment of *S. littoralis* 2nd instar larvae were corrected using Abbott's formula, Abbott (1925). The LC₅₀ values of *B.t.* (only and in combination with each additive) were determined after 3 days of treatment according to the method described by Finney (1971) through LDP line software computerized program. The synergistic ratio (SR) based on the LC₅₀ values was calculated according to the method of Sun and Johnson (1960).

5. Biochemical studies:

5.1. Sample preparation for biochemical analysis:

Three groups of *S. littoralis* 2nd instar larvae were treated with the median lethal concentration (LC₅₀) value of *B.t.* (only or in combination with each tested additive). The 1st group was treated with *B.t.* only while the 2nd group was treated with *B.t.* in combination with 0.1% Na₂CO₃ and the 3rd group was treated with *B.t.* in combination with 0.3% mint oil. The survived healthy treated larvae in the three groups were separated after 5 days of treatment. These healthy treated larvae were starved for 4 hours, then kept frozen (-5°C) until larval homogenation. The larvae were weighted then homogenated in distilled water with the fixed ratio (0.5 gm.b.wt to 10 ml d. water). The samples were centrifuged at 8000 rpm for 15 min undercooling (4°C) to remove the remnant of tissues. The supernatant fluid was divided into small aliquots (0.5 ml) to be used in the enzymes assay. Percentage of change was calculated from the obtained data according to Elhadek *et al.* (2015).

5.2. Determination of total protein content:

Table (1): Physico-chemical properties of *B.t.* solution (only or in combination with each tested additive).

Mixtures	Conc. ml/l + %	Suspensibility (ml of additive separation)	Viscosity *mP	pH value
<i>B.t.</i>	LC ₅₀	0.0	11.1	6.5
<i>B.t.</i> + Na ₂ CO ₃	LC ₅₀ + 0.1	0.0	-----	10.0
<i>B.t.</i> + mint oil	LC ₅₀ + 0.3	0.0	12.0	7.8

*mP = millipoise

Total protein content was determined by the method of Bradford (1976).

5.3. Determination of α -esterase activity:

α -esterase activity was determined according to the method described by Van Asperen (1962) using α -naphthyl acetate as substrate.

5.4. Determination of phenoloxidase activity:

Phenoloxidase activity was determined according to the method of Ishaaya (1971).

6. Statistical analysis:

The data were subjected to analysis of variance using (ANOVA) in SAS program, (SAS Institute, 1998). Mean separation was conducted using the least significant difference (LSD) in the same program at significant level $P \leq 0.05$.

Results and discussion

1. Physico-chemical properties:

Data presented in Table (1) summarized the physico-chemical properties of *B.t.* (Bay-8) only or in combination with each tested additive. Suspensibility test showed that each of the two tested additives was compatible with *B.t.* solution, they gave good suspension without any separation or precipitation at the bottom of the cylinder. In addition, the obtained result indicated that the viscosity of *B.t.* solution increased from 11.1 to 12.0 mP after addition of mint oil additive. The current data clearly showed that the pH value of *B.t.* solution increased from 6.5 to 10 and 7.8 after addition of each Na₂CO₃ and mint oil additives, respectively to be more alkaline. The current results agree with those of Abdel-Hafez *et al.* (2013).

2. Synergistic action of adding each 0.1% Na₂CO₃ and 0.3% mint oil on *B.t.* toxicity against *Spodoptera littoralis* 2nd instar larvae:

The results illustrated in Table (2) showed the LC₅₀ values after 3 days of treatment of *S. littoralis* 2nd instar larvae. Data revealed that the LC₅₀ value (7.079ml/l) of *B.t.* was reduced sharply when combined with 0.1% Na₂CO₃ or 0.3% mint oil to reach 3.972 and 3.549 ml/l, respectively. This synergistic action of Na₂CO₃ may be due to its alkaline nature, which could facilitate the endotoxin breakdown and thereby, the crystals toxic fragments will be released (Nickerson, 1980). Salama *et al.* (1985) reported that augmentation of alkaline compounds concentration in the insect gut might directly affect the crystalline protein solubility. On the other hand, synergistic action of mint oil addition could be attributed to oil properties that might increase toxicity of the insecticide. Natural oil additives may have a significant role in increasing the

persistence of the bio-insecticides on the treated leaves. Bode *et al.* (1976) stated that the synergistic effects of vegetable oils on the bio-insecticide activity might be due to changing its physical properties through increasing its viscosity by oil addition which would increase the insecticide deposit on plant leaves, minimize the drift and enhance the insecticide persistence. In addition, adding vegetable oils might increase the uptake of the toxicant by the insect or reduced its evaporation dissipation or both (Abdel-Hafez and Abdel-Aziz, 2010). Vegetable and mineral oils could increase the adhesion, wetting and spreading properties of pesticides on the surface of the targets, decreasing pesticide loss and improving pest control (Abhilash and Patil, 2006). The present result is agreed with Abdel-Hafez and Abdel-Aziz (2010) and Abdel-Hafez *et al.* (2013) they reported that emulsified oils of targets and sesame enhanced the toxicity and persistence of the *B.t.* bio-products; Protecto, Dipel 2x against *S. littoralis* 2nd instar larvae.

Table (2): Synergistic effect of adding each 0.1% Na₂CO₃ and 0.3% mint oil on *B.t.* toxicity against the 2nd instar larvae of *Spodoptera littoralis* after 3 days of treatment.

Treatments	Time after exposure (days)	LC ₅₀ (ml/l)	95%(FL)		Slope ± SE	*SR
			Lower	Upper		
<i>B.t.</i>	3	7.079	6.458	7.767	3.048±0.235	---
<i>B.t.</i> + Na ₂ CO ₃	3	3.972	2.118	6.066	2.411±0.177	1.782
<i>B.t.</i> + mint oil	3	3.549	2.335	4.805	2.321±0.174	1.995

*SR= Synergistic ratio

3. Biochemical studies:

The effect of the LC₅₀ value of *B.t.* (only or in combination with each tested additive) was evaluated on some biochemical aspects of *S. littoralis* 2nd instar larval body homogenate after 5 days of treatment.

3.1. Total protein content in the treated and untreated larvae of *Spodoptera littoralis*:

Data represented in Table (3) indicated that treatment with *B.t.* and its mixtures with Na₂CO₃ or mint oil showed a significant reduction in total protein content of the treated larvae compared with the untreated one. The percentages of change

were - 11.655, - 20.835 and - 24.446, respectively. The present data also revealed that treatment with *B.t.*-additive mixtures induced significant reduction compared to treatment with *B.t.* only. This reduction of total protein in *B.t.* -additive mixtures may be related to the increased toxicity of its mixtures with both additives than that of treatment with *B.t.* only. According to Ahmed *et al.* (1985) the depletion in protein contents in the treated larvae might be due to binding with foreign compounds as the tested insecticides. El-Shershaby *et al.* (2008) observed that *B.t.* gradually suppressed protein synthesis in *S. littoralis* 4th instar

larvae as post treatment period increased and reached its maximum effect after 120h (5 days) of treatment. The present data coincided with those of Kamel *et al.* (2010) who found that the commercial formulations

Table (3): Total protein content in *Spodoptera littoralis* 2nd instar larval body homogenate after 5 days of treatment with *B.t.* (only or combined with each tested additive).

Treatments	Total protein (mg/gm.b.wt)	
	Mean ± SE	Change %
Control	64.633 ^a ± 0.736	
<i>B.t.</i>	57.100 ^b ± 1.274	- 11.655
<i>B.t.</i> + Na ₂ CO ₃	51.167 ^c ± 0.601	- 20.835
<i>B.t.</i> + mint oil	48.833 ^c ± 0.841	- 24.446
LSD	2.932	-----

Means followed by different letters are significantly different, (P < 0.05).

3.2. α -esterase activity in the treated and untreated larvae of *Spodoptera littoralis*:

Data represented in Table (4) recorded a significant increase in α -esterase activity in the treated 2nd instar larvae of *S. littoralis* with *B.t.* only by percentage of change 10.812 compared with the untreated larvae. The two mixtures, *B.t.*-Na₂CO₃ and *B.t.*-mint oil induced significant reduction in α -esterase activity with percentages of change - 19.831 and - 6.918, respectively compared with the untreated larvae. General esterases are a large and diverse group of hydrolases that hydrolyse numerous substrates including esters and certain non-ester compounds. Numerous studies have demonstrated that esterases play an important role in conferring

Table (4): α - esterase activity in *Spodoptera littoralis* 2nd instar larval body homogenate after 5 days of treatment with *B.t.* (only or combined with each tested additive).

Treatments	α -esterase (μ g α -naphthol/min./gm.b.wt)	
	Mean ± SE	Change %
Control	2491.000 ^b ± 5.859	
<i>B.t.</i>	2760.333 ^a ± 5.783	10.812
<i>B.t.</i> + Na ₂ CO ₃	1997.000 ^d ± 6.245	- 19.831
<i>B.t.</i> + mint oil	2318.667 ^c ± 2.028	- 6.918
LSD	17.171	-----

Means followed by different letters are significantly different, (P < 0.05).

3.3. Phenoloxidase activity in the treated and untreated larvae of *Spodoptera littoralis*:

Results represented in Table (5) showed that treatments with (*B.t.* only, *B.t.*+Na₂CO₃ and *B.t.*+mint oil mixtures) indicated significant increase in the activity of phenoloxidase with

of *B.t.*; Agerin, Dipel 2x and Dipel DF showed significant reduction in total protein contents in larvae of *S. littoralis* after 120h of exposure compared to those in the untreated larvae.

or contributing to insecticide detoxifications in insect and other arthropod species (Mouches *et al.*, 1986). Thus, the increase in this enzyme activity in the present study might be referred to *B.t.* resistance in the treated pest. The current results are in agreement with those of Hamama *et al.* (2015) who reported that treatment with the bio-insecticide, *B.t.* (Profect) resulted in a significant increase in the α -esterase activity in all treated larvae of *S. littoralis* after 48h of exposure compared to the control. In contrast, Rizk (2014) reported that α -esterase activity was significantly decreased after treating the 4th instar larvae with the bio-insecticide; Protecto.

percentages of change 42.405, 16.566 and 33.972, respectively compared to the untreated larvae. Therefore, these data could explain the enhanced toxicity of the tested *B.t.* +additive mixtures than that of *B.t.* only. For that may be using Na₂CO₃ or mint oil interrupted the defense mechanism of the pest

to the bio-agent. The present results are in accordance with those of Valadez-Lira *et al.* (2012) they reported that PO activity in the treated *P. interpunctella* 2nd instar larvae with *B.t.* (Biobit) was 10 times higher than that of the untreated ones. They reported that Insects defend themselves against pathogens through innate mechanisms; as increased phenoloxidase activity. In contrast to the obtained data, Kamel *et al.* (2010) indicated that after 120h of treating *S. littoralis* larvae with the bio-product; Agerin, PO activity was significantly reduced in the treated larvae compared to the untreated ones. Whereas

after 48h of treatment, PO had a greater activity levels in treated larvae. This might be due to PO had been activated once entry of bacteria into the insect hemolymph.

Phenoloxidase is an important component of insect immune systems. Its activity had been shown to be correlated with resistance to some parasites or pathogens across species (Nigam *et al.*, 1997). Using phenoloxidase activity as a physiological parameter might also help in the determination of immune response activation against entomopathogenic microbial infections (Narayanan, 2004).

Table (5): Phenoloxidase activity in *Spodoptera littoralis* 2nd instar larval body homogenate after 5 days of treatment with *B.t.* (only or combined with each tested additive).

Treatments	Phenoloxidase (O.D.units/min./gm.b.wt)	
	Mean ± SE	Change %
Control	6.320 ^d ± 0.117	
<i>B.t.</i>	9.000 ^a ± 0.208	42.405
<i>B.t.</i> + Na ₂ CO ₃	7.367 ^c ± 0.120	16.566
<i>B.t.</i> + mint oil	8.467 ^b ± 0.088	33.972
LSD	0.4591	----

Means followed by different letters are significantly different, (P < 0.05).

It is concluded that the present laboratory investigation suggests that adding Na₂CO₃ or mint oil could enhance *B.t.* performance and it is considered a useful addition for controlling *S. littoralis* larvae affecting its enzymes activity, enhancing its susceptibility to the tested bio-agent and reducing the cost of its control via reducing the insecticidal rates used, but further laboratory, semi-field and open field experiments are still needed to confirm the results.

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Efficacy of some benzothiazole derivatives and their formulation against cotton leafworm *Spodoptera littoralis* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae)

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Abstract:

The present research is conducted to synthesize and evaluate the pesticidal efficacy of 2-(benzo[d]thiazole-2-yl)-3, 3-bis(methylthio) acrylonitrile and their new derivatives against cotton leafworm *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisduval) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) that were obtained by reaction of this compound with different aromatic and heterocyclic amines. 2-(Benzo[d]thiazole-2-yl)-3, 3-bis(methylthio) acrylonitrile (**2**) was considered as promising compound. So that it was formulated and evaluated against the 2nd instar larvae of the cotton leafworm *S. littoralis*. It was found that the latter compound has good efficacy as obtained from its LC₅₀ compared with that of the other derivatives.

Introduction

Several heterocyclic derivatives containing nitrogen and sulphur atoms serve as unique and versatile scaffolds for experimental toxicity design. One of the most important heterocyclic derivatives was benzothiazole that was considered as a weak base having different biological activities and still of great scientific interest now a days. Benzothiazole possess biological activities like anti-tumor (Racan et al., 2012), anti-microbial (Patel and Shaikh, 2010), anti-tubercular (Patel and Khan, 2011), anthelmintic (Munirajasekhar et al., 2011), antifungal (Catalano et al., 2013), antileishmanial (Delmas et al., 2002), antipsychotic (Arora et al., 2010), anti-ulcer (Chaudhary et al., 2010), local anesthetic

(Geronikaki et al., 2009), schistosomicidal (Mahran et al., 2007) and diuretic (Yar and Ansari, 2009). Although, benzothiazole derivatives are of diverse biological activities, only little, to the best of our knowledge, is of agro-applications. For instance; bentaluron, benthiavalicarb, benthiazole, chlobenthiazone and probenazole are used as fungicides, while, benazolin, benzthiazuron, mefenacet and methabenzthiazuron are used as herbicides. Insecticides are in general used in extremely small dosages. The active ingredient of insecticide formula must be distributed over a wide area as possible. So, these chemicals must be formulated. Formulation is the science or art of diluting the insecticide in a

suitable manner for application through appropriate machinery, efficiently, safely and the same time in forms, which are toxic against insects, involved. This prompted us to synthesize a set of benzothiazole modified to assess their efficacy as insecticides and formulating one of the most promising compounds in a suitable formulation type in order to use in the field of insect control [(*Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisduval) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae)] after carrying out the necessary studies in the future.

Materials and methods

1. Experimental:

1.1. Chemistry:

All melting points were uncorrected and measured on a Gallenkamp melting point apparatus. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded with a Perkin–Elmer model 157 infrared spectrophotometer. Mass spectra were acquired with GCMS-QP1000 EX and Jeol JMS600 spectrometers at 70 eV. Elemental analysis was performed by the micro-analytical center of the Faculty of Science, Cairo University. Reaction of ketene (2) with aromatic and heterocyclic amines.

1.2. General procedure:

Equimolar amounts of compound **2** (1 mmol) and amines (1 mmol) in ethanol (15 mL) containing few drops of piperidine were heated under reflux for 4 hrs. The solid product which precipitated was isolated by filtration, dried, and recrystallized from 2:1 ethanol: DMF to afford compounds **3a-j**.

2-(Benzo[d]thiazole-2-yl)-3-(methylthio)-3-(Phenyl amino)acrylonitrile (3a)

This compound was prepared from the reaction of **2** with aniline (0.1 ml, 1 mmol) Yellow crystals; yield 75 %; mp 240-242 °C; IR (KBr): ν/cm^{-1} = 2194 (CN), 3156 (NH), MS m/z (%): 323 (1.72), 308 (1.05), 217 (7.58), 191 (2.13), 135 (6.38), 109 (17.11), 77 (9.32). Anal. Calcd. For $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2$ (323): C, 63.13; H, 4.05; N, 12.99 %; Found: C, 63.26; H, 4.19; N, 12.91 %.

3-(*p*-Tolyl amino)-2-(benzo[d]thiazole-2-yl)-3-(methylthio)acrylonitrile (3b)

This compound was prepared from the reaction of **2** with *p*-toluidine (0.1 gm, 1 mmol) Yellow crystals; yield 80 %; mp 248-250 °C; IR (KBr): ν/cm^{-1} = 2197(CN), 3158 (NH), MS m/z (%): 337 (83.91), 231 (68.97), 185 (68.97), 134(75.86), 108 (72.41), 77 (71.26). Anal. Calcd. For $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2$ (337): C, 64.06; H, 4.48; N, 12.45 %; Found C, 64.13; H, 4.37; N, 12.53 %.

3-(*p*-Methoxyphenylamino)-2-(benzo[d]thiazole-2-yl)-3-(methylthio)acrylonitrile (3c)

This compound was prepared from the reaction of **2** with *p*-anisidine (0.12 gm, 1 mmol) Yellow crystals; yield 85 %; mp 255-258 °C; IR (KBr): ν/cm^{-1} = 2193 (CN), 3161 (NH), ^1H NMR (300MHz, DMSO-*d*6): δ/ppm = 2.66 (s, 3H, SCH₃), 3.78 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 6.94–8.17 (m, 4H, Ar–H), MS m/z (%): 353 (20.27), 307 (72.95), 217 (100), 191(8.11), 136 (4.79), 77 (27.32). Anal. Calcd. For $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2\text{O}$ (353): C, 61.16; H, 4.24; N, 11.89 %; Found C, 61.24; H, 4.31; N, 11.95 %.

3-(4-Chlorophenyl amino)-2-(benzo[d]thiazole-2-yl)-3-(methylthio)acrylonitrile (3d)

This compound was prepared from the reaction of **2** with *p*-chloroaniline (0.12gm, 1 mmol) Yellow crystals; yield 80 %; mp 260-263 °C; IR (KBr): ν/cm^{-1} = 2193(CN), 3155 (NH), MS m/z (%): 357.5 (8.2), 342 (3.5), 306 (2.5), 230(1.35), 217 (100), 191 (2.59), 159 (1.57), 135 (6.84), 109 (10.7), 77 (3.44). Anal. Calcd. For $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2\text{Cl}$ (357.5): C, 57.05; H, 3.38; N, 11.74 %; Found C, 57.14; H, 3.45; N, 11.79 %.

3-(4-Nitrophenylamino)-2-(benzo[d]thiazole-2-yl)-3-(methylthio)acrylonitrile (3e)

This compound was prepared from the reaction of **2** with *p*-nitroaniline (0.13 gm, 1 mmol) Yellow crystals; yield 70 %; mp 250-258 °C; IR (KBr): ν/cm^{-1} = 2182 (CN), 3107 (NH). MS m/z (%): 368 (7.07), 322(8.5), 305(8.5), 217(94.1), 190 (14.4), 134 (7.51), 108(20.66), 76 (20.93). Anal. Calcd. For

C₁₇H₁₂N₄S₂O₂ (368): C, 55.42; H, 3.28; N, 15.21 %; Found: C, 55.53; H, 3.37; N, 15.29 %.

3-(1*H*-1,2,4-Triazol-3-ylamino)-2-(benzo[*d*]thiazole-2-yl)-3-(methylthio)acrylonitrile (3f)

This compound was prepared from the reaction of **2** with 5-amino-1,2,4 triazole (0.08 gm, 1 mmol) Yellow crystals; yield 65 %; mp 265-268 °C; IR (KBr): ν/cm^{-1} = 2193(CN), 3156 (NH), ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ/ppm = 2.66 (s, 3H, SCH₃), 7.47–8.17 (m, 4H, Ar–H). MS *m/z* (%): 314 (9.93), 299 (9.25), 231 (8.9), 217(9.76), 184 (8.9), 135 (13.87), 108 (17.12), 76 (10.62). Anal. Calcd. For C₁₃H₁₀N₆S₂ (314): C, 49.66; H, 3.21; N, 26.73 %; Found C, 49.74; H, 3.29; N, 26.62 %.

3-(9,10-Dihydro-9,10-dioxoanthracen-3-ylamino)-2-(benzo[*d*]thiazole-2-yl)-3-(methylthio)acrylonitrile (3g)

This compound was prepared from the reaction of **2** with 2-aminoanthracene-9,10-dione (0.22 gm, 1 mmol) Yellow crystals; yield 60 %; mp 270-275 °C; IR (KBr): ν/cm^{-1} = 2194(CN), 3158 (NH), 1670 (C=O), MS *m/z* (%): 453 (31.1), 423 (25.84), 348 (31.10), 218(33.97), 186 (27.75), 174 (25.84), 109 (32.54), 77 (29.67) Anal. Calcd. For C₂₅H₁₅N₃S₂O₂ (453.06): C, 66.21; H, 3.33; N, 9.27 %; Found: C, 66.27; H, 3.39; N, 9.34 %.

2-(Benzo[*d*]thiazole-2-yl)-3-(methylthio)-3-(pyridine-2-ylamino)acrylonitrile (3h)

This compound was prepared from the reaction of **2** with 2-aminopyridine (0.10 gm, 1 mmol) Yellow crystals; yield 75 %; mp 267-270 °C; IR (KBr): ν/cm^{-1} = 2193(CN), 3156 (NH), ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ/ppm = 2.49 (s, 3H, SCH₃), 6.84–8.40 (m, 8H, Ar–H), MS *m/z*(%): 324 (7.94), 310 (6.80), 232 (9.86), 217(100), 184 (1.25), 135 (9.86), 109 (17.80), 77 (1.13). Anal. Calcd. For C₁₆H₁₃N₄S₂ (324.05): C, 59.23; H, 3.73; N, 17.27 %; Found: C, 59.32; H, 3.82; N, 17.19 %.

3-(1*H*-Benzo[*d*]imidazole-2-ylamino)-2-(benzo[*d*]thiazole-2-yl)-3-(methylthio)acrylonitrile (3i)

This compound was prepared from the reaction of **2** with 1*H*-benzo[*d*]imidazol-2-amine (0.13 gm, 1 mmol) Yellow crystals; yield 85 %; mp 280-283 °C; IR (KBr): ν/cm^{-1} = 2178 (CN), 3157 (NH), MS *m/z*(%): 363(12.62), 348(14.58), 231(17.72), 217(100), 173(14.08), 135(19.17), 109(26.21), 77(19.66). Anal. Calcd. For C₁₈H₁₃N₅S₂ (363.06): C, 59.48; H, 3.61; N, 19.27 %; Found C, 59.39; H, 3.67; N, 19.35 %.

3-(2,5-Dihydro-2,3-dimethyl-5-oxo-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-4-ylamino)-2-(benzo[*d*]thiazole-2-yl)-3-(methylthio)acrylonitrile (3j)

This compound was prepared from the reaction of **2** with aminoantipyrine (0.2 gm, 1 mmol) Yellow crystals; yield 70 %; mp 285-283 °C; IR (KBr): ν/cm^{-1} = 2193(CN), 3155 (NH), 1657 (C=O), ¹H NMR (300MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ/ppm = 2.3 (s, 3H, CH₃), 3.03 (s, 3H, SCH₃), 3.12 (s, 3H, NCH₃), 7.36–8.43 (m, 9H, Ar–H); MS *m/z* (%): 433 (60.19), 417 (60.19), 342 (53.40), 327(55.34), 231 (66.02), 217 (72.82), 185 (68.93), 135 (83.5), 109 (35.92), 77 (1.94). Anal. Calcd. For C₂₂H₁₉N₅S₂O (433.1): C, 60.95; H, 4.42; N, 16.15 % Found: C, 60.83; H, 4.49; N, 16.22 %.

1.3. Biological activity:

The present study was conducted to investigate the susceptibility of a laboratory strain of the 2nd instar larvae of the cotton leafworm *S. littoralis* to 2-(benzo[*d*]thiazole-2-yl)-3, 3-bis (methylthio) acrylonitrile and its derivatives. A laboratory strain of the cotton leafworm *S. littoralis* was managed under regular ailments connected with 25 ± 1 oC and 60 to 70 ± 5 % RH and kept down any contaminants by simply chemical compounds until eventually any time connected with review in order to obtain a susceptible and homogenous stress (EL-Defrawi *et al.*, 1964).

1.4. Toxicity tests:

A series of different concentration (1000, 500, 250 and 100 ppm) for each compound was prepared by dissolving it in DMSO then the volume was completed by water. Four castor-bean leaves dipped inside every single attentiveness for 30s after which remaining to dried. The 2nd instar larvae had been enclosed along with muslin for forty-eight a long time. Analyze also bundled some sort of non-treated control in which leaves ended up dipped inside mineral water. Four replicates (each regarding 10 larvae) ended up screened for each concentration. Every day examination had been accomplished for many remedies and mortality proportions ended up noted following all day and hour *via* treatment method. The average regarding mortality portion had been noted employing **Abbott's formula (1925)**. The actual remedied mortality portion of compound had been statically computed according to **Finney (1971)**, from which your equivalent attentiveness probit outlines (LCP Lines) ended up estimated as well as dedication regarding 50 and ninety days % mortalities; slope values with the screened substances ended up also estimated. Furthermore, your effectiveness regarding unique substances had been tested by means of looking at your screened substances most abundant in powerful compound while using next equation; Toxicity list = LC50 of the most powerful compound / LC50 with the screened compound $\times 100$ (**Sun, 1950**).

1.5. Formulation:

The physico-chemical properties of active ingredient of (2-(benzo[d] thiazole-2-yl)-3, 3-bis (methylthio) acrylonitrile)

Solubility was determined by measuring the volume of distilled water, acetone, dimethyleformamide (DMF) and xylene for complete solubility or miscibility of one gram of active ingredient at 20 °C (**Nelson and Fiero., 1954**). The % Solubility was calculated according to the following equation % solubility = $W/V \times 100$ [Where;

W= active ingredient weight, V= Volume of solvent required for complete solubility]. Free acidity or alkalinity: It was determined according to WHO specification (**WHO, 1979**). Melting point: It was determined by using Gallenkamp melting point apparatus.

1.6. The physico-chemical properties of surface active agents:

1.6.1. Free acidity or alkalinity: it was determined corresponding to the method described by WHO specification (**WHO, 1979**).

1.6.2. Hydrophilic-lipophilic balance (HLB) The hydrophilic-lipophilic balance (HLB) of surfactant depend on its solubility in water (**Lynch and Griffin., 1974**).

1.6.3. Critical micelle concentration (CMC) It is the concentration at which, the further increase in surfactant concentration does not decrease the surface tension of solution (**Osipow, 1964**).

d- Surface tension: it was determined by using Du-Nouy for solutions containing 0.5 % (W/V) surfactant according to **ASTM D-1331 (2001)**.

1.7. Preparation of (2-(benzo[d]thiazole-2-yl)-3,3-bis(methylthio)acrylonitrile) as suspension concentrate (SC):

Suspension concentrate formulation also termed a flowable concentrate, it is a stable suspension of an active ingredient in fluid intended for dilution with water prior to use. This type of formulation has been developed for active ingredients that are soluble in neither oil nor water. For preparing (2-(benzo[d] thiazole-2-yl)-3, 3-bis (methylthio) acrylonitrile) in the form of suspension concentrate formulation, several trials were carried out as follow: Different weights from active ingredient added to other different weights from sticking agent, emulsifier, defoamer and dispersing agent with different percentages of water. Then the mixture was stirred using magnet to ensure homogeneity. Suspensibility test was carried out according to CIPAC MT 46.1 (2002) for

all prepared formulations to judge on the success of formulation.

2. Determination of the physico-chemical properties of the local suspension concentrate formulation:

2.1. Suspensibility: It was determined according to **CIPAC MT 46.1. (2002)**.

2.2. Free acidity or alkalinity: it was determined corresponding to the method described by WHO specification (**WHO, 1979**).

2.3. Foam: It measured according to **CIPAC MT 46.1. (2002)**.

3. Determination of the physico-chemical properties of the spray solution of the local formulation at the field dilution rate:

3.1. Surface tension: It was determined as mentioned before.

3.2. Viscosity: It was determined according to **ASTM D-2196 (2005)**.

3.3. PH: It was determined according to method of **Dobrat and Martijn (1995)**.

3.4. Electrical Conductivity: It was determined according to **Dobrat and Martijn (1995)**.

3.5. Salinity: It was measured by using Cole-Parmer PH/conductivity meter 1484-44.

3.6. Sedimentation: It measured according to **CIPAC MT 46.1. (2002)**.

Results and discussion

The synthetic strategies adopted to obtain the target compounds are depicted in Scheme 1. The starting 2-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl) acetonitrile (1) was prepared according to the pervious reported method (Mohamed and Fadda, 2015). Heterocyclic ketenes are versatile starting materials for the synthesis of a wide variety of fused and non-fused different heterocyclic moieties. 2-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl)acetonitrile (1) reacted with CS₂ in DMF in the presence of NaOH to give the non-isolable salt that underwent alkylation by the action of dimethyl sulfate under the same conditions giving ketene (2) (Rudorf, 1991). Refluxing the latter ketene with different aromatic amines namely; [aniline, *p*-toluidine, *p*-anisidine, *p*-chloroaniline, *p*-nitro aniline, amino triazole, amino anthracene-9, 10-dione, 2-amino pyridine, 2-aminobenzoimidazole, aminoantipyrine] in the presence of catalytical amount of (TEA) afforded acyclic enaminonitriles (3a-j). The formation of enaminonitriles (3a-j) was illustrated through the nucleophilic attack of the primary amines to the ethylenic double bond followed by elimination of one mole of methyl mercaptan. The structures of compounds (3) were established and confirmed by their elemental analysis and spectral data.

Scheme 1. Synthesis the acyclic enaminonitriles (**3a-j**)

1.Toxicity of tested derivatives:

Toxicological assay of 2-cyanomethyl benzothiazole (1) and its derivatives were studied. Data in Table (1) indicate that, mercapto compound (2) was approved to be the most toxic compound with LC₅₀ value of 54.52 ppm against 2nd instar larvae and this may be due to the presence of two (SCH₃) groups. However, the reaction of this compound with different aromatic and heterocyclic amines decreases the toxicity due to the absence of (SCH₃) group. It is clear that the toxicity increased in case of electron withdrawing groups of aromatic amines compared with electron donating groups.

In case of aromatic amines, compounds 3d and 3e showed high toxicity values near compound 2 with LC₅₀ value of 54.59 and 57.23 ppm respectively, followed by 3a with LC₅₀ value of 74.76 ppm. Compounds 3c, 3b

and compound (1) showed low toxicity with LC₅₀ value of 123.29, 173.66 and 211.40 ppm, respectively. But in case of heterocyclic amines, 3h showed close toxicity value to that of compound 2 its LC₅₀ value was 57.89 ppm while the other compounds showed low toxicity with descending order 3g, 3i, (1), 3f and 3j with LC₅₀ values of 140.19, 152.42, 211.40, 393.01 and 856.91 ppm respectively.

In general, treatment of cotton leafworm *S. littoralis* with these benzothiazole derivatives, in comparison with the starting compound, 2-cyanomethyl benzothiazole (1) resulted in two groups. The first group consists of nine compounds, namely 3, 3d, 3e, 3h, 3a, 3c, 3g, 3i and 3b that were more toxic than compound (1). While, the second group consists only of two compounds namely 3f and 3j that were less toxic than compound (1).

Table (1): Susceptibility of 2nd instar larvae of cotton leafworm *Spodoptera littoralis* to tested 2-cyanomethyle benzothiazole and its derivatives.

Tested compounds	LC ₅₀ Its limits at 95%	LC ₉₀ Its limits at 95%	Slope	Toxicity index %
1	211.40 170.02 258.30	566.08 427.46 922.16	2.99 ±0.49	25.79
2	54.52 9.12 92.61	279.19 192.65 659.61	1.81 ±0.54	100.00
3a	74.76 17.89 116.14	245.17 171.50 502.93	2.48 ±0.76	72.93
3b	173.66 129.71 217.36	575.91 436.57 891.57	2.46 ±0.37	31.40
3c	123.29 43.18 184.88	766.03 427.81 6267.67	1.62 ±0.50	44.22
3d	54.59 17.83 93.35	721.77 398.71 2690.93	1.14 ±0.26	99.87
3e	57.23 16.20 95.04	669.03 337.33 5322.85	1.20 ±0.34	95.28
3F	393.01 324.77 476.71	1028.91 824.20 1663.06	2.91 ±0.39	13.87
3G	140.19 54.08 209.60	1262.04 604.73 21537.29	1.34 ±0.42	38.89
3H	57.89 14.67 100.11	394.48 267.72 810.36	1.54 ±0.38	94.18
3I	152.42 48.82 248.14	2969.70 1214.97 56286.83	0.99 ±0.28	35.77
3J	856.91 498.71 2715.88	13418.09 3703.24 423941.66	1.07 ±0.26	6.363

2. Formulation of the most effective derivatives:

The most tested effective derivative with high toxicity was prepared in the form of suspension concentrate (SC) formulation after carrying out the following physico-chemical properties of active ingredient and surfactant.

2.1. Physico-chemical properties of (2-(benzo[d] thiazole-2-yl)-3, 3-bis

(methylthio) acrylonitrile) (2) as an active ingredient:

Data in Table (2) showed that, acrylonitrile (2) was insoluble in water, acetone, xylene and DMF. This result gives a predication that the compound could be prepared as suspension concentrate formulation. On the other hand, it has a weak acidic property, so it requires a slight acidic to a slight alkaline adjuvant when it is prepared as formulation.

Table (2): Physico-chemical properties of (2-(benzo[d] thiazole-2-yl)-3, 3-bis (methylthio) acrylonitrile) as an active ingredient.

Solubility % (W/V)				Acidity as H ₂ SO ₄	Alkalinity as NaOH	Melting point
Water	Acetone	DMF	Xylene			
Insoluble	Insoluble	Insoluble	Insoluble	0.19	----	229-231

2.2. Physico-chemical properties of the suggested surface active agents:

As shown in Table (3), the physico-chemical properties of four nonionic surface active agents namely Sodium lauryl sulfate, tween 20, span 20 and Polyethylene glycol 600 diolate was studied to determine if it was compatible with the physico-chemical properties of active ingredient or not. According to HLB values, Sodium lauryl sulfate and tween 20 were considered as dispersing agents, their HLB values were more than 13 whereas the HLB of span 20 was 6-8 and Polyethylene glycol 600 diolate 8-10, so it was considered as wetting agent. On the other hand, all tested surface active agents decreased surface tension of water from 72 for water to 27.8, 50 and 33 dyne/cm in case of Sodium lauryl sulfate, tween 20, and Polyethylene glycol 600 diolate, respectively. Sodium lauryl sulfate and Span 20 recorded free alkalinity as % NaOH 0.48 and 0.22 respectively, whereas tween 20 and Polyethylene glycol 600 diolate recorded the

same free acidity 0.19 as % H₂SO₄. From the above results, it could be concluded that, the tested surface active agents were suitable to prepare the most tested effective derivative as SC formulation because it was act as wetting agent in case of span 20 and polyethylene glycol 600 diolate and as dispersing agent in case of sodium lauryl sulfate and tween 20. In most cases, suspension concentrates are made by dispersing the active ingredient powder in aqueous solution of wetting and dispersing agent using high shear mixer to give concentrated premix (Knowles, 2008).

According to data in Table (4), the local formulation passed successfully the hot storage test because it was acidic before and after storage in hard and soft water, no observable changes were found in suspensibility and free acidity of suspension concentrate local formulation before and after accelerated storage for three days. On the other hand, little changes observed for foam test before and after accelerated storage.

Table (3): The physico-chemical properties of the tested surface-active agent.

Surface active agent	Solubility %				CMC %	HLB	Free acidity as H ₂ SO ₄	Free alkalinity as NaOH
	Xylene	Acetone	DMF	water				
Sodium lauryl sulfate	Insoluble	Insoluble	Insoluble	27.8	8	>13		0.48
Tween 20	100.00	100.00	100.00	50.00	0.50	>13	0.19	----
Span 20	Insoluble	5.70	-----	insoluble	-----	6-8		0.22
P.E.G 600*	50.00	16.70	20.50	33.00	0.90	8-10	0.19	-----

*: Polyethylene glycol 600 diolate

Table (4): The physic-chemical properties of local formulations of (2-(benzo[d] thiazole-2-yl)-3, 3-bis (methylthio) acrylonitrile) as suspension concentrate before and after hot storage.

Type of water	Before storage			After storage		
	Foam cm ³	Suspensibility %	Free acidity as H ₂ SO ₄	Foam cm ³	Suspensibility %	Free acidity as H ₂ SO ₄
Hard water	6.00	100.00	0.16	3.80	94.00	0.15
Soft water	6.00	100.00		6.60	99.00	
Tap water	0.80	100.00		4.20	98.80	

Hard water (342 ppm as CaCO₃; Soft water (57ppm)

2.3.The physico-chemical properties of spray solution of local formulation of the tested compound as 10% suspension concentrate at field dilution rate:

As represented in Table (5) , the local formulation of this compound 10 % (SC) possesses low surface tension, high viscosity and high conductivity in addition; it showed no sedimentation, medium salinity and little alkaline PH value. Surface tension decrease of pesticide spray solution showed an increase in spreading on the treated surface

Table (5): The physico-chemical properties of spray solution of 2-(benzo[d] thiazole-2-yl)-3, 3-bis (methylthio) acrylonitrile 10% (SC) at field dilution rate.

Conductivity μ mhos	PH	Salinity %	Surface tension dyne/cm	Viscosity cm/poise	Sedimentation
1719	7.67	0.8	34.1	10.24	Pass

Data in Table (6) compares between the toxicity of compound (2) considered as an active ingredient and its 10% (SC) formulation against the 2nd instar larvae of the cotton leafworm (*S. littoralis*) under laboratory condition.

then increasing pesticidal efficacy (Osipow, 1964). Reduction drift, retention sticking, and insecticidal efficacy resulted from increasing viscosity of spray solution (Richardson, 1974). The increase of electrical conductivity of insecticide spray solution resulted in deionization of insecticide; therefore, increase both its deposits and penetration in the tested surface followed by increase in its insecticidal efficacy (Tawfik and El-Sisi, 1987).

The results obtained showed that, LC₅₀ and LC₉₀ values for compound 2 were 54.52 and 279.19 ppm respectively whereas that for formulation were 2664.39 and 15643.16 ppm. It seems likely that, this active ingredient is more efficient on the 2nd instar larvae of

cotton leafworm compared to its formulation which appears clear from its corresponding toxicity index 100 and 2.05 % respectively. These results could be explained on the bases of how the active ingredient reaches its target position in both cases, in case of active ingredient, it is dissolved during the bioassay experiment in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) which is classified as an organic solvent that facilitates the entry of active substances

(solubility rule), taking the same factor into consideration in case of (SC) formulation. Suspension concentrate formulations are water based formula, this means in contrast to active ingredient alone, the ability of active ingredient to reach its target position in case of aqueous layer containing active ingredient is difficult with a sequence difficulty to penetrate the external fatty layer of the insect under study.

Table (6): Comparison between the efficacy of benzothiazole derivatives (2) as an active ingredient and its formulation against the 2nd instar larvae of cotton leafworm (*Spodoptera littoralis*).

Tested compound	LC ₅₀ Its limits at 95%	LC ₉₀ Its limits at 95%	Slope	Toxicity index (%)
Active ingredient	54.52 9.12 92.61	279.19 192.65 659.61	1.806 ±0.5441	100.00
Formulation 10% SC	2664.39 1889.36 3563.097	15643.16 9636.57 40012.75	1.6673 ±0.3014	2.05

Regardless of their source, pesticide active ingredients include a range of solubility. Many break up commonly with normal water, some others, only with natural skin oils. Many active ingredients might be insoluble with possibly normal water or even essential oil. Solubility features and the meant using the pesticide generally determine which in turn products very best offer the active ingredient (**Pesticide safety and environmental education Program University of Minnesota extension, 2015**).

The current results are supported by the finding of several authors cited that, Benthiavalicarb-iso-Pr, iso-Pr[(S)-1-[(R)-1-[6-fluorobenzothiazol-2-yl] ethylcarbamoyl]-2-methylpropyl] carbamate is a novel fungicide which is active against Oomycete fungal pathogens of various crops. Benthiavalicarb-iso-Pr has a very favorable toxicol. and environmental profile and does not cause phytotoxic symptoms on a no. of crops, vegetables and fruits (**Miyake *et al.*, 2003** and **2005**). Thiazolecarboxaldehyde oxime ether used as insecticides, fungicides, antiviral agents, and plant activator moreover

evaluated for their antibacterial activity (**Reuveni, 2003**). Chlobenthiazone causes inhibition at a site in the aflatoxin pathway prior to the synthesis of norsolorinic acid (**Wheeler *et al.*, 1989** and **1991**).

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Effect of storage on the stability on some fungicides and determination of residues in fish

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Abstract:

The present work was carried out to study the persistence of naserzol (Propiconazole 25 % EC W/V), nofostar (Dimethomorph 5%WDG W/W) and self (Fludioxonil 25 %WG W/W). The stability of active ingredient of the tested fungicide under storage 54 °C for 14 days and influence direct sun light, monitoring of pesticide residues in fish (gills and muscles) samples in Egypt in three months : June , November and December 2018 from three Governorates (Behera , Gharbia , and Alexandria). The pesticide residues in the fish muscles, gills, studies fungicides were estimated by HPLC, and GC/Ms. The active ingredient were propiconazole, dimethomorph and fludioxonil 25.31, 5.03 and 10.21 before storage become after storage 54 °C, 18.65, 4.67 and 7.68 , respectively , at the end experiment the loose percentages were 26.31 , 7.15 and 24.77 % when the fungicides compound previously were stored at 54 °C for 14 days. Also, the stability active ingredient before influence sun light 25.07 , 5.03 and 10.21 after influence sun light 22.01, 4.10 and 9.11, respectively . The highest fungicide in Alexandria Governorate was fludioxonil more than ADI according to FAO in November. The less than in Gharbia and Behera Governorates were propiconazole and dimethomorph ADI according to FAO in June and December.

Introduction

Fungicides are widely accustomed kill or inhibit fungi or fungal spores that threaten to ruin greenhouse crops through incorporation into the soil and foliar application. On the contrary single fungicide applications, multiple applications over a season often end within the fungicide's permanency in agricultural soil (Bulbul and Ozhan, 2012). The risk to the environment posed by the employment of fungicides in

horticultural production systems has received relatively little attention compared to other kinds of agrochemicals, like insecticides and herbicides (Gillom *et al.*, 2006).

The environmentally available proportion of fungicides in water, sediment and soil can cause toxic effects to organisms. However, not all the fungicide is absorbed by organisms and react with toxic sites of action within exposed organisms (be toxicologically

bioavailable or bio accessible) (Fairbrother *et al.*, 2007 and Harmsen, 2007). In Egypt, as in many other agricultural countries, pesticides are widely accustomed control harmful pests, mainly, cotton, maize and rice. Nearly of these chemicals are readily soluble in plant oils and waxes; this common property places all under suspicion as food (Fatin *et al.* , 2016).

In this paper, we studied the effect of storage and influence sun light direct of fungicides (Propiconazole, dimethomorph

Table (1): Showed the formulation of fungicides.

and fludioxonil) during storage for 14 days at 54 °C on also the degradation of tested fungicides was studied. Determination residues fungicides of the fish were collected from each of the three Governorates, Behera , Gharbia , and Alexandria.

Materials and methods

1. Source of sample pesticides: Central Agricultural Pesticide Lab. and Table (1) observed trade name, active ingredient and formulation types of fungicides:

Trade name for fungicides	Active ingredient	M.W g/mol	Formulation types	Structure
Naserzol	Propiconazole 25 %	342	EC	
Nofostar	Dimethomorph5%	387.9	WDG	
Self	Fludioxonil 25 %	248	WG	

2. Sample preparation for tested pesticides:

Accurately weighed enough samples formulation equivalent to 10 mg of standard in a different 25 ml volumetric flask for each sample, and slowly mixed with methanol and the volume was completed with methanol.

3. Storage stability tests:

The Previously fungicides (Propiconazole , fludioxonil and dimethomorph) formulation were stored in oven at 54 °C for 14 days according to the (FAO, 2018 and 2010), respectively, 14 days storage. During the storage period the

samples were taken at 0, 1, 3, 7 and 14 days from storage to determine the active ingredient for formulation under testes if is present .

4. Influence of direct sunlight:

The fungicides (Propiconazole , fludioxonil and dimethomorph) formulation were influence of direct sunlight for 14 days according to the (Naser *et al.*, 2003) .The samples were taken at 0, 1, 3, 7 and 14 days from influence direct sun light to determine the active ingredient and impurities content for formulation under testes if is present .

5. Fish samples:

Thirty Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) growing in drainage water were collected from each of the three Governorates (Behera, Gharbia, and Alexandria) under study.

6. Extraction and cleanup of fish samples:

Fish muscles and gills were ground and blended in a warring blender just to pulplike consistency. 200 ml methanol / acetone (4/1) were added to 100 g blended both muscles and gills samples , then the mixture was shaken mechanically using electrical shaker for one hour and filtered through Buchner funnel. The collated solvent mixtures were evaporated under reduced pressure using rotary evaporator till dryness. The residue was quantitatively transferred into small vials with 5 ml methanol. The solvent was then evaporated till dryness and vials were stored at -15 °C until the cleanup (Muir *et al.*, 1981).

7. Identification of pesticides in gills and muscles fish samples:

A study was done to check the three pesticides residues (Table, 1), in different samples of both gills and muscle fish samples collected from three different Governorates (Behera , Gharbia , and Alexandria) in Egypt. The residues analysis was done using HPLC and identified the type of pesticides with gas chromatography-Mass spectrometer (GC-MS) (Iqbal *et al.*, 2009).

8. Determiation of Active ingredient by high Performance Liquid Chromatography HPLC :

The type of chromatographic HPLC system model (Agilent Technologies 1260 Infinity) with Quaternary pump, UV-detector was employed. The chromatographic C18 stainless steel column (25 cm length, 4.6 mm inner diameter, and 4.0 µm particles) .

9. Determiation of fungicides by GC/MS:

Apparatus Agilent B, 5977 AMSD gas chromatography equipped with an Agilent mass spectrometric detector , with a direct capillary interface and fused silica capacity Colum (30 m x 0.025 mm HP -5 0.25 microm 60 to 325/325 °C). Samples were injected under the following condition; helium was used as carrier gas at approximately 1 ml /min , pulsed split mode , split ratio (10:1) split flow 10 ml /min . The solvent delay was 4 min and the injection size were 1 UL . Oven temperature program , %0 °C for O<5 min , the 10 /min ramp to 190 °C followed by a 10 °C /min ramp to 210 °C for 1 min followed by a 10 °C /min ramp to 300 °C and held for 2 min (total run time followed by an injection temperature was set at 280 °C. Wiley mass spectral data was used in the identification of the separated peaks .

Results and discussion

1. The effect of storage 54 °C and influence sun light on propiconazole, dimethomorph and fludioxonil:

Date in Table (2) stability of active ingredient were propiconazole dimethomorph and fludioxonil 25.31, 5.03 and 10.21 before storage become after storage 54 °C, 18.65 , 4.67 and 7.68 at the end experiment, respectively . The loose percentages were 26.31, 7.15 and 24.77 % when the fungicides compound previously were stored at 54 °C for 14 days . The stability active ingredient before influence sun light 25.07, 5.03 and 10.21 after influence sun light 22.01, 4.10 and 9.11, respectively.

Table (2): The effect of storage 54 °C and influence sunlight on propiconazole , dimethomorph and fludioxonil .

Storage period (days)	Storage 54 C						Sunlight					
	Propiconazole 25 %		Dimethomorph 5 %		Fludioxonil 10		Propiconazole 25 %		Dimethomorph 5 %		Fludioxonil 10%	
	(a.i)	Loss	(a.i)	Loss	(a.i)	Loss	(a.i)	Loss	(a.i)	Loss	(a.i)	Loss
0*	25.31	00	5.03	00	10.21	00	25.07	00	5.03	00	10.21	00
1	25.31	00	5.03	00	10.02	1.86	25.00	2.79	5.00	0.59	10.00	2.20
3	25.07	0.23	4.95	1.59	9.02	11.65	24.00	4.26	4.85	3.57	9.94	2.60
7	21.41	15.40	4.80	1.51	8.87	13.12	22.27	11.16	4.17	17.09	9.59	6.07
14	18.65	26.31	4.67	7.15	7.68	24.77	22.01	1.03	4.10	18.48	9.1 1	10.77

0* one hour before exposure to storage.

2. The degradation product and possible pathway of propiconazole, dimethomorph and fludioxonil by GC/MS :

The data presented in Table (3) showed that propiconazole after storage 54 °C for 14 days and influence direct sun light product m/z 344 1-[[2-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-4-propyl-1,3-dioxolan-2-yl]methyl]-1H-1,2,4- triazole , M/Z 172 2,4-dichlorophenyl 1,2,4-triazole-1-ylmethyl ketone, m/Z 301 1-[2-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-4-(hydroxypropyl)-1,3-dioxolan-2-ylmethyl]- The degradation fragment ion spectrum of m/z 344 was identified by its (M -16)+ which was due to

Table (3): The degradation product on propiconazole, fludioxonil , dimethomorph and by GC/MS .

Pesticides	M/Z	Compound product
Propiconazole	344 172 301	1-[[2-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-4-propyl-1,3-dioxolan-2-yl]methyl]-1H-1,2,4- triazole 2,4-dichlorophenyl 1,2,4-triazole-1-ylmethyl ketone 1-[2-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-4-(hydroxypropyl)-1,3-dioxolan-2-ylmethyl]-
Fludioxonil	248	4-(2,2-difluoro-1,3-benzodioxol-4-yl)-1H-pyrrole-3-carbonitrile
Dimethomorph	388	4-[3-(4-chlorophenyl)-3-(3,4-dimethoxy-phenyl)-1-oxo-2-propenyl]-

loss of OH from 344 suggesting 1-[2-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-4-(hydroxypropyl)-1,3-dioxolan-2-ylmethyl]. Propiconazole has propyl side-chain on the dioxolane ring. Therefore, this degradation product was suggested to be compound hydroxylated on different carbon position of propyl side chain (Hen and Trak, 2003). Dimethomorph the fragment ion m/z 388 4-[3-(4-chlorophenyl)-3-(3,4-dimethoxy-phenyl)-1-oxo-2-propenyl]-and fludioxonil 4-(2,2-difluoro-1,3-benzodioxol-4-yl)-1H-pyrrole-3-carbonitrile (Figures 1-3) , influence sun light and storage 14 days on 54 °C.

Figure (1): Fragment of propiconazole by GC/MS.

Figure (2): Fragment of fludioxonil by GC/MS.

Figure (3): Fragment of dimethomorph by GC/MS .

3. Fungicides residues detected in *Oreochromis niloticus* fish gills and muscles samples collected from three different Governorates during June 2018:

Data in Table (4) indicated the presence residues of pesticides in fish muscles samples from three different Governorates November in 2018. The average of the detected pesticide residues in these Governorates were as follows: gill of fish samples collected from Gharbia Governorate contained propiconazole UND, fludioxonil 0.001246 ppm dimethomorph 0.000404 ppm in gills. The muscles of fish samples collected from Gharbia Governorate propiconazole, fludioxonil, dimethomorph UND, respectively.

The pesticide residues in gills of fish samples collected from Behera , propiconazole 0.00323 ppm , fludioxonil 0.00052 ppm , dimethomorph UND and fish samples collected from Alexandria propiconazole 0.00558 ppm, fludioxonil UND, dimethomorph 0.00803 ppm less than ADI. The pesticide residues in muscles of fish samples collected from Behera Governorate were propiconazole 0.00644 ppm fludioxonil 0.0001986 ppm dimethomorph UND and samples collected from samples collected from Alexandria propiconazole 0.00102 ppm fludioxonil UND, dimethomorph 0.000508 ppm dimethomorph is less than the ADI in gills and fish muscles according to FAO.

Table (4) : Pesticide residues detected in *Oreochromis niloticus* fish gills and muscles samples collected from three different Governorates during June 2018 .

Name of pesticides	Gills µg/g (ppm)			Muscles µg/g (ppm)			
	Gharbia	Behera	Alex.	Gharbia	Behera	Alexandria	ADI mg/kg
Propiconazole	UND	0.00323	0.00558	UND	0.00644	0.00102	0.07
Fludioxonil	0.001246	0.00052	UND	UND	0.0001986	UND	0.01
Dimethomorph	0.000404	UND	0.00803	UND	UND	0.000508	0.008

UND: Undetectable
 ADI : Acceptable daily intake

4. Residue of pesticides in fish muscles and gills from three different Governorates June in 2018:

Data in Table (5) indicate the presence residues of pesticides in fish muscles samples from three different Governorates November in 2018 .The average of the detected pesticide residues in these Governorates were as follows: gills of fish samples collected from Gharbia Governorate contained propiconazole 0.00303 ppm, fludioxonil 0.009042 ppm, dimethomorph UND. The pesticide residues in gills of fish samples collected from Behera propiconazole UND fludioxonil UND , dimethomorph UND

and the pesticide residues in gills of fish samples collected from Alexandria propiconazole 0.0002191 ppm , fludioxonil 0.05632ppm , dimethomorph UND less than the ADI in gills and fish muscles According to FAO . The average of the detected pesticide residues in these Governorates were as follows: muscles of fish samples collected from Gharbia Governorate contained propiconazole 0.0023090 ppm fludioxonil 0.001512 ppm dimethomorph UND. The muscles of fish samples collected from Behera and Alexandria Governorates propiconazole fludioxonil and dimethomorph UND .

Table (5) : Pesticide residues detected in *Oreochromis niloticus* fish gills and muscles samples collected from three different Governorates during November 2018 .

Name of pesticides	Gills µg/g (ppm)			Muscles µg/g (ppm)			
	Gharbia	Behera	Alexandria	Gharbia	Behera	Alexandria	ADI mg/kg
Propiconazole	0.00303	UND	0.0002191	0.002309	UND	UND	0.07
Fludioxonil	0.009042	UND	0.05632	0.001512	UND	UND	0.01
Dimethomorph	UND	UND	UND	UND	UND	UND	0.008

UND Undetectable

5. Residue of pesticides in fish muscles and gills from three different Governorates December in 2018:

Data in Table (6) indicate the presence residues of pesticides in fish muscles samples from three different Governorates November in 2018. The average of the detected pesticide residues in these Governorates were as follows: gills of fish samples collected from Gharbia Governorate contained propiconazole 0.012108 ppm, fludioxonil 0.0016594 ppm , dimethomorph UND. The pesticide residues in muscles of fish samples

collected from Behera propiconazole UND fludioxonil 0.003131 ppm, dimethomorph UND and Alexandria propiconazole 0.0002815 ppm fludioxonil 0.0036963 ppm fludioxonil 0.0036963 ppm dimethomorph UND less than AID according to FAO . The muscles of fish samples collected from Gharbia , Behera and Alexandria Governorates propiconazole UND dimethomorph UND, but fludioxonil 0.000194 , 0.001933 and 0.000694 ppm, respectively.

Table (6) : Pesticide residues detected in *Oreochromis niloticus* fish gills and muscles samples collected from three different Governorates during December 2018 .

Name of pesticides	Gills µg/g (ppm)			Muscles µg/g (ppm)			
	Gharbia	Behera	Alexandria	Gharbia	Behera	Alexandria	ADI mg/kg
Propiconazole	0.012108	UND	0.0002815	UND	UND	UND	0.07
Fludioxonil	0.0016594	0.003131	0.0036963	0.000194	0.001933	0.000694	0.01
Dimethomorph	UND	UND	UND	UND	UND	UND	0.08

UND Undetectable

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Effect of insect growth regulators on *Pectinophora gossypiella*, *Spodoptera littoralis* (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae: Noctuidae) eggs and a predator spider *Thanatus albini* (Arachnida: Philodromidae) egg-sacs with some biological aspects of predator

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Abstract:

Under the laboratory condition of $27\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 70- 75% RH. two experiments were conducted under the laboratory conditions of $26\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 65-70% RH. to study the effect of the insect growth regulator, diflurobenzeron (Dimilin) ; 48% on toxicity, of *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) , *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisduval) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae: Noctuidae) eggs and spider predator *Thanatus albini* (Audouin) (Arachnida: Philodromidae) egg-sacs as well as on some biological aspects of predator. Results were concluded that the egg incubation period averaged 6.3 days/eggs of *S. littoralis* treated, while it decreased to 4.4 days/ eggs in untreated, *P. gossypiella* was (6.5 days) in treated than (3.6 days) in untreated and *T. albini* predator egg-sacs was 18.3 days in treated compared with 13.3 days in untreated also, predatory spiderling was able to develop and reproduce better on *P. gossypiella* and *S. littoralis* untreated than treated. The spider passes through seven spiderlings during its life. The total period of the first and second instar spiderlings lasted 24.0 and 17.9 days when spiderlings resulted from eggs treated and untreated, respectively, and fed on moving stages of the *Tetranychus urticae* Koch (Acari: Tetranychidae) . While, the total period from 3rd to 7th spiderlings longer to 119.0 and 133.0 days when resulted from eggs treated and shorted to 79.76 and 81.4 days when the spider resulted from eggs untreated (control) and fed on *P. gossypiella* and *S. littoralis*, respectively. The total food consumption of the predator was 348.0 and 378.7 preys/PBW treated and untreated respectively, while it was 248.6 and 279.7preys *S. littoralis* /predator, treated and untreated, respectively.

Introduction

The pink bollworm (PBW) *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) is one of the most serious insect pests infesting the cotton,

(*Gossypium* spp.) in many cotton producing areas in Egypt or in the world. It causes serious damage in cotton from flowers to

bolts and great loss as in both quality and quantity of cotton yield (Kandil, 2001).

Spodoptera littoralis (Boisduval) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) is an economically important insect pest known to attack various agricultural crops and is widely distributed in Egypt. It is reported to potentially cause 35% to 55% yield losses at the cotton and vegetative stages of the crops (Rao *et al.*, 2014).

The true spiders are one of the most important biological control agents against of different pests infesting different crops (Huseynov, 2007). True spiders hardly play a major role in controlling insect pests; also, most spiders are generalists with respect to their diet but for efficient pest control, the spiderling *Thanatus albini* (Audouin) belong to family Philodromidae were recorded as a biological control agent against certain agricultural pests such as two spotted spider mite *Tetranychus urticae* Koch (Acari: Tetranychidae), aphids, *S. littoralis* and/ or *P. gossypiella* (Hendawy and El-Mezayyen, 2003 and Pfannenstiel, 2008).

Insecticide application is considered the best method to manage all pests such a *T. urticae*, aphids, *S. littoralis* and/ or *P. gossypiella*. Due to its economic importance and widely known losses to agricultural crops, however, repeated applications and extensive use of insecticides have resulted in ecological imbalances such as toxic effects on natural enemies and humans (Ahmad *et al.*, 2007 and Abbas *et al.* , 2012).

Insect growth regulators (IGRs) have a more specific mode of action on some Lepidoptera and are not highly toxic to non-target organisms when compared to many conventional insecticides (Desuky *et al.*, 2012). Interestingly, most of the IGRs the rapid death of the insect through failure of a key regulatory process to operate or function. that have shown effectiveness against insect pests cause the rapid death of the insect through failure of a key regulatory process to operate or function. In the treated eggs stages

the insecticide caused serious malformations of the eggshell. The exposure caused other types of clearly abnormal development of eggs: two micropylar regions were noticed. Hence, even a low concentration of IGRs in the diet can lead to serious disturbances in reproduction and thus possibly at the population level.

The role of insect chitin synthesis resulting (IGRs) in all stages developmental has been extensively reviewed (Tasei, 2001). Due to their mode of action these types of different (IGRs) by disrupting the molting process, or cuticle formation, during specific developmental stages in insects are likely to pose greater hazard to larval stages than to adult insects Prabhaker and Toscano (2007). However, there are few studies on the effects of these types of compounds on the true spider

Therefore, this work aimed to study the effect of recommended compounds (IGRs) on eggs of *P. gossypiella* and *S. littoralis* and latent effect on some biological aspects of spiderling, *T. albini* under laboratory conditions

Materials and methods

1. Insect used:

The pink bollworm *P. gossypiella*, used in this study was obtained from laboratory colony of Bollworm Department, Plant Protection Research Institute; Agriculture Research Center (ARC), reared for several generations away from any contamination with insecticides on an artificial diet that previously described by Rashad and Ammer (1985). While, first instar larvae of *S. littoralis* were reared on the castor bean leaves under the laboratory conditions of $26\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 65-70% RH.

2. Culture techniques of *Tetranychus urticae*:

The two spotted spider mite, *T. urticae* were collected from castor bean leaves infested with different stages of the spider mite *T. urticae* from Giza Governorate and transferred to the laboratory to use in the

feeding of the spider, it reared according to Dittrich (1962).

Predaceous spider specie (sac eggs and different stages of spider-ling) were collected from cultivated cotton in Qaliobia Governorate, by using the hand picking and then brought to the laboratory for identification. The spiders found on foliage, on different the plant cotton ages and associated with flower.

3. Pesticides used:

An insect growth regulator (IGR) was experimentally used in this study:

Common name: Diflurobenzeron (benzoyleurea)

Trade name: Dimilin 48%

Rate of application: 125cm/fed.

4. Prepared compounds:

Different concentrations of the tested compounds were prepared as followed:

Dimilin: 480, 240, 120, 60, 30, 15 and 7.5 mg/L.

5. Toxicity on eggs of two pests *Pectinophora gossypiella* and *Spodoptera littoralis*:

Samples of eggs for different pests eggs *P. gossypiella* or *S. littoralis* (1-3 days' old eggs) treatment were done by dipping a piece of paper containing eggs on the different tested concentrations of the compound. Three replicates from each eggs of *P. gossypiella* or *S. littoralis* were used; each replicate was 100 eggs of *P. gossypiella* and 70 eggs for *S. littoralis* the both eggs on paper was dipped in each concentration of the compound.

6. Toxicity on eggs predator spider:

The toxicity of the tested compound against eggs of *T. albini* spiderling sacs was studied. Samples of eggs for *T. albini* spiderling sacs treatment were done by dipping a piece of paper containing egg sacs on the different tested concentrations of the compound. Three replicates from each egg sacs were used; each replicate from 2-3 eggs sacs (each eggs sac contend 70-110 eggs) on paper was dipped in each concentration of

compound. After that the papers were left until dried. Other three replicates of similar eggs were dipped in water and left as control. Then, the treated and untreated (control) eggs were kept in an incubator under constant conditions $25\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and $75\pm 5\%$ RH. The numbers of hatchability daily and percentages of hatchability were estimated. Percentages of mortalities were corrected according to Abbott's formula (1925) as follows:

$$\% \text{Corrected mortality} = \frac{T - C}{100 - C} \times 100$$

Where; T: %mortality in treatment

C: %mortality in check

Data were corrected LC_{25} and LC_{50s} of diflubenzuron, were calculated by using proban software.

7. Biological studies of the spider predator *Thanatus albini*:

The eggs sacs of spider *T. albini* predator were treated with LC_{50} of tested compound; it transferred to glass vials (2 X 7cm) and kept under constant conditions of $26\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and 70-75 % RH. A control check was done in distilled water for the same time. The numbers of hatchability daily, percentages of hatchability and the incubation period of eggs sacs were estimated. The first instar *T. albini* spiderling hatchability from eggs treated and untreated was then placed singly in glass tubes containing with the individual prey. The tubes were stoppard with cotton wool and held until adults' stage.

Feeding capacity: To rearing the spiderling predator; two groups used; each group 60 individuals' spiderling were reared from hatchability eggs sacs treated or untreated to maturity on different prey. The newly emerged *T. albini* spiderling were placed individually in glass tubes (15 cm high X1.5cm wide) with enough numbers of the two spotted spider mite *T. urticae* were offered daily until (the end) developmental

period of 1st and 2nd instar *T. albimii* spiderling. After that, these tubes were divided in four groups, each of 30 tubes. The first and 2nd groups resulted from eggs sacs treated were enough numbers of eggs and newly hatched larvae of PBW, it was offered daily to first group, while, the second group was offered the 2nd instar larvae of *S. littoralis*. At the same time the third and fourth groups from hatchability eggs sacs untreated fed on the numbers offered from each prey; the two preys were increased as the predator's spiderling old. The numbers of consumed prey from each PBW and *S. littoralis* were recorded daily and the total consumptions were assessed.

8. Statistical analysis:

The relation between duration of different stages also, total of consumption for each prey examined, data were subjected to the analysis of variance test (ANOVA) (one ways classification ANOVA) followed by a least significant difference, LSD at 5% (Costat Statistical Software 1990).

Results and dissection

1.Toxicity of IGR on 1-3 days eggs of *Pectinophora gossypiella*:

The toxicity of the diflurobenzeron against the *P. gossypiella* 1-3 days' old eggs expressed as hatchability number and percentage at different concentrations was presented in Table (1). These results obviously showed that number hatchability was positively correlated with different concentrations which depend on the efficacy of IGR compound; it showing that the total number hatchability increased with decreased the concentrations (6, 26, 44, 36, 61 and 82 eggs hatchability, respectively, at the concentrations of 7.5,15, 30, 60, 120 and 240 ppm, compared to 94 total number hatchability in control and the percent hatchability reductions decreased with decreased the concentrations 94, 74, 56, 64, 39, and 18% eggs reduction at the concentrations of 240, 120, 60, 30, 15 and 7.5 ppm, respectively, compared to 6 % hatchability in control.

Table (1): Effect of diflurobenzeron compound on hatchability *Pectinophora gossypiella* 1-3 days' old eggs.

Tested eggs	Con. (ppm)	Initial number of eggs	No. of hatchability after				Total hatchability	% hatchability reduction
			4 (day)	5 (day)	6 (day)	7day)		
1-3 days	240	100	0	0	0	6	6	94
	120	100	0	0	17	9	26	74
	60	100	0	0	31	13	44	56
	30	100	0	7	39	11	36	64
	15	100	0	3	31	37	61	39
	7.5	100	3	23	49	7	82	18
	Control	100	20	73	1	0	94	6

Also, the results presented in Table (2) summarized that the efficacy of IGR at different concentrations against the hatchability of *S. littoralis* 1-3 days old ' eggs. It's cleared that the different concentrations high effected on number of eggs hatchability, which, decreasing

gradually with an increase the tested concentrations. It recorded by (64, 62, 57, 43, 27 and 11 eggs hatchability, respectively, at the concentrations of (7.5,15, 30, 60,120, and 240 ppm) and the percent hatchability reductions decreased with decreased the concentrations.

Table (2): Effect of diflurobenzeron compound on hatchability of *Spodoptera littoralis* 1-3 old days eggs.

Tested eggs	Con. (ppm)	Initial number of eggs	No. of hatchability after				Total hatchability	% hatchability reduction
			4 (day)	5 (day)	6 (day)	7day)		
1-3 days	240	70	0	0	11	---	11	84.3
	120	70	0	5	22	---	27	61.4
	60	70	0	9	31	3	43	61.43
	30	70	0	7	24	26	57	38.5
	15	70	0	15	31	16	62	88.57
	7.5	70	6	30	25	3	64	91.43
	Control	70	20	41	5	0	66	94.3

2. Effect of diflurobenzeron compound on 1-3 days eggs of the *Thanatus albini* predator:

The toxicity of the diflurobenzeron against the *T. albini* predator days' old eggs sacs expressed as number and percentage of hatchability at different concentrations was presented in Table (3). These results obviously showed that number hatchability was positively correlated with different

concentrations which depend on the efficacy and penetration of compound to the eggs inside the sacs recorded the total number hatchability decreased with increased the concentrations (82, 74, 62, 54, 47 and 11) eggs hatchability from sacs treated at the concentrations of (7.5, 15, 30, 60, 120 and 240 ppm) and the percent hatchability reductions decreased with decreased the concentrations

Table (3) Effect of diflurobenzeron compound on hatchability of *Thanatus albini* 1-3 old days eggs sacs.

Tested eggs sacs	Con. (ppm)	Initial number of eggs sacs	No. of hatchability after from treated				%Total hatchability	%hatchability reduction
			13 (day)	17 (days)	19 (days)	18-25 (days)		
1-3 days	240	2-3 (90)	0	0	0	29	11	89
	120	2-3 (85)	0	0	21	26	47	53
	60	2-3 (87)	0	10	12	32	54	46
	30	2-3 (90)	0	3	29	30	62	38
	15	2-3 (87)	0	13	31	30	74	14.9
	7.5	2-3 (93)	0	16	19	47	82	11.8
	Control	2-3 (70)	0	20	53	12	67	4.82

(2-3 eggs sacs) contents average number from 60-80 eggs inside the eggs sacs.

3. Toxicological effect of diflurobenzeron on eggs of *Pectinoghora gossypiella*, *Spodoptera littoralis* and *Thanatus albini* :

Data in Table (4) showed that LC₅₀ values of diflurobenzeron was more effective against *P. gossypiella* and *S. littoralis* than *T. albini*. The LC₅₀ values were 28.23 and 31.4

ppm for *P. gossypiella* and *S. littoralis* eggs, respectively, and increased approximately to two times with *T. albini*, the LC₅₀ value estimated by 63.24 ppm. Kandil *et al.* (2012) recorded that the toxicological of lufenuron, chlorfluazuron and chromafenozide (IGR) against *P. gossypiella* eggs.

Table (4): Toxicological effect of diflurobenzeron on eggs of *Pectinophora gossypiella*, *Spodoptera littoralis* and *Thanatus albini*.

Comp.	Stage used	LC values				Slop ± SE	
		Instars used	LC ₂₅ (ppm)	LC ₅₀ (ppm)	LC ₉₀ (ppm)		
Diflurobenzeron	1-3 old days eggs	<i>P. gossypiella</i>	8.75	28.23	493.5	1.75	0.15
		<i>S. littoralis</i>	11.57	31.4	571.5	1.85	0.13
		<i>T. albini</i>	21.38	63.24	889.7	1.43	0.19

4. Incubation periods of eggs:

Data presented in Table (5) showed that the egg incubation period averaged 6.3 days/eggs of *S. littoralis* treated, while it decreased to 4.4 days/ eggs in untreated, on the other hand, in, *P. gossypiella* the

incubation period increased approximately two time (6.5 days) in treated than (3.6 days) in untreated and *T. albini* predator the incubation period of eggs sacs was 18.3 days in treated compared with 13.3 days/ egg sac in untreated.

Table (5): Percent of hatchability and incubation period treated eggs of *Spodoptera littoralis*, *Pectinophora gossypiella* and *Thanatus albini* with IGR compound under laboratory condition (25±1°C and 65-70 % RH.).

Compound used	Insect and predator used		Conc. (ppm)	% of hatchability treated	% of hatchability control	Incubation period	
						treated	Control
IGR	Egg stage	<i>S. littoralis</i>	28.23	51	94.3	6.3.3±1.2	4.4±0.3
		<i>P. gossypiella</i>	31.4	50	94	6.5±0.6	3.6±0.5
		<i>T. albimii</i>	63.24	56	98	18.3±1.3	13.3±1.3

T. albini was able to develop successfully from egg to adult stage when fed on *P. gossypiella* and *S. littoralis*; it had seven instars spiderling; the first and 2nd instar spiderlings after hatching from the eggs sacs treated or untreated fed on immature stages of *T. urticae*; but from the 3rd to 7th instar spiderling of *T. albini* fed on treated and untreated *S. littoralis* or *P. gossypiella*.

Data in Table (6) recorded that the total duration from 1st and 2nd instars spiderling of *T. albini* was significantly shorter (17.9 days) when resulted from eggs untreated and fed on *T. urticae* during this period spiderling of *T. albini* consumed 58.3 fed on immature stages of *T. urticae*, while it

was longer (24.6 days) in case of spiderling resulted from treated eggs and consumed 48.9 preys of immature stages of *T. urticae*. Data recorded in Table (7) show that the duration from the 4th to 7th instar was longer duration than other instars in predacious, but the 7th instar decreased in time duration. The duration of different instars of *T. albini* was affected obviously by treatment and two different food sources. The total developmental periods from 3rd to 7th instar of *T. albini*, when fed on *P. gossypiella* eggs treated and untreated were 94.4 and 61.86 days/ respectively, while, being decreased to 84.4 and 63.5 days when provided by *S. littoralis* treated and untreated , respectively.

Table (6): Durations of developmental stages and prey consumption of *Thanatus albini* resulted from eggs treated and fed of *Tetranychus urticae*, at 25±1°C and 65-70 % RH.

Developmental stages <i>T. albini</i>	Duration time <i>Thanatus albini</i> resulted from treated and untreated			Prey consumption of <i>Tetranychus urticae</i>		
	Duration (in days) ±S.E.	Duration (in days) ±S.E.	LSD	Treated ±S.E.	Untreated ±S.E.	LSD
1 st spiderling	11.6±1.2	8.6±0.3	1.521	22.3±1.3	20.0±1.6	0.643
2 nd spiderling	13.0±1.4	9.3±0.3	3.110	26.6±3.5	38.3±1.5	6.127
Total 1 st and 2 nd instars spiderling	24.6±1.8	17.9±1.3	3.244	48.9±4.3	58.3±5.2	5.110

Values are mean ± SE of three replicates.

Values within the same column having the same letters are not significant different (ANOVA, Duncan's multiple range tests, P < 0.05).

Table (7): Duration (in days) *Thanatus albini* resulted from treated eggs with IGR compound and reared under laboratory condition (25±1°C and 65-70 % RH.).

Spiderling	Reared on <i>Pectinophora gossypiella</i>		control		LSD at 5%	<i>Spodoptera littoralis</i>	control		LSD at 5%
	Duration (in days) ±S.E.	Duration (in days) ±S.E.	Duration (in days) ±S.E.	LSD			P	Duration (in days) ±S.E.	
3 rd spiderling	15.6±0.6	10.6±0.66	3.106	**	13.6±0.5	11.3±0.3	0.855	***	
4 th spiderling	18.3±0.6	11.3±0.9	2.615	***	16.3±1.1	13.6±0.5	1.462	***	
5 th spiderling	19.3±0.6	12.0±0.66	4.211	***	17.3±1.3	11.0±0.6	4.213	**	
6 th spiderling	23.6±0.33	16.36±1.5	3.509	**	21.6±2.1	15.6±1.5	3.557	***	
7 th spiderling	17.6±1.3	11.6±0.66	2.11	**	15.6±1.6	12.0±0.7	1.980	***	
Total from 3 rd to 7 th	94.4±6.11	61.86±3.9	6.744	***	84.4±5.9	63.5±4.6	6.471	**	
Total immature stage	119.0±6.9	79.76±4.21	7.182	**	133.3±6.33	81.4±5.4	7.991	***	
Life cycle	137.3±6.5	93.06±6.9	11.254	***	151.16±10.33	82.7	12.211	**	

Values are mean ± SE of three replicates.

Values within the same column having the same letters are not significant different (ANOVA, Duncan's multiple range tests, P < 0.05).

The total immature stage (Total developmental periods) of *T. albini*, when spiderling resulted from untreated eggs and fed on *P. gossypiella* eggs untreated were

79.76 days/ while, being longer 119.0 days when spiderling resulted from treated eggs (Table, 7). In contrast, the total immature stages lasted a longer time (133.3 days) when

they spiderling resulted from treated eggs and fed on *S. littoralis* compared with 81.4 days in control.

5. Food consumption of the immature stages of *Thanatus albini* :

T. albini, the 1st and 2nd spiderling had the least prey consumption rates than the older stages because of their small sizes. They consumed Values gradually increased where increased the ages. The 3rd spiderling consumed an average of 40.0 and 32.6 preys/

T. albini /day on PBW eggs and 22.6 and 18.7 preys, respectively, when they were provided by *S. littoralis* (Table, 8). *T. albini* consumed of *P. gossypiella* more preys during the duration than *S. littoralis* during all stages of the predator. The total food consumption of the predator was 348.0±21.8 and 378.7±32.3 preys from PBW treated and untreated respectively, while that was 248.6±17.6 and 279.7±23.9 preys *S. littoralis* /predator, treated and untreated respectively.

Table (8): Food consumption *Thanatus albini* resulted from treated eggs with IGR diflurobenzeron and reared under laboratory condition (25±1°C and 65-70 % RH.).

Spiderling	Reared on <i>Pectinoghora gossypiella</i>	Control	LSD) x= 0:05		<i>Spodoptera littoralis</i>	Control	LSD) x= 0:05	
	Food consumption ±S.E.	Food consumption ±S.E.	LSD	P	Food consumption ±S.E.	Food consumption ±S.E.	LSD	P
3 rd spiderling	40.0±3.2	32.6±2.7	2.310	**	22.6±2.7	18.7±0.8	2.184	**
4 th spiderling	56.0±3.5	65.1±3.6	5.142	***	44.0±2.3	54.0±3.1	4.681	**
5 th spiderling	78.0±5.1	85.0±5.7	3.171	**	58.0±3.2	64.0±5.2	4.921	***
6 th spiderling	104.0±6.3	116.0±4.5	6.325	***	71.0±4.5	83.0±3.6	6.122	***
7 th spiderling	70.0± 4.9	80.0±6.3	5.114	***	53.0±4.3	60.0±4.8	4.51	**
Total consumption	348.0±21.8	378.7±32.3	7.158	***	248.6±17.6	279.7±23.9	7.722	***

Values are mean ± SE of three replicates.

Values within the same column having the same letters are not significant different (ANOVA, Duncan's multiple range tests, P < 0.05).

Under the laboratory condition some experiments were conducted to study the effect of diflurobenzeron (Dimilin) compound on two insects eggs and spiderling. The results showed that the percent of hatchability increased with increased the concentrations of compound after treated with dimilin, LC₅₀ values dimilin was more (toxicity) effective against *P. gossypiella* and *S. littoralis* than *T. albini*. The LC₅₀ values increased approximately to two times with *T. albini* spiderling predator than two insects. Also, the *T. albini* predator consumed of *P. gossypiella* more preys

during the duration than *S. littoralis* during all stages of the predator

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Potency of some elicitors plant as new approach to control some insect pests infesting okra and their effect on associated predators and okra production compared with the convention insecticide under field condition

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Abstract:

This study was carried out at El-Riyad region, Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate under field conditions during two okra growing seasons, 2018 and 2019 for examining the effect of some elicitors plant (Salicylic acid and jasmonic acid) only and mixture with conventional chemical insecticide compared with conventional chemical insecticide, actacron against the American bollworms, *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hübner), the spiny bollworm *Earias insulana* (Boisduval) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) and okra crop production. The obtained results showed the potentiality of the highest concentration of jasmonic acid mixture with actacron for controlling both *H. armigera* and *E. insulana* as a new approach. The grand reduction percentage of *H. armigera* and *E. insulana* were 97.75, 98.06 and 89.79, 87.54% respectively, in case of okra treated with at the highest concentration 300 ppm of jasmonic acid mixture with actacron (375 ml/ fed.) during at the two successive seasons 2018 and 2019. However, the lowest reduction percentage of *H. armigera* and *E. insulana* were 59.26, 61.08 and 55.87, 54.15% respectively, in case of okra treated with at the lowest concentration 100 ppm of salicylic acid during at the two successive seasons 2018 and 2019. Also, the highest concentration (300 ppm) of salicylic acid mixture with actacron (375 ml/ fFed.) showed moderately control to *H. armigera* and *E. insulana*, where the reduction percentages ranged from 78.34 -53.82 and 75.62-51.14 and for *E. insulana* the reduction percentages ranged between 73.27-48.39 and 71.64-46.67% at three examined rates during the two seasons 2018 and 2019, respectively) compared with other treatments. The highest concentration of jasmonic acid (300 ppm) was more concentration of predators than other treatments. The lowest of predators were found on okra plants in case treated with conventional insecticide. The treatment with highest (300 ppm) of jasmonic acid mixture actacron showed the positive effectiveness in okra yield.

Introduction

Okra, *Abelmoschus esculentus* (L.) , fruit vegetable crops that belongs to family Malvaceae, is widely grown all over tropical, sup tropical and warm temperature regions of the world (Saifullah and Rabbani, 2009). Okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus* L. Moench) is a popular summer vegetable crop in Egypt. The cultivated area in Egypt for okra was nearly 17 thousand feddan (one fed. = 4200m²) and produced about 97 thousand ton in 2012 cropping season (Anonymous, 2013). It is a rich source of some essential vitamins (vitamin C) and mineral salts such as calcium, magnesium, potassium and iron including water at varying proportion (Shippers, 2002). Okra plays an important role in the human diet by supplying fats, proteins, carbohydrates, minerals and vitamins. The composition of okra pods per 100 g edible portion (81% of the product as purchased, ends trimmed) is: water 88.6 g, energy 144.00 kJ (36 kcal), protein 2.10 g, carbohydrate 8.20 g, fats 0.20 g, fibers 1.70 g, Ca 84.00 mg, P 90.00 mg, Fe 1.20 mg, β -carotene 185.00 μ g, riboflavin 0.08 mg, thiamin 0.04 mg, niacin 0.60 mg, ascorbic acid 47.00 mg. (Gopalan *et al.*, 2007 and Varmudy, 2011).

One of the important limiting factors in the cultivation of okra vegetable plants is insect pests. As high as 72 species of insects have been recorded on okra plant (Srinivas and Rajendran, 2003), among of them fruit borers like *Earias* spp. and *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hübner) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) cause significant damage to crop to the tune of 91.60 % percent (Pareek and Bhargava, 2003). The fruit borers are alone reported to cause damage to the extent of 3.5 to 90 % percent to okra in different parts of the country (Mandal *et al.*, 2006). In general, the overall damage due to insect pests accounts to 48.97 % loss in fruit yields (Kanwar and Ameta, 2007). The caterpillar of the American bollworm *H. armigera*

prefers the reproductive parts of the plant, including bands, flowers and fruits. Also, this insect attacks the ripped and pre ripped fruits, contaminating them fraises and exposing them to fungi and bacteria (Ahmed, 2000). Although several workers tested different chemicals against fruit borer, still the problem continues .Plants with aromatic qualities contain volatile oils that may interfere with host plant location, feeding, distribution and mating can decrease the pest abundance (Uvah and Coaked, 1984 and Lu *et al.*, 2007). Plants have developed an elegant defenses system against insect herbivore. The defense systems employed by plants against insects can be constitutive or induced. Constitutive resistance is present in plants all the time, whereas induced resistance occurs in response to various stimuli such as insect herbivory pathogen infection and/or elicitor application.(Wasternack, 2007; Chitra *et al.*, 2008 and Kawazu *et al.*, 2012). Induced resistance is very important as it makes plants phenotypically plastic, thereby making it freakish for the insect pests to feed on it (Scot *et al.*, 2010 and He *et al.*, 2011). Induced resistance can be direct or indirect. Direct induced resistance directly effects on the insect pest through antixenosis and/or antibiosis mechanisms (Sharma and Norris, 1991 and Sharma *et al.*, 2009) whereas indirect induced resistance is mediated through volatiles emitted by the plants in response to insect damage, which attract the natural enemies (parasitoids and predators) of the insect pests (Heng-Moss *et al.*, 2004 and Arimura *et al.*, 2008). Although many plant hormones act as elicitors of induced resistance, the most important and widely used phytohormones are jasmonic acid (JA) and salicylic acid (SA) (Kawazu *et al.*, 2012 and Zhao *et al.*, 2009). The use of these phytohormones in inducing plant resistance against insect pests has raised the possibility of their implications for insect

pest management. Exogenous application of JA results in the induction of plant responses that are almost like herbivore feeding. The JA-mediated octadecanoid pathway leads to the production of many defensive components, such as plant defensive proteins, oxidative enzymes, glandular trichomes, flavonoids, terpenoids, alkaloids, volatile compounds (Wasternack, 2007; Scott *et al.*, 2010 and Arimura *et al.*, 2008). Systemic acquired resistance (SAR) is defined as the induced response to various biotic (feeding by insects or infections by pathogenic organisms) and abiotic or chemical elicitors (Such as salicylic acid and jasmonic acid), attributed to the synthesis of defensive phytochemicals (Kogan and Paxton, 1983). However, the research in the induced resistance against insect herbivore is limited (Karban and Kuc, 1999).

The present study hypothesized that salicylic acid (SA) and jasmonic acid (JA), as an inducer for plant resistance, can be used to activate the effectiveness of insecticides (Profenofos: Actacron) against the spiny bollworms *E. insulana*, and the American bollworms *H. armigera*. Therefore, this study aimed to reduce the amount of used insecticides (Actacron) by mixing them with SA and JA to control the spiny bollworms *E. insulana*, and the American bollworms *H. armigera*, and in relation to its associated predators as well as okra crop production under field conditions.

Materials and methods

1. Materials used:

Elicitor plants: Aqueous solutions of elicitors prepared from:

1.1. The salicylic acid: It were obtained from (Oxford Lab Chemicals unit No. 12,1st Neminath C7 H 603S), The salicylic acid (with a purity of 99.99%.) was dissolved in 1 ml of ethanol 95% before dispersed in one liter of tap water (Hussein *et al.*, 2014). Three concentration of salicylic acid (100,

200 and 300 ppm/4200 m²) were used under field conditions.

1.2. The Jasmonic acid: Jasmonic acid preparation: Synthetic JA was dissolved in 1 ml of ethanol 95% and dispersed in an appropriate volume of water to achieve 5 mM JA solution (Thaler , 1999). The control solution consisted of only 1 ml of ethanol 95% / 1L. dissolved in water. Three concentration of jasmonic acid (100, 200 and 300 ppm/4200 m²) were used under field conditions.

1.3. The tested insecticide: (Profenofos: Actacron) was used in this study by according to the recommended rate: 750 ml / fed. (750ml/200-liter of water). This insecticide is recommended for control of *H. armigera* and *E insulana* in vegetable crops.

1.4. Mixture of salicylic acid (SA) with half recommended rate actacron: at three concentrations SA100 ppm+ 375 ml/ fed. Actacron, SA 200 ppm + 375 ml/ fed. Actacron and SA 300 ppm + 375 ml/fed. Actacron were used under field conditions.

1.5. Mixture of jasmonic acid (JA) with half recommended rate actacron: at three concentrations JA 100 ppm+ 375 ml/ fed. Actacron , JA 200 ppm + 375 ml/ fed. Actacron and JA 300 ppm + 375 ml/ fed. Actacron were used under field conditions.

Percentages fruit infestation = Number of damaged fruits /total number of fruits × 100.

2. Experimental :

The experiment was carried out during two okra growing seasons; 2018 and 2019 on the *E. insulana* and American bollworm *H. armigera* at El-Raid region, Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate, Egypt. An area of one feddan was prepared (15 treatments × 4 replicate) and divided into 60 plots (each plot about 70 m²) in a randomized complete block design. The seeds of okra (Ladies fingers Mansoura Red Varsity) were sowed at rate 2 seeds of hole on two sides of each row with widths of 100 cm spacing and 30 cm between plants during the two seasons, of

2018 and 2019 on April 10th. Horticultural practices were performed according to the recommendations of the Ministry of Agriculture and Land Reclamation of Egypt, but without any pesticides application. Weekly samples of *E. insulana*, *H. armigera* larval were taken randomly beginning from May 25th up to September 25th. Each sample consisted of 25 fruits from five plants randomly chosen (five fruits/ plant) and it was repeated four times. Application of salicylic acid, jasmonic acid at three concentration (100, 200 300 pm) only, salicylic acid, jasmonic acid at three concentration (100, 200 300 pm) mixture with conventional chemical insecticide compared with conventional chemical insecticide were implemented at economic threshold of fruit damage due to *E. insulana* and *H. armigera* (*i.e.* 5% fruit damage) by using high volume knapsack sprayer with the required concentration of salicylic acid, jasmonic acid, salicylic acid, jasmonic acid at three concentration (100, 200 300 pm) mixed with conventional chemical insecticide and conventional chemical insecticide as well as water (control) ethanol were applied on the okra plants four times at 15 days interval during the period from June 15th up to August 15th. Subsequent spray was given based the levels of infestation during both seasons of experiments, 2018 and 2019. The numbers of larvae and reduction percentages of *E. insulana* and *H. armigera* were recorded from five plants randomly chosen (five fruits/plant) repeated four times per treatment -wise before spray as well as 7 and 14 days after each sprays. Observations on fruits damage due to *E. insulana*, *H. armigera* were recorded at each picking by counting the healthy and damaged fruits from net plot area on number as well as weights and percent fruit damage was worked out by using the following formula. The yield of marketable okra fruits from each treatment was recorded at each picking separately.

3. Abundance of associated predators:

The insect predators *Coccinella* sp. (Coleoptera, Coccinellidae) (eggs, larvae and adults), *Chrysoperla carnea* (Stephens) (Neuroptera: Chrysopidae) (eggs and larvae), *Paederus alfieri* Koch. (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae) (adults), *Scymnus* spp. (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) (larvae and adults), spiders (spiderlings and adults) were recorded and counted by the aid of lens from five plant/replicate, randomly selected per treatment by four replication-wise before spray as well as 7 and 14 days after each sprays. Each sample repeated four times beginning from May 25th up to September 25th.

4. Statistical analysis:

Data were subjected to the analysis of variance and differences among means were compared according to Duncan's Multiple Range Test (**Duncan, 1955**). Percentage of reduction was calculated according to **Henderson and Tilton (1955)**.

Results and discussion

1. Effect of elicitors plant alone, mixture with actacron compared with actacron insecticide on *Helicoverpa armigera* larvae infesting okra plants during 2018 and 2019 seasons:

Data presented in Table (1) show the reduction percentage resulted from six treatments namely; salicylic acid (SA) + actacron (three rates), jasmonic acid (JA) + actacron (three rates also), salicylic acid (SA), jasmonic acid (JA), ethanol and chemical insecticide, actacron (recommended rate) during two growing of seasons 2018 and 2019.

The efficacy of the applied treatments against *H. armigera* larvae infesting okra plants under field conditions with respect to the larval mortality are presented in Table (1) during two experimental seasons 2018 and 2019. All the tested treatments were effective against the *H. armigera* larvae infesting okra plants under field conditions relative to the control treatment. The highest reduction percentage in the *H. armigera* larvae was

occurred on okra plants treated with the high rate (300 ppm) of jasmonic acid mixed with chemical insecticide (at the rate 375 ml/ fed.), followed by the high rate (300 ppm) of jasmonic acid with respect to the reduction in the larvae counts in treated plants. The general mean reduction percentages of the *H. armigera* larvae during two of the experimental during, 2018 and 2019 seasons are shown in Table (1). Results during the

two seasons indicated that the high rate (300 ppm) of jasmonic acid mixed with chemical insecticide (at the rate 375 ml/ fed.), treatments were the most effective compared with other treatments, followed, by the high rate (300 ppm) of jasmonic acid mixture with actacron on the basis of reduction rates in the infestation by *H. armigera* larvae. The statistical analysis showed significant differences among all treatments.

Table(1): Effect of elicitor plants and actacron insecticide on the reduction percentages in *Helicoverpia armigera* larvae at El-Raid region, Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate, during two seasons of 2018 and 2019.

Treatment	Conce- Nitation	1 st Spray	2 nd Spray	3 rd spray	4 th spray	Average
Reduction percentages in <i>Helicoverpia armigera</i> larvae during 2018 season						
Jasmonic acid (JA)+ actacron	300 + 375	93.75 b	98.50 a	99.75 a	98.99 a	97.75 a
	200 + 375	79.00 d	88.45 b	96.57 a	97.85 a	90.47 b
	100 + 375	74.57 e	78.36 c	83.10 c	86.99 c	80.76 d
Salicylic acid (SA)+ actacron	300 + 375	78.90 d	82.35 c	88.00 c	91.67 b	85.23 c
	200 + 375	70.33 e	75.92 d	81.66 d	86.80 c	78.68 d
	100+ 375	62.55 f	69.00 e	75.63 e	81.22 d	72.10 e
Jasmonic acid (JA)	300 ppm	87.67c	96.96 a	98.00 a	98.78 a	95.35 a
	200 ppm	75.96 d	81.89 c	93.00 b	96.78 a	86.91 c
	100 ppm	62.99 f	70.85 e	80.22 d	85.75 c	75.95 e
Salicylic acid (SA)	300 ppm	70.25 e	77.00 c	86.36 c	90.15 b	80.94 d
	200 ppm	60.25 f	66.58 e	72.63 e	80.97 d	70.11 f
	100 ppm	46.00 g	56.22 f	60.25 f	70.55 f	58.26 g
Actacron	750ml./fed.	97.26 a	91.50 a	87.35 b	81.75 d	89.46 b
Ethanol	1ml/1L.water	-	-	-	-	-
Reduction percentages in <i>Helicoverpia armigera</i> larvae during 2019 season						
Jasmonic acid (JA)+ actacron	300 + 375	94.75 b	99.00 a	99.50 a	99.00 a	98.06 a
	200 + 375	81.50 d	89.99 b	95.50 a	99.99 a	91.75 b
	100 + 375	76.98 e	81.63 c	85.13 c	88.25 c	83.00 d
Salicylic acid (SA)+ actacron	300 + 375	79.99 d	83.78 c	89.95 c	93.65 b	86.84 c
	200 + 375	74.37 e	78.11 d	83.56 d	88.00 c	81.01 d
	100 + 375	68.36 f	70.90 e	77.33 e	83.75 d	75.09 e
Jasmonic acid (JA))	300	89.99 c	98.98 a	99.88 a	99.13 a	97.00 a
	200	78.15 d	83.26 c	95.10 b	98.99 a	88.88 c
	100	68.23 f	75.90 e	82.92 d	87.50 c	78.64 e
Salicylic acid (SA)	300	71.57 e	78.99 c	88.94 c	93.25 b	83.19 d
	200	62.77 f	68.93 e	75.10 e	82.99 d	72.45 f
	100	47.10 g	57.35 f	61.99 f	73.87 f	60.08 g
Actacron	750/fed.	98.86 a	93.92 a	89.99 b	84.65 d	91.86 b
Ethanol	1ml/ 1L.water	-	-	-	-	-

Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT

2. Effect of some elicitors plants and conventional insecticide on the reduction percentages in *Earias insulana* larvae during two seasons of 2018 and 2019:

All plants treated with significant reduction in the toxicants showed numbers of larvae infesting okra plants compared to okra untreated plants during both 2018 and 2019 of experiments (Table, 2). The highest reduction percentages in the *E. insulana* larvae were 89.79, 87.54 and 86.27, 84.52 %, during the two seasons of 2018 and 2019 respectively in case of treating the okra pants with the highest concentrations of 300 ppm of jasmonic acid mixed with actacron and actacron (at the rate 375 ml/ fed);

respectively followed by 84.57and 83.07 %, reduction in the pest infesting okra plants treated with the highest concentrations of 300 ppm of jasmonic acid in 2018 and 2019 experiments. Okra plants treated with ate the highest rate (300 ppm) of jasmonic acid mixed with conventional insecticide and the highest concentrations of 300 ppm of jasmonic acid were significantly higher than the other treatments. However, as shown in Table (2). The lowest reduction percentage of *E. insulana* larvae 55.87 and 54.15 %, was recorded during experiments, of 2018 and 2019 seasons, respectively followed by the okra plants were treated by the lowest concentration of salicylic acid (100 ppm).

Table (2): Effect of some elicitors plants and conventional insecticide on the reduction percentages in *Earias insulana* larvae at El-Raid region, Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate, during two seasons of 2018 and 2019.

Treatment	Concentration	1 st Spray	2 nd spray	3 rd spray	4 th spray	Average
Reduction percentages in <i>Earias insulana</i> larvae during 2018 season						
Jasmonic acid (JA)+ actacron	300 + 375	76.25 b	87.91 a	95.99 a	99.00 a	89.79 a
	200 + 375	70.33 c	78.63 b	88.23 b	95.99 a	83.30 a
	100 + 375	60.33 d	66.99 d	72.90 c	81.54 c	70.44 e
Salicylic acid (SA)+ actacron	300 + 375	70.0 c	75.76 b	82.99 b	90.75 b	79.88 b
	200 + 375	66.00 c	71.75 c	77.10 c	83.95 c	74.70 c
	100 + 375	56.15 d	62.36 d	70.00 c	76.80 c	66.33 d
Jasmonic acid (JA)	300 ppm	69.23 c	80.63 b	92.15 a	96.25 a	84.57 a
	200 ppm	57.52 d	64.00 d	72.85 c	80.47 c	68.71 d
	100 ppm	50.96 e	56.25 e	63.50 d	71.90 d	60.65 e
Salicylic acid (SA)	300 ppm	66.25 c	73.45 c	79.36 b	91.90 b	77.74 c
	200 ppm	53.75 d	63.34 d	70.25 c	81.97 c	67.33 d
	100 ppm	45.00 f	51.23 f	60.50 d	66.75 e	55.87 f
Actacron	750/fedd.	93.00 a	88.19 a	85.35 b	78.55 c	86.27 a
Ethanol	1ml/1L.water	-	-	-	-	-
Reduction percentages in <i>Earias insulana</i> larvae during 2019 season						
Jasmonic acid (JA)+ actacron	300 + 375	74.25 b	85.91 a	94.99 a	99.00 a	87.54 a
	200 + 375	66.33 c	75.63 b	85.23 b	94.99 a	80.55 a
	100 + 375	61.33 d	66.99 d	72.90 c	80.54 c	68.44 e
Salicylic acid (SA)+ actacron	300 + 375	66.0 c	74.76 b	80.99 b	90.75 b	78.13 b
	200 + 375	60.00 c	70.75 c	76.10 c	81.95 c	72.20 c
	100 + 375	51.15 d	60.36 d	70.00 c	76.80 c	64.58 d
Jasmonic acid (JA))	300 ppm	66.23 c	79.63 b	90.15 a	96.25	83.07 a
	200 ppm	53.52 d	62.00 d	71.85 c	80.47 c	66.96 d
	100 ppm	47.96 e	53.25 e	63.50 d	71.90 d	59.15 e
Salicylic acid (SA)	300 ppm	60.25 c	71.45 c	75.36 b	91.90 b	74.74 c
	200 ppm	50.75 d	56.34 d	77.25 c	81.97 c	64.08 d
	100 ppm	41.00 f	48.23 f	60.50 d	66.75 e	54.15 f
Actacron	750/fed.	93.00 a	88.19 a	81.35 b	75.55 c	84.52 a
Ethanol	1ml/1L.water	-	-	-	-	-

Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT

3. Effects of some elicitors plant and actacron insecticide on marketable fruit yield crop of okra plants:

The effects of treatments on marketable fruit yield for both years are shown in Table (3). All treatments significantly increased the marketable fruit yield compared with untreated okra plants in both years. The highest percentage of the marketable fruit yield of okra was obtained

from plants treated by the highest concentration (300 ppm) of jasmonic acid mixed with conventional insecticide; followed, by okra plants treated with jasmonic acid and conventional insecticide as compared with the other treatments. Conversely, the lowest percentage of marketable fruit yield was recorded for the untreated okra plants.

Table (3): Effects of some elicitors plant and actacron insecticide on marketable fruit yield crop of okra plants during 2018 and 2019 experiments at El-Raid region, Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate.

Treatment	concentration (ppm)/ fed.	2018	2019
		Percentage	Percentage
Jasmonic acid (JA)+ actacron	300 ppm + 375 mL	96.00 a	97.00 a
	200 ppm +375 mL	85.00 c	87.00 c
	100 ppm +375 mL	70.00 d	71.00 d
Salicylic acid (SA)+ actacron	300 ppm+ 375 mL	91.00 b	89.00 b
	200 ppm + 375 mL	79.00 c	77.00 c
	100 ppm+ 375 ml	63.00 e	65.00 e
Jasmonic acid (JA))	300 ppm	87.00 b	89.00 b
	200 ppm	80.00 c	82.00 c
	100 ppm	60.00 e	61.00 e
Salicylic acid (SA)	300 ppm	79.00 b	80.00 b
	200 ppm	72.00 d	73.00 d
	100 ppm	51.00 f	53.00 f
Actacron	60ml/fed.	90.00 b	91.00 b
Ethanol	1ml/1L.water	20.25 g	21.00 g
Control	-	20.00 g	21.00 g

Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

This study aims to screen the response of okra plants to some elicitors plant salicylic acid, jasmonic acid only and mixture with conventional insecticide compared with the conventional insecticide open field conditions in order to minimize using pesticide and its side effect in the consumer health. In the current study, the highest concentration of jasmonic acid mixed with conventional insecticide and the conventional insecticide actacron showed the highest reduction in the

number of larvae of *H. armigera* and *E.insulana*; also jasmonic acid kept the participated number of predators associated with *H. armigera* and *E.insulana* compared on the plants treated with the other two. Reduction percentages in *H. armigera* and *E.insulana* were obtained when okra plants treated with the highest concentration of jasmonic acid mixed with conventional insecticide compared to control. Plant response to the highest concentration of

jasmonic acid mixed with conventional insecticide showed significantly effects compared to the other treatments as well as the untreated control. The highest reduction in *H. armigera* and *E.insulana* population larvae was noticed on okra plants treated with the highest concentration of jasmonic acid mixed with conventional insecticide. These results agree with those obtained by Ali (2008). reported that the infestation levels with spiny bollworm were decreased when cotton was sprayed with combination of the insecticides used with salicylic acid compared with cotton treated with salicylic acid only and untreated cotton. These results are agreement with those reported by Peng *et al.* (2004), Younis and Ibrahim (2012), Al-Kazafy (2013), Zidan *et al.* (2012) and Albeltagy *et al.* (2013). Resistance induced in many plant species is known to influence the fitness and performance of insect pests (Mithöfer and Boland, 2012). However, the induced resistance by elicitors did not produce any phytotoxicity or negative effect on natural enemies (Bruce, 2014). Thaler (1999) reported that foliar JA application on tomato plants increased levels of polyphenol oxidase an oxidative enzyme implicated in resistance against several insect herbivores. responsible for producing certain secondary metabolites which decrease the survival of herbivores (Thaler *et al.*, 2001). This was also evidenced in *Spodoptera exigua* (Hübner) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae), feeding on induced foliage (Stout and Duffey, 1996). The high rate of pupal mortality of cotton bollworm (*H. armigera*) was correlated with high concentration of SA under laboratory conditions (Sivamani *et al.*, 1992). Farouk and Osman (2011) reported that foliar application of salicylic acid (SA) or methyl jasmonate (MeJA) on common bean plants before or after two spotted spider mite infestation proved to be effective in reducing infestations. The post-ingestive interaction between insect pests and plant toxins plays a significant role in determining

the resistance/susceptibility of plant tissues to insects. Induced resistance is an important component in this respect because it leads to the production of various toxic secondary metabolites and other compounds, which affect insect physiology, and growth and development. The negative effects of induced resistance on insect pests are attributed to the lower nutritional value of plant tissues and the toxicity of allelochemicals, proteins and protease inhibitors (Bhonwong *et al.*, 2009 and Barbehenn *et al.*, 2010). SA induces resistance against sap sucking insects and pathogens (Zhao *et al.*, 2009).The results showed that silica nanoparticles and actrone insecticide were the most effective treatment against *H. armigera* and *E.insulana* larvae infesting okra plants. The tested insecticide showed highly efficacy against *H. armigera* and the results agree with the findings of Wollweber and Tietjen (1999) as well as FERA (2009), they reported that neonicotinoid insecticides are effective against larval infestation of *H. armigera* on tomato plants.

4. Effect of some elicitors plant and conventional insecticide on the participated predators:

Data recorded in Table (4) indicated that okra plants treated by the highest concentration of jasmonic acid (300 ppm) had the highest population density of all participated predators during the two 2018 and 2019 seasons, except for *C. carnea* compared with the other treated plants. However, the lowest mean number of predators was noticed on okra treated with insecticide, followed by okra plants treated with the lowest concentration of salicylic acid (100 ppm) actacron (375 aml/ fed.). These rustles are agreed with resistance induced in many plant species is known to influence the fitness and performance of insect pests (Mithöfer and Boland, 2012). However, the induced resistance by elicitors did not produce any phytotoxicity or negative effect on natural enemies (Bruce, 2014).

Table(4): Effect of silica nanoparticles, peppermint extract and actacron insecticide on predators participated in okra plants during growing season of 2018 and 2019.

Treatment	Concentration ppm/ fed.	<i>Chrysoperla carnea</i>	<i>Coccinela</i> spp.	<i>Paederus alfieri</i>	<i>Scymnus</i> spp.	True spider
Mean number/ five okra plants during 2018 season						
Jasmonic acid	300 ppm	45.25 c	75.50 a	35.00 a	55.25 a	59.25 a
	200 ppm	38.50 d	61.50 b	25.50 c	41.00 b	49.00 b
	100 ppm	32.25 e	50.25 d	19.75 d	32.75 d	37.50 d
Salicylic acid	300 ppm	63.0 a	55.00 c	30.00 b	46.00 b	43.75 c
	200 ppm	54.75 b	43.25 e	23.50 c	30.25 d	33.25 d
	100 ppm	41.75 d	35.00 f	18.25 d	23.00f	25.50 e
Jasmonic acid + actacron	300 ppm + 375	40.25 d	66.00 b	30.75 b	45.00 b	35.25 d
	200 ppm + 375	33.00 e	55.25 c	20.75 d	36.50 c	27.00 e
	100ppm+375	27.25 f	44.50 e	11.75 e	20.75 f	18.75f
Salicylic acid+actacron	300ppm+375	53.50 b	48.25 d	24.25 c	37.00 c	32.00 d
	200ppm+375	45.25 c	35.50 f	20.75 d	25.00 e	26.75 e
	100ppm+375	25.00 f	27.00 g	12.00 e	20.75 f	19.50 f
Control	-	19.75 g	21.00 h	8.25 f	13.50 g	15.00 g
Ethanol	1m/ L.water	19.25 g	21.25 h	8.50 .f	13.25g	14.75 g
Actacron	750 ml	2.25 h	13.50 i	1.00 g	5.75 h	3.25 h
Mean number/ five okra plants during 2019 season						
Jasmonic acid	300 ppm	48.75 c	79.75 a	39.50 a	59.50a	56.50a
	200 ppm	42.00 d	63.60 b	27.00 c	45.75b	45.50b
	100 ppm	34.50 e	53.75 d	20.25 d	35.25d	35.00d
Salicylic acid	300 ppm	69.25 a	58.50 c	33.00 b	49.50b	44.25c
	200 ppm	58.50 b	47.75 e	24.50 c	32.75d	30.50d
	100 ppm	44.75 d	39.50 f	17.75 d	25.50f	22.00e
Jasmonic acid+ actacron	300ppm+375	44.75 d	73.75 b	32.50 e	42.50b	32.50d
	200ppm+375	38.50 e	60.75 c	23.25 c	47.25c	23.00e
	100ppm+375	31.75 f	46.00 e	14.50 d	18.75f	18.50f
Salicylic acid+actacron	300ppm+375	56.00 b	50.75 d	27.75	39.50c	29.50d
	200ppm+375	49.75 c	39.00 f	21.50 d	31.50e	24.75e
	100ppm+375	28.50 f	29.50 g	13.75 e	23.50f	18.50f
Control	-	21.25 g	22.50 h	9.50 f	15.75g	14.00g
Ethanol	1m/ L. water	21.00 g	22.25 h	9.25 f	15.50g	14.00g
Actacron	750	2.50 h	12.50 i	1.50	6.75h	3.25h

Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

5. Effect of some elicitors' plant and actacron insecticide on okra yield:

Data illustrated in Table (5) present the okra yield as an average two seasons of 2018 and 2019 as affected by the tested insecticides and their different rate of treatments. Okra treated by the highest

concentration of jasmonic acid (300 ppm) mixture with actacron (375 ml/fed.) pattern proved to be the best compound. This compound produced 249.25 and 255.00 K.g. / Kirat in 2018 and 2019 seasons, respectively. In 2018 and 2019 season experiments, data presented in Table (5) indicated that total

yield reduction of okra was influenced by different concentrations of elicitor treatments, other treatments compared to untreated okra plants (Table, 5). The highest total fruit yield (as weight and number) was obtained with foliar spray with the highest concentration (300 ppm) of jasmonic acid mixed with conventional insecticide, while plants sprayed with ethanol only and okra untreated (control) recorded the lowest values (Table,

5). The highest concentration of jasmonic acid mixed with conventional insecticide (300 ppm) gave 249.25 and 255.00 Kg / Kirat which about 1495.5 and 1530.00 value L.E./ Kirat , respectively, during two seasons of 2018 and 2019 , while the control plant gave 66.25 and 68.75 kg/ Kirat, respectively during two seasons of 2018 and 2019 (Table, 5).

Table (5): Effect of silica nanoparticles, peppermint extract and actacron insecticide on okra yield.

Treatment	Rate/fed.	2018 season			2019 season		
		Yield production (K. g./ Kirat)	Value L.E./ Kirat	Relative Price Benefit%	Yield production (K. g./ Kirat)	Value L.E./ Kirat	Relative Price Benefit%
Jasmonic acid+ actacron	300+375	249.25a	1495.5	376.06	255.00a	1530.0	370.91
	200+375	215.25b	1291.5	324.76	219.75b	1318.5	319.64
	100+375	180.50d	1083.0	272.33	185.00d	1110.0	269.09
Salicylic acid+ actacron	300+375	195.50c	1173.0	295.96	199.25c	1195.5	289.81
	200+375	155.25e	931.5	294.96	157.50e	945.0	229.09
	100+375	120.00f	720.0	181.05	124.75f	748.5	181.45
Jasmonic acid	300 ppm	200.75c	1204.5	302.88	210.25c	1261.5	305.82
	200 ppm	188.50c	1131.0	284.40	193.50c	1161.0	281.45
	100 ppm	156.25e	937.5	235.74	161.50e	969.0	234.90
Salicylic acid	300 ppm	170.25d	1021.5	256.86	177.00d	1062.0	257.45
	200 ppm	156.50e	939.0	236.12	160.75e	964.5	233.81
	100 ppm	123.75f	742.5	186.71	127.75f	766.5	185.81
Actacron	750 ml/ fed	212.25b	1273.5	320.23	216.00b	1296.0	314.18
Control		66.25g	397.68	-	68.75g	412.5	-
Ethenol	1ml/ L. Wat	66.25g	397.68	-	68.75g	412.5	-

Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

The highest okra yield was occurred on okra treated by the highest concentration of jasmonic acid mixture with conventional insecticide, these results agree with some investigators. In most concentrations these elicitors significantly improved common bean plant growth i.e. had a positive effect on plant height, number of branches, shoot dry weight and leaf area per plant and bean yield (Farouk and Osman, 2011). Salicylic acid (SA) (o-hydroxybenzoic acid), is a plant phenolic, widely distributed throughout the plant kingdom. It is a hormone-like substance, which plays an important role in the regulation many aspects of plant growth and development (Raskin, 1992).

It is concluded that jasmonic acid mixed with actacron insecticide showed highly efficient compound in the reduction in the infestation of *E. insulana* and *H. armigera* compared to check and the other treated on okra plants. Salicylic acid mixed with actacron insecticide treatments showed moderate efficient in control this insect however, the highest total number of predators was found on okra plants treated with the highest concentration of jasmonic acid. Generally, additional studies showed be investigated to study the side effects of tested elicitors plant on parasitoids and environmental.

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**Effect of different diets on the development and fecundity of the predacious cunaxid mite
Neocunaxoides arboreus (Acari: Cunaxidae) at different laboratory conditions**

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Abstract:

This study was undertaken to study the biological aspects on the common predacious cunaxid mite species, *Neocunaxoides arboreus* (Den Heyer) (Acari: Cunaxidae). It was reared on free living nematode (*Rhabditella muscicola* Chitwood), acarid mite, *Tyrophagus putrescentiae* (Shrank) and *Aspergillus flavus* Link. at different laboratory conditions. Current studies showed that, the lower temperature 20 °C significantly increased the life periods of individuals in comparison with 35°C. The study showed that the obtained incubation period when the males of *N. arboreus* fed on different diets showed slightly differences between the different individuals and recorded 6.79, 6.81 and 6.77 days when the males fed on the free living nematode, acarid mite and *A. flavus*, at 20 °C, respectively. The results cleared that the life cycle of obtained males significantly differed according to the introduced diets, as, it longest when the mite fed the acarid mite (29.09 days) and shortest on *A. flavus* (24.09 days), but the resulted life cycle on the living nematode recoded (27.74 days). However, the results indicated that the averaged longevity of *N. arboreus* male individuals recorded 28.96, 26.48 and 31.81 days when the mite fed on free living nematodes, acarid mite and *A. flavus*, respectively at 20 °C. The same trends were observed for the different males and females at 25, 30 and 35 °C, as the kind of foods significantly affected on the biological aspects (incubation period, life cycle, longevity and life span of *N. arboreus*) males and females.

Introduction

Mites of the family Cunaxidae (Acari) are cosmopolitan predators that occur in soil, leaf litter, compost, moss, plants and stored products (Zhang, 2003). A little is known about the biology of cunaxids, the life cycle

of only seven species of this family has been studied (Castro and Moraes, 2010). The prey preference of a predator may be affected not only by characteristics of a prey item as food, but also by the microenvironment or

architecture produced by a prey species (Furuichi *et al.*, 2005). Their potential as control agents of plant pests has not been adequately investigated but it has been suggested that mass production of these mites could be hampered by their strong tendency towards cannibalism (Gerson *et al.*, 2003). Feeding capacity of the cunaxid mite *Neocunaxoides andrei* (Baker and Hoffmann) (Acari : Cunaxidae) and its feeding capability on the rootknot nematode *Meloidogyne javanica* Chitwood, under laboratory or semi field conditions were studied (Shoala and El Kady , 2009). Zaher *et al.* (1975) stated that *Cunaxa capreolus* (Berlese) (Acari: Cunaxidae) failed to develop on diets of plant material but developed equally well on diets of book lice or citrus brown mites, *Eutetranychus orientalis* (Klein) (Acari: Tetranychidae) which were eaten in their active stages and not as eggs. Taha *et al.* (1988) studied the effect of feeding by *N. andrei* on *Panagmlaimus rigidus* (Schneider) and immature stages of *Caloglyphus rhizoglyphoides* (Zachvatkin) on development time and fecundity of the mite in the laboratory at 30 °C and 70% RH. Predators fed on nematodes developed faster (21.2 and 18.1 days for development of immature females and males, respectively) than those fed on acarid mite (23.1 and 19.85 days). However, female longevity was 55.7 days with mites as prey and 45.8 days with nematodes.

The aim of the present work is to study the effect of different diets on the development and fecundity of the predacious cunaxid mite *Neocunaxoides arboreus* (Den Heyer) (Acari: Cunaxidae) at different laboratory conditions.

Materials and methods

The mite samples were collected under tomato plants in Qalubiya Governorate (Qaha region). The cunaxid mite, *N. arboreus* extraction was carried out using modified

Tullgren funnels. Each funnel has 60-Watt electric lamp. Samples of tested mites exposed to light for 24 hrs., and the extracted mites were received in petri-dishes (diameter 9 cm, high 1.5 cm) filled with water. Three adults females and males of the cunaxid mite were placed in screening cells (2.5 cm in diameter), with a layer of mixture of plaster of Paris and charcoal (9:1) on its bottom to depth 5 mm and covered with slide cover and binded by robber band. The cells were supplied with food and kept at 25±2°C and about 75±5% RH. About two water drops were added when needed. For individual unit rearing, newly deposited eggs were transferred each to a rearing plastic cell. Each newly hatched larva was supplied with different tested food, free living nematode, acarid mite, *Tyrophagus putrescentiae* (Schrank) (Acari: Acaridae) and the fungus *Aspergillus flavus* and consumed food was replaced every 2 days interval with another new one till reaching maturity stage.

1. Rearing cells:

Mites were reared as individuals using small hemispherical of ½ inch in diameter and less than ¼ inch in depth. Bottom of each cell was covered with mixed of plaster of Paris and charcoal, and the top of each cell covered with small slide glass.

1.1. Free-living nematodes:

Broad bean and maize soil samples were put in Barman funnel for 24 hours for extracting nematodes (Abou-El-Sood, 1992). The extraction of free living nematode *Meloidogyne javanica* Chitwood was cultured in petri-dishes that contain slices of potatoes. Petri-dishes were kept under laboratory conditions at 25°C. Camel hair brushes were used to add drops of food in rearing cells of the predatory mite as the main source of food. All cultures of predators and preys were kept in laboratory at two different degrees of temperature (25 and 35 °C) and 75±5 % RH. All obtained data were

presented as means +S.D. often replicates, and all observations were recorded by means of a stereomicroscope. The obtained data were subjected to one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and means were separated by Duncan's multiple range test (Duncan, 1955).

1.2. Acarid mite *Tyrophagus putrescentiae*:

The astigmatid mite, *T. putrescentiae*, was extracted from the same fauna (debris of tomato plants at Qaha region, Qalubiyah Governorate) by aiding of a Berlese funnel. For preparing pure culture of tested mite, plastic cups of (1.5 cm high x 2.5 cm in diameter) were filled up to 0.5 cm with plaster of Paris and activated charcoal in the rate of 8: 2, respectively.

2. Biological studies of *Neocunaxoides arboreus*:

Eggs of *N. arboreus* were incubated until hatching. The newly hatched larvae were reared singly in rearing cell and fed during its life span on one of the tested diets. In all cases, number of surviving *N. arboreus*, the duration of each stage in days and egg product were assessed twice daily.

2.1. Behavior :

Field observations showed that the predatory mite *N. arboreus* was usually found around their active prey individuals only. When touching the prey, it quickly moved backward to attack it. The predator seized firmly the prey with the aid of its raptorial palps, then inserted its chelicerae in any part of the body and sucked its contents. Life history of *N. arboreus* females pass through one larval and three nymphal stages (protonymph, deutonymph, and tritonymph) before reaching adulthood, while male has one larval and two nymphal stages (protonymph and deutonymph). An active immature individual enters a resting or quiescent stage before entering the following stage.

2.2. Mating:

Laboratory observations showed that the mating process is necessary for *N. arboreus* production in this mite. The adults tended to mate immediately after their emergence. The male was able to copulate with three females, but the female accepted only one copulation. Just before mating, the male showed more activity by running around the female, then it manipulated itself underneath the female, bending its opithosoma upward and forward to meet that of female. Copulation usually lasted about 5 minutes.

2.3. Oviposition:

Females of *N. arboreus* usually deposited its eggs singly.

Results and discussion

1. Effect of different food types on the biological aspects of *Neocunaxoides arboreus* male at 20 °C :

The tabulated data in Table (1) showed that the resulted incubation period of *N. arboreus* male fed on different diets showed slightly differences between the different individuals and recorded 6.79, 6.81 and 6.77 days when the males fed on the free living nematode, acarid mite and *A. flavus*, at 20 °C, respectively. On the other hand, the same obtained data cleared that the life cycle of obtained males significantly differed according to the introduced diets, as, it longest when the mite fed the acarid mite, *T. putrescentiae* (29.01 days) and shorted on *A. flavus* (24.09 days), but the resulted life cycle on the living nematode recoded (27.74 days) (Table,1). However, the tabulated data in Table (1) indicated that the averaged longevity of *N. arboreus* male individuals recorded 28.96, 26.48 and 31.81 days when the mite fed on free living nematodes, acarid mite and *A. flavus*, respectively at 20° C. The same study showed that the life span of *N. arboreus* male individuals lasted 55.61, 55.5 and 55.9 days when the cunaxid mite fed on the same previously mentioned diets at 20 °C (Table,1).

Table (1): Effect of food types on the biological aspects of *Neocunaxoides arboreus* male at 20 °C.

Biological aspects	Hosts			L.S.D. at 0.05 level		
	A	B	C	Temp.	Diet	
Incubation period	6.79±0.04	6.81±0.03	6.77±0.01	0.0140	0.014	
Larva	a	4.63±0.04	4.93±0.03	3.8±0.06	0.042	0.053
	q	0.56±0.03	0.65±0.02	0.49±0.03	0.005	0.004
Protonymph	a	4.58±0.05	4.94±0.02	3.84±0.4	0.035	0.041
	q	0.64±0.23	0.67±0.02	0.50±0.03	0.003	0.004
Deutonymph	a	4.67±0.03	4.89±0.06	3.81±0.04	0.023	0.027
	q	0.76±0.03	0.76±0.02	0.50±0.02	0.005	0.005
Tritonymph	a	4.64±0.03	4.79±0.05	3.79±0.03	0.013	0.013
	q	0.56±0.03	0.65±0.01	0.49±0.02	0.003	0.004
Total immatures	20.9±0.18	22.22±0.11	17.34±0.15	0.041	0.045	
Life cycle	27.74±0.50	29.01±0.13	24.09±0.16	0.024	0.31	
Longevity	28.96±0.71	26.48±0.6	31.81±1.28	0.265	0.312	
Life span	55.61±0.83	55.5±0.62	55.9±1.24	0.295	0.321	

a= active q= quiescent L.S.D. = least significant difference
 A= Free living nematode B= Acarid mite C= *Aspergillus flavus*

2. Effect of different types of food on the biological aspects of *Neocunaxoides arboreus* male at 25 °C:

The tabulated data in Table (2) showed that the incubation period of *N. arboreus* male lasted 5.05, 5.34 and 5.27 days when the cunaxid mite fed on free lining

nematode, *M. javanica* acarid mite, *T. putrescentiae* and the fungus, *A. flavus* respectively at 25 °C. On the other hand, the same mentioned table indicated that the male individuals took 21.96, 23.13 and 28.19 days and 47.21, 45.43 and 47.3 days for both life cycle and life span at 25 °C.

Table (2): Effect of food types on the biological aspects of *Neocunaxoides arboreus* male at 25 °C.

Biological aspects	Hosts			L.S.D. at 0.05 level		
	A	B	C	Temp.	Diet	
Incubation period	5.05±0.02	5.34±0.04	5.27±0.05	0.013	0.012	
Larva	a	3.87±0.05	3.94±0.03	3.13±0.23	0.040	0.038
	q	0.45±0.02	0.53±0.02	0.44±0.01	0.007	0.004
Protonymph	a	3.69±0.06	3.94±0.02	3.05±0.02	0.029	0.042
	q	0.44±0.02	0.50±0.02	0.48±0.02	0.004	0.003
Deutonymph	a	3.72±0.07	3.94±0.02	3.60±0.22	0.019	0.018
	q	0.45±0.02	0.49±0.01	0.43±0.02	0.004	0.005
Tritonymph	a	3.64±0.02	3.94±0.03	3.05±0.04	0.006	0.012
	q	0.43±0.01	0.50±0.02	0.43±0.01	0.004	0.003
Total immature	16.69±0.12	17.79±0.06	13.94±0.17	0.411	0.26	
Life cycle	21.96±0.23	23.13±0.14	19.21±0.18	0.439	0.544	
Longevity	25.27±0.60	22.31±0.73	28.19±0.64	0.398	0.841	
Life span	47.21±0.69	45.43±0.73	47.3±0.68	0.247	0.267	

a= active q= quiescent L.S.D. = least significant difference
 A= Free living nematode B= Acarid mite C= *Aspergillus flavus*

3. Effect of different types of food on the biological aspects of *Neocunaxoides arboreus* male at 30 °C:

3.1. Incubation period:

As shown in Table (3), the incubation period of different *A. arboreus* male individuals did not affected by the kind of food as it recorded about 4.0 days at 30 °C.

3.2. Life cycle:

The current study indicated that the life cycle of *N. arboreus* males members did not significantly affect when fed at 30 °C. on free living nematodes (17.87 days) and on acarid mite (17.85 days), but the difference was recorded when the mites reared on the fungus *A. flavus* (15.39 days) (Table, 3).

3.3. Longevity:

The mite *N. arboreus* males durated in its adult stage period about 21.01, 18.76 and 23.12 days when the individuals fed at 30 °C on free living nematodes, acarid mite, and the fungus, respectively. The analysis of obtained data showed that L.S. D. at 0.05 = 0.782 and 0.843 for the effect of temperature and introduced food, respectively (Table, 3).

3.4. Life span:

Table (3): Effect of different types of food on the biological aspects of *Neocunaxoides arboreus* male at 30 °C.

Biological aspects		Hosts			L.S.D. at 0.05 level	
Incubation period		A	B	C	Temp.	Diet
		4.04±0.07	4.08±0.03	4.05±0.02	0.018	0.016
Larva	a	3.12±0.03	3.04±0.02	2.50±0.03	0.057	0.214
	q	0.37±0.01	0.42±0.03	0.38±0.02	0.011	0.009
Protonymph	a	3.13±0.01	3.04±0.01	2.46±0.04	0.014	0.024
	q	0.33±0.01	0.40±0.02	0.38±0.02	0.008	0.009
Deutonymph	a	3.13±0.02	3.06±0.02	2.51±0.04	0.0064	0.067
	q	0.33±0.01	0.40±0.04	0.37±0.01	0.004	0.009
Tritonymph	a	3.07±0.01	3.03±0.01	2.39±0.03	0.027	0.029
	q	0.33±0.01	0.40±0.02	0.37±0.02	0.003	0.018
Total immature		13.82±0.05	13.77±0.12	11.32±0.12	0.354	0.514
Life cycle		17.87±0.05	17.85±0.013	15.39±0.18	0.654	0.847
Longevity		21.01±0.06	18.76±0.6	23.12±0.96	0.782	0.843
Life span		38.73±0.79	36.61±0.62	38.22±0.67	1.26	1.068

a= Active Q= quiescent L.S.D. = Least significant difference

A= Free living nematode B= Acarid mite C= *Aspergillus flavus*

4. Effect of different types of food on the biological aspects of *Neocunaxoides arboreus* male at 35 °C:

4.1. Incubation period:

The obtained data in Table (4) showed that the incubation period of the cunaxid mite *N. arboreus* male individuals averaged 3.06, 3.15 and 3.07 days when the mite fed on free living nematodes, acarid mite, and the fungus at 35 °C, respectively with L.S.D. at 0.05 level = 0.051 and 0.061 for effect of temperature and food types on this period, respectively.

4.2. Life cycle:

The study indicated that the life cycle of *N. arboreus* males members significantly affected when fed on the different introduced diets at 35 °C, as it recorded 13.7 days on free living nematodes, 12.81 days on acarid

The tabulated data in Table (3) obviously showed that the life span of the tested mite. *N. arboreus* male individuals significantly affected when different food kinds were introduced at 30 °C. The male took 38.73, 36.61 and 38.22 days when reared on free living nematodes, acarid mite, and *A. flavus*, respectively with L.S.D. at 0.05 for effect of temperature and food as 1.26 and 1.068, respectively (Table, 3).

mite and 11.01 days when the mites reared on the fungus *A. flavus* at 35 °C, respectively with L.S.D. at 0.05 level = 0.624 and 0.711 for effect of temperature and food types on this period, respectively (Table,4).

4.3. Longevity:

As shown in Table (4), the longevity period of the cunaxid mite *N. arboreus* male individuals lasted 16.94, 14.68 and 19.76 days, when the mite members fed on free living nematodes, acarid mite, and the fungus, respectively (Table,4). The statistical analysis of obtained data showed that L.S.D. at 0.05 level for effect of both temperature and food types effect on this period was 0.698 and 0.785, respectively.

4.4. Life span:

The obtained data in Table (4) showed that the life span of *N. arboreus*

females at 35 °C. took 30.64, 27.45 and 30.80 days when the mite individuals fed on free living nematodes, acarid mite and the fungus,

respectively, with L.S.D. at 0.05 level = 1.25 and 1.30 for effect of temperature and food types on this period.

Table (4): Effect of food types on the biological aspects of *Neocunaxoides arboreus* male at 35 °C.

Biological aspects		Hosts			L.S.D. at 0.05 level	
Incubation period		A	B	C	Temp.	Diet
		3.06±0.02	3.15±0.014	3.07±0.03	0.051	0.061
Larva	A	2.33±0.13	2.10±0.12	1.73±0.04	0.042	0.061
	Q	0.32±0.02	0.40±0.02	0.34±0.02	0.003	0.002
Protonymph	A	2.33±0.09	2.04±0.01	1.73±0.04	0.011	0.007
	Q	0.28±0.02	0.35±0.01	0.34±0.02	0.004	0.002
Deutonymph	A	2.34±0.07	2.06±0.02	1.65±0.03	0.013	0.009
	Q	0.27±0.01	0.35±0.01	0.34±0.01	0.0017	0.031
Tritonymph	A	2.29±0.09	2.03±0.01	1.60±0.04	0.032	0.009
	Q	0.27±0.01	0.35±0.02	0.34±0.02	0.016	0.004
Total immature		10.66±0.24	9.64±0.08	7.96±0.29	0.412	0.521
Life cycle		13.7±0.27	12.81±0.19	11.01±0.31	0.624	0.711
Longevity		16.94±0.89	14.68±0.56	19.76±0.62	0.698	0.785
Life span		30.64±0.097	27.45±0.07	30.80±0.71	1.25	1.30

a= active q= quiescent L.S.D. = least significant difference
 A= Free living nematode B= Acarid mite C= *Aspergillus flavus*

5. Effect of food types on the biological aspects of *Neocunaxoides arboreus* female at 20 °C:

5.1. Incubation period:

The effect of different kinds of food on the incubation period of the cunaxid mite, *N. arboreus* did not highly affected foe female individuals at 20 °C, with L.S.D. at 0.05 level = 0.023 and 0.025 for effect of temperature and food types on this period. The incubation period lasted 6.82, 6.94 and 6.83 when the females food on free nematodes, acarid mite and *A. flavus*, respectively (Table , 5).

5.2. Life cycle:

The period of *N. arboreus* female obviously affected and took from egg stage to adult sate 30.87, 29.95 and 26.45 days when mite individuals fed on the same trend of different diets mentioned before at 20 °C, with L.S.D. at 0.05 level = 0.034 and 0.041 for temperature and food effect, respectively.

5.3. Longevity:

The adult female of *N. arboreus* averaged 40.26, 36.79 and 40.87 days on the same order of mentioned diets and at 20 °C, respectively/ The statistical analysis of obtained data showed that L.S.D. at 0.05 level for effect of temperature and food types, respectively (Table, 5).

5.4. Fecundity:

The current study clearly indicated that the number of deposited eggs by female of the tested cunaxid mite *N. arboreus* highly significantly affected by the kind of employed food, as, it laid 54.85, 47.45 and 64.25 eggs when the individuals fed on the free living nematodes, *T. putrescentiae* and *A. flavus*, respectively at 20 °C, with L.S.D. at 0.05 = 0.647 and 0.717 for effect of temperature and food types, respectively (Table, 5).

Table (5): Effect of food types on the biological aspects of *Neocunaxoides arboreus* female at 20 °C .

Biological aspects	Hosts			L.S.D. at 0.05 level		
	A	B	C	Temp.	Diet	
Incubation period	6.82±0.24	6.94±0.02	6.83±0.07	0.023	0.0252	
Larva	a	5.30±0.11	5.12±0.07	4.48±0.08	0.051	0.057
	q	0.50±0.02	0.70±0.04	0.50±0.02	0.004	0.004
Protonymph	a	5.12±0.05	5.02±0.29	4.30±0.67	0.044	0.003
	q	0.05±0.02	0.66±0.03	0.47±0.02	0.003	0.005
Deutonymph	a	5.14±0.04	5.08±0.14	4.47±0.02	0.023	0.025
	q	0.49±0.03	0.66±0.02	0.46±0.02	0.006	0.007
Tritonymph	a	5.47±0.34	5.20±0.26	4.45±0.02	0.015	0.016
	q	0.49±0.02	0.64±0.02	0.44±0.02	0.005	0.017
Total immatures	23.58±0.59	23.02±0.32	19.63±0.013	0.035	0.027	
Life cycle	30.87±2.16	29.95±0.31	26.45±0.23	0.034	0.041	
Preoviposition	5.29±0.3	5.82±0.33	4.47±0.04	0.018	0.021	
Oviposition	29.27±1.0	25.98±0.68	31.80±1.03	0.075	0.068	
Postoviposition	6.30±2.16	5.01±0.46	4.43±0.38	0.066	0.042	
Longevity	40.26±1.16	36.79±0.91	40.87±0.98	0.287	0.331	
Life span	70.57±1.41	66.60±1.38	67.29±1.14	0.313	0.351	
Sex ratio	0.33±0.1	0.33±0.01	0.33±0.01	0.002	0.002	
Fecundity	54.85±2.01	47.45±0.82	64.25±1.37	0.647	0.717	
Daily rate	1.91±0.24	1.81±0.06	2.16±0.067	0.543	0.514	

a= Active q= Quiescent L.S.D. = Least significant difference A= Free living nematode B= Acarid mite
C= *Aspergillus flavus*

6. Effect of food types on the biological aspects of *Neocunaxoides arboreus* female at 25 °C:

6.1. Incubation period:

The tabulated data in Table (6) showed that the incubation period of *N. arboreus* females did not affected by the kind of introduced food at 25 °C with L.S.D. at 0.05 = 0.012 and 0.024 for effect of temperature and food types, respectively.

6.2. Life cycle:

Data in Table (6) showed the effect of different diets on the life cycle of *N. arboreus* females at 25 °C. It was longer when the individuals fed free living nematodes and recorded 24.69 days, but the lowest period was noticed when the mites reared on *T. putrescentiae* (23.76 days), with L. S.D. at 0.05 level = 0.029 and 0.043, respectively.

6.3. Pre-oviposition, oviposition and post-oviposition periods :

The duration of pre-oviposition period of *N. arboreus* on different diets represented in Table (6), averaged 5.04, 4.78 and 3.84 days, but the oviposition period took 23.97, 21.38 and 25.59 days when fed on free living nematodes, acarid mite and the fungus, respectively at 25 °C. The statistical analysis of obtained data indicated that L.S.D. at 0.05 = 0.014 and 0.02 and 0.065 and 0.071 for effect of temperature and diets, respectively in case of pre-oviposition and oviposition periods, respectively. However, there were highly significant differences between the individuals in case of post-oviposition period, as, it recorded 5.17, 4.47 and 3.83 days on free nematodes, acarid mite and the fungus, respectively.

6.4. Longevity:

Results in Table (6) indicated that the mean longevity of *N. arboreus* females when fed on different diets averaged 34.12, 30.48

and 33.26 days at 25 °C, respectively, with effect of temperature and diets = 0.264 and 0.334, respectively.

6.5. Fecundity:

The fecundity (number of laid eggs) of *N. arboreus* female was not highly affected by diets as shown in Table (6). It was 71.75, 71.35 and 72.45 eggs when the females fed on the free living nematodes, the acarid mite and the fungus at 25 °C, respectively. The statistical analysis of obtained data showed

Table (6): Effect of food types on the biological aspects of *Neocunaxoides arboreus* female at 25 °C.

Biological aspects		Hosts			L.S.D. at 0.05 level	
		A	B	C	Temp.	Diet
Incubation period		5.41±0.015	5.44±0.07	5.44±0.04	0.012	0.024
Larva	a	4.35±0.30	4.06±0.04	3.47±0.04	0.05	0.06
	q	0.51±0.03	0.54±0.04	0.46±0.07	0.006	0.007
Protonymph	a	4.22±0.12	4.04±0.02	3.50±0.03	0.041	0.004
	q	0.21±0.02	0.52±0.03	0.43±0.02	0.005	0.003
Deutonymph	a	3.72±0.07	3.94±0.02	3.05±0.02	0.017	0.024
	q	0.50±0.02	0.45±0.03	0.43±0.02	0.008	0.011
Tritonymph	a	4.16±0.05	4.07±0.02	3.39±0.03	0.011	0.014
	q	0.50±0.02	0.51±0.02	0.42±0.02	0.009	0.015
Total immatures		19.22±0.39	18.33±0.28	15.51±0.09	0.025	0.025
Life cycle		24.69±0.49	23.76±0.29	20.94±0.09	0.029	0.043
Preoviposition		5.04±0.31	4.78±0.19	3.84±0.30	0.014	0.02
Oviposition		23.97±0.79	21.38±0.72	25.59±0.78	0.065	0.071
Postoviposition		5.17±0.06	4.47±0.18	3.83±0.41	0.069	0.043
Longevity		34.12±0.68	30.48±0.29	33.26±0.84	0.264	0.334
Life span		58.93±0.80	54.24±0.92	54.20±0.86	0.322	0.356
Sex ratio		0.33±0.01	0.32±0.01	0.33±0.01	0.004	0.003
Fecundity		71.75±2.79	71.35±1.46	72.45±1.19	0.587	0.624
Daily rate		2.96±0.22	3.29±0.29	2.84±0.09	0.511	0.705

A= active Q= quiescent L.S.D. = Least significant difference

A= Free living nematode B= Acarid mite C= *Aspergillus flavus*

7. Effect of different types of food on the biological aspects of *Neocunaxoides arboreus* female at 30 °C:

7.1. Incubation period:

As shown in Table (7), the incubation period of *N. arboreus* female was not obviously affected when fed on preys at 30 °C. The statistical analysis of obtained data showed that L.S.D. at 0.05 level= 0.12 and 0.13 for effect of temperature and food types, respectively.

7.2. Life cycle:

From the tabulated data in Table (7), it could be observed that the duration of life

that L.S.D. at 0.05 = 0.587 and 0.624 for effect of temperature and food types, respectively.

6.6. Life span:

Accordingly, the life span of *N. arboreus* females significantly differed on different diets, at 25 °C ,as prolonged on free living nematodes (58.93 days) and shorted on the fungus and acarid mite (54.20 and 54.24, respectively (Table,6).

cycle for female individuals of *N. arboreus* was obviously affected by the type of food employed at 30 °C. This period averaged 20.15, 21.83 and 17.64 days when the mite individuals fed on free living nematodes, acarid mite and the fungus. The statistical analysis of obtained data showed that L.S.D. at 0.05 level = 1.21 and 1.06 for effect of temperature and diets, respectively.

7.3. Longevity:

The maximum longevity was 31.03 days when the predatory mite fed on the fungus *A. flavus*, and the minimum corresponding figures was 26.84 days for

female individuals reared on the acarid mite at 30 °C. However, when the mite females fed on the free living nematode, they lasted about 30.23 days. The analysis of data indicated that L.S.D. at 0.05 level =12.3 and 1.64 for effect of temperature and food types, respectively (Table,7).

7.4. Life span:

The females of *N. arboreus* took 50.35, 48.68 and 74.45 days when reared on nematodes, mite, and the fungus, respectively during life span at 30 °C, with L.S. D. at 0.05 level = 3.25 and 3.15 for

Table (7): Effect of food types on the biological aspects of *Neocunaxoides arboreus* female at 30 °C.

Biological aspects		Hosts			L.S.D. at 0.05 level	
		A	B	C	Temp.	Diet
Incubation period		4.22±0.04	4.26±0.05	4.27±0.04	0.012	0.013
Larva	a	3.72±0.02	3.93±0.03	2.94±0.03	0.024	0.024
	q	0.43±0.03	0.57±0.02	0.46±0.02	0.003	0.003
Protonymph	a	3.76±0.07	3.81±0.11	2.79±0.01	0.027	0.068
	q	0.41±0.06	0.52±0.05	0.43±0.02	0.004	0.005
Deutonymph	a	3.23±0.08	3.80±0.04	2.92±0.05	0.034	0.11
	q	0.42±0.02	0.55±0.04	0.43±0.02	0.009	0.11
Tritonymph	a	3.53±0.03	3.87±0.05	3.91±0.06	0.032	0.034
	q	0.43±0.02	0.55±0.03	0.43±0.02	0.002	0.008
Total immatures		15.92±0.09	17.57±0.16	13.41±0.09	0.687	0.789
Life cycle		20.15±0.10	21.83±0.13	17.64±0.10	1.21	1.06
Preoviposition		4.86±0.08	3.90±0.03	4.28±0.27	0.021	0.111
Oviposition		20.94±0.82	18.9±0.49	22.52±0.65	0.958	0.849
Postoviposition		4.24±0.39	4.07±0.31	4.14±0.5	0.121	0.119
Longevity		30.23±1.0	26.84±0.64	31.03±0.91	1.23	1.64
Life span		50.35±1.1	48.68±0.62	48.67±0.88	3.25	3.15
Sex ratio		0.33±0.01	0.33±0.01	0.33±0.01	0.0003	0.003
Fecundity		70.6±2.33	64.25±1.52	74.45±0.09	4.26	5.333
Daily rate		3.35±0.18	3.93±0.13	3.32±0.15	0.024	0.019

A= active Q= quiescent

A= Free living nematode

L.S.D. = Least significant difference

B= Acarid mite

C= *Aspergillus flavus*

8. Effect of different types of food on the biological aspects of *Neocunaxoides arboreus* female at 35 °C:

8.1. Incubation period:

As can be seen in Table (8) the incubation period slightly similar for the predator *N. arboreus* fed on different introduced diets, 3.13, 3.14 and 3.11 days when fed on free living nematode, acarid mite and *A. flavus*, respectively at 35 °C.

8.2. Life cycle:

effect of temperature and food types, respectively (Table ,7).

7.5. Fecundity:

The adult female of *N. arboreus* as shown in Table (7) laid the high number of eggs (74.45 eggs) when fed on *A. flavus* at 30 °C., while the lowest number was observed when fed on the acarid mite, *T. putrescentiae* (64.25 eggs) at the same experiment conditions. L.S.D. at 0.05 level =4.26 and 5.33 for temperature and diets effect, respectively.

From Table (8), it was observed that at 35 °C, the life cycle of *N. arboreus* females lasted 14.69, 14.89 and 11.85 on nematode, acarid mite and *A. flavus*, respectively.

8.3. Longevity:

The adult female of *N. arboreus* changed according to the kind of food and this clearly at 35 °C observed in Table (8). The longest longevity period of female was observed when the individuals fed on *A. flavus* and recorded 25.4 days

8.4. Life span:

Accordingly, the life span of the cunaxid mite, *N. arboreus* female was highly significantly affected by rearing on different diets at 35 °C. The longest period lasted

39.49 days when the mites fed on free nematode changed to 36.95 and 37.05 days when the female fed on *T. putrescentiae* and *A. flavus*, respectively (Table,8).

Table (8): Effect of food types on the biological aspects of *Neocunaxoides arboreus* female at 35 °C.

Biological aspects		Hosts			L.S.D. at 0.05 level	
		A	B	C	Temp.	Diet
Incubation period		3.13±0.04	3.14±0.03	3.11±0.03	0.032	0.034
Larva	a	2.41±0.05	2.52±0.03	1.81±0.06	0.047	.016
	q	0.45±0.03	0.40±0.02	0.37±0.02	0.003	0.004
Protonymph	a	2.46±0.05	2.42±0.09	1.82±0.05	0.154	0.161
	q	0.45±0.03	0.39±0.01	0.37±0.02	0.003	0.008
Deutonymph	a	2.46±0.05	2.53±0.06	1.82±0.04	0.129	0.147
	q	0.47±0.04	0.38±0.02	0.36±0.02	0.001	0.002
Tritonymph	a	2.46±0.05	2.77±0.03	1.97±0.63	0.101	0.103
	q	0.47±0.04	0.38±0.02	0.36±0.02	0.003	0.004
Total immatures		11.49±0.28	12.31±0.43	8.75±0.09	0.652	0.584
Life cycle		14.69±0.25	14.89±0.12	11.85±0.09	0.346	0.289
Preoviposition		3.19±0.17	2.82±0.16	2.75±0.42	0.024	0.014
Oviposition		18.26±0.83	15.97±0.67	19.40±0.62	0.624	0.852
Postoviposition		3.62±0.79	3.25±0.39	3.37±0.40	0.003	0.002
Longevity		24.82±1.15	22.09±0.84	25.4±0.90	1.125	1.33
Life span		39.49±1.21	36.95±0.77	37.05±0.95	2.245	2.213
Sex ratio		0.33±0.01	0.33±0.01	0.33±0.01	0.002	0.004
Fecundity		54.1±2.38	64.7±1.84	59.25±2.57	2.98	3.511
Daily rate		2.95±0.14	4.04±0.21	3.05±0.17	0.005	0.009

A= active Q= quiescent L.S.D. = Least significant difference
 A= Free living nematode B= Acarid mite C= *Aspergillus flavus*

The current study demonstrated that the temperature 25°C. was the most favorable temperature for rearing the cunaxid mite *N. arboreus* when fed on different introduced diets and these results were coincident with those obtained by Khalil *et al.* (2012) where they studied the life history of the cunaxid mite, *P. martini* when fed on the different diets where they found that the best diet for rearing *P. martini* was *F. oxysporum* at 25°C where it recorded the highest number of eggs (73.79) but the least favorable one for feeding was the fungus *P. spinosum* at 35°C (48.71 eggs). Also, El-Khateeb (1998) mentioned that low temperature decreased female fecundity of the cunaxid mite, *Cunaxa setirostris* (Hermann). Also, Khalil *et al.* (2009) reared the cunaxid mite, *Coleoscirus bapto*s on different fungi and mentioned that 25°C was the most favorable temperature for

rearing this mite, as, it deposited 95.6 eggs when fed on *Aspergillus niger*. The same results were observed but on different cunaxid species by Ghallab (2002) where she studied the biological aspects on three cunaxid species, *Coleoscirus simplex* (Ewing), *C. tuberculatus* Den Heyer and *Pulaeus subterraneus* Berlese when reared on the free nematode, *Rhabditella muscicola* under laboratory conditions at 27±1°C and 75-80% RH. The author mentioned that the average life cycle of female was more longer than that of male being 12.8, 13.1 and 15.6 days, while those of male were 12, 11.7 and 13.4 days, respectively. The coleoscirine cunaxid mite *C. simplex* colonizes greenhouse pot cultures of root knot nematodes (*Meloidogyne* spp.) in Orlando, Florida, where it preyed on nematodes and soil arthropods, Walter and Kaplan (1991).

This was the first report of nematophagy in a cunaxid mite. The authors added that the cunaxoidine *Pulaeus* sp. also fed on both arthropods and nematodes, but three species in the Cunaxidinae, *Dactyloscirus inermis*, *Dactyloscirus* sp. and *Cunaxa* sp. fed only on arthropods. Also, Yassin (2006) investigated the effect of three diets mainly Collembola (*Neanurodes* sp.), free living nematode, *R. muscicola* and acarid mite, *T. putrescentiae* on the biological aspects of the cunaxid mite, *C. capreolus* Collembola proved to be the suitable prey as results in more deposited eggs and longer life span and this might be due to the collembolan was the best prey where it contained the highest total 54 sugar and higher relative concentration of glucose contents

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Control of all stages of the cowpea seed beetle *Callosobruchus maculatus* (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) by low temperature inside different bags

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Abstract:

Cooling and freezing is one of the means of physical insect control. Low temperature was evaluated for disinfections all stages of the cowpea seed beetle, *Callosobruchus maculatus* (Fabricius) (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) in cowpea seeds. Eggs, larvae, pupae and adults were exposed to temperature degrees; 5, 0, -5, and -10 °C kept inside different packages (plastic vial, plastic sack and glass jar) for various durations (1, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 24 and 48 hrs.). Results showed that the adults were the most cold-tolerant while the eggs were lowest cold-tolerant. Packages were significantly different in adults stages and in larvae stages but in eggs and pupae not significantly different between packages. LT₉₀ of adults were 313.18, 42.22, 13.82 and 5.75 hrs. For plastic sack at 5, 0, -5 and -10 °C, respectively. For eggs LT₉₀ recorded 19.64, 10.55, 4.06 and 2.43 hrs. at 5, 0, -5 and -10 °C, respectively, for plastic sack. Larvae and pupae also recorded.

Introduction

Cowpea, (*Vigna unguiculata* (L.) Walpers, Fabaceae), is an important edible legume crop in many parts of the world especially in tropical and subtropical regions. It is used as human food due to its high protein content and as livestock feed to make silage and hay (Diouf, 2011). One of the major destructive post-harvest pests of cowpea worldwide is the cowpea weevil *Callosobruchus maculatus* (Fabricius) (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae). In stored seeds, cowpea weevil causes irreparable damage to the tissue, one that can reduce nutritive value and quality seeds for planting in many areas of developing countries. The damage is caused by larvae feeding and development inside the seed, and when adults emerge, they

leave circular exit holes (Davidson and Lyson, 1979). The damage reduces the weight and may render the seeds to be unfit for human consumption due to fungal growth associated with increased temperatures in storage. This insect also causes secondary infestation during pulse storage and may cause total loss within three months (Singh and Jackai, 1985). Being an internal feeder, it is very difficult to control the larval stage of *C. maculatus* with insecticides. The management of this insect in storage using chemical insecticides leads to insecticide residues in grains and insecticide resistant populations. Chemicals, grain protectants and fumigants, are extensively used around the world to control insect pests in stored

commodities. So, there is a need for the ecologically benign methods to control cowpea weevil. The use of cool or cold temperatures to manage stored grain can be an important component of insect pest management programs. Temperature treatment of stored grains is a best physical method which successfully kills several life stages of insects at a time. Most of the stored product insects cannot tolerate extreme temperature, heating and cooling and show heavy mortality (Upadhyay and Shoeb, 2011). For several years, the use of extreme temperatures, particularly low temperatures, has been extensively used to control stored product insects. The advantages of physical control methods are that: (1) There are no leave chemical residues on the product after treatment, (2) They are effective against insecticidal resistant strains, (3) There are few risks for operators, and (4) There are no negative effects on environment.

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the effectiveness of low temperature in control of cowpea beetle exposed inside three types of packages materials to prevent damage by direct insect pests.

Materials and methods

For starting a culture of tested insect, adults *C. maculatus* reared on cowpea seeds in a glass jars (each of approximately 500 ml) and each jar was covered with muslin cloths and fixed with rubber bands. Four temperatures were used as physical control methods against egg, larvae, pupae and adult of the cowpea seed beetle, *C. maculatus*. Tested temperatures degrees were 5, 0, -5, and -10 °C. for various exposed durations (1, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 24 and 48 hrs.). Exposure times were chosen to cover the range of lethal times. Three different types of packages were tested for this study. The used packages were plastic vial, plastic sack and glass jar. To have an initial population of insect adults homogenous in age, about 500 adults were introduced into jars containing seeds for egg laying and then kept in an incubator at

28±2°C and 65±5 % RH. After three days, all insects were removed from the media and the jars were kept again at controlled conditions. The seeds were regularly observed for egg deposition and subsequent adult emergence. Hatched eggs were identified by the presence larval frass which causes egg to turn milky-white as larvae tunnel into the seeds for larvae and pupae age calculated. Five replicates of exposure and non-exposure (0 – 1 day-old) adults, (0 – 2 day-old) eggs, (8 – 10 day old) larvae and (2 – 3 day-old) pupae were used in this experiment. The temperature degrees used in this study were 5, 0, -5 and -10 °C; the time exposure at each degree were 1, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 24 and 48 hrs. Three different packages (plastic vial, plastic sack and glass jar) were used for each temperature degrees. Mortality ratios of exposure and non-exposure adults were observed after each time exposure. Reduction percentages of adults emerged from exposure and non-exposure eggs, larvae and pupae were calculated according to equation (Yamamoto and Casida, 1999). The study was terminated when no adult emergence was observed.

Data collected were analyzed using the ANOVA followed by the mean separation using the Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT). The differences were statistically significant at $p < 0.0001$. The results were statistically analysis based on statistically analyzed by Finney (1971) using thelog-probitsoftware programLdpLine@model"Ehabsoft, (Bakr, 2000).

Results and discussion

The data showed in Table (1) represented the mortality ratios of adult stage of *C. maculatus* insects exposed to different low temperature degrees (5, 0, -5 and -10 °C) for (1, 2, 4, 6, 8, 12, 24 and 48 hrs.) and kept in various packages (plastic jar, plastic sack and glass jar). The data observed that in all temperature degrees and packages, as the time increased as the mortality % increased

and as temperature decreased the mortality were faster in few hours. On the other wise, the glass jar package was less response for temperature, so the mortality of adult insects was less than plastic jar and plastic sack packages, but plastic sack package was more response for temperature. LT_{90} recorded 313.18, 42.22, 13.82 and 5.75 hrs. for plastic sack package at 0, 5, -5 and -10 °C, respectively as showed in Table (5). The statistical analysis investigated that there are significant differences between four temperature degrees and there are significant differences between three packages as showed in Table (6).

The data showed in Tables (2, 3 and 4) represented the reduction in adult emergence % treated as eggs, larvae and pupae stages of *C. maculatus* insects exposed to different cold temperature degrees (5, 0, -5 and -10 °C) for (2, 4, 6, 8, 12 and 24 hrs.) which kept in various packages (plastic jar, plastic sack and glass jar). The data observed that in all temperature degrees and packages as the time increased as the reduction % increased and as temperature decreased the mortality were faster in few hours so the reduction % increased. Also, the glass package was less response for temperature so that the mortality of eggs, larvae and pupae stages was less than plastic and sack packages. LT_{90} recorded 19.64, 10.55, 4.06 and 2.43 hrs. at 5, 0, -5 and -10 °C for plastic sack package, respectively for eggs as showed in Table (5). For larva was 38.4, 40.37, 5.83 and 2.95 hrs. at 5, 0, -5 and -10 °C, respectively. Finally, LT_{90} for pupa was 20.14, 11.53, 4.36 and 3.73 hrs. at 5, 0, -5 and -10 °C, respectively as showed in Table (5).

The statistical analysis investigated that there are significant differences between packages for eggs and larvae stages but for pupae there are no significant differences between three packages. Also, for temperature degrees there are significant differences between all temperature degrees in eggs and larvae treated while in pupae

treated there are not significant differences between -5 and -10 °C as showed in Table (6).

In general, the adults were the most cold-tolerant while the eggs were lowest cold-tolerant, but larvae and pupae were equally cold-tolerant. Finally, the sack package was the better and more response in control of *C. maculatus* insects in all different stages by freezing temperature (-5 and -10 °C) for 12 hrs. exposure to obtained 100 % mortality and 100 % reduction of their offspring.

Our results stated that the adults were the most cold-tolerant while the eggs were lowest cold-tolerant. In contrast, Johnson and Valero (2003) they confirm that *C. maculatus* eggs are the most tolerant stage to freezing temperatures and that adults were highly susceptible. Finally, the sack package was the better and more response in control of *C. maculatus* insects in all different stages by freezing temperature (-5 and -10 °C) for 12 hours exposure to obtained 100 % mortality (100 % reduction) of their offspring.

Also, these results indicated generally that *C. maculatus* in glass jars were more tolerant than those in the other bags to freezing temperature; consequently, glass jars required longer exposure periods than plastic vial and plastic sack bags to give a complete control against tested insect. These findings are agreement with those obtained by Johnson and Valero (2003) indicated that mortality % eggs of *C. maculatus* was reached to more 98 % at -18 °C after just 7 d of exposure. Complete mortality of *C. maculatus* eggs occurred after 14 d of cold storage. Also, showed that the egg stage was most tolerant to -18 °C and that adult was most susceptible. A 2-wk treatment regimen may be enough for control of cowpea weevil in organic legumes.

Product storage at temperatures of -7 to 1 °C was recommended for control of *Callosobruchus* species early in the previous century (Duvel, 1905 and Larson and Simmons (1924). Mullen and Arbogast (1979) determined the LD95 of *C. maculatus* eggs after exposure to -15 °C to be 5 h, noting that this species was among the more cold-tolerant stored-product insects. Various Cooperative Extension sources recommend 4 d at -18 °C for control of cowpea weevil in home pantries (Sorensen, 1994 and Lyon, 1997). Larson and Simmons (1924) indicated that eggs were the most susceptible stage when exposed to -7 °C. In contrast, Mullen and Arbogast (1979) compared the effect of low temperatures on the eggs of five species of stored-product insects and found *C. maculatus* eggs to be among the most cold tolerant, with LD 50 values of 2.7, 1.3, and 0.3 h for -10, -15, and -20 °C, respectively. Obretenchev (1983) who found that adults of *O. surinmensis* were the most resistant stage to low temperature. At 0.0°C, they died after 6 days, at -5°C after 60 hrs., at -10 °C after 3 hrs. and 55 min. and at -15°C after 47 min. Larvae were the most susceptible from the egg stage Donahaye *et al.* (1995) showed that the time required to produce 99.0 % kill for *O. surinamensis* larvae was 1.22 hrs. at -10 degrees °C and 0.32 hrs. at -18 degrees °C. While, the time required to produce 90.0 % kill for *O. surinamensis* adult was 1.49 hrs. at -10 degrees °C and 1.05 hrs. at -18 degrees °C., stated also , *O. surinamensis* the least sensitive stage at 0.0°C was the larvae , at -5 and -18°C was the adult. Stoyanova (1984) noticed that complete mortality of the-adult stages of *S. granarius* and *S. oryzae* occurred after 10 days at -16°C. Mullen and Arbogast (1979) showed that at -5 °C 50% of *T.*

castaneum eggs survived for 0.3 days. Also, Nagel and Shepard (1934) stated that 50 % of *T. confusum* eggs exposed to - 6 °C survived for 0.2 days. Flinn *et al.* (2015) they showed that treating flour pallets in commercial freezers is a feasible method to disinfest flour that may be infested with *T. castaneum* eggs. The fact that the treatment only required 5.5 days in the freezer makes it a practical method to disinfest pallets of flour, especially because the flour does not need to be removed from the shipping pallet. The fact that no chemicals are used would allow use of this treatment for organic or conventional flour. Dupuis *et al.* (2006) mentioned that the complete kill of all hidden stages of *Acanthoscelides obtectus* directly exposed at 0 °C and -10 °C was observed at 32 d and 24 hrs. exposure time, respectively.

Johnson and Valero (2003) stated that because the larval stages of the cowpea weevil feed and pupate within host seeds, larvae and pupae may experience some degree of insulation from cold temperatures when compared with free-living adults. This may account for some of the difference in cold tolerance between these stages. However, cowpea weevil eggs are laid on the seed surface and are not insulated from freezing temperatures, suggesting that cold tolerance of cowpea weevil eggs is due to a physiological mechanism and not placement within a protected microhabitat. Our results confirm that *C. maculatus* adults are the most tolerant stage to freezing temperatures and that eggs were highly susceptible.

It is concluded that there are many factors, such as freezing degree, exposure period and insect stage in addition to bag materials can be required to determine the time needed to kill all individuals.

Table (1): Effect of different cold temperature degrees and packages on mortality % of adult stage of *Callosobruchus maculatus*.

	Exposure time (h)	Mortality % of adult		
		Plastic jar	Plastic bag	Glass jar
5	1	0	3.33	0
	2	3.33	5	0
	4	6.67	8.33	1.67
	6	10	13.33	5
	8	15	21.67	8.33
	12	25	36.67	15
	24	35	43.33	23.33
	48	45	53.33	41.67
0	1	3.33	6.67	3.33
	2	10	11.67	10
	4	15	18.33	13.33
	6	28.33	40	15
	8	50	55	26.67
	12	55	68.33	43.33
	24	70	75	51.67
	48	83.33	100	100
-5	1	15	18.33	10
	2	35	43.33	31.67
	4	43.33	50	40
	6	58.33	66.67	56.67
	8	76.67	88.33	70
	12	95	100	91.67
	24	100	100	100
	48	100	100	100
-10	1	23.33	30	28.33
	2	46.67	58.33	43.33
	4	70	75	68.33
	6	86.67	95	85
	8	95	100	98.33
	12	100	100	100
	24	100	100	100
	48	100	100	100

Table (2): Effect of different cold temperature degrees and packages on reduction of emerged adults treated as eggs stage of *Callosobruchus maculatus*.

Degree	Exposure time (h)	Reduction of emerged adults %		
		Plastic jar	Plastic bag	Glass jar
5	2	6.93	16.79	5.95
	4	17.95	23.83	14.88
	6	29.83	34.88	29.50
	8	47.34	53.95	46.61
	10	61.07	62.44	54.55
	12	80.23	85.89	79.07
	24	91.02	97.88	89.51
0	2	16.28	14.33	18.83
	4	29.40	26.35	26.48
	6	55.55	60.16	48.28
	8	77.44	79.12	76.28
	10	94.26	95.66	89.37
	12	98.73	100	94.95
	24	100	100	98.90
-5	1	47.74	29.33	47.76
	2	86.24	89.07	88.69
	4	100	100	95.70
-10	1	63.14	83.33	42.64
	2	96.00	100	92.92
	4	100	100	100

Table (3): Effect of different cold temperature degrees and packages on reduction of emerged adults treated as larvae stage of *Callosobruchus maculatus*.

Degree	Exposure time (h)	Reduction of emerged adults %		
		Plastic jar	Plastic bag	Glass jar
5	2	5.84	2.58	0.67
	4	12.57	11.16	4.29
	6	13.43	19.62	9.68
	8	26.50	28.43	24.50
	10	37.20	43.82	33.94
	12	55.28	65.76	53.51
	24	65.12	71.26	64.71
0	2	11.14	14.80	14.18
	4	21.12	20.31	18.48
	6	25.60	31.66	23.16
	8	32.72	43.26	29.85
	10	52.39	54.57	37.60
	12	65.40	67.28	61.04
	24	75.96	79.82	69.31
-5	2	11.60	11.58	15.04
	4	42.62	59.63	39.98
	6	84.55	92.07	80.64
	8	100	100	92.40
-10	2	67.02	75.53	45.41
	4	89.94	96.00	78.94
	6	100	100	100

Table (4): Effect of different cold temperature degrees and packages on reduction of emerged adults treated as pupae stage of *Callosobruchus maculatus*.

Degree	Exposure time (h)	Reduction of emerged adults %		
		Plastic jar	Plastic bag	Glass jar
5	2	4.98	7.14	3.56
	4	12.16	22.42	11.74
	6	25.52	29.03	24.55
	8	43.34	46.69	41.21
	10	57.94	59.15	52.59
	12	77.73	80.24	77.31
	24	90.64	96.28	85.62
0	2	20.87	11.78	26.39
	4	26.92	24.73	27.17
	6	57.09	62.22	53.05
	8	75.93	75.45	75.41
	10	88.17	89.10	88.07
	12	95.57	100	91.00
	24	100	100	98.40
-5	2	38.23	39.33	39.38
	4	74.99	84.74	79.34
	6	96.57	98.21	92.07
	8	100	100	98.45
-10	2	50.73	63.38	45.89
	4	85.29	89.52	85.94
	6	100	100	100

Table (5): Lethal time and slope values of all stages of *Callosobruchus maculatus* in plastic sack package.

Temperature degree	Stage	LT50	LT90	Lower limit	Upper limit	Slope
5	Adult	33.60	313.18	178.12	721.56	1.32±0.13
	Egg	6.57	19.64	16.95	35.86	2.69±0.19
	Larva	11.86	38.4	30.97	72.09	2.51±0.20
	Pupa	7.63	20.14	16.97	28.60	3.04±0.22
0	Adult	8.36	42.22	33.54	56.35	1.822±0.012
	Egg	4.79	10.55	10.10	27.37	3.74±0.30
	Larva	8.89	40.37	30.80	58.89	1.95±0.17
	Pupa	5.07	11.53	9.84	20.37	3.55±0.30
-5	Adult	2.96	13.82	13.819	95.8	1.91±0.19
	Egg	2.47	4.06	3.7	4.7	5.94±0.58
	Larva	3.42	5.83	5.36	6.47	5.55±0.44
	Pupa	2.31	4.36	3.91	5.06	4.64±0.51
-10	Adult	1.69	5.75	4.721	7.65	2.409±0.25
	Egg	1.03	2.43	1.99	2.93	3.44±0.82
	Larva	1.26	2.95	2.55	3.56	3.47±0.66
	Pupa	1.63	3.73	3.27	4.5	3.57±0.54

The same letters are not significantly different. $P > 0.0001$

Table (6): Statistical analysis and Duncan's multiple range test for various packages on different temperature of all stages of *Callosobruchus maculatus* insect.

		Adult	Egg	Larva	Pupa
Package	Plastic	48.97 B	63.87 AB	47.43 AB	62.98 A
	Sack	52.28 A	65.95 A	49.96 A	63.97 A
	Glass	43.33 C	61.27 B	44.32 B	62.83 A
	F values	67.01	3.48	10.38	1.10
Temperature	5	19.84 D	49.05 D	30.94 D	45.23 C
	0	44.36 C	63.93 C	40.46 C	64.36 B
	-5	65.42 B	76.06 B	62.71 B	79.47 A
	-10	78.9 A	85.82 A	82.05 A	80.08 A
	F values	1261.7	135	233.45	322.47

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Movement and seasonal activity of land snails *Theba pisana* and *Eobania vermiculata* (Gastropoda: Helicidae) on citrus orchards at Qalubiya and Sharkia Governorates

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Abstract:

Horizontal and vertical dispersals of the land snails, white garden snail, *Theba pisana* (Müller) and brown garden snail *Eobania vermiculata* (Müller) (Gastropoda: Helicidae) were investigated in citrus orchards cultivated at Hod Elfadel, Almohamdia, Minya Al-Qamh district, Sharkia Governorate that had an heavy infested with different types of weeds; also, Shoubra Hars, Toukh district, Qalubiya Governorate during the growing season 2018/2019. Reverse relationship was found between abundance density and distance increasing. In vertical distribution, the abundance density of snails decreased by distances increasing on orange trees. Furthermore, spring season harbored the highest population densities followed by summer and winter. The same trend was observed for the horizontal distribution where abundance densities decreased by increasing distances.

Introduction

The Gastropoda is the only molluscs class of successfully invaded land that are a widely dispersal by human activity, mostly in association with movement of soil and plant materials. In the last few years, land snails have been increased and many species were recorded in the majority of governorates (Ghamry *et al.*, 1993; El-Deeb *et al.*, 1997; El-Masry, 1997; Ismail, 1997; Arafa, 2006 and Abed, 2017). Differs of dispersal, movement and daily activity of land snails from one species to another; it is influenced by environmental factors such as soil conditions, food supply temperature, light intensity and humidity. During adverse climatic conditions and drought times, the snails close the shell aperture with a mucus

flap that hardens, or desiccation prevent and breaking dormancy when climatic conditions are favorable again (Godan, 1983). Three common land snails, *Eobania vermiculata* (Müller) , *Theba pisana* (Müller) (Gastropoda: Helicidae) and *Monaches obstructa* (Pfeiffer) (Gastropoda: Hygromiidae) are important crop pests and cause considerable damage in agriculture and horticulture, especially in areas where they find the conditions necessary for rapid multiplication. Land snails caused damage depends on their feeding habits which differ from one species to another. The land snails feed on leaves, roots, tubers and ornamental plants; in addition, an undesirable smell cause during movement snails which not only

prevent men and even animals from feeding on these contaminated plants but also on their population density and activity (El-Okda, 1981 and 1984). *M. cartusiana* caused damage about 5.65% (5.082 tons/feddan) to fresh plant of the Egyptian clover by consecutive cutting.

The work aims to survey the different terrestrial snail species that dominant in the citrus orchards at Qalubiyah and Sharkia Governorates. Also, the vertical and horizontal distribution of common terrestrial snail abundance and knowledge of the seasonal activity for terrestrial snails and numerical density in different lands.

Materials and methods

1. Work area:

The present work was conducted in citrus orchard at Hod elfadel, Almohamdia, Minya Al-Qamh district, Sharkia Governorate that was heavy infested with different types of weeds and Shoubra Hars, Toukh district, Qalubiyah Governorate.

2. Dispersal on orange trees:

2.1. Vertical:

Abundance density of terrestrial snail were measured during three successive growing seasons (winter, spring and summer) on orange trees during 2018/2019. Three levels for each tree were chosen as to follow 1, 2 and 3 meters for each. All live snail adults and juveniles were counted and recorded.

2.2. Horizontal:

White garden snail *T. pisana* and brown garden snail *E. vermiculata* abundance density snails were counted on soil surface at the different distances 1, 3 and 5 m from adjacent. All live snail adults and juveniles were recorded.

3. Statistical analysis:

All work data were statistically analyzed, using Costat Statistical Program Software (1990) and then Duncan's Multiple Range Test (Duncan, 1955) at 5% probability level to compare the differences among means.

Results and discussion

The herbivorous land snail's species, white garden snail, *T. pisana* and brown garden snail *E. vermiculata* were found on orange trees at Qalubiyah and Sharkia Governorates. The identified species varied in incidence and level of infestation according to each locality. The snail, *E. vermiculata* was recorded in surveyed localities, but *T. pisana* snail was found and counted on certain orange trees at Sharkia Governorate only.

1. Vertical dispersal on orange trees:

1.1. Qalubiyah Governorate:

Data in Table (1) and Figure (1) showed different abundance density of *E. vermiculata* snails on orange trees from level to level and from season to another. It is observed that the numerical density decreases with increasing distances on orange trees, where averaged in Table (1) 13.3, 6 and 2.1 snails for winter at 1, 2 and 3 meters, respectively, and averaged 28.5, 10.5 and 5.2 snails for spring and 22.8, 8.75 and 3.3 snails for summer, respectively. The same trend was observed regarding general means where averaged 21.53, 8.8 and 3.52 for the three levels, respectively.

1.2. Sharkia Governorate.

Table (2) and Figure (2) demonstrated that distance of 1, 2 and 3 meters had averages 15.2, 8.06 and 4.2 *E. vermiculata* snails for winter; 20.01, 13.3 and 7.02 for spring and 18.6, 9.04 and 4.8 *E. vermiculata* snails for summer, respectively. Also, the observed regarding general means had the same trend where averaged were 17.9, 10.13 and 5.34 for the three levels, respectively. As presented in Table (3) and Figure (3), the spring season harbored the highest abundance density for the three levels. The third level gave the lowest abundance density level snails, *T. pisana* for winter, spring and summer, respectively. Also, the data in the same table resulted that general mean regarding the first levels > the second levels > the third levels.

2. Horizontal distribution on soil surface (orange orchards) at different distances:

Horizontal distribution of *E. vermiculata* and *T. pisana* snails were counted on soil surface at the different distances 1, 3 and 5 m from adjacent orchards for the three growing seasons 2018/2019 at Shoubra Hars, Toukh districts, Qalubiya governorate and Hod elfadel, Almohamdia, Minya Al-Qamh districts, Sharkia governorate.

3. Horizontal distribution on orange orchards.

Results in Tables (4, 5 and 6) and Figures (4,5 and 6) showed abundance density was decreased by increasing distances from the adjacent tree orchards for the three growing seasons.

3.1. Qalubiya Governorate:

The results of Table (4) and Figure (4) indicated that *E. vermiculata* snail was recorded 9.3, 2, 1.1 and 18.06, 7.75, 2.3 and 17.1, 6.05 and 1.75 snails for winter, spring and summer, respectively. The same trend was observed for general mean where abundance density recorded 14.82, 5.27 and 1.72 for the three levels (1, 3 and 5 m, respectively).

3.2. Sharkia Governorate:

Table (5) and Figure (5) indicated that *E. vermiculata* recorded 7.8, 3 and 1.3 snails for winter; 11.9, 6.75 and 2.9 snails for spring and 6.09, 4.05 and 1.75 snails for summer. Also, data in Table (6) indicated that *T. pisana* snails was first levels > the second levels > the third levels. The same trend was

observed for general mean where abundance density recorded in Table (5); 8.59, 4.6 and 1.98 and recorded in Table (6), 11.93, 6.93 and 2.98 for the three levels (1, 3 and 5 m, respectively). So, it could be mentioned that abundance density on soil surface differences during the three-growing season (winter, spring and summer) and with different types of weeds. Many authors discussed the activity of snails during the growing season. In Egypt, numbers of active snails, *E. vermiculata* on soil were higher than those on trunk where numbers of counted on one-meter heights on the trunk of trees (Ismail *et al.*, 2003). The distance moved by *M. cantiana* during two days in fallow lands and cultivated ranged between 0.5 and 6 m (Arafa, 2006 and Awad, 2014) that revealed the population fluctuations of land snails varied according to temperature, relative humidity and crop kind. The snails were more active during spring than autumn and lower in winter. Abdel Kader *et al.* (2016) reported the highest average of *T. Pisana* was recorded on fruit trees pear, fig, pomegranate and guava. Fig harbored the highest numbers followed by Pear while Pomegranate was the least once in this respect. Ismail *et al.* (2017) reported the population density of snails decreased by increasing distances on navel orange trees in vertical distribution. Also, it can be concluded that it is recommended to carry out pest control operations near the surface of the soil and near the tree trunks.

Table (1): *Eobania vermiculata* terrestrial snail abundance on orange trees at different levels during the growing season 2018/2019 at Qalubiya Governorate .

Levels	Abundance density at different seasons				L.S. D _{0.05}	r	R	F test	P
	Winter	Spring	Summer	Mean					
1m	13.3 ^c	28.5 ^a	22.8 ^b	21.53 ^b	2.215	0.856	0.784	95.94	0.000 ***
2m	6 ^b	10.5 ^a	8.75 ^a	8.8 ^a	2.718	0.812	0.829	5.621	0.0354 *
3m	2.1 ^c	5.2 ^a	3.3 ^b	3.52 ^b	0.816	0.911	0.897	29.32	0.0006 ***

r= correlation R= regression P= probability *= significant

Figure (1): *Eobania vermiculata* terrestrial snail abundance on orange trees at different levels during the growing season 2018/2019 at Qalubiya Governorate.

Table (2): *Eobania vermiculata* terrestrial snail abundance on orange trees at different levels during the growing season 2018/2019 at Sharkia Governorate.

Levels	Abundance density at different seasons				L.S. $D_{0.05}$	r	R	F test	P
	Winter	Spring	Summer	Mean					
1m	15.2 ^c	20.01 ^a	18.6 ^{ab}	17.9 ^b	1.798	0.838	0.747	15.09	0.003 **
2m	8.06 ^c	13.3 ^a	9.04 ^{bc}	10.13 ^b	1.631	0.963	0.947	23.28	0.001 **
3m	4.2 ^c	7.02 ^a	4.8 ^{bc}	5.34 ^b	0.999	0.809	0.6909	17.65	0.002 **

r= correlation R= regression P= probability *= significant

Figure (2): *Eobania vermiculata* terrestrial snail abundance on orange trees at different levels during the growing season 2018/2019 at Sharkia Governorate.

Table (3): *Theba pisana* terrestrial snail abundance on orange trees at different levels.

Levels	Abundance density at different seasons				L.S. D _{0.05}	r	R	F test	P
	Winter	Spring	Summer	Mean					
1m	30.8 ^c	48.9 ^a	33.09 ^c	37.59 ^b	2.579	0.781	0.612	116.6	0.000 ***
2m	15.6 ^{bc}	18.75 ^a	13.05 ^c	15.8 ^b	1.579	0.947	0.919	9.783	0.010 **
3m	5.3 ^b	7.09 ^a	2.75 ^c	5.05 ^b	1.631	0.706	0.558	14.27	0.004 **

r= correlation R= regression P= probability *= significant

Figure (3): *Theba pisana* terrestrial snail Abundance on orange trees at different levels during the growing season 2018/2019 at Sharkia Governorate season 2018/2019 at Sharkia Governorate.

Table (4): *Eobania vermiculata* terrestrial snail abundance on orange orchards at different levels during the growing season 2018/2019 at Qalubia Governorate.

Levels	Abundance density at different seasons				L.S. D _{0.05}	r	R	F test	P
	Winter	Spring	Summer	Mean					
1m	9.3 ^c	18.06 ^a	17.1 ^a	14.82 ^b	1.695	0.963	0.930	66.99	0.001
3m	2 ^c	7.75 ^a	6.05 ^b	5.27 ^b	0.999	0.801	0.794	69.81	0.000
5m	1.1 ^b	2.3 ^a	1.75 ^{ab}	1.72 ^{ab}	0.865	0.731	0.747	3.564	0.087

r= correlation R= regression P= probability *= significant

Figure (4): *Eobania vermiculata* terrestrial snail abundance on orange orchards at different levels during the growing season 2018/2019 at Qalubia Governorate.

Table (5): *Eobania vermiculata* terrestrial snail abundance on orange orchards at different levels during the growing season 2018/2019 at Sharkia Governorate.

Levels	Abundance density at different seasons				L.S. D _{0.05}	r	R	F test	P
	Winter	Spring	Summer	Mean					
1m A	7.8 ^b	11.9 ^a	6.09 ^c	8.59 ^b	0.999	0.857	0.804	71.32	0.000 ***
3m B	3 ^c	6.75 ^a	4.05 ^b	4.6 ^b	0.785	0.919	0.856	29.94	0.0005 ***
5m C	1.3 ^b	2.9 ^a	1.75 ^b	1.98 ^{ab}	0.658	0.754	0.593	5.447	0.0379 *

r= correlation R= regression P= probability *= significant

Figure (5): *Eobania vermiculata* terrestrial snail abundance on orange orchards at different levels during the growing season 2018/2019 at Sharkia Governorate.

Table (6): *Theba pisana* terrestrial snail abundance on orange orchards at different levels during the growing season 2018/2019 at Sharkia Governorate.

Levels	Abundance density in different seasons				L.S. D _{0.05}	r	R	F test	P
	Winter	Spring	Summer	Mean					
1m	10.8 ^{bc}	14.9 ^a	10.09 ^c	11.93 ^b	1.153	0.780	0.652	40.45	0.0002 ***
3m	5 ^c	8.75 ^a	7.05 ^b	6.93 ^b	0.998	0.903	0.897	21.15	0.0014 **
5m	2.3 ^b	3.9 ^a	2.75 ^{ab}	2.98 ^{ab}	1.025	0.832	0.699	4.085	0.0674 ns

r= correlation R= regression P= probability *= significant

Figure (6): *Theba pisana* terrestrial snail abundance on orange orchards at different levels during the growing season 2018/2019 at Sharkia Governorate.

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Contact and feeding effects of chlorantraniliprole, methoxyfenozid and spinosad on some histological changes in cotton leaf worm *Spodoptera littoralis* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae)

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Abstract:

The contact and ingestion effect of chlorantraniliprole, methoxyfenozid and spinosad on the 4th larval instar of *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisduval) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) were studied. Half and a quarter off the recommended rates of three insecticides (Coragen, runner and spinosad) were prepared, and the two methods of contact and food contamination were applied in laboratory to compare their effects on the histo-formation of both the midgut and the integument of the 4th instar larvae *S. littoralis*. Histomorphological changes have been observed within 48 hrs. in both applications (contact and/or ingestion) on the midgut and integument tissue formation of the treated larvae. The treatment with the tested insecticides caused in general, destruction of both goblet and columnar cells of midgut. Epithelial layer showed detached of the basement membrane, disorganized and accompanied by major vacuolization. Separation of both basement and peritrophic membrane. Lysis in the peritrophic membrane led to the mixing of the components of the lumen with the lysis cells of the midgut membrane. It progressively degeneration in the epithelial lining of the midgut. The tested insecticides affected the integument as disturbance with abnormal deposition showing different thickness, fissure in hypodermal cells and endocuticle distortion. These histopathological effects are presumed to be responsible for the food utilization and reduction in growth caused by Runner, coragen and spinosad. Therefore, be concluded that these insecticides have sublethal effects on *S. littoralis* that may affect on the dynamic population in the field by reductions in both survival and reproduction.

Introduction

Cotton, *Gossypium hirsutum* L. is one of the most important economic crops in Egypt and the world since cotton is cultivated in over 100 countries (Zidan *et al.*, 2012). The cotton leafworm, *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisduval) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) is one

of the most polyphagous destructive pests which attacked crops belonging to 40 families such as cotton, vegetables which considered the most valuable crops in the country (Azab *et al.*, 2001). The intensive use of insecticides against *S. littoralis* has led to

the development of insect resistance to many registered pesticides (Sparks and Nauen, 2015). Insecticide resistance is a long-standing and expanding problem for pest arthropod control, that needed to the development of new insecticides such as chlorantraniliprole (CAP). It is primarily active on chewing pests by both ingestion and contact. The target insect rapidly stops feeding, disrupts calcium homeostasis in nerve and muscle cells becomes paralyzed, and ultimately die occurs within 24-72 hours (Bassi *et al.*, 2009). Spinosad is a secondary metabolite produced under natural fermentation conditions by the actinomycete *Saccharopolyspora spinosa*. Routes of insecticides entry include both topical and ingestion. Signs of spinosad poisoning include initial flaccid paralysis, followed by tremors and eventual death (Thompson *et al.*, 1995). Spinosad has been applied to over 200 different crops. It has been used to control caterpillars in various crops, in addition, it is quick degradation, low toxicity to humans, and low doses of use. IGRs considered as the third generation of insecticides because their mode of action differs from other insecticides with low toxicity to natural enemies and less polluted. methoxyfenozide which belongs to dibenzoyhydrazine, developed as a non-steroidal agonist of the insect moulting hormone of caterpillar, acts on binding to ecdysone receptor protein/ ultraspiracle protein and most effective after ingestion larvae cease feeding within 2-5 days. These insecticides which belonged to different groups with a different mode of action including coragen, runner and spinosad are selected for a comparative study to clarify their effects on the histopathological structures of cuticle and midgut of the 4th instar larvae of the cotton leafworm *S. littoralis*.

Materials and methods

1. Test insect:

Field strain of cotton leafworm, *S. littoralis*, were collected from Qalyubia

Governorate and reared under laboratory condition for one generation at 25±2°C in the Department of Cotton Leafworm, Plant Protection Research Institute, Dokki, Egypt, Rearing procedure was carried out according to Ghoneim (1985).

2. Insecticides used:

Coragen 20 % SC. Common name: Chlorantraniliprole (rynaxypyr), Dupont. Recommended rate, 60ml /feddan Tracer 24% SC, Common name: Spinosad 24% Dow Agro Sciences LLC. Recommended rate, 37.5ml / 100 L. Runner 24% SC : Common name: Methoxyfenozid, Dow Agro Sciences LLC. Recommended rate, 50ml /feddan.

3. Laboratory bioassay:

The three tested compounds coragen, runner and spinosad which belonging to different groups were diluted with water to prepare (0.0075 and 0.00375%), (0.00625 and 0.00313%) and (0.0188 and 0.00938%) half and a quarter off the recommended rates of each, respectively. These insecticides were prepared freshly before treatments conducted as two methods, contact and ingestion. Contact bioassay modified to be like Rashwan *et al.* (2013), by using 4 glass jars for each concentration, adding suitable amount of insecticides on them to make insecticide residual film on the glass jar. At the same manner, water instead of insecticides as control. All treatments and the control were left to dry under the room temperature. The 4th instar larvae were placed into each jar for 48 hrs. Ingestion bioassay was carried out by dipping castor bean leaves in the tested concentration solutions for 20 sec, the treated leaves were left to dry under room temperature. The 4th instar larvae were replicated four times and fed for 48 hrs. on treated leaves. At the same time, four replicates of larvae were fed on untreated leaves and used as a control. The survived larvae in both the two treatments as well as untreated larvae were collected and preserved to perform histological preparations.

4. Histological examination of larval midgut using light microscope:

To examine histological changes of both the midgut and the integument 4th instar larvae, *S. littoralis* induced by the tested insecticides, a histological technique was done at the Animal Health Research Institute. Histological cuts of 5 µm were performed with a microtome and dyed with hematoxylin-eosin, according to previously described protocols (Rodríguez-Santiago, 2002). Slices were observed with an optical microscope with the lens of 40× and microphotographs were taken.

Results and discussion

1. Histological examination of the normal midgut 4th instar larvae of *Spodoptera littoralis*:

The midgut of 4th larval instar of *S. littoralis* was shown in Figure (1) the outer sheath of the intestine, includes two types of muscles, the outer one is a layer of longitudinal muscles, and the inner one is a layer of circular muscles. This followed internally by a thin basement membrane where the epithelium rested. The epithelium consists of a layer of epithelial cells, which are elongated and columnar in shape. Each cell consists of a dark round nucleus occupying the middle part of each cell. There are other types of epithelial cells, the regenerative or the imaginal cells, which are small, found between the bases of the columnar cells. The regenerative cells are present individually or in clusters of few cells, each cell contains a large nucleus surrounded with granular cytoplasm. The lumen of the ventriculus is surrounded by the peritrophic membrane, which envelops the food materials and protects the epithelial cells from contact with the food mass. In general, the epithelium layer in the untreated specimen was thicker than that in treated. Microscopic examination showed that the histological structure of the normal midgut of the 4th instar larvae of *S. littoralis* is represented in (Figure, 1). It consists of two

layers of muscle fibers, the outer longitudinal fibers and the inner circular ones. The circular muscle fibers are very close to the basement membrane of the epithelial cells. There is a wide space between the longitudinal fibers. The peritrophic membrane is followed by an epithelial layer of cells which lines the cavity of the midgut. There is a peritrophic membrane surrounding the lumen which protects the epithelial cells from contact with the food mass.

Figure (1): Histomorphological structure of the normal midgut of *Spodoptera littoralis* 4th instar larva. (L.m: Longitudinal muscle b: Basement membrane ep: Epithelial cell p: Peritrophic membrane L: lumen)

2. Histomorphological changes in the midgut 4th instar larvae of *Spodoptera littoralis* treated with “Coragen” insecticide:

The midgut of the 4th larval instar of *S. littoralis* treated via contact with coragen at concentrations 0.0075% and 0.00375%, respectively is shown in Figure (2 a,b). Figure (3 a,b) showed treatment with coragen by ingestion. It was noticed several histological changes compared to the control. In general, coragen was affected on midgut structure as, some epithelial cells disintegrated and necrosis, others cell boundaries were destructed and lysis, elongation of epithelial cells and appearance of vacuoles. Also, the peritrophic membrane was destructed and detached from the epithelial cell. Some complete separation and lysis of the peritrophic membrane led to release the lysis cells into lumen components.

These disturbances in the midgut structure and necrosis cells led to a disturbance in the shapes, enzyme secretion and its function.

Figure (2a,b): Histomorphological changes in the midgut 4th instar larvae of *Spodoptera littoralis* treated with coragen insecticide by contact. a. Completely separation for the basement membrane and necrosis of some cells. Scattering of the nuclear content of the epithelial cell. Partially destruction in the peritrophic membrane. b. Disappearing of basement membrane, cell boundaries, proliferation of columnar cell lining midgut, increase of goblet cell, separation of peritrophic membrane and appearance of vacuoles.

Figure (3a,b): Histomorphological changes in the midgut 4th instar larvae of *Spodoptera littoralis* treated with coragen insecticide by ingestion. a. Severe destruction of cells lining midgut with cell necrosis, complete destruction for epithelial layer and basement membrane completely separated. b. Some of the epithelial cells became detached from the wall of the midgut and full of the vacuoles, the muscle fibers lost their typical striation pattern,

where they became irregular and broad. Sever increase of goblet cells.

Coragen showed effects on the midgut structure by both the contact and ingestion treatments with different degree leading to completely losing its function, increase of goblet cells and destruction for boundaries cell and vacuolization with low concentrations. on the other hand, almost of cell necrosis, lysis and undistinguished specially in ingestion. Increasing goblet cells with losing basement membrane led to losing its permeability, transportation and more effective with high concentration by ingestion than contact.

3. Histomorphological changes in the midgut 4th instar larvae of *Spodoptera littoralis* treated with “Runner” insecticide:

The two concentrations of the compound runner produced great damage in all layers of the midgut wall as shown in (Figure, 4 a,b and Figure, 5 a,b) by contact or ingestion treated. Separation of both basement and peritrophic membrane with the appearance of vacuoles. The most effective concentration was 0.00625 and 0.00313% by ingestion and contact, respectively.

Figure (4a,b): Histomorphological changes in the midgut 4th instar larvae of *Spodoptera littoralis* treated with runner insecticide by contact. a. Sever increase of goblet cells. Partial disruption of both basement and peritrophic membrane in both concentrations. b. Sever proliferation of cell lining midgut with an increase of goblet cells.

Figure (5a,b): Histomorphological changes in the midgut 4th instar larvae of *Spodoptera littoralis* treated with runner insecticide by ingestion. a. Necrosis of some cells lining midgut as well as an increase in goblet cell appearance of vacuoles, disruption of columnar cells. b. An increase of goblet cells, epithelial cells collected in clusters, separation in the basement membrane, lysis in the peritrophic membrane.

4. Histomorphological changes in the midgut 4th instar larvae of *Spodoptera littoralis* treated with “Spinosad” insecticide:

The midgut 4th instar larvae, *S. littoralis* treated with spinosad at concentrations 0.00188 and 0.00938%, respectively, are shown in (Figure, 6 a,b and Figure, 7 a,b) by contact or ingestion treated.

Figure (6 a,b): Histomorphological changes in the midgut 4th instar larvae of *Spodoptera littoralis* treated with spinosad by contact a. Severe proliferation of cells lining midgut, separation of

the basement membrane. b. Necrosis of some cells lining midgut.

Figure (7a,b): Histomorphological changes in the midgut 4th instar larvae, *Spodoptera littoralis* treated with Spinosad insecticide by ingestion. a. Most of the cells lining midgut showing necrosis, epithelial cell undistinguished, partially disrupted basement membrane, complete separation of the peritrophic membrane. b. Severe damage in cells lining midgut.

So, spinosad more effective on midgut by ingestion than contact in both concentrations.

5. Histomorphological changes in the integument 4th instar larvae of *Spodoptera littoralis* induced by the tested insecticides:

Normal integument structure of *S. littoralis* larva is represented in Figure (8).

It consists of an outermost distinct layer, the epicuticle and the inner layer called procuticle. Procuticle, composed of exocuticle which is hardened and endocuticle remains flexible and colorless. Lastly the hypodermal layer is a distinct layer (Epidermal and oenocytes) which composed of columnar or cuboidal cells (Chapman, 2004).

Figure (8): Histomorphological structure of the normal integument of *Spodoptera littoralis* 4th instar

larva. (ep: epicuticle, ex: exocuticle, en: endocuticle, epid: epidermal cell).

6. Histomorphological changes in the integument *Spodoptera littoralis* treated with “Coragen” insecticide:

Histomorphological changes in the integument 4th instar larvae *S. littoralis* are shown in (Figure, 9 a,b and Figure, 10 a,b). Disturbance, thin or thickness of cuticle occurred. On the other hand, by ingestion, the thickness of the cuticle decreased with abnormal deposition.

Figure (9 a,b): Histomorphological changes in the integument of the 4th larval instar of *Spodoptera littoralis* treated with coragen by contact. a. Shows disturbance, thin or thickness of cuticle occurred. b. The thickness of the cuticle decreased with abnormal deposition.

Figure (10 a,b): Histomorphological changes in the integument of the 4th larval instar of *Spodoptera littoralis* treated with coragen by ingestion. a.

thickening of a fibrous layer with irregular cuticle deposition and present of some fat cells. b. Distortion, the thickness of the exocuticle decreased with abnormal deposition.

7. Histomorphological changes in the integument *Spodoptera littoralis* treated with “Runner” insecticide:

Histomorphological changes in the integument 4th instar larvae *S. littoralis* are shown in (Figure, 11 a,b and Figure, 12 a,b) with Runner insecticide by contact and/or ingestion treatments. Runner treatments showed clear a thin layer of exocuticle with abnormal deposition in both contact and ingestion treatments. Lack of fat cells in case of contact than in ingestion.

Figure (11a,b): Histomorphological changes in the integument 4th instar larvae *Spodoptera littoralis* treated with runner insecticide by contact. a. The cuticle thickness decreased with abnormal deposited, lack of fat cell, distortion of endocuticle separated from epidermal cells. b. Appearance of the fat layer, with a thin layer of exocuticle deposition and partial separation of endocuticle from the epidermal cell.

Figure (12 a,b): Histomorphological changes in the integument 4th instar larvae *Spodoptera littoralis* treated with runner insecticide by ingestion. a. Less effect on both hypodermal and fat cells. b. Decrease in the thickness and mild thickening of fibrous layers.

8. Histomorphological changes in the integument *Spodoptera littoralis* treated with “Spinosad” insecticide:

Histomorphological changes in the integument 4th instar larvae *S. littoralis* are shown in (Figure, 13 a,b and Figure, 14 a,b) with spinosad insecticide by contact and/or ingestion.

Figure (13 a,b): Histomorphological changes in the integument 4th instar larvae *Spodoptera littoralis* treated with spinosad insecticide by contact. a. Slight effect on the hypodermal cell, mild thickening layer of exocuticle. b. Thin layer of exocuticle with less irregular cuticle deposition and less distortion in endocuticle with the epidermal regular layer.

Figure (14a,b): Histomorphological changes in the integument 4th instar larvae *Spodoptera littoralis* treated with spinosad insecticide by ingestion. a. Swelling of some epidermal layers with decrease fat cells, an abnormal deposit of thin exocuticle layer with swelling. b. A thin layer of exocuticle, an increase of fat cell. Partial effective on endocuticle with separation from a hypodermal cell.

Our results showed that the highest concentration used for each tested insecticide was the most effective and produced very histomorphological disturbances in the midgut of 4th instar larvae *S. littoralis* treated with the tested compounds. The most recorded observations are destruction in all layers of the midgut, separation of both basement and peritrophic membranes which may lead to losing its permeability properties and losing its function by a disturbance in the potassium transport out of the haemolymph into the gut lumen by goblet cells which responsible for this function (Rosaiah and Mukkerjee,1985). The appearance of vacuoles and lysis in the epithelial cell was noticed. This disturbance, distortion and cell lysis in the midgut structure may be led to disturbance associated with its function and gradually death.

These results are like many previous studies for each of, Abou El-Ghar *et al.* (1994), Abou El-Ghar *et al.* (2013). Ghoneim *et al.* (2015) and Begum and Qamar (2016). They reported that such as these tested insecticides caused vacuolization of the midgut epithelium of *S. littoralis* larvae, in

addition to the sloughing off scattered groups of the midgut epithelium into the gut lumen and disappearance of the cell boundaries. Malinowski (2004) revealed that methoxyfenozide, teflubenzuron and diflubenzuron are reacting with receptors on the brush border membrane of insect midgut, reaches the target tissue mainly by alimentary canal. The ingestion of toxicant by the insects releases a toxic peptide, which binds to sites on the microvilli membranes of the midgut causing cytolysis. Epithelial cells progressively degenerated until it was totally disrupted, and larvae died. The destruction of both goblet and columnar cells of midgut together with pathological effects on microvilli (Federici, 1993). The disruption of the microvilli caused vacuolation appearance of the midgut epithelium of *S. littoralis* larvae as a result of reduced absorptive capacity of the midgut epithelium. , disappear of the cell boundaries and sloughing off scattered groups of the epithelial cells into the lumen. (Abou El-Ghar *et al.*, 1994). Coragen insecticide acts via disrupting calcium homeostasis in central neurons rather than inhibiting AChE as anticholinergic compounds and causes decreased antioxidant and biotransformation enzyme activities (Doyotte *et al.*, 1997; Li *et al.*, 2011 and Andreia *et al.*, 2015). On the other hand, methoxyfenozide and rynaxypyr exhibited the least contact toxicity, whereas spinosad was the slowest. Rynaxypyr was more effective at 24 h as ingestion (Temple *et al.*, 2009 and Rashwan *et al.*, 2013). Rynaxypyr have contact effect (residue film on glass) and ingestion (feeding on insecticide-treated leaves). This leads to paralysis and subsequent death of the insect. IGR's may have calcium-binding properties and may disorganize the cementing substance between cells and tissues of the membrane, which may disturb permeability properties of the plasma membrane and lead to water loss causing dehydration and possibly vacuolization, that explained the coragen shrinkage due to

dehydration may lead to the collapse of the lumen of midgut epithelium. Also, affect the lipid layer of the membrane, which may ultimately destroy specific permeability properties of the plasma membrane. disrupted midgut tissues would function abnormally, and the enzyme secretion and nutrient absorption would be disrupted (Mordue and Blackwell, 1993 and Abd-El-Aziz *et al.*, 2017). The differences between the inactive ingredients are due to their mode of action and method of penetration. So, histopathological changes are one of the most definitive indicators of fat changes, vacuolation and destruction of epithelial cells and their boundaries are highly recognized in both epidermal and midgut cells of tested insects and give a good explanation for the recorded disturbance in the lipid, chitin synthesis, protease lead to disturbances in the function of the internal organs as cell damage (Anitha *et al.*, 1999; Abd-El-Aziz *et al.*, 2013 and 2017). The degeneration of the epithelial cells and decay of its boundaries, caused slight and severe disintegration of the epithelium, fading of the boundaries of epithelial cells and detachment of epithelial cells. This might reflect the variable susceptibility to different insecticides. The present histopathological destruction on cuticle and midgut caused by the tested insecticides may suggest that any of these insecticides can cause the death of an insect when entering tissues either ingestion or contact in adequate amounts. Coragen, runner and spinosad have high toxicity and are considered promising for controlling *S. littoralis* and 48 hrs. after treatment is enough to promote morphological abnormalities and death. Appearance lack of fat cell may be explained the larvae could use it as a source of energy to get rid old cuticle in case of starvation.

Cuticle forms layers on the surface or very close to the surface of secretory cells, and that cuticular deposition may be completed at a distance from the secret or

sites. (Khedr, 2011). IGR's interferes with the exoskeleton chitin by contact, through the alimentary canal. The penetration of insecticides through midgut walls to haemolymph of the treated larvae is the first position to be affected by these compounds, as well as the midgut (peritrophic membrane). In fact, epidermal cells provide the chemical precursor for chitin synthesis process which is extracellular. Moulting (Ecdysis) is initiated with separating epidermal cells from the old cuticle during apolysis process (Chapman, 2004).

Insect growth regulators are known to affect through digestion and utilization of ingested food, IGR acts on the peritrophic membrane by affecting its chitin-protein structure, hindering its role in protecting secretory cells from damage. Indoxacarb caused abnormalities in the shape of the exocuticle and the hypodermal cells separated from the endocuticle, distortion in the endocuticle and some fissure were revealed blockage of its formation in case of methoxyfenozide (Hassan, 2009). While spinetoram has slight effect on the cuticle as compared with other compounds, decreased the thickness of the cuticle, separated some hypodermal cells from the endocuticle. Abd-El-Aziz *et al.* (2013 and 2017) and El-Shourbagy (2019) reported that the disturbance in LDH, indicate excessive disturbance of tissues also, total carbohydrate, chitinase and protease enzymes were significantly disrupted as *S. littoralis* treated with coragen, runner, neem, thyme and bitter and rose bengal. These components are necessary for building cuticle and lake or disruption of them postulated the reason of deformations, increasing abnormal forms due to disturbance in cuticle deposition. Khedr and Mead (2015) mentioned that inability of discarding the old cuticle or precocious molt lead to abnormal chitin deposition. That clear as partially ecdysed larvae with big batches of new cuticle without normal coloration, the

extrusion of body fluids that led to mortality. In the same trend the larval deaths by Novaluron may be due to the failure of larvae to moult owing to the inhibition of chitin formation. a prohibition of feeding and continuous starvation where it suppressed the chitin synthesis and prevented the normal deposition of new cuticle during apolysis leading to the production of abnormalities (Ghoneim *et al.*, 2000 and 2017) or interfere with the synthesis or deposition of chitin on the exoskeleton or other chitinized internal structures or to the inability to shed their exocuticle or to swallow volumes of air for splitting the old cuticle and expand the new one during ecdysis (Adel, 2012 and Zorzetti *et al.*, 2015)

Many studies on *S. littoralis* with coragen, IGR's and other insecticides according to the symptoms as a result of treatment were carried out. Ceases within hours of ingestion, paralysis and may not die for several days, die due to inability to feed, molting acceleration or incomplete molt, lethargic and develop discolored areas or bands between their larvae body by Dhadialla *et al.*, 1998; Kumar and Santharam, 2008; Abd-El-Aziz *et al.*, 2013; Rashwan, 2013; Khaled and Farag, 2015 and Abd-El-Aziz *et al.*, 2017 revealed their effect to disturbance in enzyme activities and carbohydrates hydrolyzing enzymes which inhibit the functions in all insect tissues during metamorphosis processes in the cuticle by inhibition of chitin synthesis due to reducing of chitinase, protease lipids. These components are necessary for building cuticle and digestion of old endocuticle in the molting process. So, any disturbance or lake in these enzymes may attribute to abnormal endocuticular deposition and abnormal molting by disrupted the binds to the ecdysone receptor which initiates the molting process. Another reason, the larvae die due to dehydration, starvation and prevented from shedding its old cuticle within 2-5 days. Also, great damage occurred in cuticular layer,

exocuticle and endocuticle was distinguished, endocuticle separated from hypodermis, partial degeneration with fissure and distortion of epidermal cell as a result of treatment with rose bengal for 5 hrs. (El-Shourbagy, 2019).

The effect of the tested insecticides on the midgut of *S. littoralis* larvae by contact proved their ability to interfere with the exoskeleton chitin then the alimentary canal can be affected. Via ingestion of insecticides the penetration from midgut walls to haemolymph of the treated larvae could be influenced on peritrophic membrane to lose its permeability and caused abnormal structure in midgut. These disturbance, distortion or cell lysis in the midgut structure led to disturbance associated to its function, enzyme secretion, cell degeneration, cell necrosis and gradually die. These abnormal structural may reflect the functional differences between the midgut epithelium of both treated and untreated larvae. The larvae treated with coragen become shrinking, hard, dark in color that may due to dehydration specially in the starved larvae.

The present histomorphological destruction on cuticle and midgut caused by the investigated insecticides may suggest that any of these insecticides can cause death of an insect when entering tissues either ingestion or contact in adequate amounts. Coragen, runner and spinosad have high toxicity and are considered promising for controlling *S. littoralis* and 48 hrs. of treatment enough to promote morphological abnormalities and death. Appearance lack of fat cell may explain the larvae could use it as a source of energy to get rid old cuticle in case of starvation.

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Effects of Dipel 2X and Littovir bioinsecticides on larvae of the cotton leafworm *Spodoptera littoralis* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae)

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Abstract:

Bacillus thuringiensis (Bt) and Nuclear Polyhedrosis Virus (NPV) are effective microbial control agent for controlling numerous species from different insect orders. The cotton leafworm *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisduval) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) is a polyphagous insect pest which infests many crops in Egypt. Toxicity of Dipel 2X (*Bacillus thuringiensis* *Kurstaki*) and Littovir (SpliNPV) was evaluated on *S. littoralis* 2nd instar larvae in the laboratory. Larvae were selected by the two bioinsecticides at sublethal concentrations of LC₇₀, LC₅₀, LC₂₅, LC₁₀ and LC₅. All selected larvae were died after seven days of treatment except those of LC₅ treatment. The offspring (F1 progeny) of LC₅ treatment was selected with two tested formulations at LC₅ concentration. Dipel 2X treatments caused slight depletion in the total protein content of the treated larvae whole body tissues and their gut tissue compared with untreated larvae. LC₇₀ and LC₅₀ treatments produced significant decrease (35.7 and 27.8%, respectively) in protein of treated parent larvae. LC₇₀ treatment of Dipel 2X induced a significant elevation (39.7 and 27.3%) of body tissues (Na⁺/K⁺) ATPases and gut Proteases, respectively. The vigorous histopathological effects of Dipel 2X on midgut tissue of treated larvae were observed in LC₇₀ and decreased in LC₅₀ and lower in LC₂₅. These effects were hyperplasia of epithelial cell layer, appearance of apoptotic bodies, rupture of the brush border microvilli, activation of stem cells, contraction of the muscle layer, extensive fragmentation and separation of mucosal epithelium from the basement membrane and the gut lumen was filled with debris of disrupted cells. Littovir caused insignificant decrease in total proteins of larval tissues with LC₇₀, LC₅₀ and LC₂₅ treatments but LC₁₀ and LC₅ induced increase in protein concentration of treated larvae. This content was increased in gut tissue of all treated larvae. High concentrations of Littovir produced insignificant reduction in ATPases activity in bodies of treated larvae, while lower concentrations elevated this activity which reaches to significant value (31%) in tissues of LC₅ treated larvae. All treatments inhibited the activity of midgut Protease in treated larvae and this effect was pronounced (40.1 and 32.3%) in LC₇₀ and LC₅₀ treatments. LC₇₀ treatment of littovir caused hyperplasia and destruction of the midgut epithelium, appearance of apoptotic bodies, rupture of the brush border microvilli and vacuole formation. These effects decreased with LC₅₀ and LC₂₅ treated larvae. Dipel 2X at LC₅ treatment of 1st generation (F1) larvae caused slight reduction in total proteins and ATPase in larval bodies but Littovir increased proteins and significantly elevated (31%) ATPase in treated larvae. Insignificant increasing in gut proteins and Protease were detected and, slight changes in midgut tissues were observed in larvae treated with the two tested bioinsecticides. Results of this study concluded that the (Na⁺/K⁺) ATPase and Protease played an important role in toxicity of *Bacillus thuringiensis* subsp. *Kurstaki* and Nuclear Polyhedrosis Virus (SpliNPV) and tolerance of *S. littoralis* larvae to their effects.

Introduction

The cotton leaf worm *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisduval) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) is one of the most harmful pests in Egypt and many other countries of the world. This insect infested over 112 plant species belonging to 44 families. The larval stage of *S. littoralis* is known as a notoriously leaf eater accepting almost all herbaceous plant (Hill, 1975). Cotton leaf worm control program was based mainly on use of insecticides, which created some problems such as insecticides-resistance, environmental pollution and hazard to natural enemies and beneficial insects (Toscano *et al.*, 1974 and Abbas *et al.*, 1996). Applying new types of insecticides, originated from natural agents or products that disrupt the physiological processes of the target pest, could be useful alternatives in the integrated management approach (Parsaeyan *et al.*, 2013). Microbial biopesticides are environmentally safe, self-perpetuating in nature and specific to target pests. Among the microbial biopesticides, bacterial, virus and fungal products occupy a special space in managing several pests (Bidyarani- Devi *et al.*, 2016).

Bacterial insecticides were the earliest developed and the most widely used microbial pesticides in the world. During sporulation, different strains of this gram-positive bacterium produce crystalline parasporal inclusion bodies, composed of one or more toxic proteins known as δ -endotoxins, with a high level of specificity against different species of lepidopteran, dipteran, and coleopteran insects (Höfte and Whiteley, 1989). The mode of action of the largest group of Cry proteins, can be divided into four main steps: (i) The cry toxins are ingested and solubilized of the inclusion body to release the cry proteins in their protoxin form, (ii) Gut protease processing of these protoxins to the active toxins, (iii) Binding of the active form to specific receptors in the midgut of the insect, (iv) Oligomerization, membrane insertion, and pore formation of

the active toxin, eventually leading to cellular lysis of the insect midgut epithelium (Gill *et al.*, 1992; Knowles, 1994; Schnepf *et al.*, 1998; de Maagd *et al.*, 2001 and Bravo and Soberón, 2008). The *Bt* crystal inclusion, toxicity is dependent on a complex process that requires multiple steps, these include solubilization of the crystal proteins, proteolytic processing of the protoxin to the active form, high affinity binding with the midgut receptor, and the irreversible insertion of the toxin in to the gut membrane (Jenkins *et al.*, 2000).

Alterations in any of these steps could result in the development of resistance to one or several Cry proteins in each insect population (Ferré and Van Rie, 2002 and Heckel *et al.*, 2007). *Bacillus thuringiensis* (*Bt*) is the most common bacterial insecticides which specific to larvae of lepidopteran pests (Peng, 1992). The application of *B. thuringiensis* in Egypt started at 1960 against young larvae of the cotton leafworm *S. littoralis* (El-Husseini, 1981). In 1980 many cry specific toxin genes cloning was subsequently performed, led to *Bt* uses development as well as in transgenic plants and manifested to be an alternative to the chemical pesticides.

Viruses are sub microscopic, intracellular and obligate pathogenic entities with nucleic acid and protein. These viruses are often genus or species specific and highly virulent to their hosts. Entomopathogenic viruses are currently used as alternatives to traditional insecticides. Several groups of viruses having a potential in controlling many insect pests. Among these groups of viruses, Nuclear Polyhedrosis Virus (NPV) which belongs to the family baculoviridae was exploited widely as a microbial control (Herniou *et al.*, 2012). Its use should not be generalized because each pest has its own case. In specific cases, viruses proved very effective in managing populations of certain pests as Lepidoptera and Hymenoptera (El-Husseini,

2006). Baculoviral preparations are made up based on viral polyhedral, composed of virions embedded in a matrix of polyhedrin protein, highly resistant to the ecological factors and recently utilized alone and in combined with *Bt* called, recombinant viruses. The virus enters the nucleus of infected cells and reproduces until the cell is assimilated by the virus and produces crystals in the fluids of the host and death. These crystals will transfer the virus from one host to another (Chiu *et al.*, 2012). NPV forming polyhedra like occlusion bodies kills most important crop pests such as *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hübner) and *Spodoptera litura* (Fabricius) (Lepidoptera:Noctuidae) (Bidyarani-Devi *et al.*, 2016). Fact is that the NPVs infect and replicate in different host tissues (fat bodies, hypoderm, trachea, and blood cells). In sawflies (Symphyta: Hymenoptera), NPVs infect only the midgut tissue. Such differences influence greatly the number of virions produced per infected host individual, affecting both the dynamics of horizontal transmission in nature and the economics of commercial virus production (Van Driesche and Bellows, 1996). Asri *et al.* (2013) reported that the polyhedral occlusion bodies of *S.litura* Nucleopolyhedrosis Virus (SplMNPV) infected various organs i.e. lumen, peritrophic membrane, midgut epithelial layers, trachea, blood vessels, malpighian tubules, muscles and adipocytes but not the cuticle.

The laboratory techniques of experimental biochemistry and histopathology were used to elucidate the tissue changes as a result of insect pathogen interaction (Kellogg, 1903). Insect adenosinetriphosphatase (ATPases) and gut proteases were affected by bioinsecticide treatments. ATPases are a class of enzymes that catalyze the decomposition of ATP into ADP and a free phosphate ion. This dephosphorylation reaction releases energy, which the enzyme (in most cases) harnesses to drive other chemical reactions that would not otherwise occur. This process

is widely used in all known forms of life. Some such enzymes are integral membrane proteins and move solutes across the membrane, typically against their concentration gradient. These are called transmembrane ATPases. ATP-binding cassette (ABC) transporters, a large class of transmembrane proteins, are widely found in organisms and play an important role in the transport of xenobiotics. Insect ABC transporters are involved in insecticide detoxification and *Bacillus thuringiensis* (*Bt*) toxin perforation (Wu *et al.*, 2019). Proteases are defined as peptide hydrolases and include all enzymes that hydrolyze peptide bonds (Beynon and Bond, 1993). Proteinases refer to a specific class of proteases and are synonymous with the term endopeptidases, which cleave internal bonds in a peptide. Most of the proteases that degrade *Bt* insecticidal crystal proteins (ICPs) are proteinases. ICPs were degraded by proteases from a variety of sources, including those endogenous to the bacterium, those purified from animals and plants, or those found in insects. Proteases in the bacterium function in protein metabolism during sporulation; in some cases, they hydrolyze ICPs. Insect proteases are implicated in *Bt* toxin specificity, mode of action and insect adaptation to *Bt* (Oppert, 1999). Wu *et al.* (2016) stated the insect midgut proteases generally activating Cry toxins. Proteases are the most important protein digestive enzymes in the midgut of insects. The histopathological investigation of midgut epithelial cells in treated insect showed signs of apoptosis manifested as shrinkage of the cells and the presence of condensed chromatin with some vacuolization. This process is considered as the proper mechanism of cells against pathogens and toxic compounds (Dougherty *et al.*, 2006 and Sakr, 2007).

This work aims to investigate the effects of bioinsecticides (Dipel 2X and Littover) on ATPase and protease enzymes and histology

of midgut in treated larvae of the cotton leafworm *S. littoralis*.

Materials and methods

1. Insects:

The lab strain of the cotton leaf worm *S. littoralis* was collected as egg masses from fields of Giza Governorate, Egypt. Eggs were kept in glass jars until hatching under laboratory condition ($25\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$, $65\pm 5\%\text{RH}$. and photoperiod of 16 hrs. and 8h.D). The larvae were fed on castor bean plant leaves (*Ricinus communis*) until pupation and adult emergence. The newly emerged adults were mated inside glass jars supplied with a piece of cotton wetted with 10% sugar solution as feeding source and branches of tafla plant (*Nerium oleander*) were added to each jar as an oviposition site (Hatem *et al.*, 2011). The insects were reared without any exposure to insecticides for seven years in Central Agricultural Pesticides Laboratory, Agricultural Research Center, Giza, Egypt.

2. Insecticides:

2.1. Dipel 2X 6.4% WP (32×10^3 spores/mg) product of Valent BioSciences company–Canada. Dipel 2X is a biological insecticide produced to control lepidopteran larvae and prepared as dry flowable formulations containing live spores and endotoxin of *Bacillus thuringiensis*, subsp. *Kurstaki* in the form of a water dispersible granule

2.2. Littovir SC (5×10^{11} polyhedral inclusion bodies - PIB /liter) product of Bienvenue Chez Andermatt Biocontrol company-Switzerland. Littovir SC is a formulated insecticide specified to *S.littoralis* larvae and classified as order nucleopolyhedrovirus (SpliNPV) and Family baculoviridae.

3. Bioassay:

Seven serial aqueous concentrations of Dipel-2X and Littovir were prepared by water dilution. Castor bean plant leaves were dipped in each prepared concentration and left to dry in air then they placed in petri dishes. Almost 280 larvae of the cotton leafworm *S. littoralis* newly molted 2nd instar were used in the initial bioassay with 4

replicates. Treated castor bean leaves introduced to feed larvae for two days then they provided with clean castor bean leaves. Control Larvae were fed on leaves dipped in tap water. Larval mortality was scored daily. Mortality percentages were recorded after four days and corrected by Abbott's formula (Abbott, 1925). Data were analysed by probit analysis (Finney, 1971) to estimate the sublethal concentrations. Other 200 larvae were selected with each of determined LC₇₀, LC₅₀, LC₂₅, LC₁₀ and LC₅ of two tested bioinsecticides. The offspring (F1 progeny) from the previous LC₅ treatment was selected with different concentrations of the two tested bioinsecticides. The survivals from selected parent and LC₅ of F1 2nd instar larvae were collected for biochemical investigation and histopathological examination.

4. Biochemical assays:

4.1. Preparation of samples:

Hundred milligrams of the untreated, LC₇₀, LC₅₀, LC₂₅, LC₁₀ and LC₅ treated parent and LC₅ treated (F1) larvae were homogenized in 1ml of sodium phosphate buffer (pH=7) for 3 minutes using a manual teflon homogenizer surrounded by a jacket of crushed ice and centrifuged for 30 min at 10000 rpm / min at 4°C by a cooler centrifuge (Mikro – 22R, Germany). The supernatant was transferred to new tubes and frozen at (-20°C) for biochemical analyses. Total protein content and the activity of adenosinetriphosphatase (ATPase) enzyme of control and treated larvae were determined by spectrophotometer (Unico UV 2100 spectrophotometer U.S.A).

4.2. Determination of total protein contents:

Total protein content in the whole-body homogenate of the untreated, treated parent and F1 larvae was determined based on Biuret test (Henry, 1964), using Kit purchase from dp international laboratory. A mixture of 1.0 ml of the total protein reagent (0.2N sodium hydroxide, 18mM/L sodium

potassium tartrate, 12mM/L potassium iodide and 6mM/L cupric sulfate), 20µl of each sample and 20µl of deionized water then incubated for 5 minutes at 25°C. Read and recorded the absorbance at wavelength of 546 nm versus the reagent blank as reference and standard. The total protein concentration in the whole-body homogenate of control and treated larvae was represented as mg/gm body weight of insects.

4.3. Determination of adenosinetriphosphatase (ATPase) activity:

ATPase catalyzed the conversion of ATP to ADP. During this conversion, one molecule of phosphorus was liberated. The inorganic phosphorus liberated was assayed (Fiske and Subbarow, 1925). The specific activity of sodium and potassium dependent on ATPase in the whole-body homogenate of untreated, treated parent and F1 larvae was determined according to the method of Shiosaka *et al.* (1971) with some modifications. Reagent 1 consisted of 6 mM MgCl₂, 6 mM ATP, 50 mM Tris, 100 mM NaCl and 20 mM KCl. Reagent 2 was trichloroacetic acid (T.C.A., 10%) and reagent 3 was ammonium molybdate consists of 1.5 gm ammonium molybdate, 40 ml distilled water (d.w.) and 20 ml sulphuric acid 10 M completed to 80 ml d.w. Reagent 4 was 0.5 gm Metol in 50 ml sodium bisulfate 3%. Reagent 5 was the standard phosphate solution consists of 0.022 gm KH₂PO₄, 100 ml d.w and few drops of chloroform. The procedure was: 1ml of d.w., 100 µl of sample and 1ml of reagent (1) were added to test tube then incubated at 45°C for 10 min and added 0.5 ml T.C.A., then incubated in ice for 30 min and centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 min, 200 µl of supernatant was put to 1.8 of T.C.A., then mixed and centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 5 min, three tubes were prepared as sample (S), standard (ST) and blank (B), then pipetted 200 µl of ammonium molybdate solution and metol into each tube, 0.9 and 1ml of T.C.A in (ST) and (B) tubes

respectively, 100 µ of standard phosphate solution in (ST) tube, and 1ml of sample into (S) tube, finally each tube was measured spectrophotometry at 680 nm after 30 min. The standard curve was prepared by using serial dilutions of KH₂PO₄ solution (0.2µm-1µm) and the activity was represented as ml mol / min / mg protein.

4.4. Determination of gut protease activity:

The untreated, treated parent and F1 larvae were dissected and the gut tissues were isolated. Then gut tissues were homogenized and prepared for protein and protease analysis. The activity of gut protease enzyme was determined spectrophotometry according to the method of Brik *et al.* (1962) with some modification by Wang *et al.* (2007). The procedure was, 20 µl of midgut homogenate was mixed with 150µl 1% azocasein in 50mM NaHCO₃-Na₂CO₃ buffer, (pH 11) and incubated at 28°C for 2hrs. The digestion was stopped and indigestive azocasein was precipitated by addition of an equal volume of trichloroacetic acid (T.C.A., 10%), followed by incubation at room temperature for 1hrs. The precipitated proteins were removed by centrifugation at 18000 rpm for 10 min, the supernatant was collected and mixed with an equal volume of 1M NaOH, and then its optical absorbance was measured at 450 nm. Control reactions were identical except for the absence of gut extracts. The rate of proteolysis of azocasein was expressed as change in absorbance / min / mg protein.

The total protein content and enzyme activities of all samples are reported as mean ± standard error and statistically analyzed using Excel Microsoft Office and Student's t-test Program. Differences were considered significant at $p < 0.05$ level.

5. Histopathological assay:

The survival from untreated and treated parents (LC₇₀, LC₅₀ and LC₂₅) and 1st generation (LC₅) larvae were fixed in 10% formalin solution for quick larvae killing and tissue fixing. About ten larvae were bulked in

vials and kept in refrigerator till cutting. The fixed specimens were trimmed, washed and dehydrated in ascending grades of alcohols and cleaned in xylene. The larvae were imbedded in paraffin wax and serial sections of 4- 6 microns were made by microtome and mounted on glass slides and stained with haematoxyline and eosin and counterstained in alcoholic solution and prepared for examination by light microscope and photography (Durry and Wallington, 1980).

Results and discussion

1. Bioassay:

Toxicity parameters (concentration of insecticide and response of treated insects) of the two biological insecticides were illustrated in Tables (1 and 2). The value of LC₇₀, LC₅₀, LC₂₅, LC₁₀ and LC₅ of *B. thuringiensis*, sub sp. *Kurstaki* (Dipel 2x) reached to 36600, 18400, 7640, 7000 and 3450 spores/ml for parent 2nd instar larvae of *S.littoralis* and LC₅ value of 1st generation (F1) was decreased to 2150 Spores/ ml. The same values of Nucleopolyhedrovirus NPV (Littovir) were 2.38x10⁸, 1.45x10⁸, 7.75x10⁷, 7.71 x10⁷, 4.40 x10⁷ and 3.13 x10⁷ PIB/ml for parents and 1st generation (F1) larvae, respectively. These data showed that Dipel 2x was more toxic to *S. littoralis* 2nd instar larvae than Littovir. The parent and their offspring (F1) larvae submitted insecticide doses dissimilar between the two generations, where the parents tolerated the dose that was equal LC₇₀ while the 1st generation (F1) was more susceptible and the dose declined to LC₅. The mortality rate was arising quickly and noticeable timely and was obligated according to the biological degradation affected by insecticide stressful and refer to the pest population at the subsequent generation had weak tolerance to this type of insecticide formulations. The two insecticide concentration values refer to the definite number of spores and virion that can kill the larvae of *S. littoralis* and the selection methods by the two formulations was not steepest but always decreased to smallest

number of spores and virions responsible for killing. General observations on treated *S. littoralis* 2nd instar larvae were taken during the selection period with two pathogens. Treated larvae with higher concentrations of Bt produced morphological abnormalities appeared shortly after treatment and mortality become higher. After few days larvae died and remaining inactive ingoing prolonged moulting and body color changed. Abnormalities and growth disruption were taking place at lower concentrations, failure moulting and incomplete shaped were performed, infected larvae had small bodies and large heads. Feeding of larvae on virus revealed no symptoms during the first three days of treatment, but in the 4th day, infected larvae appeared more slowly, whitish, weak cuticle, body swelling than healthy larvae, body turn to liquid and death of treated larvae within few days. All treated larvae with the two bioinsecticides were dead except some of those treated with LC₅ which could grow to pupae and adult moths and produce 1st generation (F1) larvae. These larvae (F1) were more susceptible to the two tested pathogens and all selected larvae were dead after few days except those treated with LC₅.

Other researchers were detected the same results as, Jakka *et al.* (2014) mentioned that no differences in susceptibility to XenTari WG and Dipel ES pesticides were detected. No re-entry interval spraying is needed, and resistance development is slower than other chemicals. Time of application depend on the insect early stages. Hallad *et al.* (2011) recorded the highest mortality of *S. litura* was 80.3,72.6 and 64.2% for 2nd, 3rd and 4th instar larvae which treated with leaf disc feeding method by 80 Ppm of cry toxin. Polanczyk *et al.* (2000) reported that treatment of *S. frugiperda* 2nd instar larvae with suspensions of *Bt aizawai* (HD 68) and *Bt. thuringiensis* (4412) which containing 3 x 10⁸ cells/ml, produced 100% and 80.4% mortality of treated larvae, respectively. Abd-El Wahed *et al.* (2011) evaluated the potency

of commercially formulated biological insecticide; protecto (*Bt* var. *kurstaki*), viruset (Nuclear Polyhydrosis Virus SLNPV) and their mixture protect against *S. littoralis* 2nd instar larvae. Protecto is more effective than others, viruset was more effective on 4th instar larvae than protect. LC₉₀ and LC₅₀ for viruset were 1x10⁶ and 1x10³ PIBs/ml, respectively. Benuzzi *et al.* (2012) mentioned that timing of application and standard dosage of Littovir (SpliNPV) 200 ml/hectar reduced the hatching of *S.littoralis* larvae at repeated sprays in 8-day intervals. No residues were recorded on the crop and safe on mammals, beneficial insects and can be in uses in organic farming. Bt toxins and Baculoviruses are invertebrate-specific pathogens cause alterations in the physiology, metabolism and morphology of insects. Feeding of larvae on the two bioinsecticides

produced symptoms which observed by Sharaby and El-Bendary (2017) who mentioned that the spore δ -endotoxin complex of *Bt* var aizawai effect on *S. littoralis* larvae. Toprak *et al.* (2005) reported that after inoculated of *S. littoralis* larvae with SpliNPV doses of 3000 and 20,000 OBs/ml (for neonates) and 10⁶ and 3x 10⁶ OBs/ml (for third instar), the symptoms appeared as; slowness of movement, vomiting ,diarrhea, complete paralysis and death. A unique dissimilar symptom and killing efficiency of multiple nucleopolyhedrovirus- SfmNPV-6th isolates were detected by Vieira *et al.* (2012) as no liquefaction in integument of *S. frugiperda* larvae and took a long time to kill than the high virulent isolate, SfmNPV-19.

Table (1): Distinct concentrations of Dipel 2X and Littovir submitted to *Spodoptera littoralis* 2nd instar larvae (parents).

Insecticides	LC ₇₀ (95% FL)	LC ₅₀ (95% FL)	LC ₂₅ (95% FL)	LC ₁₀ (95% FL)	LC ₅ (95%FL)	Slope \pm SE	χ^2 (df)
Dipel 2x 6.4% WP (32x10 ³ Spores /mg)	36600 (27300- 53400)	18400 (12600-24800)	7640 (3770-11430)	7000 (3200-10400)	3450 (1190-6080)	1.76 \pm 0.297	1.2
Littovir SC (5x10 ⁸ PIB /ml)	2.38X10 ⁸ (1.9X10 ⁸ - 2.5X10 ⁸)	1.45X10 ⁸ (1.15X10 ⁸ - 1.8X10 ⁸)	7.75X10 ⁷ (5.5x10 ⁷ - 6.9x10 ⁷)	7.71X10 ⁷ (4.7x10 ⁷ - 6.1x10 ⁷)	4.40 X10 ⁷ (3.7x10 ⁷ - 5.2x10 ⁷)	2.46 \pm 0.312	0.634

FL: Fiducial Limits

Table (2): Distinct concentration of Dipel 2X and Littovir submitted to *Spodoptera littoralis* 2nd instar larvae (1st generation F1).

Insecticides	LC ₅ (95% FL)	Slope \pm SE	χ^2 (df)
Dipel 2x 6.4% WP (32x10 ³ Spores /mg)	2150 (590-4210)	1.76 \pm 0.297	1.2
Littovir SC (5x10 ⁸ PIB /ml)	3.13 x10 ⁷ (2.5x10 ⁷ - 4.4x10 ⁷)	2.46 \pm 0.312	0.634

FL: Fiducial limits.

2. Biochemical assays:

2.1. Total protein content:

Total protein content is one of the major biochemical components necessary for an organism to develop, grow and perform its vital activities. Protein are important for individual level fitness associated traits such as body size, growth rate and fecundity and at higher levels of organization they have been linked to population dynamics, life histories and even biological diversification (Fagan *et al.*, 2002). Data in Table (3) illustrated the effect of LC₇₀, LC₅₀, LC₂₅, LC₁₀ and LC₅ (for parents) and LC₅ (for F1) of Dipel 2X and Littovir treatments on total protein content in the whole-body homogenate of *S. littoralis* 2nd instar larvae. The protein concentration reached to 0.227 ±0.052, 0.146 ±0.075, 0.164 ±0.036, 0.177 ±0.064, 0.192 ±0.031, 0.201 ±0.016, 0.216 ±0.027 (mg/ mg B.W.) in the whole-body tissues of untreated (control) and Dipel 2X treated larvae, resp. These values were 0.208 ±0.044, 0.211 ±0.042, 0.217 ±0.033, 0.234 ±0.047, 0.263 ±0.023, 0.291 ±0.011 (mg/ mg B.W.) in Littovir treated larvae, respectively. These results revealed the presence of significant depletion (35.7 and 27.8%) in total proteins of treated parent larvae with LC₇₀ and LC₅₀ of Dipel 2X compared with control larvae. Insignificant decrease in proteins of treated larvae was detected in other treatments of Dipel 2X and high concentrations of Littovir. Insignificant increase (3.1 and 15.9%) in larval proteins was recorded with LC₁₀ and LC₅ treatments of Littovir, but a significant value (28.2%) was presented in tissues of F1 larvae treated with LC₅ of virus.

Nath *et al.* (1997) mentioned that protein depletion in tissues may constitute a physiological mechanism and might play a role in compensatory mechanisms under insecticidal stress to provide intermediates to the kerbs cycle by retaining free amino acid content in insect tissues. Abd El-Aziz (2000) reported that infection of the cotton leafworm, *S. littoralis* larvae with *B.*

thuringienses var. *kurstaki* (Dipel 2X) produced high significant reduction in the protein content. LC₅₀ treatment of *P.gossypiella* larvae with Bt and NPV caused insignificant increasing (13.9 and 7.3%) in the total protein of treated larvae than untreated ones (Radwan *et al.*, 2018).

2.2. ATPases activity:

ATPases are membrane bound enzymes, the role of membrane lipids and their micro-environmental changes at physical and chemical levels may be responsible for the differential response observed at the level of ATPases activity in the insect populations. Membrane ATPases assist transport, reabsorption of metabolites and nutrients. These enzymes are secondary carriers of ions and non-electrolytes (Lechleitner and Phillips, 1988 and Fogg *et al.*, 1991). ATPases are essential for the transport of glucose, amino acids, and other organic molecules. Any impairment in their activity will affect the physiology of the insect gut. These enzymes are in the midgut, malpighian tubules, muscles, and nerve fibers of the lepidopteran insects (Nathan, 2013). In lepidopterans, the perineurium serves as a diffusion barrier for polar cardenolides and provides an active barrier for non-polar cardenolides, and the P-glycoprotein-like transporter mediates the efflux of cardenolides in the nerve cord, thereby preventing interaction of these toxins with the susceptible target site in Na⁺/K⁺ ATPase (Petschenka *et al.*, 2013).

The effects of Dipel 2X and Littovir treatments on the activity of Na⁺/K⁺ ATPase enzymes in the whole-body tissues of *S.littoralis* larvae were shown in Table (3). The activity of ATPases in untreated larvae reached to 7.71 ±0.822 μ mol/ mg protein/ min, but this activity was insignificantly elevated (16.5 and 20.4 and 15.1 and 24.0%) with LC₅₀ and LC₂₅ of Dipel 2X and LC₂₅ and LC₁₀ of Littovir treatments for parent larvae, respectively. A significant elevation (39.7 and 31.0%) in ATPase enzymes was

recorded in Bt LC₇₀ and virus LC₅ treatments of parent larvae compared with control. Insignificant inhibition of enzyme activity was presented in other treatments of parents and F1 larvae.

Dermauwa and Van Leeuwen (2014) mentioned that the hydrolysis of ATP during substrate transport is followed by quantification of the liberated inorganic pyrophosphate. The transported compounds such as inhibitors controlled this ATPase activity. Nathan *et al.* (2004) reported that the rice leaf folder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guenée) (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) larvae exposed to bacterial toxin were exhibited reduction in ATPase activities. The ATP content of toxin-treated tissue of the spruce budworm, *Choristoneura fumiferana* (Clemens) (Lepidoptera: Tortricidae) is inversely proportional to the amount of toxin added and incubation with δ -endotoxin protein for 60 min and revealed massive outer membrane disruption and subsequent loss of cytoplasmic constituents, accompanied by swelling of the nuclear

membrane (Johson, 1981). Castagnola and Stock (2014) reported the binding of Bt to ATP reported to disrupt ion channels in the midgut neuromuscular junctions that causes paralysis by the release of K⁺ from the midgut into the hemolymph or from intracellular sources such as K⁺ channels and disrupt ion transport across a membrane and named Bt receptors. The midgut plasma membrane V-ATPase of the tobacco hornworm *Manduca sexta* L. (Lepidoptera: Sphingidae) was occurred in the apical cell membranes of goblet cells, and down-regulated during moulting and starvation. The decrease in transcript levels lead to minimizes V-ATPase biosynthesis, inactivation and save cellular energy (Wieczorek *et al.*, 2000). Mikhailova (1989) stated the *Spodoptera frugiperda* (Smith) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) cells exposed to baculovirus vector SUR1 and Kir 6.2 infection, ATP-sensitive K-channels was sensitive to ATP, glibenclamide and diazoxide, and anywhere blocked by ATP but insensitive to sulphonylureas.

Table (3) : The total protein content and Na⁺/K⁺ ATPase enzyme activity in the whole-body tissues of untreated and treated *Spodoptera littoralis* larvae.

Bioinsecticide concentration	Dipel2x				Littovir			
	Total protein concentration (mg/mg B.W.)		ATPase activity (μ mol/mg protein/min)		Total protein concentration (mg/mg B.W.)		ATPase activity (μ mol/mg protein/min)	
	Mean \pm S.E	Change %	Mean \pm S.E	Change %	Mean \pm S.E	Change %	Mean \pm S.E	Change %
Untreated	0.227 \pm 0.052	0.0	7.71 \pm 0.822	0.0	0.227 \pm 0.052	0.0	7.71 \pm 0.822	0.0
LC ₇₀	0.146 \pm 0.075	(-) 35.7*	10.77 \pm 0.614	(+)39.7*	0.208 \pm 0.044	(-) 8.4	7.52 \pm 0.572	(-)2.5
LC ₅₀	0.164 \pm 0.036	(-) 27.8*	8.98 \pm 0.353	(+)16.5	0.211 \pm 0.042	(-) 7.1	7.38 \pm 0.384	(-)4.3
LC ₂₅	0.177 \pm 0.064	(-) 22.0	9.29 \pm 0.467	(+)20.5	0.217 \pm 0.033	(-) 4.4	8.87 \pm 0.276	(+)15.1
LC ₁₀	0.192 \pm 0.031	(-) 15.4	7.68 \pm 0.482	(-)0.4	0.234 \pm 0.047	(+) 3.1	9.56 \pm 0.355	(+)24.0
LC ₅	0.201 \pm 0.016	(-) 11.5	6.55 \pm 0.753	(-)15.1	0.263 \pm 0.023	(+) 15.9	10.10 \pm 0.437	(+)31.0*
F1) LC ₅ (0.216 \pm 0.027	(-) 4.9	5.98 \pm 0.677	(-)22.4	0.291 \pm 0.011	(+) 28.2*	7.19 \pm 0.922	(-)6.7

Each value represents the mean of three replicates \pm S.E (+) = Increase, (-) = Decrease, S.E = Standard Error at P < 0.05
* = Significant

3. Proteases activity:

Insect midgut proteases are original targets for insecticidal agents such as Bt Cry toxins

and viruses (Terra and Ferreira, 1994). Data in Table (4) revealed that the total protein content (0.205 \pm 0.052 mg/mg gut) of gut

tissue was low than in the whole-body tissues of untreated *S.littoralis* larvae with insignificant value (9.7%). The concentration of gut proteins was slightly decreased (16.6, 9.8 and 5.4%) in parent larvae treated with LC₇₀, LC₅₀ and LC₂₅ of Dipel 2X than control larvae. The remaining treatments of Dipel 2X and all Littovir caused insignificant increase in gut proteins of treated larvae. Rashed *et al.* (2012) mentioned that after 24 and 48 hrs. of treatment the pink bollworm, *P. gossypiella* 3rd instar larvae with LC₅₀ of Dipel 2X and Abamectin, the total protein content of gut tissue was decreased by 33.1, 33.5% and 39, 26.3%, respectively.

A set of protease enzymes allows *S.littoralis* to feed on different host plants, so that the activity of protease enzymes in gut tissue of control larvae was 181.20 ±4.752 (mM/mg protein/ min) and increased in bacterial treatments till significant value (27.3%) with LC₇₀ treatment of parent larvae. Littovir caused slight reduction in gut proteases of treated larvae which reach to significant value (40.1 and 32.3 %) with LC₇₀ and LC₅₀ (Parent) treatments. LC₅ treatment of two pathogens caused a slight increase in activity of F1 treated larvae gut proteases. The same results were detected in *S. littoralis* gut by Keller *et al.* (1996) who found that the degradation rate of δ –ednotoxin was

consistent with the increase of protease activity during larval development. Trypsin proteases in *S. litura* larvae midgut were involved in the Vip3Aa toxin activation (Song *et al.*, 2016). Oppert (1999) found no differences in midgut proteinase activity from susceptible and *Bt kurstaki*-resistant strains, but *Bt subsp. Entomocidus*, had lower soluble gut proteinase activities. Bt resistance mechanisms may include changes in gut pH, or modifications in proteases and changes in solubility, differences in the degree of protoxin activation, enhanced toxin or receptor-toxin degradation. Wilkins (2017) stated that changes in proteases activity are insecticide resistance evidenced and play role in maintaining healthy cells and elevated protease activity leave more degradation products (amino acids) of intracellular proteins. The specific activity of total protease, chymotrypsin and elastase enzymes was significantly decreased with increasing of *Btk* concentrations (Fathipour *et al.*, 2019). The ingestion of *S. exigua* to sub-lethal doses of two *B. thuringiensis* toxins, Cry1Ca and Vip3Aa, and nucleopolyhedrovirus (SeMNPV) caused high transcriptional activation of genes encoding antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) and lysozymes in the midgut (Crava *et al.*, 2015).

Table (4) : The total protein content and total protease enzymes activity in the gut tissues of untreated and treated *Spodoptera littoralis* larvae.

Bioinsecticide concentration	Dipel2x				Littovir			
	Total protein concentration (mg/mg gut tissues)		Protease activity (mMol /mg protein/min)		Total protein concentration (mg/mg B.W.)		Protease activity (mMol /mg protein/min)	
	Mean ± S.E	Change %	Mean ± S.E	Change %	Mean ± S.E	Change %	Mean ± S.E	Change %
Untreated	0.205 ±0.052	0.0	181.20 ±4.752	0.0	0.205 ±0.052	0.0	181.20 ±4.752	0.0
LC ₇₀	0.171 ±0.075	(-) 16.6	230.64 ±4.625	(+) 27.3*	0.246 ±0.016	(+) 20.0	108.51 ±3.621	(-) 40.1*
LC ₅₀	0.185 ±0.036	(-) 9.8	219.88 ±6.112	(+) 21.4	0.231 ±0.067	(+)12.7	122.75 ±3.954	(-) 32.3*
LC ₂₅	0.194 ±0.064	(-) 5.4	211.58 ±3.877	(+) 16.8	0.218 ±0.036	(+)6.3	150.51 ±5.222	(-) 16.9
LC ₁₀	0.213 ±0.031	(+) 3.9	201.45 ±5.566	(+) 11.2	0.224 ±0.033	(+) 9.3	162.93 ±4.363	(-) 10.1
LC ₅	0.234 ±0.016	(+) 14.2	194.67 ±2.451	(+) 7.4	0.209 ±0.064	(+) 2.0	177.24 ±2.883	(-) 2.2
F1) LC ₅ (0.226 ±0.027	(+) 10.2	188.54 ±3.621	(+) 4.1	0.216 ±0.027	(+) 5.4	184.12 ±6.455	(+) 1.6

Each value represents the mean of three replicates ± S.E (+)=Increase, (-)=Decrease, S.E = Standard Error at P < 0.05
* = Significant

4. Histopathological examination:

The digestive system in insects consists of three parts, foregut (stomodaeum), midgut (mesenteron) and hindgut (proctodaeum). Midgut is the important part which produces digestive enzymes and, absorbs the digested food (Terra and Ferreira, 1994). In lepidopteran insects the midgut is composed of 3 major laminations: peritrophic membrane, mucosa, and musculature. The peritrophic membrane is chitinous forms and envelops the food particles, along the midgut. The mucosa is consisting of midgut epithelium and stem cells embodied by group closely packed, spherical nuclei with thin chromatin surrounded by a thin layer of clear cytoplasm. The epithelial cells are responsible for absorption and secretion of enzymes (columnar cells), ion homeostasis (goblet cells), and the epithelia (regenerative or stem cells). The columnar and goblet cells have a brush border of microvilli in outside and spherical vesicular nucleus with a large vacuole at its distal end, or they have a larger oval-shaped nucleus in the middle of the cell and a smaller vacuole above the nucleus (Chi *et al.*, 1975 and Schünemann *et al.*, 2014).

The photomicrograph of transverse section in midgut of untreated *S.littoralis* larvae revealed that the gut wall has normal muscular tissues, epithelial cells (regenerative, goblet and columnar cells), brush border membrane and peritrophic membrane (Figure, 1). Treatment of larvae with LC₇₀ of Dipel 2X produced serious effects on midgut tissues as the epithelial cells of the midgut appear to be swollen (hyperplasia is increase in the number of cells and mass of tissue) and ruptured, rupture of the brush border microvilli, appearance of apoptotic bodies, activation of midgut stem cells, contraction the muscle layer, extensive fragmentation and separation of mucosal epithelium from the basement membrane and the lumen was filled with debris of disrupted cells. LC₅₀ of Dipel 2X caused disarrangement and degeneration of the

columnar cells, appearance of apoptotic bodies, enlargement of vacuoles, contraction of the circular muscle bands, rupture of the brush border microvilli and the lumen was filled with debris of disrupted cells. LC₂₅ treatment of Dipel 2X induces epithelial lifting, appearance of apoptotic bodies, rupture of the brush border microvilli, vacuoles formation and the lumen was filled with debris of disrupted cells. Treatment of F1 larvae with LC₅ of Bt increased vacuole numbers, swelling, and disarrangement of epithelial cells and rupture of the brush border microvilli (Figure, 2). LC₇₀ treatment of Littovir caused hyperplasia and destruction of the midgut epithelium, appearance of apoptotic bodies, rupture of the brush border microvilli and vacuoles formation. LC₅₀ of Littovir showing increase in number of stem cells, degeneration of most columnar cells, appearance of apoptotic bodies and rupture of the brush border microvilli. LC₂₅ of Littovir shown hyperplasia of cells lining mid gut and cytoplasmic vacuolization. Mid gut of treated F1 larvae with LC₅ of Littovir produced cytoplasmic vacuolization (Figure, 3).

The histopathological effects of Bt and virus on midgut tissues of treated insect larvae were investigated by other researchers. Galluzzi *et al.* (2012) investigated that some cell death phenomenon as apoptosis is a mechanism included in cell death program conferring to pathogenic infection, firstly this cells activate enzymes whereas key proteins are cleaved by cysteine proteases, known as caspases, that degrade the cells own nuclear DNA and cytoplasmic proteins, break up into fragments, called apoptotic bodies and contained portions of the cytoplasm and nucleus. The dead cell and its fragments are rapidly gobbled. Dougherty *et al.* (2006) mentioned that the midgut epithelial cells showed signs of apoptosis manifested as shrinkage of the cells and the presence of condensed chromatin with some vacuolization. This process is considered as the proper mechanism of cells against

pathogens and toxic compounds (Sakr, 2007). Escriche *et al.* (1988) stated that *Bt.* crystal proteins Cry1Ca, induce pore formation in midgut cell membranes of *S. littoralis*, made brush border membrane vesicles permeable to KCl (osmotic swelling) but Cry1Aa, Cry1Ab, and Cry1Ac did not. Rouis *et al.* (2007) recorded the histopathological changes in midgut of olive pest insect, *Prays oleae* (Bernard) (Lepidoptera: Praydidae), larvae by *Bt.*, included vacuolization of the cytoplasm, hypertrophy of the epithelial cells and nucleus, brush border membrane impairment, disintegration of vesicle formation in the apical region of cells toward the midgut lumen, and leakage of cytoplasm material in the lumen proved that proteolytic processing of cry toxins is responsible for activation, and in insect resistance. Physiological hyperplasia can cause by hormones induce increases in the functional capacity of a tissue when needed, or compensatory hyperplasia, induce increases tissue mass after damage (Sanderson *et al.*, 2017). Cry34Ab1 and cry35Ab1 are proteins derived from *B. thuringiensis* together comprise a binary insecticidal toxin with

specific activity against the western corn rootworm, *Diabrotica virgifera virgifera* (LeConte) (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae). Clear symptoms of intoxication were observed for proteins tested, including swelling and sloughing of enterocytes, constriction of midgut circular muscles, stem cell activation, and obstruction of the midgut lumen (Bowling *et al.*, 2017). Sanjaya *et al.* (2010) reported the histological change in *S. litura* exposed to SINPV at serial concentrations was peritrophic membrane eternally affected by the longer time of immobilisation of the virion. Pachiappan *et al.* (2018) found that mulberry Leaf webber, *Diaphania pulverulentalis* (Hampson) (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) infected with NPV showed virus virions scattered throughout the granular virogenic stroma and accumulated peripherally.

Results of this study concluded that the Na⁺/K⁺ ATPase and Protease played an important role in toxicity of *Bacillus thuringiensis* subsp. *Kurstaki* and Nuclear Polyhedrosis Virus (SpliNPV) and tolerance of *S littoralis* larvae to their effects.

Figure (1): Photomicrography of transverse section in midgut of untreated *Spodoptera littoralis* larvae (stained with Hematoxylin and Eosin, H + E 200X). B:Basement membrane, C:Columnar, G:goblet cells, M:Muscular tissue, P: peritrophic membrane, R:Regenerative cells, and V:Microvilli.

LC₇₀ of Bt 400X

LC₅₀ of Bt 400X

LC₂₅ of Bt 200X

LC₅ of Bt (F1) 400X

Figure (2): Photomicrography of of partial transverse section in midgut of treated *Spodoptera littoralis* larvae with Dipel 2X (stained with Hematoxylin and Eosin, H + E). Ab: Apoptotic bodies, B: Basement membrane, C:Columnar, G: goblet cells, P:Peritrophic membrane R:Regenerative cells, V:Microvilli and Vc:Vacuole.

LC₇₀ of V 400X

LC₅₀ of V 400X

LC₂₅ of V 400X

LC₅ of V (F1) 400X

Figure (3): Photomicrography of partial transverse section in midgut of treated *Spodoptera littoralis* larvae with Littovir (stained with Hematoxylin and Eosin, H + E). B:Basement membrane, C:Columnar, G: goblet cells, P:Peritrophic membrane, R:Regenerative cells, V:Microvilli, and Vc:Vacuole.

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Isolation of entomopathogenic fungi and efficacy as a biological control agent on red spider mite *Tetranychus urticae* (Acari: Tetranychidae)

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Abstract:

Entomopathogenic fungi and non entomopathogens were isolated from Egyptian soil using two isolation methods, from soil by *Galleria* bait method and insect. The sample were identified using the conventional methods. The virulence of four entomopathogenic fungi isolates were tested on red spider mites *Tetranychus urticae* (Koch) (Acari: Tetranychidae), *Beauveria bassiana* (B1 and B2) and *Metarhizium anisopliae* (M1 and M2). Results proved that (B2) was more effective against adult compared with all other isolates. When studying the toxicity of fungal metabolites the results showed that, highest effective toxin was of the M1, followed by B2, M2 then B1, the mortality percentages at seventh day in concentration 100% of crude were 85.13, 76.12, 73.8 and 61.97 for M1, B2, M2 and B1, respectively.

Introduction

Tetranychus urticae (Koch) (Acari: Tetranychidae) attacks a wide range of plants, which often cause severe damage to a variety of crops, it frequently occurs in glasshouse and outdoor crops (Gotoh *et al.*, 2004). It is one of the most serious pests responsible for yield losses of many horticultural, ornamental and agronomic crops, causing considerable crop damage and economic loss (Puinean *et al.*, 2010). This pest is commonly controlled by pesticides. However, resistance to pesticides has guided research to find new methods intended to control *Tetranychus* sp. Additionally, the indiscriminate use of different synthetic acaricides to avoid serious health hazards for mammals. There is an essential and urgent need to develop new

acaricides which can be termed green pesticides or new combinations of allelochemicals to gain effective control of this pest.

Biological control agents such as entomopathogenic fungi can be used as a component of integrated pest management. Entomopathogenic fungi can be isolated from the soil (Korosi *et al.*, 2019). Under natural conditions, fungal pathogens are frequent and often cause natural mortalities to the insect populations. Many fungal species such as *Metarhizium anisopliae*, *Lecanicillium lecanii*, *Isaria fumosoroseus* and *Beauveria bassiana* are used as biocontrol agents for controlling various insect pests including termites, black vine weevil, whiteflies,

aphids, corn borers, colons and other insects (Ravensberg, 2011). Various researchers in different parts of the world conducted bioassays on different crops and found one or two isolates of entomopathogenic fungi (EPF) to be highly effective against mites like *Paecilomyces fumosoroseus*, *M. anisopliae* and *B. bassiana* etc. (Draganova and Simova, 2010).

Most published reports reveal that multiple toxic substances were derived from entomopathogenic fungi, which is an attractive approach for identifying important bioactive compounds from EPF. Based on this approach, few studies on EPF have been directed at elucidating the relevant virulence factors of insecticidal metabolites, antifeedants. EPF produce secondary metabolites that disable several immune mechanisms allowing the fungus to overcome and then kill its host. This characteristic makes *B. bassiana* and *M. anisopliae* promising model for biological control of insect pests (Zibae *et al.*, 2011). The insecticidal activities of secondary metabolites against many pests have been described in several reports (Ríos-Moreno *et al.*, 2017). The traditional bait insect is the highly susceptible larvae of the wax moth, *Galleria mellonella* (L.) (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) but also mealworm larvae, *Tenebrio molitor* L. (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae), are suitable. Baiting soil samples with larvae of *G. mellonella* is a widely applied tool to screen for indigenous species of entomopathogenic fungi (Meyling and Eilenberg, 2006). Keller *et al.* (2003) showed that galleria bait method was sensitive than traditional plating on media and was therefore useful for isolation and identification of the entomopathogenic fungi indigenously present in soils. The aim of the present work is to study the isolation entomopathogenic fungi and its effect against the red spider mite *T. urticae*

Materials and methods

1. Isolation of fungi:

1.1. From soil by *Galleria* bait method:

The soil samples were collected from random locations under different crops (Table, 1). About 5 cm depth were removed first in the site of collected soil, then the sample was collected from the next 10 cm depth into clean sterile bags and brought back to the laboratory. Three samples at least were taken randomly from each locality. Samples from each place were mixed to make homogeneity and coarse debris removed (Ali-Shtayeh *et al.*, 2002). Avoid sample drying or exposure to high temperatures during the mixing process.

Galleria mellonella L., greater wax moth was reared in Bio-Insecticides Production Unit, Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Giza, Egypt. Each five larvae of *G. mellonella* were placed into a small plastic box filled with soil. The boxes were shaken and incubated at (27±1°C). The larvae were examined on days 3, 4, 5, 7, until 14 days. The surface of dead larvae was sterilized by alcohol (70%) for 10 sec. and then rinsed with sterile distilled water then the larvae were placed in Petri dishes on moistened filter paper to germination of fungal spores on the cuticle of the insect. The Petri dishes were covered with parafilm to maintain suitable relative humidity and incubated in darkness at 70 ± 5 % relative humidity (R.H.) and 27 ± 1°C. Larvae were observed until mycelium appeared. Infected larvae placed into plates of Czapeck's Dox's agar medium. The fungi were identified using traditional procedures, morphological characteristics with the help relevant taxonomic literature.

1.2. from insect:

Desert locust *Schistocerca gregaria* Forskål (Orthoptera: Acrididae) cadaver was coated with fungal spores. It was taken and purified as follow:

Infected cadavers of larvae placed into Czapeck's Dox's agar medium (NouriAin *et al.*, 2014). The isolates were incubated at 27± 1°C for 8–14 days. The

plates were daily examined for up 14 days or more, the differently looking fungal colonies developed on each plate. After fungal hyphae emergence and spores, they were sub cultured by placed into a new Dox's agar medium and incubated at $27^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 1$. The pure developed fungal colonies were identified to the species level These fungi identified by using the conventional methods (Sahar and Moharram , 2014). The identification was done at the Plant Pathology Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Giza, Egypt. The identification of entomopathogenic fungi was made with the help of the following universally accepted keys for identification of different isolated fungi (Domsh *et al.*, 1980; Nelson *et al.*, 1983 and Barnett and Hunter, 1987).

3. Virulence test on *Tetranychus urticae* :

3.1. Rearing of mites:

The original colony of the red spider mites *T. urticae* in this study was supplied from Acarology Laboratory in Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center at Dokki, Egypt. *T. urticae* was reared for several generations at $25 \pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ away from any pesticide contamination. *T. urticae* was maintained on detached mulberry leaves with the lower surface upwards placed on moist cotton wool pads in fiber-dishes (20cm in diameter). The cotton pads were moistened daily to prevent mite escape and to avoid dryness leaves of mulberry were replaced by fresh one when necessary (Hassan, 2018).

3.2. Bioassay by conidiospores:

Entomopathogenic fungi conidiospores (aerobic spores produced asexually by a fungus) were harvested by distilled water mixed with 0.05. % Tween 80 to obtain the stock spore suspension. The suspension was vortexed well and then filtered through cheesecloth to reduce mycelium clumping. Heamocytometer (Neubauer improved HBG, Germany) was used to counted the spores in the suspension (Lozano-Tovar *et al.*, 2013). Three

concentrations of each isolate were prepared: 1×10^6 , 1×10^7 , and 1×10^8 spores/ml. Twenty adult mites were placed on a single leaf-disk of mulberry (2.5 cm in diameter) and kept on moist cotton wool in fiber-dishes with cotton around each disk in a circle way to prevent mite escaping. Each dish contained five replicate (disks). The direct spray technique was applied by a glass atomizer at 30cm away from the treated surface with 1ml spore suspension for each treatment and 1ml sterilized distilled water of 0.05% Tween 80 as a control (Abo-Shabana, 1980 and Hassan, 2018). The treated adult was incubated at $27 \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$. Mortality was assessed daily. The mortality percentage corrected by Abbott's formula (1925) .

3.3. Production of fungal metabolites:

One ml of spores suspensions contented of 1×10^7 spore/ ml from Entomopathogenic fungi isolates were prepared then poured into flask with 100 mL Czapek-Dox broth medium , and incubated for 21 days at 240 r/min and $27\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$. Each isolate was replicated 4 times. Each flask was filtered twice time through Whatman 1 filter paper to remove the spores and mycelia (El Basyouni and Vining ,1966; Kershaw *et al.*, 1999; Hsiao and Ko, 2001 and Hu *et al.*, 2006 and Ting-yan *et al.*, 2016).

3.4. Toxicity of fungal metabolites :

Four concentrations of each fungal metabolites were prepared as follow: (100%) metabolites as it is, (75%) were added 3 parts of metabolites to 1part of distal water, (50 %) were added 2 parts of metabolites to 2 parts of distal water and (25%) were added 1 part of metabolites to 3 parts of distal water, each treatment had five replicates. Sterilized distilled water were a control to each concentration. Mortality was assessed daily. The percentage of mortality was determined and corrected by Abbott's formula (1925).

4. Statistical analysis:

LC_{50} , LC_{90} and slope values were calculated according to Finney (1971), using "Ldp Line" software (Bakr, 2000). All

experiments contained. 3-5 replicates and data were analyzed by one – way analysis of variance (ANOVA) using SPSS 17.0 statistical software. When the ANOVA

statistics were significant (P <0.05), means were compared by the Duncan’s multiple range test.

Table (1): Location of soil samples.

Governorate	Location	Crop
Giza	Malaut	Okra, rocca and corn.
Qilyubia	Qaha	Orang, corn and strawberries
Bani-Sweif	Bani-Sweif	Taro and banana
Kafr EL Sheikh	Desouq	Banana

Results and discussion

The study revealed the presence of entomopathogenic and non entomopathogenic fungi isolates. Four isolates of entomopathogenic fungi *i.e.*, two isolates of *B.bassiana* (B1 and B2) and

another two isolates of *M. anisopliae* (M1 and M2) were isolated, 3 isolates from soil at random location and one from insect. Data given in Table (2) showed entomopathogenic isolates and non-entomopathogenic fungi isolates.

Table (2): The fungal isolates

Isolate	From	Crops	Location	Pathogenicity*
<i>Paecilomyces lilacinus</i> (Thom) Samson <i>Aspergillus flavus va columnaris</i> Raper <i>Aspergillus tamarii</i> Kita <i>Fusarium semitectum</i> Berkeley	Soil	Orang	Qilyubia	NP PP PP PP
<i>Gladiolium roseum</i> Bainier. <i>Mucor hiemalis</i> Wehmer	Soil	Strawberries	Qilyubia	PP, NP and FP PP
<i>Beauveria bassiana</i> (Balsamo) Vuillemin	Soil	Vegetable crops	Giza	EP
<i>Cunninghamella echinulata</i> (Thaxter) <i>Aspergillus tamari</i>	Soil	Taro	Bani-Sweif	SF PP
<i>Beauveria bassiana</i> <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> Schlechtendal	Soil	Banana	Kafr ELSheikh	EP PP
<i>Metarhizium anisopliae</i> (Metschnikow) Sorokin <i>Fusarium semitectum</i>	Soil	Watercress plant	Giza	EP PP
<i>Metarhizium anisopliae</i>	Insect (Desert locust)	Alfalfa	Baharyia Oasis	EP

Pathogenicity* = (NP) Nematode Pathogen; (PP) Plant Pathogen; (EP) Entomo pathogen;(SF) Saprophytic Fungi or (FP) Fungi Pathogen.

B. bassiana and *M. anisopliae* are a common entomopathogenic fungi in soil. Several studies in Egypt demonstrated isolation of entomopathogenic fungi (Nada, 1999 ; Sahar and Moharram, 2014; Hussein, 2015 and Lokma, 2016).

1.Virulence of entomopathogenic isolates:

The efficiency of four entomopathogenic isolates, two isolates of *B. bassiana* (B1 and B2) and two isolates of *M. anisopliae* (M1 and M2), against adult *T. urticae* in laboratory experiments. Total mortality percentage values after exposing to series of concentrations of 1×10^6 , 1×10^7 and 1×10^8 spores/ml were shown for seven days after

treatment in Table (3). While the highest concentration of 1×10^8 spores/ml revealed 39.2, 78.65, 21.15 and 43.8 % for B1, B2, M1 and M2, respectively after the same consecutive days. LC_{50} and LC_{90} values were tabulated with their corresponding slopes after treatment in The LC_{50} for B1, B2, M1, and M2 were 4.90×10^8 , 2.86×10^7 , 2.75×10^9 , and 4.58×10^8 spores/ml, respectively. Results proved that (B2) was more effective against adult compared with all other isolates (Table, 3).

One way ANOVA statistical analysis indicated that significant levels of effect between fungal isolates B1, B2, M1 and M2,

Table (3): virulence of entomopathogenic fungi isolates on *Tetranychus urticae* after seven days post treatment.

Isolate	Total mortality%	LC_{50}	Slope	LC_{90}	Index	Mean \pm SE
B1	39.2	4.90×10^8	0.768	2.28×10^{10}	5.835	$38.49 \pm 1.1b$
B2	78.65	2.86×10^7	0.565	5.33×10^9	100	$78.54 \pm 0.95a$
M1	21.15	2.75×10^9	0.724	1.62×10^{11}	1.038	$21.27 \pm 0.37c$
M2	43.8	4.58×10^8	0.357	1.77×10^{12}	6.245	$42.44 \pm 1.6b$

B1, B2 = *Beauveria bassiana* M1, M2= *Metarhizium anisopliae*

Figure (1): Comparison LT_{50} between four entomopathogenic isolates against adult *Tetranychus urticae*.

Virulence of entomopathogenic isolates against spider mites. In the light of the results obtained during the present experimental work, it was clear that entomopathogenic fungi; *B. bassiana* (B1, B2) and *M. anisopliae* (M1, M2) were pathogenic to adult *T. urticae*. Pathogenicity of fungus increased with the increase of concentration and time. Death results due to a severe damage in the tissues., toxicosis, cell dehydration, loss of nutrient intake, and finally the hyphae emerge from the insect body sporulates and starts a new infection cycle (Perez *et al.*, 2014). The results compatible with Various researchers in different parts of the world conducted bioassays on different crops and found one or two isolates of entomopathogenic fungi (EPF) to be highly effective against mites like *M. anisopliae*, *B. bassiana* and *Paecilomyces fumosoroseus*, etc. (Nugroho and Ibrahim, 2004 and Draganova and Simova, 2010). These findings in agreement with Chandler *et al.* (2000) they studied pathogenicity a commercial isolate of

entomopathogenic fungi *B. bassiana* (Naturalis - L) against *T. urticae* on tomato leaflets under laboratory conditions and glasshouse experiments. they found that (Naturalis – L) was high pathogenic against *T. urticae*. Also, Hassan *et al.*, 2017 tested two *M. anisopliae* and four *B. bassiana* isolates for virulence against *T. urticae*, egg and adult stages. B4 isolate was found to be the most potent, causing 88.5% mortality for adult stage at a concentration 10^8 spores/ml. The LC_{50} was 6.61×10^6 .

2.Toxicity of fungal metabolites:

The comparison percentage mortality values after exposing to series concentrations of four metabolites extracts at 100%, 75%, 50% and 25% crude/ml were shown in Table (4). Results obtained revealed that the four tested metabolic crudes were toxic to *T. urticae*. The highest effective toxin was of M1, followed by B2, M2 then B1 . The mortality percentages at seventh day and in concentration 100% of crude were 85.13, 76.12, 73.8 and 61.97% for M1, B2, M2 and B1, respectively.

Table (4): Percentage total mortality of adult *Tetranychus urticae* treated with four concentrations of *Beauveria bassiana* and *Metarhizium anisopliae* crudes after seven days.

Concentration	Mortality%			
	<i>Beauveria bassiana</i> B1	<i>Beauveria bassiana</i> B2	<i>Metarhizium anisopliae</i> M1	<i>Metarhizium anisopliae</i> M2
25%	24.39	34.48	56.45	58.33
50%	37.17	38.33	63.38	65.85
75%	40.54	63.15	77.02	71.57
100%	61.97	76.12	85.13	73.8

B1 and B2 = M1 and M2=

Results in Table (5) proved that (M1) crude was more effective against adult compared with all other isolates. The LC_{50} value of M1 was 45.67 crude/ml while M2, B2 and B1 revealed greater LC_{50} value, 50.92, 62.47 and 101.65 crude/ml, respectively. Generally, the highest values of mortality were in the M1 treatment. One way

ANOVA statistical analysis indicated that were significant levels of effect ($F_{3,16}=3.19^*$; $P \leq 0.05$) between different fungal crude M1, M2, B1 and B2 on adult *T. urticae* were presented in Table (5). Means of mortalities were 84.4, 74.09, 69.08 and 59.71 % for M1, M2, B1 and B2, respectively. Data indicated M1 was more effective. Figure (2) illustrated

mortality percentages of different curds at within intervals times seven days at 100%

crudes/ml. It proves M1 crude was most effective toxin against *T. urticae*.

Table (5): Comparison between four metabolic crude of *Beauveria bassiana* (B1, B2) and *Metarhizium anisopliae* (M1,M2), *Tetranychus urticae* adult stage according to LC₅₀ and means of mortality ±SE.

Crude	LC ₅₀	Lower limit	Upper limit	Slope	LC ₉₀	Index	Mean±SE
B1	101.65	81.94	149.55	1.95	461.67	44.93	59.71±5.36c
B2	62.47	52.69	74.89	2.22	235.77	73.10	69.08±8.41cb
M1	45.67	35.51	54.89	1.91	214.03	100.00	84.4±5.11b
M2	50.92	30.87	71.60	1.00	970.65	89.69	74.09±2.42cb

Index compared with M1* significant at level (P≤0.05). b and c Mean within the same row having different superscripts significantly different (P≤0.05).

Figure (2): Mortality percentages of adult *Tetranychus urticae* after treated with 100% concentrate of metabolites from four fungal isolates.

Entomopathogenic fungi secrete secondary metabolites which toxic to insect. Destruxins are insecticidal metabolites of a fungus, *M. anisopliae*. These metabolites are usually secreted into the culture medium during growth. The structure of destruxins is classified as being a cyclic hexadepsipeptide. More than 35 different destruxins have been characterized with a wide range of insecticidal activities (Kershaw *et al.*, 1999 and Liu *et al.*, 2004). In the present investigation, the aim was to provide data for enhancement of entomofungal virulence and production of toxic macromolecular insecticidal substance from native entomopathogenic isolates. The present study showed that four native Isolates *B. bassiana*

and *M. anisopliae* (B1 and B2 M1 and M2) and its metabolites had toxic effects on *T. urticae* adult, may be due to variations of the composition of the chemical composition of crude. These agree with previous studies carried out by Gaber (2016) who Compared the effect of two extracts (destruxins) from two isolates *M. anisopliae* (Ma1 and Ma2) achieved toxicity against both *T. cucurbitacearum* adult females and deutonymphs three days post treatment. The LC₅₀ values of destruxins from isolate (Ma1) were 2.26 and 3.26 gm./100ml against deutonymphs and adult females, respectively. LC₅₀ of destruxins from isolate (Ma2) were 2.35 and 3.98 gm./100ml against deutonymphs and adult females, respectively.

Also, agree with Fan *et al.* (2013) they study reviled toxicity effect secondary metabolites of *B. brongniartii* against *Dendrolimus tabulaeformis*. The mortality rate of the larvae in the bioassay positively changed with the concentration of the fungal secondary metabolites. In the groups treated with fungal secondary metabolites at three concentrations, 5.5, 55, and 550 µg /mL, the larval mortalities were $29.33 \pm 3.2\%$, $46.00 \pm 1.47\%$, and $71.33 \pm 3.07\%$, respectively. The differences were significant between the groups.

In comparison toxicity of crudes with the conidial infection, it was found that the fungal metabolites were more effective in killing the mite than infection with the conidia. That may be due to conidial infection required more time to complete the series of infection processes, including conidial attachment on the host cuticle, germination, hyphal penetration through the integument, and infection of the internal tissues and organs, whereas the secondary metabolite was more direct attack. Hence, fungal secondary metabolites should be considered for pest management programs in the future. These results in the line with Fan *et al.* (2013) and Zibae *et al.* (2011), they suggested that the secondary metabolites produced by *B. bassiana* caused problem in several defense mechanisms of *Eurygaster integriceps*, thus helping the fungus to destroy its host. These results agree with those obtained by Lozano-Tovar *et al.* (2015), they investigated the insecticidal activity of the crude extract obtained of *M. brunneum* (Petch EAMb 09/01- Su) strain and its ability to secrete secondary metabolites including destruxins (dtx). Dtx A and A2 were toxic against *Ceratitis capitata* (Wiedemann). The crude extract of seven *Metarhizium* and one *Beauveria* isolates were evaluated against medfly adults. The isolate crude extracts. (EAMb 09/01-Su) resulted in mortality ranging between 95 and 100% at 48 h.

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Survey of pests and their associated natural enemies occurred on cucumber plants (*Cucumis sativus*)

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Abstract :

A survey was carried out to investigate different types of insects, mites and associated natural enemies found on three hybrids of cucumber (Hayal, ashrak, and bahi) at Qaha area, Qalubiya Governorate, during two successive seasons, 2015 and 2016. The results revealed 28 insect and mite species belonging to 25 families within 9 orders. Among the recorded pest species, six species namely, *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae), *Aphis gossypii* Glover (Hemiptera: Aphididae), *Thrips tabaci* Lindeman (Thysanoptera: Thripidae), *Liriomyza bryoniae* (Kaitenbach) (Diptera: Agromyzidae), *Dacus ciliatus* (Loew) (Diptera: Tephritidae) and *Tetranychus urticae* Koch (Acari: Tetranychidae) are of highly economic importance. While the rest were of no economic importance based on population. It was found also that, cucumber plants in the surveyed area were inhabited with five natural enemies, that were: *Hippodamia (Adonia) variegata* (Goeze) (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae), *Polistes gallica* L., *Vespa orientalis* (L.) (Hymenoptera: Vespidae), *Brachymeria aegyptiaca* Masi (Hymenoptera: Chalcididae) and *Euseius scutalis* (Athias-Henriot) (Acari: Phytoseiidae).

Introduction

Cucumber (*Cucumis sativus* L.) is one of the most important vegetable crops grown in Egypt and cultivated in both the open fields and greenhouses. Cucumber plant is one of the annual plants in the Cucurbitaceous family that has been cultivated by man for over 3,000 years (Adetula and Denton, 2003 and Okonmah, 2011). The cultivated area recently increased, especially for exportation. The production of cucumber was 11750 tons from the cultivated areas of about 1726 feddans (Abdallah *et al.*, 2019).

Cucumber plants are a subject for infestation by many pests that reduce the productivity and quality. Some of these pests

are known to be of great economic importance and causes many direct and indirect damages (transmitting several viral and fungal pathogens) such as, the whitefly, *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae), the aphid, *Aphis gossypii* Glover (Hemiptera: Aphididae), *Thrips tabaci* Lindeman (Thysanoptera: Thripidae), *Liriomyza bryoniae* (Kaitenbach) (Diptera: Agromyzidae) and in addition to the two spotted spider mite, *Tetranychus urticae* Koch (Acari: Tetranychidae) (Abdel-Rahman *et al.*, 2016 ; Adly, 2016; Chaven *et al.*, 2015; Hassan *et al.* , 2008; Ibrahim *et al.* , 2017; Saleh *et al.*, 2017 and Shaheen *et al.*, 1973).

The present work was undertaken to survey the pests and associated natural enemies occurred on some hybrids of the cucumber plants to assist in their control.

Materials and methods

A survey of insects, mites and associated natural enemies found on three cucumber hybrids (Hayel, ashrak and bahi) was conducted during two successive seasons (2015 and 2016) at the experimental farm of the Plant Protection Research Station at Qaha, Qalubiya Governorate. An area of about quarter Fadden (1050 m²), planted with the three hybrids of cucumber (each hybrid of 2 Kirats) was chosen for the survey. The survey was conducted using the sweeping net (25 double stokes were taken across the two diagonals) and counting on leaves (15 leaves picked at random before sun rise), at weekly intervals. The survey started on 5th of August till 18th of November in the two seasons. All the recommended agricultural practices were conducted, and no chemical insecticides were applied throughout the two growing seasons.

The collected insects were killed in cyanide Jars in the field, transferred to the laboratory in paper bags, then sorted, counted and preserved in vials containing 70% ethanol. The materials were identified in the Taxonomy Department of the Plant Protection Research Institute. The obtained insects and mites were classified according to its numbers as follows:

- a. Rare (from 0.0 to 2 individuals).
- b. Few (from 3.0 to 5 individuals).
- c. Moderate (from 5 to 10 individuals).
- d. Abundant (more than 10 individuals).

The data obtained were arranged in a Table (1) including the order, family, scientific name, together with the economic status, the stage, the abundance degree, the part of infested plant and the period of occurrence.

Results and discussion

Survey of insects, mites and their natural enemies associated with cucumber plant was conducted at the experimental farm

of the Plant Protection Research Station at Qaha, Qalubiya Governorate, during the Nile season of two consecutive years of 2015 and 2016. The survey revealed the presence of 28 insect and mite species belonging to 25 families and 9 orders. Of these only 6 species were most abundant and considered as the major pests of cucumber, these are: the cotton and tomato white fly, *B. tabaci*, the cotton aphid, *A. gossypii*, the cotton and onion thrips, *T. tabaci*, the clover leaf fly, *L. bryoniae*, the cucurbitaceous fly, *Dacus ciliatus* (Loew) (Diptera: Tephritidae), and the two spotted spider mite, *T. urticae*. The rest were of minor importance, based on population density per plant, nature and extent of damage (Table,1).

Among the minor species, the seed eating bugs, *Graptostethus servus* (F.) (Hemiptera: Lygaeidae), the green bug, *Nezara viridula* Mill. (Homoptera: Pentatomidae), the cotton cicadell, *Empoasca lypica* De Berg Gean (Homoptera: Cicadellidae), the cotton mealybug, *Phenacoccus solenopsis* Tin. (Homoptera: Pseudococcidae), the spiny boll worm, *Earias insulana* (Boisd.), the greater cotton leafworm, *Spodoptera littoralis* (B.) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae), Mallow bind weed butterfly, *Danaus chrysippus chrysippus* L., *Gegenesn ostromus* Fab. (Lepidoptera: Nymphalidae), the cabbage butterfly, *Artogeia paeleucosoma* (Schawerda) (Lepidoptera: Pieridae), *Hetera crisannuslosa* Walker (Orthoptera: Acrididae) the African stick grasshopper, *Pyrgomorph congota* Krauss (Orthoptera: Pyrgomorphidae). The surveyed and recorded predators during the study were: The predaceous mite, *Euseiuss cutalis* (A.-H.) (Acari: Phytoseiidae), Adonis ladybird, *Hippodamia (Adonia) variegata* (Goeze) (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae), the paper wasp, *Polistes gallica* L., the oriental hornet, *Vespa orientalis* F. (Hymenoptera: Vespidae). They were found to be of moderate populations. The parasitoid *Brachymeria aegyptiaca* Masi (Hymenoptera: Chalcididae) was found to be rare (Table, 1).

Table (1): Checklist of insects, mites, predators and visitors surveyed from cucumber plants, *Cucumis sativus* in Qaha, Qalubiya during 2015 and 2016 seasons.

Taxonomic position		Common name	Scientific name	Economic status	Stage	Frequency	Part of infested plant	Period of occurrence	
Order	Family								
(A) Insects									
Coleoptera	Coccinellidae	Adonis ladybird	<i>Hippodamia (Adonia) variegata</i> (Goeze)	Predator	Adult and nymph	Rare	Aphid	October and November	
Diptera	Agromyzidae	Clover leaf fly	<i>Liriomyza bryoniae</i> (Kaitenbach)	Pest	Larvae and adult	Abundant	Leaves	August and November	
	Chloropidae		<i>Eutropha triangularis</i> Becker	Visitor	Adult	Rare	Leaves	October	
	Muscidae	Hunter fly	<i>Coenosia attenuate</i> Stein	Visitor	Adult	Few	Leaves	October	
				<i>Helina confiformis</i> (Stein)	Pest	Adult	Rare	Flower	October and November
			Lesser house fly	<i>Fannia conicularis</i> (L.)	Visitor	Adult	Rare	Any part of plant	October
			Eyes fly	<i>Morellia albina</i> Wied.	Visitor	Adult	Rare	Leaves	October
		Phoridae	Laboratory fly	<i>Megaselia scalaris</i> (Loew)	Visitor	Adult	Rare	Fruits	October
	Tephritidae	Cucurbitaceous fly	<i>Dacus ciliatus</i> (Loew)	Pest	Adult and larvae	Moderate	Fruits	September and November	
Hemiptera	Aleyrodidae	Cotton and Tomato white fly	<i>Bemisia tabaci</i> (G.)	Pest	Eggs, Nymph and adults	Abundant	Leaves	August and November	
	Aphididae	Cotton aphid	<i>Aphis gossypii</i> Glover	Pest	Nymph and adults	Abundant	Leaves stems flower fruit	August and November	
	Cicadellidae	Cotton cicadell	<i>Empoasca lypica</i> De Berg Gean	Pest	Nymphs and Adults	Moderate	Leaves	September and November	
	Lygaeidae	Seed eating bugs	<i>Graptostethus servus</i> (F.)	Pest	Adult	Rare	Seeds	October	
	Pentatomidae	Green bug	<i>Nezara vridula</i> Mill.	Pest	Nymphs and Adults	Rare	All plant parts	September	
		Pseudococcidae	Cotton mealybug	<i>Phenacoccus solenopsis</i> Tin.	Pest	Nymphs and adults	Moderate	Leaves Flower stem	August and November
Hymenoptera	Andrenidae	Solitarybee	<i>Andrena biskrensis</i>	Visitor (Pollinator)	Adults	Few	Flowers	September	

Table (1): Cont.

Taxonomic position		Common name	Scientific name	Economic status	Stage	Frequency	Part of infested plant	Period of occurrence
Order	Family							
(A) Insects								
	Apidae	Western honeybee	<i>Apis mellifera</i> L.	Visitor (Pollinator)	Adults	Few	Flowers	September
			<i>Lasioglossum (Ctenonomia) vagans</i> (Smith, 1857)	Pollinator	Adults	Few	Flowers	October
	Chalcididae		<i>Brachymeria aegyptiaca</i> Masi	Parasitoid	Adults	Rare	Pupa of <i>Euploca core</i>	October
	Formicidae	Ants	<i>Tapinoma erraticum</i> Latr.	Scavengers	Nymphs and adults	Moderate	Leaves	September and November
	Ichnemonidae	Parasitoid wasp	<i>Diadegma aranginator</i>	Parasitoid	Adults	Few	Flowers	October
	Vespidae	Paper wasp	<i>Polistes gallica</i> L.	Predator	Adults	Few	Insects	August
		Oriental hornet	<i>Vespa orientalis</i> F.	Predator	Adults	Few	Insects	August and October
Lepidoptera	Noctuidae	Spiny boll worm	<i>Earias insulana</i> (Boisd)	Pest	Larvae	Rare	Fruit	September
		Greater cotton leafworm	<i>Spodoptera littoralis</i> (B.)	Pest	Larvae	Few	Many parts of plant	August
	Nymphalidae	Mallow bind weed butterfly	<i>Danaus chrysippus chrysippus</i> L.	Pest	Larvae	Few	Leaves	October and November
			<i>Gegenes ostromus</i> Fab.	Pest	Adults	Rare	Leaves	October and November
	Pieridae	Cabbage Butterfly	<i>Artogeia rapae leucosoma</i> (Schawerda)	Pest	Adults	Few	Leaves	August
Orthoptera	Acrididae		<i>Heteracris annuslosa</i> Walker	Pest	Adults	Rare	Leaves	October and November
	Pyrgomorphidae	African stick grasshopper	<i>Pyrgomorph congata</i> Krauss	Pest	Adults	Rare	Leaves	October and November
Thysanoptera	Thripidae	Cotton and onion thrips	<i>Thrips tabaci</i> Lind.	Pest	Nymphs and adults	Moderate	Leaves stems	August and November

Table (1): Cont.

Taxonomic position		Common name	Scientific name	Economic status	Stage	Frequency	Part of infested plant	Period of occurrence
Order	Family							
(B) Mites								
Acarina	Phytoseiidae		<i>Euseius scutalis</i> (A. H.)	Predator	Nymph and adults	Moderate	Phytophagous mites and small insects	August and November
	Tetranychidae	Two spotted spider mite	<i>Tetranychus urticae</i> Koch	Pest	Nymph and adults	Moderate	Leaves	August and November
	Tydeidae		<i>Tydeus californicus</i> (Banks)	Mesolemus	Nymph	Moderate	Leaves	August and November

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Phytochemical and insecticidal evaluation of agro-waste of *Lagenaria siceraria* (Cucurbitaceae) plant against the cotton leafworm *Spodoptera littoralis* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae)

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Abstract:

Lagenaria siceraria (Cucurbitaceae) commonly known as bottle gourd cultivated in Africa, Asia and now cultivated in Egypt. After harvesting fruits of *L. siceraria*, the leaves of the plants are remained as agro-waste in the field. Preliminary phytochemical screening of *L. siceraria* leaves revealed the presence of steroids, alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, tannins and saponnins. The leaves extracted by ethanol and fractionated *via* solvents of different polarities; petroleum ether, ethyl acetate and n-butanol. The toxicity of extracts was tested against the cotton leafworm, *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisduval) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) under laboratory conditions. The petroleum ether extract exhibited more activity followed by ethanol, ethyl acetate and n-butanol. The LC₅₀ were 0.201, 0.352, 0.539 and 0.735%, respectively. The petroleum ether extract was subjected to saponification reaction and its chemical constituents were investigated by Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry. This indicated that the agro-waste of *L. siceraria* plant can be applied as green insecticide to control the cotton leafworm, *S. littoralis*.

Introduction

The Plant kingdom produce a great variety of phytochemicals (secondary metabolites) including flavonoids, saponnins, tannins, steroids, terpenoids and alkaloids are often important for mediating interactions between plants and their biotic environment. They can be models of active defense against phytophagous insects and pathogens. *Cucurbitaceae* family is commonly known as gourd, melon and pumpkin family. This family is composed of 118 genera and 825 species, which are widely distributed in the

warmer region of world (Rahman, 2003).

Among all the plants of Cucurbitaceae family *Lagenaria* species is the most popular. *Lagenaria siceraria* (Molina) member of genus *Lagenaria* that is derived from the word lagena, meaning the bottle. *L. siceraria* known as bottle gourd is a common fruit vegetable used throughout the India. This species follows the plant Kingdom : Plantae, Division: Magnoliophyta, Class: Magnoliopsida, Order: Cucurbitales, Family: Cucurbitaceae, Genus: *Lagenaria* and Species

: *L. siceraria* *L. siceraria* large pubescent, annual, prostrate or climbing herb cultivated in Africa, Asia and now cultivated in Egypt, its fruit is a source of vitamin-B complex and choline along with fair source of vitamin-C and β -carotene, amongst any other vegetable known to man till date, it is also good source of minerals and amino acids (Kirtikar and Basu, 2001). The fruits have antimicrobial, cytotoxicity, anticancer and antihepatotoxicity properties (Answar *et al.*, 1984; Desta, 1993; Furukawa *et al.*, 1995 and Shiwaikar and Sreenivasan, 1996). Lagenin, a ribosome inactivating protein (RIP) isolated from the seeds of *L. siceraria* possesses immune protective, antitumor, anti HIV and anti proliferative properties (Wang and Ng, 2000). After harvesting fruits of *L. siceraria*, the leaves of the plants are remained as agro-waste in the field. Rahman (2003) described the morphology of this plant species as follows: Stem: The stem is prostrate or climbing in nature with angular, ribbed thick, brittle, softly hairy. Leaves: Leaves are simple with long petiole from 25-30 mm long thick, hallow, densely hairy with two small lateral glands located at the leaf base. Leaf lamina: The lamina of leaf is usually five lobed, broad cordate, pubescent with soft hairs and the tendrils are branched. The flowers are solitary axillary, pedicellate, unisexual and monoecious. Petals: Petals are mainly five, white or cream colored which opens in the evening. Fruits: Fruits are green in color which turns to yellow on maturity. Fruits are large densely hairy often cylindrical or flask shaped or globose. They are constricted at the middle. Pulp: Pulp is pale brown in color and the dried fruit has thick hard hollow structure. Seeds: Seeds are embedded in the spongy pulp and

compressed with two flat facial ridges (Figure, 1).

Figure (1): *Lagenaria siceraria* plant

This study was planned to evaluate the insecticidal activity of ethanolic extract of *L. siceraria* agro-waste (leaves) and its fractions in solvents of different polarities against the cotton leafworm *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisduval) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) under laboratory conditions. Depending on the insecticidal evaluation, identify the chemical constituents in the bioactive fraction using chromatographic techniques.

Materials and methods

1. Chemicals:

The organic solvents of different polarities (petroleum ether, ethyl acetate, ethanol and n-butanol) used in the present work were obtained from Edwic Company.

2. Gas Chromatography-Mass

Spectroscopy analysis (GC/MS):

GC-MS analysis was performed on a Varian GC interfaced to Finnegan SSQ 7000 Mass selective Detector (SMD) with ICIS V2.0 data system for MS identification of the GC

components. The column used was DB-5 (J&W Scientific, Folosm, CA) cross-linked fused silica capillary column (30 m. long, 0.25mm. internal diameter) coated with poly dimethyl-siloxane (0.5µm. film thickness). The oven temperature was programmed from 50 °C for 3 min., at isothermal, then heating by 7 °C /min. to 250 °C and isothermally for 10 min., at 250 °C. Injector temperature was 200 °C and the volume injected was 0.5µl. Transition-line and ion source temperature were 250 °C and 150 °C, respectively. The mass spectrometer had a delay of 3 min. to avoid the solvent peak and then scanned from m/z 50 to m/z 300. Ionization energy was set at 70 eV. (Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza).

3. Experimental insect:

Newly molted 4th instar larvae of the cotton leafworm *S. littoralis* were selected for this study. The culture of laboratory susceptible strain was reared under optimum conditions 25±2 °C, 75±5% RH. and (16L:8D) light: dark photoperiod in the plant protection research institute, Dokki, Giza, Egypt. The larvae were reared on castor bean leaves

4. Plant material:

The agro-waste leaves of *L. siceraria* plant were remained after harvesting fruits. *L. siceraria* leaves were collected from field of experimental farm in Zagazig Governorate, Egypt and identified by Dr. Reda Mohamed El-Sayed, Faculty of Agriculture, and Zagazig University. The collected leaves were cleaned, left to dry under shade and homogenized to fine powder using electric mill.

5. Extraction and fractionation

A weighed amount of the powder (250 gm) was soaked in ethanol, the obtained extract from filtration was evaporated under vacuum at 40 °C on rotary evaporator to yield (45.32 gm). Part of the crude extract (30 gm) was suspended in distilled water in a separating funnel, petroleum ether was added to the funnel which was shaken gently and allowed to stand for about 2 hrs, the pet. ether

layer was separated in a flask, and the process was repeated three times to ensure maximum extraction. In the same manner, ethyl acetate and n-butanol fractions were obtained, leaving behind a residual aqueous fraction. The solvents were evaporated in rotary evaporator and the dried fractions were collected.

6. Preliminary phytochemical screening;

Preliminary phytochemical screening of *L. siceraria* leaves was carried out as the standard procedures (Sofowara, 1993 and Harborne, 1998).

6.1. Alkaloids: The alcoholic extract (corresponding to 2.5 g leaves powder) was evaporated to dryness and the residue was heated on a boiling water bath with 2N HCl (2 ml). After cooling the mixture was filtered and the filtrate was treated with few drops of Mayer's reagent.

Mayer's reagent: dissolve 136 g HgCl₂ in 60 ml water and 5 g KI in 10 ml water. Combine both solutions and make up with water to 100 ml. add a few drops to an acidified solution (HCl or diluted H₂SO₄), a yellow to orange precipitate will appear indicated a positive test.

6.2. Terpenoid: Alcoholic extract was evaporated and the residue was treated with anhydrous chloroform and filtered. Conc. sulphuric acid was added to the filtrate and shaken. Yellow color was produced, changed to orange then red.

6.3. Steroids: Alcoholic extract was evaporated and the residue was treated with anhydrous chloroform and filtered. The filtrate was treated with acetic acid and drops of Conc. sulphuric acid were added carefully on the side of test tube. Greenish color appeared (lower layer).

6.4. Flavonoids: A small quantity of the extract was dissolved in diluted sodium hydroxide (5%) and hydrochloric acid was added to the mixture. A yellow solution that turns colorless on addition of hydrochloric acid indicated the presence of flavonoids.

6.5. Saponins: one gram of the leaves was boiled with 10 ml water for few minutes and filtered. The filtrate was vigorously shaken. The persistent froth (1 cm height) was observed for 1 hr. indicates the presence of saponins.

6.6. Anthraquinones: The alcoholic extract (corresponding to 5g plant material) was evaporated to dryness and the residue was heated on a boiling water bath with 2N HCl (10 ml). After cooling the mixture was filtered and the filtrate was extracted with benzene. The benzene extract was shaken with NH₄OH (5 ml) and a positive reaction was evidenced by the formation of a red color in the alkaline layer.

6.7. Tannins: About one gram of the powdered sample was boiled with 10 mL of distilled water for five minutes, filtered while hot and a few drops of ferric chloride reagent was added to the filtrate. A red color indicates a positive test.

7. Preparation of tested concentrations:

The prepared fractions of *L. siceraria* were diluted in distilled water containing one drop of an emulsifier Tween[®]20 (Tween[®]20; Sigma-Aldrich), to ensure complete solubility of constituents. The applied concentrations were selected after preliminary bioassays with a wide range of concentrations to determine the proper range. Two negative control treatments were used in each experiment. One of them was for one drop of emulsifier (Tween[®]20) in water, where the Tween[®]20 solutions showed no significant mortality effect against *S. littoralis* larvae (data not shown) compared with water.

8. Toxicological evaluation:

Leaf dipping technique was applied; Castor bean leaves were dipped for 30 seconds in each concentration of tested extracts then left to dry. The treated leaves were offered to newly molted 4th instar larvae of *S. littoralis* for 48 hrs. then replaced by untreated ones. Accumulative mortality percentages were recorded, then corrected according Abbott's formula (1925). From the

corrected mortality percentages, the corresponding toxicity lines (LC-P lines) were estimated in addition to determine LC₂₅ and LC₅₀ values and their confidence limits, slope values of tested extract were also estimated.

9. Chromatography and identification of chemical constituents:

Petroleum ether fraction, which showed the highest toxicity activity against the 4th instar larvae, was selected for phytochemical investigation through GC/MS technique.

Pet. ether extract was subjected to Saponification reaction; hydrolysis with 10% alcoholic NaOH over water bath under reflux for 30 min., cooling, then diluted with water and extracted with diethyl ether afforded unsaponifiable fraction, while the saponifiable fraction was acidified with diluted HCl then extracted with diethyl ether. The saponifiable fraction was analyzed by GC/MS technique for characterization the petroleum ether constituents.

Results and discussion

L. siceraria plant was cultivated in Africa, Asia and now cultivated in Egypt. After harvesting fruits of the plant, the leaves are remained as agro-waste. Phytochemical screening of *L. siceraria* leaves showed the presence of flavonoids, saponins, tannins, steroids, terpenoids and alkaloids active phytoconstituents as shown in Table (1).

L. siceraria leaves were extracted by ethanol and fractionated via solvents of different polarities; petroleum ether, ethyl acetate and n-butanol, and examined as natural insecticides against newly molted 4th instar larvae of *Spodoptera littoralis* under laboratory conditions. , the tested extracts of *L. siceraria* leaves exhibited a high degree of efficiency as insecticide against *S. littoralis* larvae.

The petroleum ether extract exhibited a high degree of efficiency as insecticide followed by ethanol, ethyl acetate and finally n-butanol extracts. The activity was concentration dependent of the tested

extracts. LC₂₅ and LC₅₀ values and their confidence limits obtained from probit analysis for mortality values are showed in Table (2).

The obtained results agree with those obtained by Amit and Sangh (2012) who

suggested that the crude methanol extract of *L. siceraria* leaves produced anthelmintic activity against Indian earthworm, *Pheretima posthuma* when compared with the conventionally used drug (Albendazole).

Table (1): Preliminary phytochemical screening of *Lagenaria siceraria* leaves.

Test	Observation	Result
Test for Flavonoids Filtrate + NaOH (5%)	Yellow color was observed in test tube, then turned to colorless on addition of HCl	Presence of Flavonoids
Test for Tannins 5g of leaf extract + 10mL of distilled water. Filter + drops of ferric chloride (0.1%)	Brownish green to blue black precipitate was observed in test tube.	Presence of Tannins
Test for Saponins (Frothing test) 1g of leaves + distilled water + gentle warming and shaking vigorously	Froth was observed in the test tube, while disappeared after about one hour.	Presence of Saponins
Test for Alkaloids alcoholic extract + 5mL Aqueous HCl (2N) + drops of Mayer's solution	An yellowish precipitate was observed in test tube	Presence of Alkaloids
Test for Terpenoids alcoholic extract + 2 ml CHCl ₃ + 3 ml Conc. H ₂ SO ₄	yellow layer then turned to orange was observed in test tube	Presence of Terpenoids
Test of Steroids alcoholic extract + 2 ml CHCl ₃ + 3 ml Conc. H ₂ SO ₄ + acetic acid	Greenish color layer was observed on test tube	Presence of Steroids
Test for Anthraquinones 5g of leaves + 10mL Benzene. Filtrate +5mL 10% NH ₄ OH solution	No color change was observed.	Absence of Anthraquinones

Table (2): Insecticidal activity of *Lagenaria siceraria* leaves against the 4th instar larvae of *Spodoptera littoralis*.

Tested extract	LC ₂₅ (%) Confidence limits at 95%	LC ₅₀ (%) Confidence limits at 95%	Slope ± SE	Toxicity index
Petroleum Ether	0.083 (0.057 – 0.108)	0.201 (0.164 – 0.238)	1.754 ± 0.177	100
Ethanol	0.159 (0.125 – 0.191)	0.352 (0.305 – 0.407)	1.947 ± 0.179	56.94
Ethyl acetate	0.213 (0.166 – 0.257)	0.539 (0.457 – 0.654)	1.669 ± 0.179	37.22
n-butanol	0.310 (0.254 – 0.365)	0.735 (0.618 – 0.915)	1.801 ± 0.196	27.34

The obtained insecticidal evaluation data indicated that pet. Ether fraction is the most toxic extract. For this reason, this extract was subjected to saponification

reaction, and its chemical constituents were chemically investigated using GC-MS technique (Table ,3).

Table (3): Chemical constituents of petroleum ether extract.

Component name	R.T	Area%	Molecular formula
Dodecane	10.42	0.41	C ₁₂ H ₂₆
Hexadecene	16.81	0.43	C ₁₆ H ₂₃
Octadecane	20.96	0.20	C ₁₈ H ₃₆
Neophytadiene	24.21	0.35	C ₂₀ H ₃₈
6,10,14-trimethyl-1,2-pentadecanone	25.05	1.16	C ₁₈ H ₃₆ O ₂
3,7,11,15-tetramethyl-1,2-hexadecen-1-ol (Phytol)	28.51	53.01	C ₂₀ H ₄₀ O
9,12,15-octadecatrienal	32.82	2.05	C ₁₈ H ₃₀ O
Eicosene	34.06	1.09	C ₂₀ H ₄₀
Docosene	36.49	2.38	C ₂₂ H ₄₄
Hexacosene	40.11	2.24	C ₂₆ H ₅₂
Squalene	42.33	3.02	C ₃₀ H ₅₀
Cholesterol	44.38	0.32	C ₂₇ H ₄₆ O
Campesterol	46.48	1.04	C ₂₈ H ₄₈ O
Spinasterol	47.11	7.89	C ₂₉ H ₄₈ O
β-Sitosterol	47.76	1.38	C ₂₉ H ₅₀ O
Fucosterol	48.01	1.65	C ₂₉ H ₄₈ O
22-dihydro-spinasterol	48.78	5.78	C ₂₉ H ₅₀ O

The qualitative and quantitative compositions of petroleum ether extract were analyzed GC/MS where, the most abundant

constituents were phytol (53.1%), spinasterol (7.89%) and 22-Dihydrospinasterol (5.78%).

Phytol

Spinasterol

The insecticidal activity of petroleum ether extract of *L. siceraria* leaves against the 4th instar larvae of *S. littoralis* may be due to the presence of natural phytosterols such as spinasterol, 22-dihydrospinasterol, Fucosterol, β -Sitosterol and Campesterol. Spinasterol exhibited different biological activities including anti-ulcerogenic (Klein *et al.*, 2010), anti-inflammatory (Borges *et al.*, 2014), and antiproliferative activities (Ntie-Kang and Yong, 2014). Spinasterol, 22,23-dihydrospinasterol possess pharmacological and cytotoxic exertions likewise, it was isolated from *Bougainvillea spectabilis* and exhibited strong inhibition of xanthine oxidase being IC₅₀ of 39.21 μ M, (Chang *et al.*, 1994).

Meneses-Sagrero *et al.* (2017), identified spinasterol from the methanol extract of *Stegnosperma halimifolium* and evaluated against cancer cell line, they found that spinasterol exhibited potential activity as antiproliferative against two cell lines of cervical cancer such as HeLa and RAW 264.7. The petroleum ether, chloroform, methanol, absolute alcohol and water of *Lagenaria siceraria* plant showed moderate

22-Dihydrospinasterol

to potent antimicrobial activity against the bacterial strains: *Escherichia coli*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Klebsiella pneumonia*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and antifungal strains: such as *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus oryzae* and *Trichoderma harzianum* (Nagaraja *et al.*, 2012). Cucurbitaceae family is major source of medicinal agents since ancient time. Various plants parts of this family have been established for their pharmacological potential. The use of *L. siceraria*, *Cucumis sativus* and *Cucurbita maxima* leaves as useful anti-oxidant and cytotoxic agents (Alamgir *et al.*, 2016). The potency of methanol, acetone, chloroform and petroleum ether extracts of *Lagenaria siceraria* leaves against the 3rd instar larvae of the housefly, *Musca domestica* (Diptera: Muscidae) which consider as a diseases vector was evaluated by Mostafa *et al.*, (2018), where all plant extracts showed a larvicidal activity against the 3rd instar larvae of *M. domestica* larvae; however, the petroleum ether extract was found that to be the more effective than chloroform, acetone and methanol extracts. The LC₅₀ values of methanol, acetone, chloroform and petroleum ether extracts

recorded 468.5, 432.1, 433.8 and 101.4 ppm; respectively. As well, at the LC₅₀ values of the tested extracts exhibited repellent activity against *M. domestica* adults. The effective plant extract that exhibited high antifeedant or repellency action was petroleum ether extract as compared to chloroform, acetone and methanol extracts. From all mentioned results, it can be concluded that the petroleum ether extract of *L. siceraria* leaves (Agrowaste) can be applied as natural insecticide to control the cotton leafworm, *S. littoralis*.

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Effect of directions and weather factors on seasonal abundance of pink sugar cane mealybug, *Saccharicoccus sacchari* (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) in Nage Hamade, Egypt

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Abstract:

The pink sugar cane mealybug *Saccharicoccus sacchari* (Cockerell) (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) is serious pest on sugarcane (*Saccharum officinarum* L.). This study was carried out in Nage Hamade, Egypt, through two successive years (2016/2017 and 2017/2018). Obtained results indicated that east direction is highly population then north, west and finally south in two years of study. Nymph of *S. sacchari* on the east recorded four peaks, the highest one on end of August whereas the lowest one in middle of December in first year. While the adult recoded three peaks, the highest one on first week of November 2017. Second year of study both of nymph and adult stage had four peaks. The population of nymph and adult was positive with temperature and negative with RH% in two years of study.

Introduction

Sugarcane *Saccharum officinarum* L. (Poaceae) is considered the main materials for sugar processing. It is cultivated of large areas in Upper Egypt, especially in Qena Governorate persisting half of total sugarcane in Egypt (Bakry *et al.*, 2012). Sugarcane in Egypt is subject of seven major pests and 24 other minor pests (Abd-Rabou and Parker, 2008).

Saccharicoccus sacchari (Cockerell) (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) is the major pest in Egypt and the world. It lives on sugarcane both under-ground and on aerial stem tissue. Crawlers infest upper internodal tissue behind leaf sheaths and develop through a series of juvenile instar stages before becoming adult. It obtains nutrition from the plant's phloem and excess

carbohydrate is exuded as honeydew. Previous studies of *S. sacchari* have found that numbers increase as stem tissue develops (Inkerman *et al.* 1986). The effect heavy infestations of *S. sacchari* have on crop performance has seldom been quantified, but a negative one is often suspected (Beardsley 1960). Atiqui and Murad (1992) and Mohamed *et al.* (2009) have demonstrated significant loss of total dissolved solids (Brix) and sucrose as estimated by polarimetry in juice from infested compared with uninfested cane. Combined with the potential for exudates to cause problems during sugar manufacture (Inkerman *et al.* , 1986), observations of poor growth of sugarcane when heavily infested with *S. sacchari* summarized by (Dick, 1969), the damage

when highly infested is associated with a reduction in juice quality (brix, purity, and polarization), vigor and yield of culms (Mohamed *et al.*, 2009) and the ability of *S. sacchari* to transmit virus particles (Lockhart *et al.*, 1992) make *S. sacchari* an insect pest of continued commercial interest. *S. sacchari* outbreak occurred in last years to change temperature, and temperature had a positive correlation with incidence. Therefore, we examined the influence of directions and weather factors on the seasonal abundance of pink sugar cane mealybug, *S. sacchari* on sugarcane in Qena Governorate.

Materials and methods

The present study was carried out *S. sacchari* on sugarcane *S. officinarum* at Nage Hamade, Qena, Governorate, Egypt during a tow growing years (2016/2017) and (2017/2018) (i.e. from April, 2016 to March, 2018).

1. Seasonal activity of *Saccharicoccus sacchari*:

The design of experiment was as follows: An area of about one feddan (i.e. 4200 m²) was divided into four direction north, east, west and south. A sample of 5 internodes were chosen at random from each direction and replicated 4 times. The samples were examination, using a magnifying glass biweekly basis. Alive stages found on each sample were recorded as: nymph and adult females.

2. Effect of weather factors on the abundance of sugarcane mealybug *Saccharicoccus sacchari*:

Weather factors maximum, minimum temperatures, mean % and relative humidity (RH %) was obtained from the Egypt-Weather Underground <https://WWW.Wunderground.com/global/EG.html>. The biweekly maximum and minimum temperatures as well as relative humidity were calculated. Multiple regressions were conducted for weather factors combined. The obtained determination factor (R²) of E.V. % was used to explain the effect of testing

factors. Process Correlation and Regression were used in SAS to analysis they obtained date (SAS Institute, 1998).

Results and discussion

1. Seasonal activity of *Saccharicoccus sacchari*:

The seasonal activity of *S. sacchari* for fourth direction (West, north, east and south) as nymphs and adults was illustrated in (Figures 1 and 2) for two seasons of study (2016/2017 and 2017/2018). In both year of study nymphs and adults of *S. sacchari* were recorded high population in east, north, west and south, respectively. In the first year of study nymphs of *S. sacchari* were recorded fourth peaks in (27th of August, 22nd of October, 17th of December 2016 and 22nd of April 2017, respectively, in all direction (Figure, 1 B). The highest peak of *S. sacchari* nymphs were in 27th of August by (780 individuals /sample) while the lowest one in 17th of December 2016 by (240 individuals /sample) for east direction. Whereas the south direction the highest peak recorded (138 individuals /sample) in 27th of August and the lowest one in 17th of December 2016 by (28 individuals /sample).

Adults of *S. sacchari* was recorded three peaks in (13th of August, 8th of October 2016 and 25th of March 2017, respectively in all direction (Figure 1 A). The highest peak of *S. sacchari* adults were in 13th of August by (152 individuals /sample) while the lowest one in 25th of March 2017 by (100 individuals /sample) for east direction. Whereas the south direction the highest peak recorded (31 individuals /sample) in 13th of August and the lowest one in 25th of March 2017 by (20 individuals /sample).

In the second year of study nymphs of *S. sacchari* was recorded fourth peaks in (27th of August, 22nd of October, 17th of December 2017 and 22nd of April 2018, respectively in all direction (Figure 2 B). The highest peak of *S. sacchari* nymphs were in 27th of August by (800 individuals /sample) while the lowest

one in 17th of December 2017 by (260 individuals /sample) for east direction. Whereas the south direction the highest peak recorded (143 individuals /sample) in 27th of August and the lowest one in 17th of December 2017 by (33 individuals /sample).

Adults of *S. sacchari* was recorded three peaks in (13th of August, 8th of October 2017 and 25th of March 2018, respectively in all direction (Figure 2 A). The highest peak of *S. sacchari* adults were in 13th of August by (172 individuals /sample) while the lowest one in 25th of March 2018 by (120 individuals /sample) for east direction. Whereas the south direction the highest peak recorded (36 individuals /sample) in 13th of August 2017 and the lowest one in 25th of March 2018 by (25 individuals /sample).

These results agree with Abou Dooh *et al.* (1999) population of *S. sacchari* was high during July and September and low from December to March. Hafez and Salama (1969) recorded the peak populations in August-September. When the average monthly temperatures were 26.6-27.3 C. The insect had four generations/ year. Tohamy *et al.* (2008) found three peaks and four falls in the first season, while five peaks and six falls occurred in the second season. Moreover, showed that the pink sugarcane mealybug 3 to 5 annual generations, most of them occur during the summer, since they are mainly warm climatic insects. Borges Filho *et al.* (2019), was found during most year of Brazil, but infestation levels were highest in March.

2. Effect of weather factors on the abundance of *Saccharicoccus sacchari*:

We studied the effect of weather factors maximum, minimum, average temperature and relative humidity were illustrated Figure (3 A, B) for two years of

study. Correlation, regression analysis and multi regression between weather factors and population of *S. sacchari* was in liner degree, two years of study 2016/2017 and 2017/2018. Statistically, the results represented in Tables (1 and 2) showed the effect of the weather factors (maximum, minimum, average temperature and relative humidity) activity on *S. sacchari* to first and second year of study (2016/2017 and 2017/2018). With the respect to weather factors had significant effect on the population of the nymph stage *S. sacchari* in both years of study, for west direction, while east direction had highly significant effect on the population with maximum temperature (Tables, 1 and 2). The common effect of temperature and relative humidity was responsible for (56.83 %, 62.62%, 75.22% and 56.48 %) of the nymph to west, north, east and south, respectively Table (1). While the E.V for the adult stage of *S. sacchari* was (68.16 %, 68.17%, 70.02% and 66.92 %) of the adult to west, north, east and south, respectively Table (1) in first year of study (2016/2017). The common effect of temperature and relative humidity was responsible for (66.45 %, 69.97%, 78.73% and 65.70 %) of the nymph to west, north, east and south, respectively, Table (2) in second year. While the E.V. for the adult stage of *S. sacchari* was (67.71 %, 67.48%, 68.94% and 66.51 %) of the adult to west, north, east and south, respectively Table (2) in the second year of study (2017/2018).

(A)

(B)

Figure (1 A,B): Number of adults (A) and nymphs (B), *Saccharicoccus sacchari* at Nage Hamade, Qena, Governorate, Egypt during first growing year (2016/2017).

(A)

(B)

Figure (2 A,B): Number of adults (A) and nymphs (B), *Saccharicoccus sacchari* at Nage Hamade, Qena, Governorate, Egypt during second growing year (2017/2018).

(A)

(B)

Figure (3 A, B) : Weather factors maximum, minimum temperatures and mean % relative humidity (RH.%) at Nage Hamade, Quena, Governorate, Egypt during a tow growing years (2016/2017) (A) and (2017/2018) (B).

Table (1). The simple correlation and regression coefficients and multiple regressions between the different stages of *Saccharicoccus sacchari* and weather factors in first year (2016/2017).

Factors			Simple correlation and regression			Multiple regression
			R	B	P	E.V.%
Nymph	West	T max.	0.56	7.20	0.0028	56.83
		T avg.	0.57	8.78	0.0016	
		T min.	0.60	10.25	0.0013	
		R.H.%	-0.08	-0.64	0.6989	
	North	T max.	0.62	12.91	0.0008	62.62
		T avg.	0.65	15.73	0.0004	
		T min.	0.66	18.46	0.0003	
		R.H.%	-0.13	-1.71	0.5245	
	East	T max.	0.72	20.49	0.0001	75.22
		T avg.	0.74	24.53	0.0001	
		T min.	0.74	28.15	0.0001	
		R.H.%	-0.18	-3.16	0.3843	
	South	T max.	0.50	3.05	0.0089	56.48
		T avg.	0.53	3.76	0.0051	
		T min.	0.55	4.50	0.0035	
		R.H.%	-0.01	-0.05	0.9464	
Adult	West	T max.	0.68	2.06	0.0001	68.16
		T avg.	0.71	2.48	0.0001	
		T min.	0.71	2.89	0.0001	
		R.H.%	-0.21	-0.39	0.3058	
	North	T max.	0.68	3.24	0.0001	68.17
		T avg.	0.71	3.93	0.0001	
		T min.	0.72	4.61	0.0001	
		R.H.%	-0.23	-0.67	0.2690	
	East	T max.	0.70	4.81	0.0001	70.02
		T avg.	0.73	5.83	0.0001	
		T min.	0.74	6.83	0.0001	
		R.H.%	-0.24	-1.01	0.2477	
	South	T max.	0.69	0.90	0.0001	66.92
		T avg.	0.71	1.09	0.0001	
		T min.	0.71	1.28	0.0001	
		R.H.%	-0.22	-0.18	0.2790	

Table (2). The simple correlation and regression coefficients and multiple regressions between the different stages of *Saccharicoccus sacchari* and weather factors in second year (2017/2018).

Factors			Simple correlation and regression			Multiple regression
			R	B	p	
Nymph	West	T max.	0.56	7.20	0.0028	66.45
		T avg.	0.53	7.87	0.0050	
		T min.	0.60	10.25	0.0013	
		R.H.%	-0.08	-0.64	0.6989	
	North	T max.	0.62	12.91	0.0008	69.97
		T avg.	0.60	14.42	0.0012	
		T min.	0.66	18.46	0.0003	
		R.H.%	-0.13	-1.71	0.5245	
	East	T max.	0.72	20.49	0.0001	78.73
		T avg.	0.69	22.78	0.0001	
		T min.	0.74	28.15	0.0001	
		R.H.%	-0.18	-3.16	0.3843	
	South	T max.	0.50	3.05	0.0089	65.70
		T avg.	0.48	3.36	0.0130	
		T min.	0.55	4.50	0.0035	
		R.H.%	-0.01	-0.05	0.9464	
Adult	West	T max.	0.68	2.06	0.0001	67.71
		T avg.	0.68	2.34	0.0001	
		T min.	0.71	2.89	0.0001	
		R.H.%	-0.21	-0.39	0.3058	
	North	T max.	0.68	3.24	0.0001	67.48
		T avg.	0.68	3.73	0.0001	
		T min.	0.72	4.61	0.0001	
		R.H.%	-0.22	-0.67	0.2690	
	East	T max.	0.70	4.81	0.0001	68.94
		T avg.	0.70	5.55	0.0001	
		T min.	0.74	6.83	0.0001	
		R.H.%	-0.24	-1.01	0.2477	
	South	T max.	0.69	0.90	0.0001	66.51
		T avg.	0.68	1.03	0.0001	
		T min.	0.71	1.26	0.0001	
		R.H.%	-0.22	-0.18	0.2790	

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Potential toxicity of some essential oils on mealybug, *Maconellicoccus hirsutus* (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae)

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Abstract:

The present work was conducted to evaluate the efficiency of some essential oils on the populations of the *hibiscus mealybug Maconellicoccus hirsutus* (Green) (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) under Laboratory and field conditions. The essential oils were ginger (*Zingiber officinale*), garlic (*Allium sativum*), lemone (*Citrus aurantiifolia*) and mint (*Menth* sp.) . One compound insecticide (Actara) was used as control measure for the essential oils. LC₅₀ of each treatment were established after 24, 48 and 72 hours the alive of mealybugs and the obtained results revealed that the lemone was the most effective. Ginger and garlic, also, was more effective than mint which has very low effect on mealybug. LC₅₀ was 0.78, 3.07, 0.02 and 57.94; 0.47, 2.29, 0.01 and 41.80 and 0.32, 1.51, 0.01 and 24.39 0.32, 1.51, 0.01 and 24.39 ppm, for ginger, garlic, lemone e, mint, after 24, 48 and 72 hrs., respectively. Mortality percentages were calculated after 7, 15 and 21 days post treatment. The results indicated that the average mortality percentages of mealybugs were 63.92, 51.89, 72.72, 29.67 and 87.38 for 2018 year and 61.49, 54.46, 73.77, 31.75 and 88.55 for 2019 year by ginger, garlic, lemone e, mint and actara, respectively. The efficacy of ginger, garlic, mint, lemone and actara in all treatments can be useful for development safe elements for an IPM strategy to mealybugs. So, it prefers to use the essential oils for controlling the insect in IPM program and more studies should be carried on ginger and garlic to improve their efficiency for control insect pests to minimize the environmental pollution with pesticides.

Introduction

Grapevine is considered as one of the most important fruit crops in Egypt not only as popular fruit but also used for many agricultural industries. Egypt ranks fourth worldwide in the global production volume of table grapes and has shown impressive

growth in the past 5 to 10 years. In Egypt, grapes are one of the most widely grown fruit crops, second only to citrus. In 2016, production of grapes in Egypt amounted to 1 691 194 tones on 184 254 feddans of cultivated land (FAOSTAT, 2019).

The hibiscus mealybug *Maconellicoccus hirsutus* (Green) (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) is one of the most important mealybugs insect infesting grapevine in Egypt. It recorded with heavily infestation on trunk, bunches, leaves and roots of grapevine, the sever infestations of *M. hirsutus* affected greatly on bunches resulting poor crop with poor quality and quantity. The hibiscus mealybug *M. hirsutus* has wide range of host plants include many agricultural crops e.g. hibiscus, citrus, coffee, sugarcane, annonas, plums, guava, mango, okra, pigeon pea, peanut, grapevine, maize, asparagus, chrysanthemum, beans, cotton, soybean, cocoa, and many other plants (Williams, 1996 and Abd-Rabou, 2000). Chemical pesticides pollute the tissues of almost every form of life on earth, air, lakes, oceans, the fish they inhabit and the birds that feed on fish and the application of pesticides cause serious problems such as the accumulation of resistant pests, disturbance of natural balance and dangers to the environment (Hurley *et al.*, 1998 and Abd-Rabou, 2008). Essential oil (EO) products are natural compounds that have insecticide properties, and their use in crop protection is as old as agricultural practices (Bakkali *et al.*, 2008). It may provide potential alternatives to currently used pest control agents, and essential oils are complex natural metabolites that are characterized by strong odor and volatility and have generally lower density than water. Because of its volatility, essential oils are environmentally unstable. Recent research has reported the nature of insecticides for many essential oils (Bell *et al.*, 1990).

Mode of action of the use of EO and their principal compounds for mealybug control, as these lipophilic compounds can penetrate the waxy cuticle and may thus more effectively kill these insects. In fact, as botanical products impair lipid synthesis, they lower the lipid content of the insect cuticle, thereby making the mealybugs more

sensitive to pesticides and chemical action (Patil *et al.*, 2010).

So, the present work was conducted to evaluate the efficiency of some essential oils on the populations of the *hibiscus mealybug M. hirsutus* under Laboratory and field conditions

Materials and methods

1. Laboratory tests:

1.1. Bioassay experiment:

The experiments were carried out in the laboratory of Organic agriculture center laboratory, Agricultural Research Center, Giza, collected of *M. hirsutus* by cutting leaves in fasted it from hibiscus tree then transferred to potato sprouts in laboratory with 23 ± 2 °C and 65 ± 5 RH.%. The following four plant extract oils were tested: Ginger (*Zingiber officinale*), garlic (*Allium sativum*), lemone (*Citrus aurantiifolia*) and mint (*Mentha* sp.) oils used at aerate of five concentration (0.5, 1, 3, 5 and 7 ml. /Lw of water then dipping hibiscus leaves into each concentration for five seconds, has been moved plant leaf treatments to clean wide plastic dishes, which were then covered with muslin cloth held in position by rubber bonds. Mealybugs transferred to plastic dishes, mealybugs individuals were divided into three replicates, each replicate contains it 10 from mealybugs. Addition to water used in untried cheek. After 24, 48 and 72 hours the alive of mealybugs.

1.2. Statistical analysis:

The mortality percentages were calculated and corrected for natural mortalities by **Abbott's formula (1925)**. The corrected percent mortalities were statistically computed according to **Finney (1971)** and plotted on probity analysis paper. The tested oils according to their Lc_{50} , Lc_{90} , slopes and relative potency of the toxicity lines.

2. Field tests:

Field evaluation of the tested essential oils on populations of the hibiscus *mealybug* *M. hirsutus* infested grapes. Four compounds of plant extract oils, ginger, garlic, lemon and mint oils used recommended concentration and actara® 25 WG (Thiamethoxam) evaluation carried out in July 2018 and 2019 at Atfih, Giza Governorate under field conditions for controlling the *M. hirsutus*. The evaluated compounds were:

A. Ginger (*Zingiber officinale*): This group was presented with one Mineral compound Super Misrona oil 95% EC Mayonnaise: Formulated by Misr Company for Petroleum Egypt, used with rate of 2.5%.

B. Garlic (*Allium sativum*), an entomopathogenic fungi (3200 viable spore/mg), containing the fungus *Beauveria bassiana* applied at a rate 2ml/liter of water.

C. Lemon (*Citrus aurantiifolia*) an entomopathogenic fungi (32×10^2 viable spore/ml), containing the fungus *Metarrhizium anisoplae* applied at a rate 2ml/liter of water.

D. Mint (*Mentha* sp.), applied at rate of 2.5g/liter of water.

E. Actara® 25 wg (Water Dispersible Granules) (Thiamethoxam) **compound**: This group was presented with one insecticide compound *i.e.* Malathion 57%EC formulated by Sumitomo Company, used with rate of 1%. This compound was used as control measure for the four alternatives groups. The grapevine orchard kept away from any control measures before and during the investigation. Five treatments were applied in four replications, each replicate contain four grapes orchards besides other four trees were

left as control (untreated check) . Spraying was accomplished by motor sprayer with diluted solution of 15 liter/tree. Random samples of 80 infested leaves were picked up from each replicate, *i.e.* 240 leaves for each treatment immediately before spraying application. The leaves samples were put in polyethylene bags and transferred to the laboratory. The population of *M. hirsutus* was sorted to different stages *i.e.* eggs, nymphs, and adults.

The reduction percentages were estimated according to Henderson and Tilton (1955) equation. Reduction percentage of the insect populations was transferred to arc sine before conducting analysis of variance (F test) and LSD values were used to separate the means. The statistical analysis of the present work was conducted using MSTATC computer Program.

Results and discussion

1. Laboratory experiments:

The data in Table (1) demonstrated that, although the extract concentrations were low, the mortality rate of *M. hirsutus* populations was low and when the concentrations increased, the total mortality increased. However, Table (2) demonstrated that, Our results from the study showed that LC_{50} was 0.78, 3.07, 0.02 and 57.94 ; 0.47, 2.29, 0.01 and 41.80 and 0.32, 1.51, 0.01 and 24.39 ppm, for ginger, garlic, lemon e , mint, after 24, 48 and 72 hrs., respectively. While LC_{90} was 15.34, 47.59, 5.48 and 1239.46 ; 12.04, 30.15, 1.15 and 1968.77 and 9.60, 84.23, 1.15 and 4397.08 ppm, for ginger, garlic, lemon e , mint, after 24, 48 and 72 hrs., respectively.

Table (1): Toxic effect of some essential oils against the mealybug *Maconellicoccus hirsutus* at different concentrations.

Treatment	Con. ML/lw	Mortality %			Mean
		24 hours	48 hours	72 hours	
<i>Zingiber officinale</i> (Ginger)	0.5	43.3	50	53.3	
	1	56.6	63.3	73.3	
	3	63.3	73.3	76.5	
	5	80	83.3	83.3	
	7	86.6	86.6	90	
<i>Allium sativum</i> (Garlic)	0.5	23.3	26.2	40	
	1	26.6	30	43.3	
	3	46.6	56	53.3	
	5	56.6	56.3	56.3	
	7	70	79.3	80	
<i>Citrus aurantiifolia</i> (Lemone e)	0.5	73.3	86.6	86.6	
	1	86.6	86.6	96.6	
	3	86.6	96.6	96.6	
	5	90	96.6	100	
	7	90	100	100	
<i>Menth</i> sp. (Mint)	0.5	6.6	6.6	16.6	
	1	10	26.6	30	
	3	13.3	20	36.6	
	5	13.3	26.6	36.6	
	7	20	30	40	

Table (2): Efficiency of some essential oils on mealybug *Maconellicoccus hirsutus*.

Treatment	LC ₅₀			LC ₉₀		
	24h	48h	72h	24h	48h	72h
<i>Zingiber officinale</i> (Ginger)	0.78	0.47	0.32	15.34	12.04	9.60
<i>Allium sativum</i> (Garlic)	3.07	2.29	1.51	47.59	30.15	84.23
<i>Citrus aurantiifolia</i> (Lemone e)	0.02	0.01	0.01	5.48	1.15	1.15
<i>Menth</i> sp. (Mint)	57.94	41.80	24.39	1239.46	1968.77	4397.08

2. Field experiments:

2.1. Field evaluation of the tested alternative insecticides on population of the hibiscus mealybug *Maconellicoccus hirsutus* in 2018 year:

The initial effect of tested compounds on the populations after one week of population as well as the residual effect after two and three weeks of application were shown Table (3 and 4). The obtained results shown that the initial effect of tested insecticides after one week of application was varied on the egg population. The highest effective compound was actara (84.05%). While the moderate

effective compound was lemone, ginger and garlic. They reduced the egg population to (62.51%, 57.35 and 49.14%, respectively). The less effective compounds on the egg populations was mint, it reduced the population to (27.98 %). The initial effect of the tested compounds on nymph populations showed that the highest effective compound was actara (82.39%). While the moderate effective compound was lemone, ginger and garlic. They reduced the nymph population to 61.18, 53.34 and 45.5%, respectively. The less effective compounds on the nymph populations was mint, it reduced the

population to 24.15 %. The same trend of the effect essential oils on adult populations showed that the highest effective compound was actara (79.29%). While the moderate effective compound was lemongrass, ginger and garlic. They reduced the egg population to 59.03, 49.69 and 43.01%, respectively. The less effective compounds on the egg populations was mint, it reduced the population to 21.85 %.

The residual effect of the tested compounds on the populations of *Maconellicoccus hirsutus* stages was appeared after 2 weeks, was varied on the egg population. The highest effective compound was actara (90.15%). While the moderate effective compound was lemongrass, ginger and garlic. They reduced the egg population to (77.4, 65.24 and 55.25, respectively). The less effective compounds on the egg populations was mint, it reduced the population to (33.49 %). The initial effect of the tested compounds on nymph populations showed that the highest effective compound was actara (87.7 %). While the moderate effective compound was lemongrass, ginger and garlic. They reduced the nymph population to 74.73, 66.16 and 52.86 %, respectively. The less effective compounds on the nymph populations was mint, it reduced the population to 30.8 %. The same trend of the effect essential oils on adult populations showed that the highest effective compound was actara (85.1%). While the moderate

effective compound was lemongrass, ginger and garlic. They reduced the adult population to 70.23, 61.93 and 51.47 %, respectively. The less effective compounds on the adult populations was mint, it reduced the population to 26.16 %.

After 3 weeks of application, the residual effects of tested insecticides were varied was varied on the egg population. The highest effective compound was actara (95.38%). While the moderate effective compound was lemongrass, ginger and garlic. They reduced the egg population to (86.71, 77.23 and 59.27, respectively). The less effective compounds on the egg populations was mint, it reduced the population to (38.16 %). The initial effect of the tested compounds on nymph populations showed that the highest effective compound was actara (92.68 %). While the moderate effective compound was lemongrass, ginger and garlic. They reduced the nymph population to 83.58, 79.96 and 56.21%, respectively. The less effective compounds on the nymph populations was mint, it reduced the population to 34.83 %. The same trend of the effect essential oils on adult populations showed that the highest effective compound was actara (95.0%). While the moderate effective compound was lemongrass, ginger and garlic. They reduced the adult population to 79.13, 69.42 and 54.32 %, respectively. The less effective compounds on the adult populations was mint, it reduced the population to 29.66 %.

Table (3): Average numbers of the mealybug *Maconellicoccus hirsutus* after treatment with different compounds on grapes in Atfih (Giza) during 2018.

Treatment	Rate of Applic. /L.W.	Pre spraying count			Post spraying count after									Average number			
					7			14			21						
		E.	N.	A.	E.	N.	A.	E.	N.	A.	E.	N.	A.	E.	N.	A.	AV.
Ginger	10 ml	23.2	13.0	6.9	9.0	10.03	2.7	6.6	4.5	2.2	4.9	3.9	2.0	6.83	4.66	2.3	4.59
Garlic	10 ml	22.7	15.3	9.4	10.5	11.7	4.3	9.7	6.9	4.0	9.4	6.7	4.2	9.86	6.93	4.16	6.98
Lemongrass	2.5 gm	26.1	18.2	9.1	8.9	13.2	2.9	8.5	4.4	2.3	5.63.1	3.1	1.8	7.66	4.53	2.33	4.84
Mint	5 ml	20.0	14.2	10.2	13.1	6.2	6.2	12.7	9.4	6.4	12.5	9.6	6.8	12.76	9.43	6.46	9.55
Thiamethoxam (Actara 25% WG)	2 gm	25.5	17.1	9.6	3.7	13.0	1.5	2.4	2	1.3	1.2	1.3	1.0	2.43	1.96	1.26	1.88
Control		24.3	16.1	15.3	22.1	16.1	11.9	23.2	15.4	13.0	24.7	16.7	14.5	23.33	15.33	13.13	17.26

E. Egg N. Nymphs A. Adult AV. Average

Table (4): Reduction percentage of different compounds on the mealybug *Maconellicoccus hirsutus* on grapes in Atfih (Giza) during 2018.

Treatment	Rate of Applic. /L.W.	%Reduction after:									Average %reduction			
		7			14			21			E.	N.	A.	AV.
		E.	N.	A.	E.	N.	A.	E.	N.	A.				
Ginger	10ml	57.35	53.34	49.69	65.24	66.16	61.93	77.23	79.96	69.42	67.27	64.15	60.34	63.92
Garlic	10ml	49.14	45.5	43.01	55.25	52.86	51.47	59.27	56.21	54.32	54.55	51.52	49.6	51.89
Lemone	2.5gm	62.51	61.18	59.03	77.4	74.73	70.23	86.71	83.58	79.13	75.54	73.16	69.46	72.72
Mint	5ml	27.98	24.15	21.85	33.49	30.8	26.16	38.16	34.83	29.66	33.21	29.92	25.89	29.67
Thiamethoxam (Actara 25% WG)	5ml	84.05	82.39	79.92	90.15	87.78	85.1	95.38	92.68	95.0	89.86	87.61	89.01	87.38

E. Egg N. Nymphs A. Adult AV. Average .

2.2. Field evaluation of the tested alternative insecticides on population of the hibiscus mealybug *Maconellicoccus hirsutus* in 2019 year:

The initial effect of tested compounds on the populations after one week of population as well as the residual effect after two and three weeks of application were shown Table (5 and 6). The obtained results showed that the initial effect of tested insecticides after one week of application was varied on the egg population. The highest effective compound was actara (85.56%). While the moderate effective compound was lemone, ginger and garlic. They reduced the egg population to (69.55%, 54.97 and 50.81%, respectively). The less effective compounds on the egg populations was mint, it reduced the population to (31.49 %). The initial effect of the tested compounds on nymph populations showed that the highest effective compound was actara (83.29%). While the moderate effective compound was lemone, ginger and garlic. They reduced the egg population to 66.94, 51.68 and 46.53%, respectively. The less effective compounds on the egg populations was mint, it reduced the population to 29.13 %. The same trend of the effect essential oils on adult populations showed that the highest effective compound was actara (81.27%). While the moderate effective compound was lemone, ginger and garlic. They reduced the egg population to 63.95, 48.41 and 42.86%, respectively. The

less effective compounds on the egg populations was mint, it reduced the population to 25.55 %.

The residual effect of the tested compounds on the populations of *Maconellicoccus hirsutus* stages was appeared after 2 weeks, was varied on the egg population. The highest effective compound was actara (91.15%). While the moderate effective compound was lemone, ginger and garlic. They reduced the egg population to (77.19, 67.34 and 58.94, respectively). The less effective compounds on the egg populations was mint, it reduced the population to (34.5 %). The initial effect of the tested compounds on nymph populations showed that the highest effective compound was actara (89.27 %). While the moderate effective compound was lemone, ginger and garlic. They reduced the nymph population to 74.7, 62.1 and 54.4 %, respectively. The less effective compounds on the nymph populations was mint, it reduced the population to 31.1 %. The same trend of the effect essential oils on adult populations showed that the highest effective compound was actara (86.41%). While the moderate effective compound was lemone, ginger and garlic. They reduced the adult population to 70.01, 58.45 and 50.05 %, respectively. The less effective compounds on the adult populations was mint, it reduced the population to 28.85 %.

After 3 weeks of application, the residual effects of tested insecticides were varied was varied on the egg population. The highest effective compound was actara (96.18%). While the moderate effective compound was lemone, ginger and garlic. They reduced the egg population to (84.59, 74.95 and 66.53, respectively). The less effective compounds on the egg populations was mint, it reduced the population to (38.96 %). The initial effect of the tested compounds on nymph populations showed that the highest effective compound was actara (93.47%). While the moderate effective compound was lemone ,

ginger and garlic. They reduced the nymph population to 80.85, 71.36 and 62.75 %, respectively. The less effective compounds on the nymph populations was mint, it reduced the population to 34.46 %. The same trend of the effect essential oils on adult populations showed that the highest effective compound was actara (90.44%). While the moderate effective compound was lemone, ginger and garlic. They reduced the adult population to 76.5, 68.28 and 57.32 %, respectively. The less effective compounds on the adult populations was mint, it reduced the population to 30.13 %.

Table (5): Average numbers of the mealybug *Maconellicoccus hirsutus* after treatment with different compounds on grapes in Atfih (Giza) during 2019.

Treatment	Rate of Applic. /L.W.	Pre spraying count			Post spraying count after:									Average number			
					7			14			21						
		E.	N.	A.	E.	N.	A.	E.	N.	A.	E.	N.	A.	E.	N.	A.	AV.
Ginger	10 ml	22.9	15.3	7.4	8.4	6.0	4.2	7.1	5.8	3.8	6.3	5.3	3.1	7.26	5.7	3.7	5.55
Garlic	10 ml	27.2	18.2	9.14	10.9	7.9	5.2	10.6	8.3	5.0	10.0	8.2	4.8	10.5	8.13	5.0	7.87
Lemone	2.5 gm	25.4	16.4	10.4	6.3	4.4	4.6	5.5	4.2	4.3	4.3	3.8	3.7	5.36	4.13	4.2	4.56
Mint	5 ml	26.7	19.3	11.6	14.9	11.1	9.5	16.6	13.3	10.2	17.9	15.3	11.0	16.46	13.23	10.23	13.30
Thiamethoxam (Actara 25% WG)	2 gm	23.8	17.7	13.1	2.8	2.4	2.7	2.1	1.9	2.2	1	1.4	1.7	1.96	1.9	2.2	2.02
2.02Control		27.5	19.1	14.0	22.4	15.5	15.4	26.1	19.1	17.3	30.2	23.1	19.0	26.23	19.23	17.23	20.89

E. Egg N. Nymphs A. Adult AV. Average .

Table (6): Reduction percentage of different compounds on the mealybug *Maconellicoccus hirsutus* on grapes in Atfih (Giza) during 2019

Treatment	Rate of Applic. /L.W.	%Reduction after:									Average %reduction			
		7			14			21						
		E.	N.	A.	E.	N.	A.	E.	N.	A.	E.	N.	A.	AV.
Ginger	10ml	54.97	51.68	48.41	67.34	62.1	58.45	74.95	71.36	68.28	65.75	61.71	58.38	61.94
Garlic	10ml	50.81	46.53	42.86	58.94	54.4	50.05	66.53	62.75	57.32	58.76	54.55	50.07	54.46
Lemone	2.5gm	69.55	66.94	63.95	77.19	74.7	70.01	84.59	80.85	76.5	77.11	74.06	70.15	73.77
Mint	5ml	31.49	29.13	25.55	34.5	31.1	28.85	38.96	34.46	30.13	34.98	31.56	28.17	31.57
Thiamethoxam (Actara 25% WG)	5ml	85.56	83.29	81.27	91.15	89.27	86.41	96.18	93.47	90.44	90.96	88.67	86.04	88.55

E. Egg N. Nymphs A. Adult AV. Average.

Statistical analysis demonstrated in first highly significant differences between the different compounds (Ginger, garlic, lemone e, mint and actara) and control of population of eggs ,nymphs and adult of *M. hirsutus*

during , 2018 (F=177.04, 186.99 and 225.79, and LSD=3.3536, 12.6136 and 2.7874) respectively. While, during 2019 (F=325.78, 359.71, 225.79 and LSD=2.38, 2.7252 and 2.7874) respectively (Table, 7).

Table (7) : Statistical analysis of the efficacy of different compounds against *Maconellicoccus hirsutus* populations.

Treatment	Rate of Applic. /L.W.	Average % reduction 2018			Average %reduction 2019		
		Egg	N	Adult	Egg	N	adult
Ginger	10ml	67.27b	64.15b	60.34b	65.75b	61.71b	58.38b
Garlic	10ml	54.55c	51.52c	49.6c	58.76c	54.55c	50.07c
Lemone	2.5gm	75.54a	73.16a	69.46a	77.11a	74.06a	70.15a
Mint	5ml	33.21d	29.92d	25.89d	34.98	31.56d	28.17d
Thiamethoxam (Actara 25% WG)	5ml	89.86	87.61	89.01	90.96	88.67	86.04
F test		177.04	186.99	225.79	325.78	359.71	225.79
L.S.D		3.3536	12.6136	2.7874	2.38	2.7252	2.7874

Essential oils are much preferable as green insecticides against different pest groups (Işık and Görür, 2009). They are volatile, natural, complex compounds characterized by a strong odor and are formed by plants as secondary metabolites (Sharaby *et al.*, 2012). In nature, essential oils seems to be important agents of interspecific communication as they are favour pollination by attracting insects, they also play an important role in protection of the plants as antibacterial, antiviral, antifungal, insecticides and also against herbivorous by reducing their appetite for such plants (Bakkali *et al.*, 2008). Peschiutta *et al.* (2017) showed the capacity of EO derived from plants as a potential tool for mealybug control, due to its insecticidal activity. This type of research contributes to the search of potential novel active compounds to environmentally friendly control of mealybug in vineyards.

Our results from the study showed that LC50 was 0.78, 3.07, 0.02 and 57.94 ; 0.47, 2.29, 0.01 and 41.80 and 0.32, 1.51, 0.01 and 24.39 0.32, 1.51, 0.01 and 24.39 ppm, for ginger, garlic, lemone e , mint, after 24, 48 and 72 hrs., respectively. Mortality percentages were calculated after 7, 15 and 21 days post treatment. The results indicated that the average mortality percentages of mealybugs infested vineyards were 63.92, 51.89, 72.72, 29.67 and 87.38 for 2018 year and 61.49, 54.46, 73.77, 31.75 and 88.55 for 2019 year by ginger, garlic, lemone e , mint and actara, respectively. Overall results

suggested that the essential oils tested may help for us in controlling *M. hirsutus* populations in various agroecosystems.

The repellency of ginger oil was attributed to its odor, effective at the concentrations used over a distance of 1-2 mm. Tomato leaf disks dipped in ginger oil repelled whiteflies at concentrations of 0.5, 0.75, and 1%, but not at concentrations <0.5%, in a dose-response experiment conducted in the olfactometer (Zhang *et al.*, 2004). The results showed that, garlic oil was the best efficient in reducing the population of leafhoppers and planthoppers by a mean reduction percentage of 68.09% at 3% conc. However, in controlling aphids, also garlic surpasses again by a mean overall reduction 90.96 % (Mousa *et al.*, 2013). Ahmadi *et al.* (2012) tested the effects of sirinol (garlic extract) with five doses (1000, 1500, 2000, 2500 and 3500 ppm) on citrus mealybug and found that the highest mortality with sirinol (3500 ppm) with 87.11% mortality, 72 h after spraying. The EOs of the aromatic plants of mint species (*Mentha* spp.) have adulticidal, larvicidal, and growth and reproduction inhibitory effects, as well as repellent activity against various stored product pests and vectors (Michaelakis *et al.*, 2012). They also exhibit strong fumigant toxicity against greenhouse pests such as *Trialeurodes vaporariorum* (Westwood) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae), *Tetranychus urticae* Koch (Acari: Tetranychidae) (Choi *et al.*, 2003 and 2004), and several aphids species (Kimbaris *et al.*, 2010). Cloyd *et al.* (2009) reported that

a mixture of thyme and mint oil resulted in 89% mortality of citrus mealybugs 3 days after spraying.

The insecticidal activity of pure limonene has been shown against other mealybug species. Spray applications of limonene in 1% aqueous solution (together with a spray adjuvant as an emulsifier/surfactant and another agricultural surfactant) resulted in 44% mortality of 3rd and 4th instar nymphs of *Planococcus citri* (Risso) (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) on gardenia pot plants in the greenhouse. In addition, laboratory bioassays with the same limonene solution showed 95–100% mortality to the nymphs and adults of the coconut mealybug *Nipaecoccus nipae* (Maskell) (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae), on sprayed coconut leaves, 92% mortality against 3rd and 4th instar nymphs of the long tailed mealybug, *Pseudococcus longispinus* (Targioni-Tozzetti) (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae), when applied on green beans by dipping for 1 min, and 100% mortality of eggs of the root mealybug, *Rhizoecus* spp., on Gardenia roots by dipping in application for 1 min (Hollingsworth, 2005).

In conclusion, our results suggest that the essential oils tested in the present study may help in reducing *M. hirsutus* populations in different agroecosystems through their repellent, oviposition-deterrent and egg-hatching inhibitory effects. Furthermore, they appear to be environmentally safe because many of them, including those tested in the present study, are commonly used in the food and beverage industry as flavorings, in the cosmetic and perfume industry for fragrances and in the pharmaceutical industry for medicinal purposes. They also have the potential to be adopted on commercial scale. These results are promising for future research.

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Comparative biological features of cotton whitefly, *Bemisia tabaci* (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) when reared on four host plants

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Abstract

Cotton whitefly *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) is a polyphagous devastating insect of numerous agronomic crops in Egypt. Comparison between the biological features of *B. tabaci* when reared on four vegetable plants, tomato, eggplant, cucumber and squash was established. Data showed a non-significant difference for the egg incubation period of *B. tabaci* on the investigated four vegetable plants. The developmental time of *B. tabaci* nymphal stage when fed on the different investigated diets was a significant longer period in tomato plant than other host plants (16.45 days). However, the smallest period of nymphal stage was observed on eggplant (10.36 days), followed by squash (11.96 days) and cucumber (12.04 days) plants. The accomplishment of *B. tabaci* life cycle (egg - adults per day) was a longest on tomato being 20.26 days, but it was a shortest on eggplant (12.57 days). In addition, a survival rate of *B. tabaci* when reared on different tested host plants was higher on squash and eggplant plants (84% and 80%, respectively) than on other examined host plants. Present data indicated that the net reproductive rate (R_0) was ranged from 27.081 on tomato to 52.560 on eggplant plants. The present data also reflected the highest finite rate of increase (λ) on eggplant (1.2128), followed by squash plant (1.1788) and the lowest on tomato plant (1.1222), and followed by cucumber plant (1.1546). The finite rate was ranged from 1.1222 – 1.2128, that means, *B. tabaci* was able to increase the population ($\lambda > 1$) on all tested host plants. In the present study, the preference of whitefly influenced by the plant enzyme activities as well as Phenoloxidase and Peroxidase, as like, the *B. tabaci* infestation increased by increased the polyphenoloxidase and peroxidase activities in host plant. Moreover, the leaf phytochemical components influenced on the development of whitefly on the four tested vegetable plants. Finally, *B. tabaci* is obviously a greater host preference for eggplant and squash plants as compared to cucumber and tomato plants by documenting a short life and mortality. Hence, one should consider the susceptibility of vegetable plants when planning the IPM program for *B. tabaci* in Egypt.

Introduction

Cotton whitefly *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) is a polyphagous devastating insect of numerous agronomic crops in tropical and subtropical regions (Oliveira *et al.*, 2001 and Schuster *et al.*, 1996). *B. tabaci* infested about 506 plant species from 74 families in all plant growth stages, seedling, flowering and fruiting. After feeding on plant sap, both nymph and adult excreted honeydew on plant (Van Doorn *et al.*, 2015). Host plants effect on the development of *B. tabaci* (Sharaf *et al.*, 1985 and Fekrat and Shishehbor, 2007). *B. tabaci* caused numerous damages by direct feeding (Wan and Yang, 2016) but also as vectors of plant viruses (Tocko-Marabena *et al.*, 2017), promoting fungi growth caused soot molds and reducing crop yield (Coudriet *et al.*, 1985). *B. tabaci* caused serious damages due to secrete a large amount of honeydew on to leaves (Gangwar and Gangwar, 2018). Moreover, it's caused silver-leafing symptoms in squash (Vyskocilova *et al.*, 2019). They compared the survival and fecundity of *B. tabaci* on 13 vegetable hosts viz. aubergine, squash and tomato plants.

The developmental time needed to *B. tabaci* for completing stages from egg to adult on cucumber and squash by Coudriet *et al.* (1985), cantaloupe by Nava-Camberos *et al.* (2001). In addition, the development and reproduction of *B. tabaci* under screen house conditions was determined by Tamilselvan *et al.* (2019) on resistant and susceptible cotton genotypes. Numerous studies on *B. tabaci* biology had been carried out under diverse conditions and recorded that the variation in biological features related to temperature, RH and host plant (Palaniswami *et al.* 2001). *B. tabaci* life cycle from egg to adult was carried out on cucurbita host species depend on temperature and humidity (Šimala and Masten, 2003). Bayhan *et al.* (2006) studied the whitefly rearing on squash, cucumber, cantaloupe and watermelon at 20, 25 and 30°C to determine the development time and

survival rate. On cucumber plant, Kakimoto *et al.* (2007) recorded that the developmental and reproductive of *Bemisia argentifolii* Bellows and Perring (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) increased under the laboratory at 25°C. They found that the developmental period of *B. argentifolii* took about 22.4 days. Furthermore, Sohani *et al.* (2007) determined the life table of *B. tabaci*. The development period was 14.1 days at 30°C, and immature mortality was 17.3% with 30°C. The longevity of female was 16.8-34.1 days. Total fecundity was 150-263 eggs/female. Mean daily laid eggs ranged from 4.2-12.7 eggs/female. The generation extended from 19 to 43 days by increased temperature.

On tomato plants, Fekart and Shishehbor (2007) and Takahashi *et al.* (2008) determined that the developmental duration from the egg-to-adult period under laboratory conditions was ranged between 20 and 22 days. Moreover, the biology aspects of *B. tabaci* were evaluated on 18 tomato genotypes by Oriani *et al.* (2011) under laboratory greenhouse conditions. The history of life was determined by Khan and Wan (2015) at 25±2°C, 60±5% RH. They indicated that the total egg - adult duration stage on tomato was 33.6 days. Total mortality percent from egg to adult was 34.4%. Females lived longer than males. Mean female and male stayed alive for about 19.1, 18.5 days. The total laid eggs were 78.3 eggs/ female and sex ratio were 52:48 (Female: Male).

Rarely issues were concerned on the cotton whitefly, *B. tabaci* biology in Egypt, so that, this work was undertaken to comparison between the biological features of *B. tabaci* when fed on four vegetable plants, tomato (*Lycopersicon exculentum* variety, supper strain-B), eggplant (*Solanum melongena* variety, black baladi), cucumber (*Cucumis sativus* variety, hayl) and squash (*Cucurbita pepo* variety, azid f1).

Materials and Methods

1. Stock culture:

Cotton whitefly *B. tabaci* infestations were collected through May 2018 from eggplant crop under green house at Fayoum governorate, Egypt. Eggplant nurseries cultivated in pots. After that, the collected *B. tabaci* infestations and adults were put on the cultivated pots in two wooden cages under normal conditions. The cage (80 cm length x 50cm width x 90 cm height) covered by

Agrylic clothes (anti *B. tabaci* screening) (Figure, 1). The eggplant nurseries were irrigated and fertilized by balanced fertilizer contained 20N: 20P: 20K; additionally, the new nurseries were added to the stock cages when needed. After that, the cotton whitefly artificial infestation was placed on new tomato, eggplant, cucumber and squash nurseries in the wooden cage (35cm length x 25cm width x 45cm height) (Figure, 1).

Figure (1): Wooden cages.

2. Biology of *B. tabaci*:

A total of 4 nurseries of each tested crop were placed on the stock cage to artificial infestation by *B. tabaci* adults for 24 hours. After that, these 4 nurseries for each crop (tomato, eggplant, cucumber and squash) were transferred to new cages (25cm width x 35cm length x 45 height); two nurseries from each plant were placed in the small wooden cage which covered by white Agrylic clothes. Stay about 50 deposited eggs was counted on 4 nurseries of each tested crop and the exceeded eggs were removed. The development of cotton whitefly, *B. tabaci* was observed and diagnosed by 20X lens from immature stages to adult emergence. The newly adults were transferred to a new nursery of each plant in wooden cage, after that, the laid eggs were

counted. In addition, the adult longevity, life cycle, survival rate and sex ratio were determined. Also, net reproductive rate (R_o), intrinsic rate of increase (r_m) and finite rate of increase (λ) as suggested by Carey (1993), according to the method of Birch (1948) and Lin (1964) were calculated.

3. Statistical analysis:

Data were analyzed by using SAS program computer including F- test and simple correlation (SAS Institute, 2003) at 5% levels of probability.

Results and Discussion

The impact of four vegetable plants, tomato, eggplant, cucumber and squash plants was observed on the biological features of *B. tabaci* under natural conditions. *B. tabaci* life cycle pass through egg, 1st

nymphal instar, 2nd nymphal instar, 3rd nymphal instar, 4th nymphal instar and adult stages (Table, 1). Data showed a non-significant difference for the egg incubation period of *B. tabaci* on the investigated four vegetable plants. The egg incubation period was small on squash plant (2.15 ± 0.11 days) while on tomato plant was a long (3.80 ± 0.14 days) under natural (Table, 1). The tomato plant was recorded a high value of the egg incubation period under natural conditions. The first nymphal instar is called crawling. A significant difference was observed between 1st nymphal instar fed on the four tested vegetable plants. The development time of 1st nymphal instar was small with cucumber and squash plants (1.74 ± 0.08 and 1.53 ± 0.10 days, respectively). However, it was a long when fed on tomato and eggplant plants (3.23 ± 0.10 and 2.56 ± 0.09 days, respectively). The development time of 1st nymphal instar seems to a longer when fed on tomato and eggplant plants under natural conditions (Pr. > |F| value = 2.94, LSD value = 1.486) (Table 1).

The nymphal instars from 2nd - 4th were sessile. The feeding impact on different host plants was observed to exhibit longer duration on tomato plant (4.86 ± 0.19 days) than on other host plants. The lowest duration period of the 2nd nymphal instar was found in case of eggplant plant (2.62 ± 0.12 days) with significant difference between both host plants. Also, data was indicated that the developmental time of nymphal instars from 2nd - 4th was longer on tomato plant and smaller on eggplant plant. A non-significant difference was found with 3rd and 4th nymphal instars when fed on the four tested plants. In general, the developmental time of *B. tabaci* nymphal stage when fed on the different investigated diets was a significant longer period in tomato plant than other host plants (16.45 ± 0.35 days) at 0.05 level of probability according F-test analysis (F value

= 7.43, LSD = 3.132). However, nearly developmental period of nymphal stage was observed in case of eggplant (10.36 ± 0.03 days as smallest period), squash (11.96 ± 0.52 days) and cucumber (12.04 ± 0.43 days) plants without significant difference between them (Table, 1). Finally, the impact of host diet for eggplant was suitable diet for *B. tabaci* stage, followed by cucurbit hosts, but tomato plant was recorded a longest developmental period of *B. tabaci* stages under natural conditions.

On the other hand, the impact of different vegetable plants on longevity of was reported confining by females and males just immediately on emergence on different tested plants, tomato, eggplant, cucumber and squash (Table, 1). The mean longevity of *B. tabaci* male (immediately from 4th nymphal moult to adult death) was found to be longer when *B. tabaci* male feeding on squash plant (17.69 ± 1.48 days), followed by eggplant (14.50 ± 2.46 days). Contrariwise, in case of female, it was to be longer when *B. tabaci* female fed on eggplant (21.00 ± 1.36 days), followed by squash plant (19.38 ± 0.94 days). Doubtless, eggplant was a suitable diet for development of *B. tabaci*, on which, the female longevity was observed the longest duration under natural conditions (Table, 1). The longest mean generation survived for 21.26 ± 0.56 days on tomato and the shortest was *B. tabaci* that survived for 13.57 ± 0.2 days on eggplant (Table, 2). The mean generation was significantly different between eggplant and tomato, but it was insignificantly difference with both other tested host plants (F = 2.93, LSD = 6.363). The accomplishment of *B. tabaci* life cycle (egg-adults per day) was a longest on tomato being 20.26 ± 0.62 days, but it was a shortest on eggplant (12.57 ± 0.18 days) with significantly different between them (Table, 2).

Table (1): Developmental period (Mean±SE) of *Bemisia tabaci* on different vegetable plants.

Stage	Incubation period (days)	Duration of nymphal instars (days)				Nymphal stage	Longevity (days)	
		1 st nymph	2 nd nymph	3 rd nymph	4 th nymph		Male	Female
Tomato	3.80± 0.14 ^a	3.23± 0.10 ^a	4.86± 0.19 ^a	4.43± 0.20 ^a	3.93± 0.20 ^a	16.45± 0.35 ^a	10.89± 2.01 ^b	13.78± 1.00 ^b
Eggplant	2.21± 0.10 ^a	2.56± 0.09 ^{ab}	2.62± 0.12 ^b	2.66± 0.08 ^a	2.53± 0.09 ^a	10.36± 0.03 ^b	14.50± 2.46 ^{ab}	21.00± 1.36 ^a
Cucumber	2.91± 0.12 ^a	1.74± 0.08 ^b	3.41± 0.12 ^{ab}	3.68± 0.14 ^a	3.19± 0.19 ^a	12.04± 0.43 ^b	13.20± 2.07 ^{ab}	14.50± 2.46 ^b
Squash	2.15± 0.11 ^a	1.53± 0.10 ^b	3.19± 0.11 ^{ab}	4.02± 0.17 ^a	3.21± 0.15 ^a	11.96± 0.52 ^b	17.69± 1.48 ^a	19.38± 0.94 ^{ab}
F value	1.29	2.94	2.04	1.48	0.66	7.43	3.77	3.63
LSD	2.211	1.486	2.177	2.035	2.306	3.132	4.769	6.11

Values signed by the same letter in the same column are statistically non-significant.

The obtained data in Table (1) were in line with Hendi *et al.* (1984) who recorded the developmental duration of *B. tabaci* being 19.5 days for on tomato at 30°C. Additionally, Sohani *et al.* (2007) observed that the development of *B. tabaci* stages was 14.1 days at 30°C on cucumber plant, and the generation times decreased with increasing temperature from 43 to 19 days. Moreover, on some cucurbita species, Bayhan *et al.* (2006) reported that the developmental duration of all nymphs was 19.3 days on cucumber, 20.1 days on squash, 20.8 days on cantaloupe and 23.8 days on watermelon plants at 25°C. In other crops, Butler *et al.* (1983) on cotton was 17 days on aubergine. In addition, Oriani *et al.* (2011) studied some biological aspects of *B. tabaci* on 18 tomato genotypes under laboratory greenhouse conditions. The development period of insects grown on these genotypes took ranged from 20.3 – 23.3 days. Moreover, Numerous issues was detected the development times of

B. tabaci stages as like as Powell and Bellows (1992a) on potato (14.2 day), cucumber (16.74 days) at 30°C. Expectedly, the difference may be explained by disparities in the phytochemical components in the investigated host plants. In case of longevity, the females lived longer than males on host plant. Similarly, mean longevity was 19.1 of female and 18.5 days of male on tomato plant (Khan and Wan, 2015). In addition, the longevity of *B. tabaci* adult in this study was like those reported in other studies conducted at similar constant temperatures (Butler *et al.*, 1983 and Powell and Bellows, 1992 b). In which, most of these researchers reported that female insects lived longer than males, that it may be due to the plant ability to defend themselves against any herbivores.

Present data in Table (2) showed that the influence of four vegetable plants, tomato, eggplant, cucumber and squash on fecundity, generation and life cycle, sex ratio

and survival rate was studied. All deposited eggs were daily recorded until adult death. Also, the numbers of male and female adults were reported and calculated the sex ratio on all investigated host plants. Fecundity of *B. tabaci* was crucial in determining the potential of *B. tabaci* populations on these hosts. Fecundity was affected by these tested host plants. *B. tabaci* female deposited the greatest and least egg numbers when fed on eggplant and cucumber plants with average of 109.50 ± 7.08 and 83.80 ± 6.10 eggs/female, respectively (Pr. > F= 27.05 and LSD= 7.025). However, a mean daily egg was the greatest on tomato plant being $5.60 \pm$

0.99 eggs/ day/ female, and the least was 4.29 ± 0.65 eggs/ day/ female on squash plant without significant difference between them (Pr. < F= 0.47 and LSD= 2.806) (Table, 2).

Results showed that *B. tabaci* sex ratio (female %) was not affected by different tested host plant on which it was reared. Statistical analysis stated no significant differences in sex ratio between them (F= 0.95, LSD= 10.423). A survival rate of *B. tabaci* when reared on different tested host plants was higher on squash and eggplant plants (84% and 80%, respectively) than on other examined host plants (Table, 2).

Table (2): Biological aspects of *B. tabaci* fed on four vegetable plants under natural conditions.

Biological parameters	Host plants				Significant level	
	Tomato	Eggplant	Cucumber	Squash	F value	LSD
Total eggs	89.56± 8.30 ^b	109.50± 7.08 ^a	83.80± 6.10 ^b	90.15± 8.42 ^b	27.05	7.025
Daily rate of eggs	5.60± 0.99 ^a	4.76± 0.61 ^a	4.41± 0.95 ^a	4.29± 0.65 ^a	0.47	2.806
Mean generation time (days)	21.26± 0.56 ^a	13.57± 0.26 ^b	15.95± 0.43 ^{ab}	15.10± 0.47 ^{ab}	2.93	6.363
Life cycle (days)	20.26± 0.62 ^a	12.57± 0.18 ^b	14.95± 0.75 ^{ab}	14.10± 0.98 ^b	3.67	5.685
Sex ratio (Females %)	53.57 ^a	60.00 ^a	55.56 ^a	59.52 ^a	0.95	10.423
Survival rate %	56 %	80 %	72 %	84 %	—	—
Net reproductive rate (R₀)	27.081	52.560	33.788	45.438	—	—
Daily intrinsic rate of increase (r_m)	0.1153	0.1929	0.1438	0.1645	—	—
Finite rate of increase (λ)	1.1222	1.2128	1.1546	1.1788	—	—

Values signed by the same letter in the same row are statistically non-significant.

The obtained results were in line with Šimala and Masten (2003), they found the ability of *B. tabaci* female to deposit eggs up to 160 eggs on cucurbita plants. Moreover, a mean deposited eggs of *B. tabaci* ranged between 150 - 263 eggs /female and 4.2-12.7

eggs/day (Sohani *et al.*, 2007). Other whitefly species, Nava-Camberos *et al.* (2001) stated that *B. argentifolii* laid about 14.6 - 36.0 eggs/ day. A low deposited eggs of female was 78.3 (Fekart and Shishehbor, 2007) and 60.1 eggs/ female (Khan and Wan,

2015) on tomato plants. Other laboratory experiments had detected a variety of fertility values of whitefly. On cotton and cucumber, Powell and Bellows (1992 b) observed that *B. tabaci* deposited about 73.7 and 208.6 eggs at 29°C, respectively. On tomato plants, Hendi *et al.* (1984) found a mean of 203.1 eggs at 30°C. They also found that the daily of laid eggs was 8, with a range of 5.5 - 10.8. On cotton, Horowitz (1983) recorded a mean of 95.5 eggs at 30°C. Regarding life cycle, the present data was comparable agree with Šimala and Masten (2003), who found that the life cycle requires 2-3 weeks. Fekart and Shishehbor (2007) and Takahashi *et al.* (2008) recorded that the period from egg-to-adult was 20.0-22.0 days on tomato crop. On the other hand, Khan and Wan (2015) recorded about 33.6 days of egg-adult period on tomato plant at 25 °C. Finally, it clarity emphasized that the egg- adult period of *B. tabaci* requires about 2-3 weeks on investigated host plants under natural condition at the experimental time.

During the study of survival rate, comparable present results were generally satisfactory with Nava-Camberos *et al.* (2001) were reported that the survival of *B. argentifolii* was 76.5% on cantaloupe. Present data showed that the survival rate of this pest was raged from 56 - 84 % on the four tested host plants, similarly, at different temperatures, the percentage survival of immature instars was 72.9 - 83.2% on cucumber, 72.9 - 84.9 % on cantaloupe, 52.1-76.1% on squash and 37.6 - 64.8 % on watermelon (Bayhan *et al.*, 2006). Throughout the aforementioned issues, the survival rate was not exceeded than 85%, it may be depended on the feeding host plants or heat degree units require for development. In the present study and previous issues, the sex ratio of whitefly, was independent of the feeding on different plant species (van Lenteren and Noldus, 1990). The current study recorded that sex ratio of *B. tabaci* female was 53.57 -60 %, as like as Khan and

Wan (2015), who recorded that the sex ratio was 52:48 female: male on tomato plant.

By comparison in Table (2) between tomato, eggplant, cucumber and squash plants, all studied life table statistics were diversity on the examined host plants. The net reproductive rate (R_o) was ranged from 27.081 on tomato to 52.560 on eggplant plants. Moreover, the intrinsic rate of increase (r_m) was the highest on eggplant (0.1929), however, the lowest was recorded with tomato plant (0.1153). The present data also reflected the highest finite rate of increase (λ) on eggplant (1.2128), followed by squash plant (1.1788) and the lowest on tomato plant (1.1222), and followed by cucumber plant (1.1546). The finite rate of increase is the ability of *B. tabaci* to increase the population growth per unite time (female/female/ day). The finite rate was ranged from 1.1222 – 1.2128, that means, *B. tabaci* was able to increase the population ($\lambda > 1$) on all tested host plants (Table 2). Similarly, Fekart and Shishehbor (2007) showed that the daily r_m was extended from 0.1438 to 0.1645 on aubergine, tomato and potato plants, and *B. tabaci* was capable of population increase ($\lambda > 1$) on different host plants. Yang and Chi (2006) conducted the life table of *B. argentifolii* on tomato at different temperatures, and they found that the intrinsic rate of increase (r_m) was 0.1469 at 25°C. Comparably, the developmental time, r_m , R_o and fecundity of *B. argentifolii* raised on four vegetables as eggplant, cucumber, sweet pepper and tomato at 25°C by Kakimoto *et al.* (2007). They recorded that the r_m and R_o was 0.168 & 185.1 on eggplant; 0.153 & 130.7 on cucumber; and 0.110 & 36.1 on tomato, respectively. In these two studies, the r_m and R_o of reared *B. tabaci* in the present work and *B. argentifolii* was lower on tomato when it's compared with than other tested vegetables.

Data tabulated in Table (3) showed that a high amount of the proteins was represented in eggplant and squash plants by

55.77±1.47 and 54.63± 0.70 mg/gdw. However, tomato plant had low amount of this leaf components. However, both cucumber and tomato plants had a highest level of total phenols being 4.22± 0.21 and 4.07± 0.34 mg/gdw, and the lowest one was found in leaf of tomato and squash plants (3.13± 0.19 and 3.20± 0.26 mg/gdw, respectively). In Table (3), a heavily

Peroxidase and Phenoloxidase levels were represented in tomato leaves (10.63± 1.70 ΔO.D.430/min/gdw and 13.02± 0.96 ΔO.D.units/min/gdw than other tested plants. Contrarily, eggplant leaves contained a low amount of two examined plant enzymes (5.10 ±0.58 ΔO.D.430/min/gdw and 5.47 ±0.13ΔO.D.units/min/gdw, respectively).

Table (3): Certain phytochemical components and plant enzymes in four tested vegetable plants.

Leaf contents		Host plants				Significant level	
		Tomato	Eggplant	Cucumber	Squash	F value	LSD
Enzymes	Peroxidase (ΔO.D.430/min/gdw)	10.63± 1.70 ^a	5.10 ± 0.58 ^b	12.02 ± 1.00 ^a	6.30 ± 0.78 ^b	9.21	3.240
	Phenoloxidase (ΔO.D.units/min/gdw)	13.02 ± 0.96 ^a	5.47 ± 0.13 ^c	7.85 ± 0.16 ^b	6.72 ± 0.70 ^{bc}	30.11	1.782
Phytochemical contents	Total proteins (mg/gdw)	31.85 ± 0.53 ^c	55.77 ± 1.47 ^a	39.17 ± 0.86 ^b	54.63 ± 0.70 ^a	150.40	2.830
	Total phenols (mg/gdw)	4.07 ± 0.34 ^a	3.13 ± 0.19 ^b	4.22 ± 0.21 ^a	3.20 ± 0.26 ^b	4.93	0.753

Values signed by the same letter in the same row are statistically non-significant.

A significantly positive effect was found between the tested components except in case of total proteins were recorded negative effect on the life cycle, generation and nymphal stage of *B. tabaci*. By contrast, a significantly negative effect was stated

between the tested components on the male and female longevity and fecundity of *B. tabaci* except in case of total proteins were recorded positive effect on these parameters (Table, 4).

Table (4): Effect of certain phytochemical components and plant enzymes on biological aspects of *B. tabaci* fed on four vegetable plants.

Leaf contents		Biological parameters					
		Life cycle	Generation	Nymphal stage	Longevity		Fecundity
r value	Prob.				E.V.%	Male	
Peroxidase (ΔO.D.430/min/gdw)	r value	0.64	0.64	0.58	- 0.67	- 0.96	- 0.79
	Prob.	0.04	0.05	0.14	0.03	0.01	0.05
	E.V.%	40.43	40.36	33.96	46.08	93.56	63.92
Phenoloxidase (ΔO.D.units/min/gdw)	r value	0.99	99.18	0.91	- 0.76	- 0.82	- 0.48
	Prob.	0.001	0.001	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.51
	E.V.%	99.77	99.84	92.88	58.32	64.72	23.72
Total proteins (mg/gdw)	r value	- 0.88	- 0.84	- 0.84	0.86	0.94	0.62
	Prob.	0.01	0.01	0.05	0.01	0.01	0.03
	E.V.%	78.34	72.87	70.14	74.40	92.48	39.62
Total phenols (mg/gdw)	r value	0.67	0.62	0.61	- 0.76	- 0.97	- 0.73
	Prob.	0.03	0.03	0.05	0.02	0.01	0.03
	E.V.%	45.18	41.50	37.77	57.67	94.61	53.39

r value= correlation coefficient

Prob. = Probability

E.V.%= Explained variance

Plants respond against pests by numerous biochemical substances to reduce their pest damage. The plant defense was wide-ranging, by direct and indirect actions (War *et al.*, 2012) In the present study, the preference of whitefly influenced by the plant enzyme activities as well as Phenoloxidase and Peroxidase, as like, the *B. tabaci* infestation increased by increased the polyphenoloxidase and peroxidase activities in host plant (Shize *et al.*, 2008; Kai *et al.*, 2014 and Hongsheng *et al.*, 2017)

In the present study, the leaf phytochemical components influenced on the development of whitefly on the four tested vegetable plants as viewpoint of Hegab (2017) and Fucui *et al.* (2014) in cucumber plants, Saleh and Al-Shareef (2010) in cantaloupe plants and Khan *et al.* (1999) in ash gourd plants. Vegetable crops have a large variety of phytochemical compounds, as alkaloids, tannins, steroids, glycosides, phenolics, flavonoids among others (Rajasree *et al.* 2016), that it may be affected on whitefly preferences and some of these may be execute as repellent agents. Moreover, the role of phytochemicals may be act as an antifeedant approach on whitefly control (Koul, 2008 and Fucui *et al.*, 2014).

In recent issues and this study, the antifeeding and/or phytochemical contents in host plants influenced on the whitefly density. These observations might lead to the diversity of whitefly-vegetable plant interactions which related to leaf phytochemical components. Some of these factors may be played as well as antifeeding and/or repellent in plant of the four investigated vegetable plants against the infestation of *B. tabaci* during this study.

Cotton whitefly, *B. tabaci* is obviously a greater host preference for eggplant and squash plants as compared to cucumber and tomato plants by documenting a short life and mortality with high net reproductive rate (R_0), the intrinsic rate of increase (r_m) and finite rate of increase (λ). Hence, one should consider

the susceptibility of vegetable plants when planning the IPM program for the *B. tabaci* in Egypt.

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